

**AN EXPLORATION OF CULTURALLY DIVERSE PATTERNS OF
IMMIGRANTS' USE OF ALCOHOL & OTHER DRUGS IN THE WEST OF
SCOTLAND**

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Abstract

The use of alcohol and other drugs (AOD) among Black Minority Ethnic (BME) groups is under-researched in Scotland. There is a lack of empirical data on them and their opinions are absent from the literature. This thesis presents the factors that influence alcohol use among a wide range of BME age groups (18-69) in the West of Scotland. While alcohol was the main drug used, the use of some controlled¹ drugs were reported. This qualitative research utilises one to one semi-structured interviews to provide rich sources of data. A purposive sample of 30 hidden BME AOD users were recruited (drugs included legal and illegal substances, and their uses both licit and illicit²) to examine the influence of gender, age, and religion on use and avoidance. These individuals were hidden or hard to reach as they were or perceived themselves to be at risk of shame from some individuals in their culture or family for breaching cultural norms. Participants were interviewed in their preferred first language using translation and language skills of the researcher. Interviews were transcribed and analysed thematically from a social constructionist perspective.

There is a perception that cultural factors influence migrants' choices to drink or use drugs, and interestingly act as a significant factor in the avoidance of drugs and alcohol. The thesis illustrates how perceived 'Scottish' social and personal practices understood as deviance were adopted or rejected by the BME participants. Acculturation theory is a central part of this thesis, which posits that individuals who migrate from one country to another, over time, assimilate a variety of aspects of the new culture they reside in. In addition, participant self-perception and identity as users or non-users of AOD were interpreted and explored through a sociology of deviance lens, in particular labelling and stigma theory. This research contributes to a thesis by presenting an understanding of a mediated acculturation underpinned by individual agency on how the use of alcohol and other drugs is understood and negotiated by non-white populations.

The findings challenge existing views of alcohol use or avoidance as a cultural norm among some BME individuals. Indeed, some participants expressed discourses of inverse racism as a form of cultural validation to manage personal identities in relation to accepting or rejecting cultural norms regards AOD use. The practical implications of the results of this thesis are explored and recommendations for future research are discussed.

¹ This refers to drugs controlled within the confines of the United Kingdom Misuse of Drugs Act 1971.

² In this thesis, the term "illicit" includes those drugs used secretly; or condemned by certain professions as illicit (non-medicinal) and which may or may not be illegal.

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Abbreviations

ADP	Alcohol and Drug Partnerships
AOD	Alcohol and Other Drugs
BCS	British Crime Survey
BME	Black Minority Ethnic
LGBT	Lesbian, gay, bisexual and transsexual
MDA	Misuse of Drugs Act
MDMA	Methylenedioxyamphetamine
NHS	National Health Service
RDS	Respondent Driven Sampling
SDMD	Scottish Drug Misuse Database
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
TA	Thematic Analysis
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States

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1 Introduction

1.1 Rationale and Objectives

Due to the personal nature of this research and to situate the rationale of the thesis that emerges from it, it is necessary to introduce the author and to narrate this section in the first person. This will help provide insights into my background and how this informed my approach to this research.

My family originates from Kerala, India, however I grew up in North Africa, Libya, and at 16, I migrated with my family to Scotland. My experiences of India were limited to a few sporadic school breaks with my family during my childhood. These experiences exposed me to a wide variety of cultures, countries, languages and religions. Having spent my formative years in Libya, and now living in Scotland, I soon realised that my personal identity as a Libyan, Indian Scottish educated woman were challenging to how and in what way my family understood to be the norm within the Keralan and Indian culture I was raised in. This partly stemmed from the proud claim that my family made of their Syrian heritage, and more so of belonging to the Jacobite Syriac (Syrian) Orthodox faith³. My family adhere to this identity, arguing that our ancestors migrated from Syria to Kerala several centuries ago. Accordingly, the Syriac Orthodox church can be traced back to the first-century Christian communities - the Antioch of Syria on the Orontes River where early Jewish Christianity are believed to have been

³ Jacobite Syrian Christian Church: <http://www.jacobitesyrianchurch.org/>

founded. My multi-cultural upbringing made it very difficult for me to accept this Jacobite Syrian identity and I enjoyed testing the boundaries of the norms underpinning the religion and the culture I was considered a part. It was in acts of youthful exploration and rebellion or deviance from cultural norms underpinning my heritage that I recognise stigma associated with the use of alcohol and drugs. As Libya is an Islamic country, the use of alcohol and drugs is prohibited by religion and illegal by law. Hence, any use of alcohol and/or drugs is highly stigmatising resulting in actual discrimination. However, in my youth, I frequently witnessed people consuming alcohol and drugs. Indeed, socialising opportunities in Libya with my parent's local and foreign colleagues were often alcohol fuelled. I can recount similar experiences of consuming alcohol during my short visits to Kerala. However, here I noticed a divide, where men were encouraged drink while women abstained or if they did choose to use alcohol, did so illicitly. It is fair to say that it was forbidden to talk openly about AOD in my family, and most of the other families I interacted with. Similar observations were also noted by my close friends and peers who shared the same kind of multi-cultural upbringing as myself.

It was these experiences that sowed the seeds of interest in cultural norms, stigma and deviance regarding the use of alcohol and drugs among BMEs. My identity as a female BME individual, my experience and understanding of stigma, and my ability to speak and translate several languages allowed me to access and recruit a small sample of BME individuals in the west of Scotland into this study.

This thesis explores and reveals how participants perceive themselves as social actors from minority groups living in Scotland, how cultural norms influence their use of AOD, and how they manage their personal identities engaging with other BME groups and wider Scottish culture. Their social worlds are “hidden” because these individuals would have been inaccessible to others for research. These individuals are also hidden as they risk shame, stigma and discrimination from some individuals in their family or culture if identified as alcohol or other drug users. Furthermore, BME groups are categorised as hard-to-reach due to differences in cultural perceptions, language and social isolation from ‘outsiders’. Often these individuals have a membership in a group with individuals from their own ethnic background, which might prevent them from talking to ‘outsiders’ about matters that concern the group. I touch upon how my personal identity (as an insider) was helpful to allow me to access hidden and hard to reach individuals at greater length in the methodology chapter (Chapter 3).

An initial review of the BME literature revealed a limited and fragmented understanding of how and in what way BME groups use alcohol and other drugs. While there is an abundance of North American literature, the limited British research which is available focuses mainly on BME groups in England. Much of the United Kingdom (UK) research into alcohol and drug use by BME’s presents estimated patterns and prevalence for comparison, with the aim of informing public health interventions.

It is theorised that there is a tendency for people to misreport their daily or weekly use of alcohol in the United Kingdom. Medical, legal and religious discourse on how citizens should conduct themselves is thought to contribute to the lack of accuracy in estimating the patterns and prevalence of alcohol use in the general population (Boniface et al., 2014; Livingston and Callinan, 2015). This is further explored in Chapter 2, Section 2.1.

De Kock et al., (2017) suggest that while epidemiological studies focus on calculating risk factors from patterns and prevalence estimates, public health discourses are increasingly controlling and paternalistic often linking use to pathology. From a public health perspective, abstinence from non-medical drugs, and 'moderation' in the use of alcohol is often defined as optimal for healthy functioning (Goode, 2006; West and Brown, 2013).

Estimating risk factors or health behaviours in populations will depend on how the data is gathered, by whom, and targeting what population. Measurement is further impeded by how public health discourses which link addiction to users who are presented as deviant risk takers, gambling (sic) with their health, sanity for their unhealthy life choices.

Estimating the use of illegal drugs particularly among non-white populations, presented as official statistics are problematic due to methodological weakness. The limitations of self-reported data, and methodological weaknesses in data are explored in more detail in Chapter 2.

In the UK shame, secrecy, and stigma confound our understandings of the use of legal drugs such as alcohol, tobacco, prescription medications, and over the counter medications.

Alcohol use is considered a normal part of human activity and recreation, evidenced in the UK by the number of retail outlets and public houses and restaurants selling it legally. In some cultures that prohibit alcohol by law or by religious observance, being identified as a user of alcohol can be a source of stigma, shame and discrimination (Fountain et al., 2003; Sangster et al., 2002a). Being judged, being labelled as abnormal or considered deviant, can result in negative self-perceptions and constructions of deviant stereotypes.

While alcohol use has an abundance of literature focusing on estimating patterns, prevalence and risk factors for ill health, very little is known about what the use of alcohol means to BME individuals, their families, their communities, or from certain religious perspectives, or gendered practices. It was evident that this gap in the literature regards how BME individuals assimilate or reject Scottish cultural attitudes, beliefs and norms regards alcohol and drug use required further exploration. Hence, the central research question explores:

What AOD use and avoidance ‘means’ to ethnic minorities (including an exploration of stigma associated with the use of licit and illicit drugs), between sexes, and age groupings.

The objectives explored in this thesis include:

1. Identify a hidden group of non-treatment seeking individuals from BME populations who use alcohol or other drugs.

This objective was approached by describing how and why the research participants were recruited. Researching the use of AOD amongst BME groups is a complex and challenging undertaking for researchers, health, social services and the criminal justice system as they are often met with distrust (Sangster et al., 2002a; Flanagan and Hancock, 2010; Fountain, 2003; Boag-Munroe and Evangelou, 2012). Furthermore, research on BME use of AOD indicates that BMEs have a higher risk of developing problems with drugs and alcohol, in contrast to the white population. BME individuals particularly in England and Wales who are known to treatment and other services, often reside in areas characterised by inequality and deprivation (Pearson and Patel, 1998; Rassool, 2006; Shaw et al., 2016; Hunt and Kolind, 2017; Durrant and Thakker, 2003; Paoli and Reuter, 2008).

Research indicates that BMEs who may have problems with alcohol and other drugs have a low uptake of services (Sangster et al., 2002b; Fountain, 2003; Johl, 2017; Rassool, 2006; Abdulrahim, 2005; Luger and Sookhoo, 2005). It is also suggested that policy makers are reluctant to focus on addressing these issues for fear of accusations of racism by drawing attention to the use of AOD in these communities, further increasing the potential for stigma, shame and discrimination (Fountain, 2003; Sangster et al., 2002a; Rassool, 2006). While BME groups report

higher than average rates of abstinence, there exist nuances within and between ethnic groups that explain abstinence (Hurcombe et al., 2010).

In a review of ethnicity and health research in Scotland in 2001, the data indicates that little is known about the decisions to use or avoid alcohol, and even less is known of their use of other drugs (Jarvis, 2008; Mills, 2012; Crawford et al., 2013). Therefore, the second objective is:

2. To examine how the use of alcohol and drugs influences how BME's manage their personal and social identity.

While alcohol and drugs users are much studied by social scientists, little attention has been paid on how the use of alcohol and other drugs by ethnic groups influences their perceptions and understandings of alcohol and other drug users in their own communities, in the context of Scottish culture. Furthermore, addiction discourses locate the source of problems within individuals, or to the power of drugs to alter behaviour, while little attention is paid in mainstream academic research on how cultural environments act as mediating factors in preventing or increasing risk factors for problems.

Consumption of alcohol to become inebriated in Scotland is common and accepted at least in part, as 'normal', however there is also a tension in whether this normality is acceptable over the entire culture or located in specific sub-groups (Simon and Burkhart, 2015). Individuals whose parents were born in other cultures may be raised in a household where abstaining from alcohol is a requirement of religious observance, which influences their attitudes to alcohol as adults (Gordon et al., 2012; Heath, 2012).

There are also cultural misunderstandings about what drugs are, and in defining 'legitimate' and culturally accepted use, such as the use of prescription drugs as medications, including over-the-counter medicines, and the 'legitimate' moral and legal condemnation of the use of drugs among certain BME groups.

There is little argument from the academic literature that use of illegal drugs is much stigmatised due to widespread misperceptions that drug users are deviant, criminal and unhealthy (McPhee et al., 2009; MCPhee et al., 2013). They are considered deviant because they breach socially accepted norms of conventional conduct, they are perceived as criminal because possession of some substances is a criminal offence, and they are considered unhealthy due to the vast literature that documents the negative health consequences of problematic users known to treatment services, and high profile media stories that sensationally report drug related deaths. In identifying these inconsistencies in the literature the third and final objective is:

3. To explore how cultural norms and values influence the use or avoidance of alcohol and drugs by BME's in relation to age, gender, religious observance, and generational differences.

Acculturation theory posits that individuals, who migrate from one country to another, over time, adopt a variety of aspects of the new culture they reside in (Berry, 2003; Berry, 2005; Rudmin, 2003; Redfield et al., 1936). The attitudinal and behavioural norms of migrants living and working in Scotland may be markedly different from the contemporary norms of

people like them currently residing in South India, Pakistan, Nigeria, Ghana and China. Coalescing minority norms with Scottish norms challenge norms and values of migrant communities and families who live within them. As such, although certain cultures place restrictions on the use of alcohol and drugs, there is a perception that living in Scotland influences how alcohol and drugs are perceived and used as part of a typical 'British' or 'Scottish' social and personal identity.

With a lack of empirical data on non-problematic BME alcohol users, their opinions are largely absent from the literature. To understand the ways in which people use (or abstain) from alcohol, it is necessary to document and reposition certain beliefs and social practices, to understand the meanings they have, and how and in what way BME individuals exercise agency in use and avoidance of negative labels and social affronts (Dutton, 2017; Goffman, 1968).

I was aware that being an insider did allow me access to hard to reach and hidden populations and helped me identify people who do not often volunteer for research (Ritchie et al., 2013). However, there were times that I had to acknowledge the potential for bias in using my identity to identify and recruit participants. To reduce the potential for bias, I searched for methodologies that could help limit this and approached the interview process and analysis of participant data from a detached outsider's perspective, while rigorously applying the training I received from more

experienced supervisors. This is discussed in greater detail in Chapter 3, Sections 3.2.

Understanding why certain BME individuals actively choose to keep their use of AOD hidden to preserve a 'clean' untainted ethnic identity from being exposed while engaging with certain aspects of their origin and familial culture was required. As such, semi-structured qualitative interviews were the most appropriate method. The theory of acculturation which has social constructionist underpinnings, is used to analyse and interpret the participant data and underpins this thesis. Interviews with 30 BME individuals were conducted and a few interviews were conducted using telephone (three participants) and Skype (five participants) to satisfy the requests of participants who feared being identified as deviant and being stigmatised in their community. The transcripts of all 30 interviews were thematically analysed and interpreted from a social constructionist perspective (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Flick et al., 2015; Clarke and Braun, 2013).

The central research question and the three objectives were directed by gaps in the literature as well as my personal reflexive experience during the research process. The objectives were addressed in the coding structures that emerged from analysis and interpretation of the data. Furthermore, the four analysis chapters and the discussion and conclusion explore the influence of cultural norms, gender, religion and age on

participant identity and how participants understand and manage use or avoidance of alcohol and drugs as BME's living and working in Scotland.

The thesis that emerged from a review of the literature, recruitment of participants and analysis of the data is underpinned by acculturation theory, deviance theory, labelling theory, gendered social practices and intersectionality theory.

In this thesis, the term "illicit" refers to any drug including alcohol that is used beyond culturally established norms and considered stigmatising and shameful. Illegal refers to those categories of drugs controlled by law.

1.2 Structure of the Thesis

The following section will provide an overview of this thesis, by outlining each of the eight chapters.

Chapter 2 provides a review of the literature on drug and alcohol discourses in the UK, BME Groups' use of AOD in the UK, how BME alcohol and drug use is researched, and focuses on the theoretical perspectives of acculturation, social norms, and socialisation. A focus on the sociology of deviance, in particular labelling theory and stigma, is then followed by an overview of how religious sanctions influence the use or abstinence from alcohol and drugs, before addressing the influence of gender on drinking and drug taking practices, and how this impacts on self-perception and identity. Intersectionality theory is also discussed which is a perspective that simultaneously examines the influence of multiple social categories as - race, immigration, socio-economic status, disability and gender.

Chapter 3 presents the rationale underpinning the methodological decisions of the researcher and presents reflections on the research journey and design. It describes how and why in-depth semi-structured interviews were chosen as the methodological framework. The adapted use of a social constructionist paradigm for analysing, interpreting and presenting the rich qualitative data is also discussed.

Chapter 4 introduces the first of four themes which emerges from the analysis of the data, and explores participant perceptions of alcohol use, particularly how culture, family, peers, colleagues, and social class influences their decision to use alcohol openly or in secret. This chapter introduces a new term in the AOD lexicon, that of 'alcohol enculturation' which refers to BMEs acquiring or rejecting Scottish drinking norms via a complex process of interaction and assimilation, which are core tenets of acculturation theory. Participants' perceptions are explored using a modified version of Landrine and Klonoff's (2004) bi-dimensional model of acculturation.

Chapter 5 presents participant perceptions of the use of illicit drugs and how they manage identity as users within their community living in Scotland. How, and in what way, known users are constructed as deviant, the active decision made by participants about what facets of their perceived and actual identity to present to others in their social world is also explored.

Chapter 6 examines participant beliefs and attitudes concerning AOD use within the context of four mainstream religions: a Christian perspective; an Islamic perspective; a Hindu perspective; and a Buddhist perspective, as each have particular relevance to the social and personal identity of the participants. The interpretations of the use of alcohol and drugs set out in the four dominant religious texts are discussed to establish how these tenets inform and influence participant identity and decisions to use or avoid alcohol and other drugs. This is linked to socialisation processes, alcohol enculturation, and the active agency used by the participants to avoid stigma and discrimination.

Chapter 7 investigates AOD use among men and women as a gendered social practice. 'Intentional dissimulation' is introduced as a new term to describe drinking practices engaged in by African female participants living in Scotland who were originally socialised in a largely male dominated culture. Narratives of male and female participants from Indian, African, Chinese, and Pakistani backgrounds are presented.

Chapter 8 offers a discussion of the findings, and Chapter 9 is the concluding chapter introducing a synthesis of the key themes that emerge from the literature and data analysis. Also included are research limitations and future recommendations.

2 Review of the Literature

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a review of the literature on the patterns and trends of alcohol and drug use among BME groups in UK. This chapter will review some historical studies to highlight the methodological weaknesses presented as official statistics such as the British Crime Survey in England and Wales and Census and population surveys in Scotland. These have been scrutinised for their methodology and accuracy in reporting ethnic categorisations as well as their use of AOD. Therefore, a Cultural Psychology perspective on acculturation is adopted to critically explain BME AOD use. Deviance and stigma as social constructions and their attendant discourses on the use or avoidance of AOD is also explored. Intersectionality theory conceptualises multiple social categories as - race, disability and gender in relation to identity is critically reviewed in relation to AOD use by BME groups. The social context of gender in relation to religious structures and how these impact on individual agency in decisions to use or avoid AOD among BME individuals is also critically discussed.

For this review, a wide variety of publications were examined: peer reviewed journals, book chapters, Government reports, and systematic literature reviews. Various databases were also searched including: ASSIA, Google Scholar, Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, Routledge, Science Direct, and Medline to find peer reviewed articles that examined AOD among BMEs in Scotland and UK. As there is an abundance of literature on AOD use among

minorities in America which primarily consist of African Americans, Hispanics, Native Americans, Asians and Pacific Islanders, emphasis was given to reviewing studies that were conducted in the UK and in particular Scotland.

The researcher conducted keyword searches, cited references, and hand searched relevant academic journals for grey literature (e.g. local surveys/reports). As BME use of AOD is largely under-researched in Scotland, accessing 'grey' literature provides insights at a local level.

2.2 Drug & Alcohol Discourses in Scotland & UK

The term 'drugs' when used in contemporary discourses are heavy with meaning. To be known as a drug user alters how one is viewed by others. Do drugs refer to pharmaceutical medicines, or natural plants, or synthetic analogues that mimic their effects? The use of drugs which are illegal to possess are routinely condemned as unhealthy and has led to constructions of determined pathways or careers from initial use to ill health, degradation and death.

The academic literature is increasingly attempting to present terms which do not discriminate, stigmatise, and label others as deviant. The term 'substance' is often used to refer to drugs to avoid negatively labelling users as deviant and criminal.

Psychoactive substances refer to commodities that when ingested, have an impact on thinking, feeling, mood and perceptions (Goode, 2006). Their widespread use currently and historically has created binary discourses

presenting arguments both for and against their use. There are widespread understandings that describe how and in what way drug problems develop, suggesting that the chemical properties of drugs are responsible, that the pleasure associated with their use leads to problems, or that the psychoactive properties of certain drugs lead to repeated use and eventually mental ill-health and problems (Shewan and Dalgarno, 2005a; McPhee, 2012). Explanations from Social Psychology and Sociology, reject these embodied explanations for deviance and indicate the importance of cultural factors that lead to drug taking and problematic use. Goode (2006) states that while pharmacology and neurology explain what happens when drug use occurs biologically, they cannot explain the influence of culture nor explain why some people are more stigmatised than others for their behavioural choices. Additionally, while some substances defined as “drugs” have medicinal, therapeutic or aesthetic value (e.g. antibiotics, antacids, steroids etc.), they are not in any way psychoactive.

There is little argument that natural plant remedies were commonly used historically to alleviate pain and suffering, to stimulate and enhance social interactions, and used recreationally. During the 1800s patent medicines containing drugs derived from natural plants were made available commercially and used for a variety of reasons (Goodman et al., 2007). For instance, Virginia Berridge describes how cocaine was known as “a miracle of modern science” in the late 19th century amongst medical professionals and its use as a stimulant and tonic was not condemned. However, within a decade of ‘unrestricted’ use of the drug, issues of overdosing referred to

as cocaine poisoning were reported (Berridge, 1978). The use of opium derived from the seed pod of the opium plant was widespread and was consumed in massive quantities, however it was not necessarily considered problematic. Historically opiate drugs were used for their analgesic properties as plant based medicines (Harding, 1998; Mott and Bean, 1998; Holmwood, 2014; Barton, 2011). Caffeine based drinks such as tea and coffee are psychoactive drugs, and are used as stimulants, but are not considered to be medicines, and are freely available without restriction. While the historical development of drug use from recreation to condemnation is outwith the scope of this thesis, this has been well documented in the academic literature (see Davenport-Hines 2012; Davenport-Hines, 2003: the 'Pursuit of Oblivion').

By the 1900s, unrestricted non-medical use of drugs shifted to increasing calls for strict controls over the distribution and sale of all drugs, underpinned by a view that non-medically prescribed drugs dispensed by a pharmacist was frivolous, and later increasingly described as harmful, and eventually pathological (Goode, 2006). The construction of drugs as licit or illicit and their use and users labelled as 'good' or 'bad' is a recent phenomenon. Historically many stakeholders from religion, medicine including psychiatry, and law enforcement, and businesses including alcohol and pharmaceutical corporate interests have shaped the social construction of what drugs are, who should control them, when they should be used, and for what purpose.

Alcohol has a long history, and its importance as a basic food, source of calories and as a medicine are well documented (Davenport-Hines, 2012; Davenport-Hines, 2003). In addition, its condemnation by religious groups (the Moors for example during the religious wars fought in the Middle East in early Christian times), and moral campaigners (during prohibition between 1919 and 1929 in the USA) are also well documented.

Drugs derived from natural plants such as opium, cocaine and cannabis which were once legally and freely available are now illegal (stemming from the UN Convention on Narcotic Drugs, 1961 and controlled under the UK Misuse of Drugs Act (MDA 1971) (London Police Foundation, 2000; Monaghan, 2014; Misuse of Drugs Act, 2013). This has led to their use being condemned.

Hence, consumption of drugs in contemporary culture is controlled not just by a medical system of prescriptions, and dispensation by licensed pharmacists, but also by legal proscriptions (penalties for unauthorised possession which are intended to deter use and punish infringements).

There is much overlap between the licit and illicit categories, as well as the psychoactive and medicinal categories; for instance, MDMA or ecstasy is both psychoactive and controlled by law, but is useful in therapeutic situations, while opiate drugs are used as medicines, are psychoactive and possession by individuals for recreational purposes are illegal. Thus, some drugs can be categorised as 'illicit' as well as having a licit medicinal purpose.

Possession of certain controlled drugs beyond these legal and medicinal realms is categorised as both illegal and problematic. For these reasons, and the bizarre and deviant categorisation of licit and illicit, good and bad, moral and immoral, medicinal and non-medicinal, problematic and recreational, it is understood why some individuals choose to abstain from them or have any association with people who use them. In like manner, it also offers a rationale for why some people become curious about their deviant allure, and risk their health, sanity and liberty by choosing to experiment with psychoactive drugs.

In the UK, despite restrictions on the sale of alcohol, alcohol is widely used in mainstream culture. More recently however, the use of alcohol by some groups is perceived as being excessive and problematic to the extent that it continues to be the focus of social, political and media attention (European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2016; National Health Services Scotland, 2012). Such perceptions stem from government public health strategies that suggest that per capita alcohol consumption must be reduced to minimise the burden of disease and costs to the UK taxpayer.

Alcohol despite being widely used in a variety of situations and contexts its use was condemned historically by religious groups. In the late 19th and early 20th century Scotland had a strong temperance movement. In Great Britain Hogarth's engravings of Gin Lane and Beer Street document that during times of great social upheaval, the notion that temperance was good

for the soul, and that intemperance was the cause of poverty, ill health and inequality, led to several 'dry' towns and villages. The temperance movement of the 19th century portrayed alcohol as the object of all social and moral evil and eventually moved from moral suasion to promoting total abstinence as an intervention (Yeomans, 2011). The use of grain alcohol was prevalent among the rural and urban poor in Scotland. Drinking was used as a means to alleviate the stress and distress of labouring in fields and factories and living in cramped conditions in large towns and cities. The temperance ideology was powerful in explaining alcohol as the cause of poverty and inequality rather than being a consequence of several complex factors such as the social dislocation and the inequalities caused by early capitalism (Levine, 1992). However, despite temperance leading to the banning of alcohol in the USA in the early 20th century, and restrictions on the use of alcohol during the First World War there has been an erosion in temperance traditions. In contemporary Scotland it is estimated that 90% of Scots reportedly consume alcohol (Hammersley and Dalgarno, 2012a).

In contemporary Scotland, alcohol is considered to be a normal part of Scottish culture, and the most common drug associated with pleasure, commerce (the whisky and small craft beer industry as examples) and in being considered by many people to be the source of problems in wider Scottish society (Ormston, 2008). In particular, there has been a greater emphasis on social life which revolves around the pub or at least drinking heavily as a form of recreation and enjoyment (Hammersley and Dalgarno, 2012b). As such, in Scottish culture, alcohol serves a central role in marking

the transition from work to play, where drinking is associated with recreation, or time away from responsibilities of work and family (Savic et al., 2016).

The prevalence of alcohol use and its nearly universal occurrence as an item of human behaviour since ancient times helps in understanding this as a normal custom, which survived against competing customs (Pittman and White, 1991; Nencini, 1997; Room, 2005) argue that the use of alcohol as a custom prevailed in the face of definite, organised, and consciously directed opposition. For instance, early Christian groups such as the Coptic sects regularly consumed large quantities of alcohol as part of Eucharistic celebrations, but both drinking alcohol and the use of plant-based intoxicants were condemned in later subdivisions within these sects. This resulted in many Christians becoming abstinent from alcohol to demonstrate their faith (Jay, 2011). Among some religious groups, drinking is frequently regarded as a dangerous practice, and several efforts have been made to control or abolish it (Pittman and White, 1991; Michalak et al., 2007; Nonnemaker et al., 2003; Drerup et al., 2011). Given the legal status of alcohol and wide availability in the UK, and the growing influence of health professionals who describe alcohol as unhealthy, problem drinking emerged as a potent social concern even before the emergence of drugs as a problem. Indeed well-meaning individuals in contemporary Scots society often feel obliged to condemn the use of drugs, and stigmatise users as deviant individuals, while excessive drinking alcohol to intoxication is not considered unusual (Forsyth et al., 2005; Labhart et al., 2013).

Formal records of the use of drugs in Scotland before the 1970s is limited, but existing documents indicate that drug use was primarily confined to students, intellectuals, music and art lovers who were often labelled 'freaks' and considered to be deviant users, although not necessarily criminal (Hammersley and Dalgarno, 2012a). It is important to note that this notion of referring to drug users as freaks is highly contested, and merely labels the users as outside or on the margins of mainstream norms of what should and could be used to become intoxicated, relax, and socialise.

Cannabis dominated the 'early' UK drug scene and remains in Scotland one of the most widely used substance in large surveys. Amongst students and intellectuals, and prior to the widespread use of heroin in the UK drugs with hallucinogenic properties were perceived positively as they were considered to be mind-expanding drugs, while other drugs were to be used with caution. Indeed Hammersley and Dalgarno (2012a) distinguish between freaks and punks, where the former were those who approached drugs as a spiritual, mind-expanding experience, while the latter are constructed as hedonistic and ill informed.

Having briefly outlined the changes that occurred impacting on drug and alcohol use in Scotland, the next section explores how BME groups approach, accept or reject these perceived norms in Scotland, particularly in relation to the use of alcohol. The moral, social and religious sanctions imposed on individuals and social groupings are discussed in greater detail in Section 2.5. However, it is important to emphasise that BME populations

in Scotland are different from those in England in size, ethnic composition, patterns of settlement and AOD use. The next section explores the BME population statistics in Scotland and the concept of ethnicity as identity.

2.2.1 BME Statistics in Scotland

The 2011 Census provides the most recent published information on ethnicity in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2014). Figure 1 documents BME populations in Scotland.

Figure 1: BME Population in Scotland (2011)

In 2011, the BME population was just over 200,000 (4%) of the total Scottish population. Of this, the Asian population is the largest group comprising 3% of the total population (141,000; Asian includes: Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, Chinese or other South Asians). Pakistanis are the

largest minority in Scotland (0.9%), followed by Indians and Chinese (0.6%), Bangladeshis (0.1%) and other Asians (0.4%). Glasgow had the highest percentage BME population with 12%. This is followed by the City of Edinburgh and Aberdeen at 8%, and Dundee at 6% (Scottish Government, 2014).

Figure 2: Ethnic Groups in Scotland (2011)

In 2011, the largest groups were within the categories of White: Other White (102,000 people), Polish (61,000 people) and Irish (54,000 people). This was followed by those that identified as Pakistani (49,000 people),

Chinese (34,000 people), Indian (33,000 people) and African groups (30,000 people). It is important to note that while such categorisations are useful in identifying minority ethnic groups, they do not distinguish by gender, age, religion or socio-economic settings and assume homogeneity within ethnic groups.

To begin to obtain a comprehensive picture across Scotland requires comparable data. However, this is a difficult undertaking given that BME communities are not a homogenous group. There is a large variety of these communities in the UK and in Scotland, with cultural variations between them, and within each group, as well as differences between those who were born in another country and those born after parental migration. Indeed, changes in the population due to migration is difficult to ascertain as people can enter Scotland through a wide variety of routes and for varying purposes, such as to work, study etc. with no one source that can provide this information (National Records of Scotland, 2018).

The geographical context is important when considering the risk factors that explain both the use of AOD and developing problems among BMEs in Scotland. It is clear that poverty and inequality are risk factors that can lead to increased likelihood for the development of drug problems. The evidence for this explaining drug use and problems in Scotland is less clear cut. It is commonly accepted that a large proportion of problematic drug and alcohol users known to addiction services that provide treatment, are concentrated in areas characterised by deprivation (McPhee et al., 2013).

However, little is understood about the impact of culture on how problem use is understood in BME populations. Where poverty and minority groups intersect, social problems such as poor health, crime, and unemployment are reported (Pearson and Patel, 1998; Johl, 2017; Skjærvø, 2018; Murji, 2019). Large scale studies on BMEs have predominantly been conducted in the US, and provide evidence of ethnic minorities living in poverty in comparison to the white population who are perceived to be more at risk of developing alcohol and drug problems (Stronks and Kunst, 2009; Wenham, 2015).

This is also true for BMEs in England (Darlington et al., 2015; Shaw et al., 2016), however the socioeconomic context in Scotland is more varied (Scottish Government, 2014). The 2011 Scottish census indicates that individuals from Indian, Chinese, and mixed ethnicities reside in the least deprived neighbourhoods. Individuals that define themselves as 'other' (non-white) and 'other Asian' report residing in areas that are most deprived. While this was also similar for Pakistanis, there was a large proportion who live in areas that are neither affluent nor deprived. Known as 'middle areas', within the SIMD (Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation) decile, where one is the most deprived area and 10 those areas that are least deprived. Hence, areas that fall between four or five would be middle areas. Other ethnicities that live in the most deprived areas include African, Caribbean or Black. The Scottish Government analysis further indicates differences using a comparison between Scottish and English data. Compared to Scotland, a higher proportion of Indian, Pakistani,

Bangladeshi and mixed ethnic groups in England lived in the most deprived neighbourhoods (Scottish Government, 2014).

Given the above, BME groups reported and estimated use of AOD in Scotland also vary when compared to England. For instance, Jivraj and Khan (2013) reported that among those BMEs in England who reside in deprived neighbourhoods with low income, lacking education, having limited access to health services and with higher levels of unemployment were more likely to use and report problems with the use of AOD. While ethnic concentrations are more widespread in areas in England, this it is not as prevalent in Scotland. Data that is collected by health care services in Scotland, are often driven by clinical demand and therefore less responsive to social processes, meaning that there is great difficulty in estimating the patterns, prevalence and risk factors for AOD use and problems (Jarvis, 2009).

The latest figures from the Scottish Drug Misuse Database (SDMD) indicate the prevalence of four illicit drugs between the period of 2006-2015 for people known to services (NHS Scotland, 2018). Heroin was reported as being the drug that was most used, followed by cannabis, diazepam and cocaine. Similar findings were also reported among ADP⁴ and NHS Board areas.

It is crucial to note that while estimates of AOD is available for the general population, BME use of AOD is not available. While ethnic categorisation

⁴ Alcohol and Drug Partnerships

has been used during routine data collection by health boards, it is still limited as it does not often include information on age, gender, religion or socio-economic context. This then substantiates the assumption that BMEs in Scotland have lower levels of drug use or abstain.

2.3 Ethnicity and Ethnic Identity

The following section reviews how ethnicity and identity are understood and presented in the existing literature. In doing so, a distinction is made between ethnicity as individual identity and its widespread use as a category for measurement and comparison.

The concept of ethnicity has no universal definition, and could be argued as having different meanings across time, places and people (Quintana, 2007; Marcia et al., 2012; Phinney and Ong, 2007). Culture is not implicitly defined by ethnicity alone, as religion also plays a role in influencing identity construction and perception. Ethnicity can be divided into two concepts – identity and category. As an identity, ethnicity can be described as the means with which people distinguish an 'us' from a 'them' through a feeling of belonging and through principles of social structuring, thereby forming a discrete category of identity (Jenkins, 2014; Ahmad and Bradby, 2007). However, individual ethnic identities may be formed by a number of factors ranging from country of origin, religion, language etc. (Jenkins, 2014). In differentiating between ethnic categories and ethnic identity, Subhra (2002) describes ethnic categories as the process by which external

categories are created and imposed by others and with which people so categorised may or may not identify themselves. On the other hand, ethnic identity is associated with country of origin and is a factor when people identify themselves as for example British, or Scottish. For instance, African as a category discreetly downplay the reality that this continent encompasses many diverse and different countries, using a wide variety of languages and localized dialects and tribal customs and practices, religions, and diverse belief systems. In order to understand this use of category as an identity marker in its entirety it is necessary to reflect on the anthropological foundations of ethnicity.

From an anthropological perspective Comaroff (1987) observes that ethnicity is an ontological dichotomy, as on the one hand it is regarded as a unique explanatory factor for various human actions and beliefs, and yet on the other hand, it can form an object of analysis to explain other forms of human attitudes, beliefs and behaviour. In Anthropological research literature (Leach, 1952), ethnicity emerged as a problem in a study on Kachins of northern Burma, where members of a social group do not need to share idiosyncratic cultural traits. Leach argued that subjective processes of categorical designation are what produce social units, and these designations do not necessarily need to have any relationship to the observer's perceptions of cultural discontinuity. Thereby contributing to the debate as to whether social units should be based on the observer's criteria or on the original-ethnic social distinction. This then led to a successive shift to whether subjective claims to ethnic identity derived from the

biological sense closely related to race - 'primordial attachments' (Geertz, 1963; Isaacs, 1975) or that of 'instrumental manipulation' and social construction (Wallerstein, 1960; Cohen, 2014).

The differences between these two approaches stems from their different assumptions about human actions. The instrumentalists within this area of study consider human actions as rationally oriented towards practical goals when faced with socioeconomic changes, thereby leading to circumstantial manipulation of identities. Hence, people with common interests, for instance those with the same ethnicity, form groups to maintain their interests (Cohen, 2014). On the other hand, 'primordialists' view actions as value-oriented, stressing the emotional power of primeval symbols (Bentley, 1987; Ahmad and Bradby, 2007). Instrumentalists regard the market allocation of resources to rationalise ethnic conflict (Despres and Smith, 1967; Alvin and Kenneth, 1972); while primordialists favour the adaption of ethnic collectivities through communal pluralism (Powell, 1979, Glazer, 1983).

In opposition, Bentley (1987) notes that both models fail to address how people recognise common interests or sentiments to their claims of common identity. While primordialists detail diverse forms of symbols (e.g. familial decent, religion, language etc.) to explain shared ideas, they fail to explain what elements of commonality are confirmed in these particular symbols within a particular context. Instrumentalists, on the other hand view ethnicity as a conscious but fluid rather than fixed expression of short-

term economic interests. Both models have not considered the peculiarities by which collectives of interests come into existence (Bentley, 1987). Ultimately ethnicity involves a claim to be identified as a particular kind of person, irrespective of whether the individual's interest is to favour kin, ecological adaptation, shared attitudes to production and distribution of wealth, resources and power (Miles, 1984; Phizacklea, 1984; Hunt and Kolind, 2017; Jenkins, 2014) etc. In this sense, ethnicity is a symbolic interpretation of similarity and variation and at least in part, a social construct.

As a basis for developing the subsequent argument, the 'theory of practice' formulated by Bourdieu and Passeron (1977) offers significant insights. Theories of practice have Marxist underpinnings that relate to class consciousness to objective conditions of existence. In this model, ones' self-conscious explanations for action is sufficient to explain it. As such, social practices are artificially constructed as an automatic consequence of determining 'objective' structures. Central to Bourdieu and Passeron (1977) is the notion of the 'habitus' which is defined by as:

"...the structures constitutive of a particular type of environment (e.g. the material conditions of existence characteristic of a class condition) produce habitus, systems of durable, transposable dispositions... The habitus is the product of the work of inculcation and appropriation necessary in order for those products of collective history, the objective structures (e.g. language, economy, etc.) to succeed in reproducing themselves..." (Bourdieu and Passerson, 1977:72, 85).

This description of habitus is a set of generative schemas that produce and influence social practices and representations. These schemas are such that

they do not require explicit rules, and yet are goal-directed without the need for a specific means to achieve these goals. Indeed, Bourdieu contends that what is commonly considered rational interest-seeking behaviour is in actual fact a consequence of a shared understanding of one's place in one's environment. He extends that experiences of objective constraints begin early in life, for instance through the family (sexual division of labour, tasks etc.), thereby producing conditioned 'class' perceptions that occur unconsciously. Hence, while actions and identities may be purposive, their orienting logic is expected and is deeply ingrained in the schemas of practice. Likewise, a sense of belonging or ethnic affinity is established on grounds of common life experiences, successively generating similar habitual dispositions (Bentley, 1987; Merriam, 2017). For instance, when people migrate, they carry with them norms and values to places where they did not exist. Their sense of familiarity to each other is bolstered through a commonality of experience and the preconscious habitus it generates that gives individuals of ethnic groups a sense of familiarity and fellowship to each other. This understanding of cultural and even ethnic identity is elaborated by Epstein (1978) who describes the experiences of being Jewish to a psychoanalyst Theodor Reik:

"...a man can prefer to be together with others and even avoid his own people; he can feel estranged from them—but he can never be a stranger to them. The very intimacy of the experience, which is nothing but common memories that have become unconscious, excludes the possibility of cutting a tie that was formed, not alone by the same blood, but by the same rhythm of living." (Epstein, 1978:140).

Reik's description cited in Epstein's work captures how kinship can also become a means for expressing ethnic affinities. Kinship embodies a similitude of shared habitus of the affections and emotions that an individual relates to family members and members of an ethnic group (De Vos and Romanucci-Ross, 1975). Bentley (1987) describes habitus as the result of unconscious early childhood socialisation being modified and resulting in practice that responds to objective constraints in habitual and unexamined ways. In like manner ethnic identity is derived from the habitus of the group, which is characterised by a preconscious awareness of connection with others sharing similar habitus.

In this sense, 'class', 'race' and 'ethnicity' can be understood as simulations through which power is not just disguised, but also challenged through the '*veil of enchanted relationships*' (Bourdieu 1977). Hence, while an ethnic category as British Asian has the intention of informing a researcher seeking to analyse data, it can also be conceived as a racist notion seeking to subjugate, or at the very least categorise from a position of power, but without true awareness of what this category actually means. This highlights the rigidity of ethnic boundaries since it abandons the perspectives and models of what ethnicity is. However, it is important to

note that, the theory of habitus by Bourdieu is not free from criticism. For instance, Bourdieu is unable to explain how dispositions and motivations are created (Yelvington, 2009). In uncritically accepting Bourdieu's theory, Bentley too inherits these criticisms, with the addition that Bentley is unable to identify what kind of practices help or hinder ethnic identification, as habitus explains everything, and in many ways, nothing. Additionally, Bentley fails to give a clear definition of ethnicity with the exception of reference to ethnicity as a shared descent and kinship. A specific habitus instigates a specific ethnicity and not two ethnic identities, it goes beyond his explanations of kinship. Social representations as 'things' described by Durkheim are considered useful by some researchers in explaining ethnicity as a category of social identity, as it reflects an individual's attempts to situate themselves in their society on the basis of social representations of their society (Howarth, 2006; Duveen, 2013).

Sections 2.2 and 2.2.1 demonstrate how different authors use dissimilar ethnic terms to describe groups which while useful, do not capture what ethnicity actually is. Ethnicity as a category is used as a label which is often quite broad, and while ethnic identity is considered a means by which people identify themselves, and upon which to minimise social affront, and maximise status and act to identify where they fit in social hierarchies. These explanations of ethnicity as a category of meaning do not fully capture what it means to be 'ethnic'. The debate exposes the complexity about the appropriateness in identifying people by race or ethnicity which are both social constructions, which as categories ironically produce

empirical data. In classifying people as White or Black the emphasis is on racial distinction based on skin colour, while classifying people as South Asian or Chinese denotes the country of origin of the individual. Such inconsistencies in government and national census statistics can often reinforce racial differences while failing to understand the cultural differences of the individuals who have been classified in this manner. Even in studies that make reference to the ethnicity of participants, what is used is a combination of ethnic and racial categories, which fails to uncover the differences within groups, as it obscures the differences in experiences and attitudes of individuals.

These issues are significant in the field of alcohol and drug research. Adopting a context-specific notion of ethnicity allows for some comparisons to be made on how an individual's socioeconomic and geographical environments influence and constrain them. In this respect, through social practices, the ethnic identity of an individual continues to be constructed and re-constructed. In a similar manner, the consumption of AOD as commodities like music or clothes can become an important symbol of individual ethnic identity and acts as a boundary marker between their social group and other groups. By exploring how BME individuals' use or avoid alcohol and other drugs helps illustrate how this impacts personal and socially defined identities.

2.4 BME Alcohol & Drug Use in UK

The following section critically examines the literature on patterns and trends of alcohol and drug use among BME groups in the UK. Also considered are the limitations of epidemiological data in describing and understanding the customs and habits of a diverse heterogeneous population.

2.4.1 Alcohol Use

Existing research in the UK indicates that individuals from BME backgrounds tend to have higher rates of abstinence and if they report the use of alcohol, they do not drink as much as the British population (Bayley and Hurcombe, 2011). However, it is difficult to determine whether there are changes in drinking patterns among BME groups due to the small sample size of the studies or the increased focus on problem populations, and estimating risks from such data (Hunt et al., 2018; Bayley and Hurcombe, 2011).

There has been a lack of distinct research in this area of BME alcohol use and particularly so in Scotland. A key study by Heim et al., (2006) examined the rate of observed or reported abstinence from alcohol among BMEs in Greater Glasgow and reported the proportion of those who did not drink as follows: Pakistanis (91%) were the highest; followed by Afro-Caribbean (64%); Chinese (63%); Indian (57%), and the general (identified as white) population (30%). Heim et al., (2006) reported that 70% of the general (white) population reported lower levels of consumption than BMEs. However, self-reported results are not always accurate due to

methodological difficulties. Some participants in this study were remunerated for taking part, and this may have impacted on response rates, and as alcohol use is much stigmatised among some groups with certain religious observances, this may have influenced what was reported, and what could reasonably be concluded in this study.

A study by Bhopal et al., (2012) reveal that more European respondents reported more frequent alcohol and tobacco use than those in minority ethnic groups; and in surveys which examined alcohol use by religion, fewer Muslim participants reported drinking alcohol than other groups. However, it could be argued that such responses could be a result of the interviewers identified as being from a similar ethnic/ religious group, and this may have influenced what was reported. Furthermore, there were difficulties in categorisation of the participants, which may have confounded the data, and what could be concluded from it.

Indeed, while certain groups place cultural and religious restrictions on the use of alcohol, complex patterns of alcohol use coexist within these communities. Studies from Purser et al., (2001); Subhra and Chauhan, (1999) and Subhra (2002) document alcohol consumption among both males and females with heavy drinking occasions reported as uncommon.

In a community survey by Cochrane and Bal (1990), 800 Sikh, Hindu, Muslim and White men in the West Midlands was conducted. The survey reported Sikhs as being most likely to be regular drinkers (and reported family problems), followed by Whites (reported problems with the law) and

Hindus. Among both Sikhs and Hindus, alcohol consumption was heaviest among older men, thereby challenging the notion that heavy alcohol consumption is a youthful activity. The survey further showed that alcohol related problems were positively related with consumption levels for all groups, and the few Muslims who drank reported to have the highest rates of problems. This study demonstrates that while the individuals had similar consumption rates, there were differing contexts and consequences. However, the authors did not explain the reasons for excessive consumption among Muslims, particularly given the prohibitions imposed in Islam. The potential for reporting bias must also be acknowledged due to the implications of reporting alcohol use among Muslims. However, recent studies indicate that the drinking rates of second generation Sikh males are similar to that of the first generation, while second generation Muslim males drink more than those who migrated (Orford et al., 2004; Bradby and Williams, 2006; Johl, 2017). These studies indicate a complexity in reported use and problems with alcohol, that BME populations are homogeneous and can be easily categorised based on religion, ethnicity, gender, and age.

Surveys and routine data collection from health services also form a source of data on alcohol consumption for BMEs. A longitudinal study by Denscombe and Drucquer (2000) compared the drinking patterns of White and South Asian 15-16 year olds in 1990 and 1997 in East Midlands. They reported the levels of abstinence between both groups decreased during this period, suggesting that the differences between the ethnic groups may be narrowing. However, reported use of alcohol among South Asians was

still significantly lower than their White counterparts. Similarly, a longitudinal study of alcohol cirrhosis by ethnicity over 14 years by Douds et al., (2003), revealed cirrhosis diagnosis occurring among a greater proportion of South Asian men in comparison to the local white population in Birmingham. The authors noted that majority of South Asian males were non-Muslim and were younger than the local white patients.

It is important to note that there are considerable ethnic differences among migrants to Britain from the Indian, African and Chinese subcontinents, and consumption patterns for these different groups need to be disaggregated to gain a clearer understanding of these groups use and reported avoidance or abstinence from alcohol (Orford et al., 2004; Bayley and Hurcombe, 2011; Hanna et al., 2006). Furthermore, there are considerable regional variations in drinking practices among First generation Asians (Rassool, 2006). Harrison et al., (1997) suggest that migrants from Muslim Pakistan and Bangladesh are primarily abstinent, while Indian drinking practices vary. Several Indian states prohibit alcohol, yet there are other states where consumption is high e.g. Punjab, Kerala etc. People from mixed ethnic backgrounds are less likely to abstain and more likely to drink heavily compared to other non-white minority ethnic groups. However, while this study explored substance and alcohol use related morality among first generation migrants in England and Wales, it was unable to establish that the deaths were caused by the use of alcohol.

The studies cited above indicate that there is a tendency for inconsistency due to the incorrect categorisation of respondents for instance, occasionally by nationality, by religion and at other times grouped together into categories such as 'South Asian', merging a diverse range of people from different cultures and religions into one explanatory category for ease of comparison.

Research by Cameron et al., (2002) focused on both South Asian and White British males, with South Asian males indicating that their social networks, family and honour (reputation and status) were negatively affected if they were known to use alcohol. However, the study did not employ rigorous means of data analysis and Sikh males were overrepresented, and as this group do report high rates of problem drinking, this may have influenced the results. This overrepresentation of Sikhs was rationalised as one of the interviewers were Sikh, and as Sikhs were more forthcoming about their use of alcohol, this explained their inclusion and overrepresentation in this study. Furthermore, while first- and second-generation males were included in the study, no generational differences in the levels of consumption were reported.

While these studies discuss the patterns and trends in the use of alcohol among BMEs in the UK, some reservations are necessary as they cannot be generalised. Surveys and data collection among BMEs often underestimate alcohol consumption, while localised small scale studies have a tendency of over representing certain groups (e.g. Sikhs, Bangladeshis), and incorrectly

categorise individuals on the basis of religion rather than nationality. As a result of such discrepancies, the diversity of ethnic groups and their reported and estimated consumption of alcohol are often inaccurate. The next section considers studies of drug use amongst BMEs.

2.4.2 Drug Use

British researchers have not explored BME drug use in much detail, relative to that of the general (white) population (Wanigaratne et al., 2003; Beddoes et al., 2010; Rassool, 2006). This may be due to several factors, and most significant is the level of distrust and difficulty in accessing BME populations and recruiting them into surveys and other research studies. There are commonly reported suspicions that White-academic research teams will present their people unfavourably. There are also issues that prevent accurate reporting of drug taking in BME families and communities and widespread denial of drug use by individuals or the use of a community spokesperson to talk to researchers which seeks to avoid stigmatisation of the community etc. are all known barrier in both accessing and making comparison between and within groups very difficult (Fountain, 2003; Patel, 2000; Patel et al., 2004). Attempts to address the impact or influence of ethnicity on use and avoidance are further complicated by the assumed heterogeneity of the BME population by researchers both due to convenience and lack of awareness, and also due to poor methodologies in research (Jayakody et al., 2006; Pannu et al., 2009; Williams et al., 2017).

Evidence on ethnic variations in reported rates of the use of illicit drugs is derived primarily from official statistics (e.g. Crime Surveys (Home Office National Statistics, 2014) in England and Wales, and in Scotland – Census and population surveys (e.g. Scottish Health Surveys and Local Surveys by Health Boards). The 1991 UK Census was the first to include a question on ethnic origin, and to categories BME's by ethnic identity primarily by geographical region (African, Asian, or Chinese origin for example) in England and Wales (Bulmer, 1991). The 1994 British Crime Survey (BCS) was the first to adapt and include questions on illicit drug use in England and Wales (Ramsay and Percy, 1996). It reports data on drug use in relation to gender, age (those between the ages of 16-59), socioeconomic status, ethnicity, types of drugs used and the levels of use. The BCS reported highest lifetime prevalence of drug use to be for Whites, followed by Black and then those from Indian, Pakistani, and Bangladeshi origins.

A review of the BCS by Sangster et al., (2002a) reveals that the proportion of BME respondents were too small to conduct a meaningful analysis of the heterogeneity between the groups. Subsequently the BCS in 2000 included an ethnic booster sample which revealed a higher proportion of BME drug users in comparison to previous BCS surveys (Ramsay et al., 2001). Nevertheless, the reported levels of drug use among BME individuals as a percentage of the total population were lower than the white population. Its method of data collection and unintentional misrepresentation of those who reported the use of drugs reduces its validity. The BCS explicitly fails to identify BME populations due to aggregation of census categories into

five broad groups. Furthermore, while the religion category acknowledges religious affiliation, its usefulness as a category is limited, as not only do religions span ethnicities and continents, but it does not account for an individual's devotion and practices to their religion. Religious affiliation is insufficient as a measure to argue that people will consume less or abstain from the use of AOD based solely on whether they do or do not identify with a religious group that promotes abstinence, or has nothing to say about the use of alcohol as a marker of religious identity and affiliation. Furthermore, self-reported drug use is further made inaccurate due to fear of sanctions, or when used as an indicator for requiring help and or support to access treatment, housing or other state service (Napper et al., 2010; Cohen et al., 2007).

In studies that have targeted South Asians (Southern Asia is vast and comprises Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal, India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka), the heterogeneous nature of this group have been neglected and ethnicity has been substituted with religion, for instance Hindu, Muslim, Sikh individuals (Ahmad and Bradby, 2007). Furthermore, South Asians do not just differ in geographical terms, but they also speak and write different languages such as – Hindi, Urdu, Malayalam, Tamil, Telegu, Kannada, etc. Attempts to differentiate between the social significance of Hinduism as a religion and identity and not an ethnic trait has been absent in research that uses this broad category of ethnicity.

Research has broadly concluded that BME drug users are under-represented in drug treatment numbers for many of the reasons documented earlier, and as a result of several factors including structural racism, and police using scarce resources to target specific areas, BME's are, certainly in England and Wales, over-represented in drug law offence statistics (Fountain et al., 2002; Mitchell and Caudy, 2017). The myths and stereotypes that surround BME groups are under-researched and as such, claims made both within and without these groups can neither be contested nor confirmed (Williams et al., 2017). Adverse media reports further heighten BME individuals' association with drugs in the UK who stand out from the white population due to their skin colour, and as an example there are assumptions that certain ethnic groups are concerned in large scale organised criminal networks supplying drugs (Fountain et al., 2002). Such assumptions, as well as how crime statistics are used in sensationalist media stories gives an extremely distorted picture of the prevalence of drug use and of drug-using patterns among BMEs (this is further explored in Sections 2.4 and 2.4.2).

Furthermore explanations of drug use have often focused on the impact of social exclusion, educational disadvantage and deprivation because of unemployment in England (Seddon, 2006; Hunt et al., 2018) to explain sociologically the factors that lead to the misuse of AOD by BME groups. Hence, BMEs are often considered to be at risk of problematic drug use despite evidence that they are less likely than white respondents to use illicit drugs (Heim et al., 2006; Bradby, 2007; Fountain et al., 2003). As

such, it is assumed that drug use is insignificant among BME groups, or that use is intentionally concealed due to fears of stigma and shame within specific types of ethnic and religious communities. Also evident is the greater focus on male drug users and less so on female users (Bashford et al., 2003; Fountain et al., 2003; Fountain, 2009; Rassool, 2006). Additionally lacking is research that considers drug use beyond social exclusion and deprivation among BME groups (Hunt et al., 2018; Nazroo, 2006; Jivraj and Khan, 2013; Mantovani and Evans, 2019). For instance, the prevalence of non-problematic use of drugs.

Numerous quantitative studies present estimates of the patterns and prevalence of the use of drugs among BMEs and support the impression that drug use is on the increase, and that this is deterministically linked causally to negative consequences. The use of qualitative research methods by Cottew and Oyefeso (2005) explored drug use of Bangladeshi women in London. The study included eight female participants and explored their perception of drug use, the role of 'honour' in contributing to secrecy in drug use and perception of treatment services. The Bangladeshi women were considered to constitute an at-risk population as they were financing their drug use through commercial unsafe sex work with injecting and non-injecting drug users. This study provides important insights into the shame and stigma of illicit drug use among Bangladeshi females, as previous research has mostly focused on Bangladeshi males. A study by Mantovani and Evans (2019) also reported shame and stigma occurring in both sexes of Bangladeshi men and women in London who used drugs. Drug use was

associated with a stain on their characters, loss of status associated with heritage and resulted in identity crisis. Some participants also questioned whether they had become 'westernised' and as a result had broken links to their culture and identity.

A comparative study between South Asian and white males in Glasgow found that South Asians did report the use of drugs, but that their use was lower in comparison to the white sample (Khan et al., 2000). This was attributed to South Asians knowing fewer drug contact sources than the white participants. Conversely Arora and Khatun (1998) in a Bradford-based study among Asians, discovered that rates of alcohol, drugs and tobacco use matched that of the general (white) population. Research by Patel et al., (1996) and Chaudry et al., (1997) on South Asians found that a large proportion of participants were drug aware, and had in some way assimilated the prevailing cultural norms in their geographical location in the UK. While dated, these studies contradict the assumption that BMEs do not use drugs and that their cultural identities act as protective factors in minimising their drug taking.

Furthermore, while some studies have attempted to capture the prevalence of drug use in particular minority groups, the data on patterns of use is often difficult to obtain as communities fear societal reprimands and shame. Due to the diversity of ethnic groups, generalising findings is challenging. Regardless of the fact that there is a gap in more recent research, existing qualitative and quantitative studies indicate that there is a prevalence of

drug and alcohol use among BME groups, and that it is increasing even though rates are lower than the white population. The covert nature of illicit drug use is such that true estimates are inconceivable, and care needs to be exercised in interpreting prevalence data as it does not present a detailed picture of the extent of use.

The studies documenting the known patterns and prevalence of BME alcohol and drug use is dated, however they have contributed in highlighting the prevalence of alcohol and drug use among BMEs in UK. However, with the lack of more recent studies it is difficult to confirm whether certain BME groups have been perceived to be at greater risk than other BME groups (e.g. Bangladeshis and Sikh's). As outlined previously, poor ethnic categorisations does not reflect the diversity of the populations or the true nature of drug and alcohol use. Indeed, those BME groups more recently established in the UK have been overlooked (e.g. South Indian migrants from Kerala, Tamil Nadu etc.). Also evident is the lack of standardised tools to measure BME alcohol and drug use in Scotland, which is more sensitive to cultural constructs as beliefs, values, norms, etc. to help capture the core life experiences of BME individuals. Apart from surveys and data collection by local health services, there have not been any contemporary large-scale studies to document BME individuals' use of alcohol and other drugs.

The next section explores how culture is defined within the context of AOD use.

2.5 Alcohol Use in a Cultural context

Culture is a complex term which holds multiple meanings based on its context (Spencer-Oatey and Franklin, 2012). Culture influences an individual's beliefs and values to the extent that it goes beyond ethnicity. This section outlines the relevant components of culture that underpin the definition of this concept from a psychological and sociological perspective.

Culture is a term which is used differently in different contexts. Generally when considering culture Spencer-Oatey (2008) notes that:

"Culture is a fuzzy set of basic assumptions and values, orientations to life, beliefs, policies, procedures and behavioural conventions that are shared by a group of people, and that influence (but do not determine) each member's behaviour and his/her interpretations of the 'meaning' of other people's behavior." (Spencer-Oatey, 2008:3).

Belonging to different cultural groups can include being defined by ethnicity, linguistic background, country of origin, religious background, shared customs etc. Each facet of identity is expressed and maintained in its patterns of behavior and organisation. Cultural identity as a dynamic concept which is ever-changing and forms a defining feature of every individual's identity contributing to how they see themselves and the groups with which they identify (Liebkind, 1992; Berry, 1997; Berry, 2003; Harries et al., 2016).

Research by Wirth (1964) asserts that human behaviours are labelled as social problems when they are defined by certain groups as breaching

dominant cultural codes, and that cultural conflicts are therefore central to understanding crime and delinquency. He further argued about the personal meaning that individuals gave to cultural values, remarking that:

"...a culture has no psychological significance until it is referred to a personality..." (Wirth, 1964:239).

In relation to personal identity and the meaning that alcohol has to an individual in his or her culture is influenced by cultural beliefs within that individual's culture.

Each society has its own culture and individuals within that society learn habits and tend to confirm what that culture 'knows' about alcohol, influencing use or abstention, and behaviour while intoxicated. What alcohol means to an individual in a cultural context has been documented in several key pieces of historical research that explored the use of alcohol cross-culturally (MacAndrew and Edgerton, 1969; Heath, 1991; Babor, 2010; MacAndrew and Edgerton, 2003). The first large scale research documenting the use of alcohol cross-culturally was conducted by MacAndrew and Edgerton (1969) in their book 'Drunken Comportment'. While the use of alcohol produced universal outcomes at large doses, such as sleep, slurred speech, and impaired gait, other outcomes appeared to be unique to cultural beliefs about the use of alcohol, and cultural expectations while intoxicated, known as 'drunken comportment'. Of the 46 cultures included in their research, aggression and overt sexuality was documented in less than one fifth, suggesting that cultural norms have a

great influence on intoxicated behaviour rather than pharmacology or genetics alone.

There are several univariate theories that seek to explain why individuals in society use psychoactive substances that alter how they perceive their social worlds. Historically, prior to a scientific revolution associated with a decline in the power of religion to help us understand our reality, religious leaders and religious doctrine provided answers that explained breaches of social norms as the work of the devil (McPhee et al., 2013). Post enlightenment, several perspectives explain breaches of social norms using theories resting on biology, genetics and exposure of powerful drugs that enslave the users brain (West and Brown, 2013; Leshner, 1997). However, such monocausal explanations fail to explain the reason for breaching social norms and trying for example illegal drugs, or the use of alcohol in a culture that condemns use. In order to explain how and in what way culture contributes to individual decision making about whether one uses or abstains from AOD to explain the factors that make AOD use seem desirable, and explain why breaches of social norms occur, and also, once deviance such as alcohol use in a 'dry' culture is discovered, why it might continue, or stop.

Unlike biological and psychological theories that place great emphasis on individual factors, sociologists focus on broader structural factors that go beyond the characteristics of the individual to explain deviance. Here the focus is on the situations, social relations or structures in which the

individual is situated in. Table 1 presents an overview of theories of deviance. As previously discussed, the UN conventions makes it illegal to possess commodities as cocaine, heroin etc. By focusing on drug use as deviance this section will discuss how and in what way deviance occurs.

Table 1: Sociological Theories of Drug Use

Authors	Theory	Description
Merton (1968); Goode (1960); Cloward (1959)	Anomie tradition, also known as Strain Theory	Distinctions between institution of control in society (e.g. family and religion) exist to regulate human behaviours (e.g. the use of drugs). While success is achievable by every social actor, it is often only attainable by a small section in 'modern culture'. Hence deviant behaviour is explained by an inability of these structural factors to regulate conduct.
Hirschi (1969), (Hirschi, 1986)	Social Control Theory	Considers the decisions individuals make based on internal and external controls on the basis of class. Middle class individuals are perceived to hold attachments with institutions or people, commitment to convention, belief in the moral validity of norms etc. For example, middle class individuals were perceived to be able to defer gratification which was perceived to be their key to success unlike the working classes. This was perceived to reduce the probability of deviance. Individuals unable to defer gratification are more susceptible to hedonistic pleasure and hence deviance. Absence of bonds to conventional society is considered to lead to deviance.

<p>Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990), Hay (2001); Ford and Blumenstein (2013)</p>	<p>Self-control Theory</p>	<p>The authors put forward their own theory of deviance where the absence of self-control leads to criminality. For example, individuals with high self-control consider the long-term consequences of their behaviour while those with low self-control engage in deviance. They argue that self-control is learned usually early in life, and once learned, is highly resistant to change, making inferences to inadequate parenting, or inadequate socialising and lack of self-control which explains deviance. The authors argue that people who lack self-control are more likely to engage not just in criminal activities but also deviant behaviours such as drinking, smoking and gambling. Such behaviours offers short-term pleasure with minimal effort. Furthermore, such individuals are unable to consider the long-term consequences of their actions due to low self-control. More recent research by Ford and Blumenstein (2013) offers general support of self-control theory across binge drinking, cannabis use and prescription drug misuse as an inability to exercise control.</p>
<p>Akers (2011); Akers (1996); Rosenstock et al., (1988); Becker (2008)</p>	<p>Social Learning Theory</p>	<p>Informs that behaviour is learned through face-to-face interaction with others. Learning is also dependent on priority, intensity and duration, and involves various techniques, motives and attitudes, including rewards and punishments (differential reinforcement), where individuals associate with groups or people who reward or punish behaviour. Some</p>

		<p>theorists have argued that not all learning takes place face-to-face (differential identification).</p>
<p>Matza and Blomberg (2017); Sykes and Matza (2002); Cohen and Short (1958)</p>	<p>Subcultural Theories related to Social Learning theory and includes: Group Socialisation, Identity Change.</p>	<p>Through social learning individuals learn to violate norms, and need only one significant other to learn that violation is acceptable. Subcultural theories explore how individuals learn a different set of norms and construct their social identity on the basis of these new norms.</p>
<p>Johnson (1973)</p>	<p>Selective interaction/socialisation</p>	<p>In this theory deviance is explained theory individuals who seek out similar deviants who share their values and attitudes. Considers the transition that individuals undergo during their developmental stage, and how they are drawn to other deviants. This results in alienation of parental subculture norms. From this theory deviants experience and accept a new subculture where the use of drugs is accepted as there are deviants who also use drugs. Hence, the closer the bond with the group, greater is the impact of the shared values and norms, normalising this deviance.</p>
<p>Reinarman and Levine (1997); Currie (1994)</p>	<p>Conflict Theory</p>	<p>Considers the differences in power, income, class, and opportunities, between social classes. This theory also seeks to explain how drug experimentation becomes compulsive and problematic. It highlights that there are two types of drug use: recreational drug use (this notion varies by culture), and problematic use (as a result of class inequality and focuses on at-risk populations).</p>

It is evident from a summary of the sociology of deviance in Table 1 that there is a degree of overlap among sociological theories that explain drug use in a society that condemns it. Theories of deviance help explain how individual behaviour violates cultural norms. This helps explain how an individual's use of alcohol in certain cultures is highly stigmatised, while drug use is routinely condemned and controlled globally.

Deviance in the context of anomie theory holds that people feel alienated when commonly held norms and values disappear, which can result in for e.g. self-destructive behaviour like drug use. Anomie theory describes problematic users as being a 'double failure' (Cloward and Ohlin, 1998; Toby et al., 1961; Merton, 1968) as they are unsuccessful in using legitimate and illegitimate means to achieve success, and thrive in late modernity. However, this theory has been criticised for failing to explain the cause of drug use, abuse or addiction. Nevertheless, the theory does provide some useful insights into how illegitimate means of achieving success is conceivable, for instance through drug dealing, which can be considered to be an innovative means to achieving success (Adler and Laufer, 1995; Goode, 2006; Preble and Casey, 1969; Goode, 2015).

The concept of social control refers to the process of how individual behaviour can be regulated, or alternatively, how the larger social institutions such as education, religion, law etc. help maintain order in society (Wiatrowski et al., 1981; Goode, 2015). Social control theory emphasises the invisible bond between the individual and society which

acts to prevent from becoming involved in delinquent behaviours, suggesting that it is precisely those individuals who fail to form a bond and become delinquents (Hirschi, 1969). In other words, people will deviate from social norms unless constrained. Social control, self-control and social learning theory within the context of deviance are explored in greater detail in Section 2.5.1.

Subcultural theories of socialisation suggest that identity, norms and values occur as a result of individuals absorbing the values and customs of a specific subcultures. Becker (1953) focused on individuals' motivations to use and experience marijuana⁵ as well as the pleasure derived from its use. Becker argued that pleasure was attained from learning how to use the drug to allow the user to appreciate the effects of the drug. This involved learning to enjoy the effects, as otherwise the sensations from the use of the drug were not pleasurable. Furthermore, merely learning to use marijuana is insufficient to explain the deviance as the individual has to learn how to deal with non-users and others in positions of power (moral entrepreneurs) who use their influence to try to prevent and even stop the deviance from continuing. Later publishing (*Outsiders: Studies in the Sociology of Deviance*) in 1963, Becker points out that deviant behaviour occurs when:

⁵ The use of this terms has a long history associated with racism, and in Spanish it literally translates as 'Mary-Jane', a derogatory term linking use with the moral failure of Mexican immigrants to become part of American society. I will use the term here as Becker intended, however in all other instances, I will refer to drug originating from the Cannabin genus as cannabis.

"...people are emancipated from the controls of society and become responsive to those of a smaller group...a subcultural group" (Becker, 1963:60).

Hence for users to continue their use of cannabis, they need to have a dependable supply of the drug, manage their use illicitly and in secret from disapproving others, and identify means to invalidate the moral objections that mainstream society uses to enforce these socially constructed norms. As such, Becker's model explains not only why individuals first use drugs, and how they learn to enjoy it, but also explains how and in what way it becomes necessary to justify their use, and their perceived deviance beyond their chosen sub culture to whom the cannabis user identifies. He argues that this is only possible through the individual's involvement and contact with members in a specific group. It should be noted that the model does not address the reasons why certain individuals are attracted to the use of drugs or groups who use drugs.

Research by Johnson (1973) and Kandel (1980) also make reference to subcultural and socialisation theory to explain how deviance occurs. Johnson discusses socialisation in the context of an individual's transition from adolescents to adulthood, where adolescents are isolated from their parent's subculture, which is more conventional and anti-drug, to having more involvement with a peer subculture which in comparison is unconventional. Consequently, adolescents who have a stronger affinity with the peer subculture are more susceptible to experimenting with drugs, while those who have a greater attachment to the parental subculture

adhere to its norms and abstain from drugs. Hence, the more involved one is with a peer subculture, the more one is influenced by its values and engage in its activities, which challenge their parental views on social norms.

Kandel's Model of Socialisation incorporates concepts from social learning theory, social control, as well as subcultural theories and gives greater emphasis to 'selective recruitment', explaining how deviants act volitionally and choose the groups to which they wish to identify with. She contends that during the transition from adolescents to adults an individual's drug and alcohol use also experience changes, where there are periods when individuals drift from one group to another. For instance, in early adolescence alcohol is the drug of choice, and hence the need for an associated circle of peers who use alcohol (Kandel et al., 1978; Kandel, 1980). Engaging with others creates opportunities for experimenting with cigarettes, and other drugs such as cannabis. Kandel argues that in middle adolescence, strong changes in values and lifestyle is a predictor for the use of cannabis (Kandel and Logan, 1984). During this stage, attitudes towards drug use are very important as peer influences are the strongest, while parental influences are in comparison weakest. In later adolescence, psychological pressure (more troubled adolescents tend to gravitate to groups and individual who use 'harder'⁶ drugs), relationships with parents

⁶ I use this terms as Kandel uses it, however recognising that the category 'hard' and 'soft' drugs are in essence meaningless, and are a reflection of the cultural domination of one group over another in creating discourse highlighting what is and is not to be labelled and categorised as dangerous.

(the greater the disaffection with parents, the higher the likelihood to try harder drugs); and relationship with peers (having at least one friend who uses drugs assumes central importance) influence drug use, and acts as a predictor of full engagement with deviant sub groups.

Conflict theory is comprehensive in nature, as it not only seeks to explain factors that influence individuals, but also members of a whole society, or neighbourhoods or communities. Goode (2006) asserts that conflict theory is useful as a means to explain heavy, chronic or compulsive use/misuse of heroin and crack and does not fully explain the use of 'soft (sic) drugs such as alcohol, tobacco and cannabis. He argues that conflict theory can in part explain issues that are the most troubling to the public. However, advocates of the theory argue that heavy and problematic use of heroin and crack are a result of economic and political changes and are related to social class, income, power and locale. Hence, problematic use of drugs are most likely to be identified among the deprived than the affluent communities (Lupton et al., 2002; Seddon, 2006). Nevertheless, it is important to note that even individuals from middle-class backgrounds can experience problematic drug use. It is however clear that individuals from deprived backgrounds are exposed to greater risk factors for using drugs problematically, and this theory suggests this is because they lack the resources to overcome the difficulties they encounter. It is their vulnerability and relative powerlessness that exacerbates their situation (Walsh et al., 2010).

The sociology of deviance highlights that culture is a complex concept that goes beyond ethnicity and the influence of norms in explaining why people choose to use or abstain from using alcohol and other drugs. In general these theories explain deviance by explaining how deviance occurs. These include: the extent of an individual's identification with a 'deviant' group; the degree of consistency in the group's norms, as well as the presence of confounding or complementary forces (e.g. gender and/or age norms) (Oetting et al., 1998). Furthermore, the perception of risk associated with the consumption of alcohol and other drugs may differ among ethnic and cultural groups. Cultural values and norms, transmitted within the family form an important aspect, as these shape the ways in which different ethnic groups use various substances (O'Connor, 1978; Vaillant, 2013). These culturally specific traits develop in interaction with other cultures and with political, social and economic variables, and are not fixed.

While the shared norms and values of a society appear invisible to others, it has an immense impact on the way in which people behave and think as these are internalised (Hofstede and Hofstede, 2001). However, embracing other cultures is not an easy undertaking for a minority group. The tendency to identify with one's own culture and to judge other cultures on the basis of one's own cultural values is referred to as ethnocentrism (LeVine and Campbell, 1972). As such, the distinctions of 'us' and 'them' may result in discrimination, or even racism against what is seen to be dissimilar of the other culture. It is also important to consider the influence of history on an individual's perception of cultures. Indeed the experiences

of some BME groups might include internalised experiences of coming from a colonised culture, resulting in some people perceiving themselves as inferior or superior (Pyke, 2010).

2.5.1 A Sociocultural approach to understanding alcohol use

This section reviews the theoretical models that explain the various reasons how and why people drink. While alcohol use is accepted in many cultures, it is also demonised in others. The norms surrounding the moderate and excessive use of alcohol are discussed.

Alcohol is the is the most widely used means of altering human consciousness (McGovern, 2009), and yet is almost universally subject to rules and regulations unlike other drinks. However, these rules do not just apply to the drink, as every type of alcoholic drink has a symbolic meaning which governs rules regarding drunkenness and drunken comportment (MacAndrew and Edgerton 1969, 2003). Beliefs regarding the use of alcohol vary from positive, negative, or ambivalent, as well as from culture to culture, but impassivity is rare (Dietler, 2006; Heath, 2012). Cultural norms for governing drunken and sober behaviours are transmitted through a learning process associated with socialisation. Certain behaviours are considered excusable when intoxicated, and perceived inexcusable if sober and vice versa (MacAndrew and Edgerton, 1969, 2003). Even in societies that are not strongly bound by long-standing drinking traditions, the social meaning of alcohol is defined and understood. Indeed, drinking norms may vary between groups in a large social networks and result in different types

of drunken comportment within the same society (Abel and Plumridge, 2004).

Furthermore, countries have been divided into groups as either wet or dry cultures and refer to countries with high (wet) or low (dry) per capita consumption (Peele, 1997; Room and Makela, 2000; Pitman, 1965). Using a sociocultural approach to the use of alcohol, Bales (1946) was the first to contribute towards identifying four types of attitudes to drinking. First, complete abstinence (refers to Muslim societies); second, ritual attitudes (illustrated with the significance of wine in Jewish rituals); thirdly, utilitarian attitudes (refers to the functional use of alcohol and distinguishes between medicinal drinking and drinking for pleasure); and finally convivial drinking which Bales asserts is a combination of ritualistic and utilitarian attitudes towards drinking. While Bales refers to Jewish, Irish and Muslim cultures to illustrate the first three typologies, he has been criticised for failing to offer an example for his fourth typology (Room and Makela, 2000). Undoubtedly Bales demonstrated how attitudes to drinking and use and avoidance are dominated by cultural factors.

A theory by Pitman (1965) classified drinking cultures into four categories: (i) abstinent cultures, which condemn the use of alcohol in any form e.g. Muslims or Protestants; (ii) ambivalent cultures, where there is a coexistence of negative and prohibitive attitudes as well as idealising of intoxication; (iii) permissive cultures, where moderate consumption is tolerated while excessive drinking is condemned e.g. Jews and Italian

cultures; (iv) overly permissive cultures, where drinking is permissive and drunkenness is accepted in certain contexts, e.g. French cultures. With regards to the fourth category, Pitman (1965) comments:

"...in one sense, this type...does not occur completely in societies, but only approximations in certain non-literate societies, in those cultures undergoing considerable social change, and those in which there are strong economic vested interests in the production and distribution of alcoholic beverages" (Pitman, 1965:5).

Pitman argues that cultural attitudes on drinking does not always determine behaviour, rather it is the extensiveness of the alcohol consumed that correlates with the type of culture, and as such is not a perfect correlation. However, Pitman has been commended for substantiating where societies could be placed in his typology.

Cultural attitudes are only built up and passed on through habits and choices of individuals, and hence are dialectically linked. Societal reaction to alcohol users will be classified into three categorisations – deviance, disease and disability and the next section explores labelling theory and stigma.

2.5.1.1 *Deviance & Stigma*

2.5.1.1.1 *Deviance*

Deviant behaviour has been explained as a product of learning, and led to the theory of 'differential association' (Sutherland, 1939). This theory maintains that individuals associate with other individuals or subculture who define their deviance in a positive or favourable manner. As such,

deviant behaviours are learned through face-to-face interactions with significant others. Sutherland notes that the key to this process lies in the ratio between favourable and unfavourable definitions, and individuals will use alcohol for example under the age of 21 in the USA when this ratio has been exceeded.

Using a psychological perspective known as social learning theory suggest that behaviour is shaped by rewards, punishments or reinforcements (Akers and Jensen, 2011; Akers, 2017). Through the interaction with specific social circles and within that group setting through rewards and punishments, individuals learn what is considered 'good' or 'bad' behaviour. The processes of exposure, imitation of behaviour and social reinforcement direct how deviance occurs.

Both social control and self-control theories attempt to explain deviant and criminal behaviour from an individualistic perspective, with a focus on control and why some people conform to society's norms while others do not. Social control theory emphasises that deviance occurs in the absence of social control and bonds of conformity that allows individuals to be free to deviate. Hence, the more attached an individual is to the particular norms of a society, the less likely they are to engage in behaviours that would violate widely accepted, or widely disseminated norms and values (Goode, 2006). Conformity results in engagement and involvement with conventional others in society (e.g. people, employers, religion, family etc.)

and this commitment to the created bonds would make an individual less likely to engage in deviance (Hirschi, 1986).

There are ties between self-control theory and social control theory, in explaining how individuals would engage in deviance, self-control theory differs in 'how' controls come to be absent. Of emphasis here is that individuals engage in deviance (such as the use of illegal drugs) as a matter of self-interest as it provides immediate short-term pleasure (Hirschi and Gottfredson, 1994). Hence, Hirschi and Gottfredson (1994) argue that drug users lack self-control, as they are impulsive and pleasure oriented, with disregard for the long-term consequences of their actions. They further argue that the lack of self-control is a consequence of inadequate parental socialisation. Improper parental monitoring and affection to children results in a failure to mediate wrongdoings in the child, and therefore a higher likelihood to engage in drug use. Hence, lower levels of self-control signify an increased likelihood to use drugs and vice versa.

Hirschi (1969) incorporated four elements of social bond as a means to explain control. The first element being attachment to others, which has been tested by many (Hindelang, 1973; Morris, 1964; Nye, 1958; Poole and Regoli, 1979), but has revealed little consistency in the measurement of affective ties or bonds to the family. However, Hirschi noted that attachment to others was not always an effective means of constraining deviance. He also added that having friends, who were delinquent, had a deviance-producing effect rather than a constraining effect. Commitment

is the second element and refers to the 'cost' involved in engaging in deviant activities. As such, those individuals who do not want to put their social and status investments at risk, would refrain from deviant activities and be more likely to conform. The third element refers to involvement, which Hirschi views as a temporal dimension of commitment, as individuals who are involved in conventional activities would not have enough time left to pursue deviant acts. The fourth element of social bond theory is belief in conventional values and norms. Individuals who do not believe in conventional values are freed from the bond and as such, are more likely to commit deviant acts.

Hence, the meaning attributed to a particular alcoholic drink or drug explains not just the reasons for its use, but also the accepted or condemned beliefs attached to its use. While the excessive use of alcohol which leads to uncontrolled and drunken behaviour is often condemned in various cultures, the reality for a drug user is very different.

2.5.1.1.2 Stigma

The term 'stigma' originated from the Greeks, as a means to describe things that were unusual or bad about the moral status of the person concerned (for instance, signs burnt into the body to signify the bearer as a slave, criminal, ritually polluted etc.). In Roman times, individuals were branded with the use of a hot iron, to the extent that the term figuratively denoted eternal disgrace (Jones, 1987). Indeed this symbolism prevails to this day, which Goffman (1997) prudently captured. Goffman asserts that stigma

could be seen as having a double perspective; one where the stigmatised individual perceives their difference as already evident, and secondly, where their difference is not immediately apparent, it is hidden, or has the potential to be revealed. In the first scenario, the individual has an obvious stigma (e.g. facial scar), and in the second predicament, refers to the potential of being discredited if the stigma were discovered (e.g. closeted LGBT). As such, Goffman explains that there are three different types of stigmas: firstly, the body is detested due to physical deformities; secondly, it is the individuals' character that is flawed by means of being weak willed, dishonest, for their rigid beliefs, for reasons such as having mental health problems, addictions, unemployment, etc. And finally, the stigma that originates from being from a certain race, nation and religion, where the stigma can be transmitted generationally and affect all members of a family.

The foundations for labelling theory were laid by (Becker, 1963), in which he explains the means by which the powerful in society can label others to impose order and rationality in social relations. Building on Goffman and Becker, Link and Phelan (2006) proposed five interrelated components which when combined together produce stigma. These include: (i) Identification and labelling of individual differences, where the process of social selection determines which differences are considered relevant and significant and which are not (e.g. skin colour, sexual preferences etc.). (ii) The process of stereotyping, where the labelled individuals are linked to undesirable characteristics. (iii) Those that exercise the labelling process

create a separation by classifying themselves as 'us' and the stigmatised individuals as 'them'. (iv) Stigmatised individuals experience a loss of status and discrimination, thereby devaluing, and excluding them. (v) Exercising power to facilitate stigma to occur. It has also been noted by other authors that the more dangerous the possessor of the stigma is thought to be, the more rejected the individual is (Jones et al., 1984).

Lately, the term stigma is being applied to minority groups such as BME groups, disabled or those with mental health conditions, as a means to explain the stigma they face as well as the detrimental impact of discrimination on these individuals (Lloyd, 2013). Indeed, there are several behaviours and beliefs which are considered positively, even normalised by the dominant culture, and yet at the same time be considered unconventional and deviant in the same society. For instance, drinking is a social custom in Scotland, however, this is not a behaviour that is accepted within several ethnic groups (e.g. Pakistani communities; female drinking in certain Indian subgroups etc.) in Scotland. At the same time, the use of drugs, is largely criminalised and considered problematic, while still occurring despite legal and moral sanctions (Akins and Mosher, 2015).

Historically specific plants and herbs have been used in most societies for spiritual, medicinal or experimental reasons worldwide, and consequently when individuals migrate they have taken their drug-using traditions with them (Coomber and South, 2004; Klein, 2008). In the UK, Chinese migrant workers were associated with the supply of opium and cocaine in East

London, while Jamaican migrants were considered suppliers of cannabis in the early 20th century (Coomber et al., 2013). As a result, some ethnic minorities were susceptible to being stigmatised and discriminated against. Often ethnic minorities have been perceived as 'dangerous others' and demonised as providers of drugs that would contaminate the morals of the majority (Higate et al., 2006). As such, certain BME groups not only face social exclusion, poverty and discrimination, but for subsequent generations these drugs were perceived as symbolic threats that had to be removed or controlled. The 1970s saw disproportionate policing of migrant workers being targets to regulation and drug testing and as such creating tensions (Murji, 2019).

Drawing on Goffman's (2009, 1963) (helps in illuminating the process of stigmatization. He provides a detailed account of the ways in which stigmatized individuals interact with others and how this interaction is shaped by their mutual awareness of the presence of stigma.

What is evident from these explanations is that, society creates a stigma to describe those individuals who do not conform, or possess a trait that is different from culturally accepted norms (Major and O'Brien, 2005). Hence, while 'deviance' can be perceived as characteristics, beliefs or behaviours, 'the deviant' in an individual from a specific society or culture who is isolated or stigmatised in a negative manner (Goode, 2015; Sagarin, 1975). Furthermore, stigma can also be a source of stress, where individuals are constantly under the threat of being stigmatised. The stress

associated with stigma can be particularly difficult for those individuals where in their culture problematic use of alcohol or drugs is considered a disease. Indeed, the fear of being labelled may result in abstinence being considered the prevailing norm of that group. What is considered deviant varies by society and historical time periods.

Behaviour in society is regulated through its power relationships, by a system of social differentiation based on religion, gender, age, class or caste, thereby creating social inequalities (Haralambos and Foster-Carter, 1985) while also replicating power differences (Eriksen, 2001). Ideological conventions concerning male and female behaviours are internalised by individuals, and form means of social control (Hall, 2001) and are explored below.

An individual's sense of identity is grounded in their own cultural group and the dominant culture of the county in which they live, and to understand this further, theories of acculturation are now discussed.

2.5.2 Acculturation Theory

An individual's social and cultural background exerts influence on their beliefs and behaviours about their use of alcohol. Be that as it may, BME individuals also bring with them their distinctive cultures, which over time may undergo some degree of change. This section offers a lens through which BME individuals integrate some of the values and behaviours from the mainstream society they reside in. Acculturation theory offers useful

insights into an individual's cultural identity as well as how it shapes their perceptions of the use or abstinence from alcohol.

Caetano et al., (1998) defines acculturation as:

"...The adaptation to or acquisition of the beliefs and values of the dominant culture..." (Caetano et al., 1998:234).

Sumerian inscriptions dating from 2370 BC indicated that there were established written codes of law as a means to protect the traditional cultural practices from acculturative change occurring as a result of assimilating conquered people and established fixed rules for commerce with foreigners. These codes were also in place to inform foreigners of offences and punishments within Sumerian culture (Gadd, 1971; Wiseman, 1971). Archeological evidence from Egypt also indicates the existence of a code of conduct or 'acculturation policy' which separated Egyptians from Nubians, to prevent Egyptians assimilating with them (Smith, 1993). Biblical texts commonly known as the Old Testament demonstrate an acculturative perspective by giving Israelis an ethnic identity and establishing norms for intercultural contact with other groups (Jackson, 1995). Ancient Greeks were also concerned about the impact of immigrants in influencing Greek customs (Cohen, 2002; Hall, 1998). Indeed, Plato was the first to cite that acculturation could cause social disorder and suggested types of acculturation policies to limit locals to port districts to minimise their contact with immigrants, and warned that the young were particularly

vulnerable to assimilating ideas from other cultures which would weaken what it meant to be a Greek.

Acculturation came to the forefront of academic literature by anthropologists observing indigenous people (Redfield et al., 1936). These initial studies focused on how 'primitive' societies changed and became civilized through acculturative contact with the 'enlightened' western world.

The classical definition of acculturation by Redfield et al., (1936) holds that:

"Acculturation comprehends those phenomena which result when groups of individuals having different cultures comes into continuous first-hand contact, with subsequent changes in the original culture patterns of either or both groups" (Redfield et al., 1936:149).

There are various disciplinary differences in conceptualising the process of acculturation in Sociology, Psychology and Anthropology, as each discipline places differing emphasis on cultural context. For instance, in Sociology different traditions develop towards a single acculturation outcome known as modernity, explained as a unidimensional process (Flannery et al., 2001). In Anthropology, acculturation is perceived to be a multilinear process with varying outcomes that are related to varying starting points. In Psychology, acculturation is considered in the same vein as Anthropology, with an incorporation of the terms integration and marginalisation (Berry, 1970). Furthermore, there are three Psychological disciplines concerned with the study of culture: cross-cultural Psychology, Cultural Psychology and Indigenous Psychology (Ozer, 2013).

Within Psychology, Hall (1904) arguably was the first to write about acculturation as a learning process that is similar for first and second generation individuals. While Graves (1967) elaborated the understandings of psychological acculturation. Thomas et al., (1984) conducted the first full psychological study on acculturation through an empirical study of immigrants in Chicago. They constructed a theory where minority groups were defined by their shared attitudes and habits (schemas), which could be adapted to any ethnic community, family or occupation. They argued that the dominant culture imposed acculturative stress on the minority group through their social and occupational groups. However, Bartlett (1923) emphasised the importance of the attitudes that minority groups had toward the dominant culture. Bartlett argued that if neither of the two cultures are dominant, it could lead to a blending of cultures, while dominance of one culture could cause complete cultural assimilation of one group (Rudmin, 2003).

Another factor in explaining how acculturation occurs is the extent or level that minority groups perceive a need to protect their own culture or their willingness to modify it to acculturate and fit in and live alongside other cultural groups. Along with differences in individual's personalities, similarities in cultures also increase the transference of old practices to new ones. The stress of transition and resettlement associated with the migration process which could have an impact in families over many years is referred to as "acculturative stress" (Kulis et al., 2009). However, contemporary perceptions of acculturation are relatively elusive with

fluctuating meanings and histories attached to it (Sam, 2006; Ozer, 2013; Rudmin, 2010).

A few studies on culture and ethnicity have suggested that drinking is used as a coping mechanism for dealing with stress to cope with feeling of being on the margins of a society. In UK literature, many minority ethnic groups have reported alcohol helping in the form of a relaxant and aiding their social life. South Asians suggest that they drank alcohol to improve their self-confidence (Purser et al., 2001; Bradby, 2007). However, a study by Heim et al., (2004), reported drinking among Indian, Pakistani, and Chinese individuals as having little impact on their friendships or social life. While drinking can lead to facilitation of social integration among some ethnic groups, it can also lead to alienation from the local community in some others. Negative community responses and religious restrictions can result in drinking in secret to avoid shame and a loss of status (Heim et al., 2004; Alcohol Concern, 2003; Orford et al., 2004; Mantovani and Evans, 2019).

Acculturation theory helpfully explains how stress reported by minorities are complex and how these stresses influence them individually and as a community. Acculturative stress refers to the strain occurring from social adjustment to the dominant culture; socioeconomic stress occurs when individuals feel weak due to inadequate financial resources and limited social standing; and minority stress refers to the tensions that minorities

encounter resulting from racism (Mantovani and Evans, 2019; Bradby, 2007).

A longitudinal study conducted by Hurcombe et al., (2010) reported that the experiences of moving to a new country can be stressful. Issues such as access to education and employment opportunities, socio-economic status, peer influences and lifestyle choices, all impact on immigrant's individual and collective identity.

There are studies which argue that the increases in alcohol consumption among some BME groups are a consequence of time spent in the host country, rather than a result of the stressors associated with migration (Sam and Berry, 2006; Berry, 2005; Becares et al., 2011; Puri et al., 2018; Kulis et al., 2007). Studies have noted boredom, peer influence, curiosity, seeking pleasure, improving self-confidence etc. as being some of the reasons for the use of alcohol and drugs (Fountain et al., 2003; Sangster et al., 2002a; Buchanan, 2008; Mantovani and Evans, 2019).

Furthermore, two different models can be distinguished among stress and integration as risk factors for alcohol use and problems. The stress model holds that alcohol use will subside once the initial pressure of living in Western society is resolved. According to the integration model, continued exposure to western society over time will have a corresponding increase in the risk of alcohol and other drug use, as people gradually adopt the norms and values of the host country (Hurcombe et al., 2010).

The bi-dimensional model of acculturation independently mapped individual attitudes toward the majority culture and towards that of the heritage culture (Berry, 1997). This model holds that the use of alcohol can be influenced by the maintenance of the original culture (enculturation) as well as adaptation to the drinking culture in the host country (acculturation). However, Landrine and Klonoff (2004) view acculturation as a multidimensional process, where identification with one culture does not necessarily mean reduced identification with another culture. This bi-dimensional model of acculturation describes four types of identity for migrant groups, with some factors being seen as extraneous and independent. These include assimilation, disassociation, marginal and bicultural. Assimilation refers to those who identify with the host country but identify less with their own origins. At the same time, dissociative individuals retain their ethnic identity without developing an affiliation with the host country. Marginal individuals include those who do not identify with either culture. However, globalisation has meant that cultural influences are being transmitted across nations, and different ethnic groups will have experienced westernisation within their own country before moving to the UK, and as such will have experienced certain aspects that were similar in their own country within British society. Such individuals are immersed in both cultures and are bicultural. Hence, it is worth considering the extent of acculturation in the individual's native culture with the new host country (Hurcombe et al., 2010).

Different disciplines have differing dimensions for understanding acculturation, for example Landrine and Klonoff's bi-dimensional model (2004). These acculturation theories describe the different ways in which individuals from BME backgrounds relate to a new culture and the transitions or resistance from their heritage that occur as a consequence of living in another culture. Research described in the next section reveals more about how and why people drink and the role of the cultural context.

2.6 Religion, Alcohol & other Drug Use

The use of AOD and the functions they have in relation to health, relaxation, and recreation and in the expansion of consciousness have been influenced by religion throughout history, however the nature of this relationship has differed from place to place and over time. While both alcohol and drugs play an important role in religious observance and practices among numerous groups, some religious doctrines oppose recreational use, while others fervently forbid the use of any drugs. For instance, wine represents the blood of Christ, and is central in the observance of rituals among Roman Catholic and some Protestant sects in Christianity. Similarly, tradition in India maintains that the Hemp plant was a gift from the gods for attaining delight and courage and is perceived to bestow supernatural powers to its users (Schultes and Hofmann, 1992; Korsmeyer and Kranzler, 2009; Hanson et al., 2011). However, in the early 1800s the Protestant Christian sect had a prominent role to play in the emergence of Temperance movements which called for the condemnation and ultimately prohibition of alcohol (Gusfield, 1986). Prohibition was also enforced by other religious

groups and some Christian sects e.g. Latter-day Saints (Mormons) who included many common drugs, tobacco and caffeine to the prohibition (Barrows, 1991).

Thus, the omnipresent nature of religion in human culture and the diversity of interpretations and understanding suggest at least in part that it is socially constructed. All major religions seek to regulate norms concerning the use or avoidance of alcohol. Social theorists cite religion as one of the forces that influences a sense of moral obligation to norms within specific cultural groups (Durkheim, 2012; Turner, 1991a).

Religiosity is a multidimensional concept which refers to an individual's engagement and depth of belief of a religion regardless of the individual's beliefs (Amey et al., 1996). Two types of religiosity are described as intrinsic and extrinsic by (Allport, 1963). Intrinsic religiosity is where an individual's approaches to religion are internally motivated, sincere and committed in terms of living by religious belief regardless of the consequences. Extrinsic religiosity describes low commitment to religious practice as a result of external pressures through family and religion.

Gunn (2003) helpfully describes three facets of religion: (i) religion as a belief, (ii) religion as identity, and (iii) religion as a way of life. Religious belief relates to individual convictions regarding matters such as God or truth and places greater emphasis on adherence to doctrines and understandings of reality. Religious identity emphasises affiliation with other individuals and groups experienced by an individual through family,

ethnicity, race or nationality. As such, religion can be viewed as something that an individual is born into rather than converted to following a process of studying, or reflection. Finally, religion as a way of life is associated with action, ritual, customs and traditions that distinguish believers from non-believers. For instance, individuals are motivated to observe certain rituals (e.g. avoiding alcohol).

Variations exist in religions with regards to their views on the use of alcohol and these differences also extend to the various sects in a particular religion. Research conducted by Smith (2003), indicates that strong religious identity increases norm adherence, and enhances social approval by others. Furthermore, identifying or being part of a religious group encourages social conformity (McIntire, 2007). For instance, Hinduism encompasses a diverse range of beliefs, with some groups abstaining while others cherish alcohol intoxication as a valuable religious experience (Carstairs, 1954b; Glazier, 1999; Heath, 2012). Islam forbids the use of alcohol, by considering it a "sin", as using alcohol are believed to be a cause of social problems and interfere with praying and the remembrance of Allah. Catholics tolerate the use of alcohol, while Methodists sanction absolute abstinence. While wine is incorporated into some rituals among Jews, and moderate use of alcohol is accepted, deviance resulting from intoxication is not accepted (Humphreys and Gifford, 2006). Generally alcohol use is not condemned in Christianity as wine is often used in the ceremony of Communion (Ellison et al., 2008; Beeghley et al., 1990). However, there

are extreme views within this religion that condemn the use of alcohol, and associate the risks of intoxication with deviance. Indeed, studies have shown that the greater the subjective religious involvement the greater the probability of abstinence from alcohol (Mullen et al., 1996). Cultural groups not only drink differently they also perceive problem drinking differently (Danko et al., 1988; Edwards et al., 2002).

A study by Abbotts et al., (2001) in Scotland hypothesised that being a Roman Catholic was a proxy for lower socio-economic status. Participant's that were born Catholic were significantly more likely than others to suffer from poor general and physical development and health, and psychological distress, but that this is not explained by differences in smoking or alcohol consumption. Proxy measures cannot completely capture the diversity of a group or their attitudes to smoking and drinking by religion. However, identifying or being part of a religious group encourages social conformity (McIntire, 2007).

Studies have indicated that individuals who considered themselves 'not religious' consumed more alcohol, and were more likely to smoke and use marijuana as well as amphetamines (Luczak et al., 2014). Similarly, other religions such as sects in Buddhism express lower levels of disapproval (Tart, 1991; Stolaroff, 1999; Palamar et al., 2014), while certain cultures have consumed psychoactive drugs to enhance their spiritual and religious experiences (Humphreys and Gifford, 2006; Miller, 2013; Smith et al., 2004). Finally, research among Atheists and Agnostics in the US reveal that

they tend to report higher rates of marijuana and cocaine use in comparison to those who follow a religion (Degenhardt et al., 2007). However, it is important to note that much of the research that focuses on religion tend to separate the research on either alcohol, tobacco or other illicit drugs individually, and not consider these together (Engs and Mullen, 1999; Engs, 2013).

Ambivalence between and within cultures influence the use of AOD and related problems with a historical uncertainty leading to a curious contemporary worship of abstinence, which is little practiced and when practiced is seldom respected (Zinberg, 1981; Casper et al., 2006). While religion occupies a very distinctive place in culture, by providing ideological and behavioural guidelines for ethical and moral behaviour (Hogg et al., 2010; Hunsberger and Jackson, 2005), religions are not monolithic structures. For instance, in cultures where the use of intoxicants are integrated into religious and social customs and where consumption patterns are regulated by tradition, related problems are at a minimum (Blum and Blum, 1969; Greene et al., 2017). Religious affiliation is itself influenced by ethnicity and acculturation. These influences in turn alter the impact of affiliation on drug use for individuals in certain ethnicities (Hunt, 2001).

In summary, the relationships between religious observance and drug use practices have shown that the extent of involvement in a religious group is related to avoidance of alcohol and other drugs. This relationship is also

exhibited across religious denominations; however, there are variations to the strength of association (addressed in Chapter 6). The notion of religion being a protective factor in preventing the use of AOD needs to be considered with caution as several studies have evidenced alcohol and drug problems among those from the Islamic faith. Furthermore, oversimplification of religious affiliation (e.g. Christian or Hindu) is insufficient as a factor in explaining use or avoidance as there is a complex interaction between ethnic identity, cultural norms, social structures and economic factors (e.g. price and income) among participants. The next section reviews the literature on the use of alcohol by gender.

2.7 Gender

While the consumption of alcohol as an activity is similar for men and women, the experiences they undergo are rather dissimilar. Participation in the consumption of alcohol, the ideas, feelings and the ideals associated with intoxication in a Scottish environment are markedly different for both genders in BME communities. Throughout historical periods and in countries which have conducted general-population surveys, there is evidence that indicates that in comparison to men, women drink smaller quantities and consume less frequently (Wincup, 2016; Robertson, 2014; Wilsnack et al., 2009; Fillmore et al., 1998). However, the magnitude of these gender differences varies greatly from one society to another as well as from one social context to another.

The majority of the drug use research conducted in the UK has focused mainly on young male users, while service provision efforts have also only considered the needs of white male users (Barton, 2011; Lewis et al., 2011). It is only relatively recently that gender has become the focus of AOD research in the UK (Sterling and Weisner, 2002; Van Wersch and Walker, 2009; Staddon, 2009; Wincup, 2016; Ettore, 2007). Up until the 1980s women were invisible as users of AOD, including service users, and were considered even more vulnerable to risk when intoxicated. Perceptions of risks were exacerbated when drug users are demonised as 'mad' or 'bad' (Coomber et al., 2013). While drinking and drug-taking have been established as symbols of masculinity, it could be argued that for women, the use of alcohol and drugs have become an extension of the way society controls their body either socially, medically or legally as child bearers, nurturers, sex workers and romantic partners (Ettore, 2007; Coomber et al., 2013). Such rationalisations of the use of AOD between men and women not only shape individual responses, but also the wider society in the manner in which users are viewed, reported and treated.

Studies that have detailed ethnic variations in rates of alcohol consumption in the UK by gender have demonstrated that men and women from African-Caribbean and Indian (South Asian) origins report lower levels of drinking than those from Britain (Bradby and Williams, 2006; Becares et al., 2011). Yet other studies indicate that, while lower levels of consumption are reported by those from Indian origins, there have been high rates of male hospital admissions for alcohol-related diseases (Harrison and Harrison,

2002; Hurcombe et al., 2010). The discrepancy between high hospital admission rates and lower reporting of consumption are arguably due to the unreliability of self-reported data, and unwillingness to disclose drinking habits (Hurcombe et al., 2010).

More recent research from health surveys in England indicates that frequent and heavy drinking has increased for Indian women (from 15% to 21%) and older Chinese men (from 39% to 48%) between the period of 1999 to 2004 (Hurcombe et al., 2010; Erens, 2006), while rates of drug use are just as prevalent as the dominant white population (Fountain, 2003; Bashford et al., 2003; Luger, 2009). Drinking among Sikh girls has increased, whilst second generation Sikh men drink less than first generation (Purser et al., 2001). Collectively, these studies outline that while some data has been gathered on AOD use among BME groups, patterns of AOD use have been difficult to obtain. These difficulties can be attributed to BME groups higher refusal rates to participate in surveys; in particular, refusal to answer questions about AOD use or under-reporting of use; and language difficulties (Khan et al., 2000; Luger, 2009).

As previously discussed, parental drinking beliefs also influence the drinking behavior of children. For instance, Orford et al., (2004) reported that less than half of the Sikh participants and 20% of Hindu participants in their study reported that their father drank. However, only 3% of Muslim participants reported this. As such, the authors argue that across all South Asian groups, parental drinking might have an influence on alcohol

consumption by South Asian men. Similarly, while Sikh and Hindu men were willing for their parents to know of their alcohol consumption, a third of Muslim men did not want their parents to know of their drinking. However, no reasons were provided by the authors for this.

A study by Heim et al., (2004) looked at alcohol consumption, perception of community responses and attitudes to service provision living in Greater Glasgow. Muslim participants had the lowest level of reported alcohol consumption. However, amongst Muslims who did drink alcohol (19%), a higher level of consumption was reported than in other religious groups although this was only statistically significant when compared to the non-religious participants.

A similar observation was made in a survey carried out amongst men in the West Midlands (Cochrane & Bal, 1990) in which participants were randomly selected from a list of eight General Practices in Wolverhampton and Birmingham. These locations were specifically selected due to their higher concentration of Asian populations. The survey included samples of 200 Sikh, Muslim and Hindu men and 200 white English-born men, matched for age, were interviewed using a structured questionnaire containing a retrospective drinking diary. Sikhs were most likely to be regular drinkers followed by white and Hindu respondents. The very few Muslim men who reported drinking consumed the most alcohol on average, although again, the very small sample sizes should be considered.

Gendered socialisation further affects an individual's behaviour, through preconceived expectations of roles, which are constructed socially and culturally. The variations in gender related issues are evident in socially and culturally constructed roles and expectations of males and females; and ranges from complete equality to restriction (Haralambos and Foster-Carter, 1985; Staddon, 2015).

2.8 Intersectionality Theory

Intersectionality is a theoretical framework that examines the influence of multiple intersections in social categories such as age, race, disability and gender on identity. The origins of intersectionality lie in the writings of US Black feminists and critical race theorists in response to second-wave feminism which gave greater emphasis to categories such as gender, race or ethnicity (Crenshaw, 1989; Collective, 1977). Crenshaw (1989) opposed this as she felt this neglected identity and identity politics, as categories like race and gender are understood as the constructs and reflected dominated and subjugated by structures of power. Mainstream liberalist ideologies failed to consider multiple layers of identity. This led to the development of an analytical approach to capture the meaning and consequence of multiple categories of group membership. Instead of considering gender, race and class as distinct social categories, this theory considers these social positions as systems of oppression that work together to produce inequality (Collins, 1990; Cole, 2009; McCall, 2008).

Crenshaw (1989) described three transpositions: similar experiences, double discrimination (discrimination specific to race and sex, e.g. the status of being a black woman), and as an individual with their own distinct abilities and interests. The first principle posits that social categories are not independent, but rather multiple, and interdependent (Cuadraz and Uttal, 1999). A single identity alone is insufficient in explaining the unequal outcomes without the intersection of the other identity or identities (Bowleg, 2012). The second principle of intersectionality focuses on the historically oppressed and marginalised population such as ethnic minorities, individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, disabled individuals etc. (Weber and Parra-Medina, 2003). The third principle focuses on the multiple social identities possessed by an individual (e.g. gender, race, socio-economic status) and how this intersects with structural factors like poverty, racism etc. Each of these transpositions explain how groups can experience multiple social statuses (and inequalities) at the same time.

Intersectionality has been critiqued by Pluckrose (2017) for its greater emphasis on group identity and lower focus on universality and listening to the views of all women, people of colour and lesbian, gay, bisexual and transsexual (LGBT) people. Pluckrose argues that women of colour, LGBT and disabled people uphold and subscribe to a diverse range of ideas on the political spectrum. She suggests that intersectionality is based on a very specific far-left ideology that requires all members of the group to follow its positioning or be rejected as part of a patriarchy linked to

modernity and colonialism. By prescribing such a far-left ideology, intersectionality excludes a significant proportion of women, LGBT and disabled people. Pluckrose further argues that to adopt an intersectional world view requires an individual to not simply focus on several different categories of marginalised identity at once but be convinced of being marginalised and be concerned about them all. Hence, it is not just sufficient to be a woman or a feminist, but also endorse critical race theory, queer theory, and trans-equality discourses. However, an individual may not support, be interested or knowledgeable in all or any one of these categories of the intersectionality framework. Individuals may also decline to be intersectional which is an additional disadvantage of an ideology which claims to listen and represent all marginalised people. Intersectionality also fails to explain why marginalised groups discriminate against each other, for instance when BME individuals demonstrate homophobic or patriarchal attitudes. Therefore, Pluckrose contends that intersectionality devalues universality and individuality by focusing solely on group identity and intersectional ideology, thereby restraining individuals to a collectivist position.

Similarly, Peterson and Panfil (2014) concur with Pluckrose on multiple categories of marginalised identity, as these create multiple intersections. And every time another category is added it increases the intersections in a multiplicative fashion. This increases the difficulty in comparing the categories across dimensions of equality. This makes it inconceivable to compare the various dimensions of inequality. As such, intersectionality

fails to recognise the diversity of ideas, and insists on conforming to group identity.

2.9 Conclusion

This literature review highlights how factors such as ethnic identity, culture, religious affiliation and gender can impact on individual behaviour and lifestyle choices. This can directly or indirectly contribute to the use or avoidance of AOD.

The usefulness of epidemiological data on BME groups has been highlighted in the review. However, studies that have attempted to capture the prevalence of AOD use in particular minority groups have faced several impediments. As a result, capturing the hidden nature of AOD use has been difficult to quantify. Attempts to address ethnic categorization of participants have been limited by the heterogeneity of the BME population, due to the lack of well-devised, reliable research (Jayakody et al., 2006; Pannu et al., 2009; De Kock et al., 2017). Social exclusion and deprivation among BME groups have been cited as the main reasons for problematic use of AOD, while research that goes beyond this as an explanation are limited.

The theory of acculturation from a Cultural Psychological perspective was also reviewed. Acculturation offers useful insights in seeking to explain what cultural identity is, and how it shapes perceptions for the use or avoidance of AOD.

Both social control and self-control theories attempt to explain deviant and criminal behaviour from an individualistic perspective, with a focus on control and why some people conform to society's norms while others do not. Social control theory emphasises that deviance occurs in the absence of social control and bonds of conformity, that allows individuals to be free to deviate, thereby explaining deviance from cultural norms.

Furthermore, this review has revealed that religion is considered as a proxy for culture, as religion exerts much influence on attitudes and behaviours, and such categorisation limits our understanding of what it is to be a part of a BME as a group member and an individual. While religion has also been cited as a protective factor in preventing AOD use among BME groups, religious affiliation is not an indication of religiosity. Gendered socialisation further affects an individual's behaviour, through preconceived expectations of roles, which are constructed socially and culturally.

This thesis adopts a Cultural Psychology perspective on acculturation, which is based on the theoretical and methodological foundations of relativism and social constructionist perspectives of how a specific culture shapes and is shaped by the individual. Here culture is conceptualised as something inside the individual from that of an emic perspective, by trying to understand what is meaningful for the local actor (Ozer, 2013; Boiger et al., 2013). This research explores the social world of a hidden population of BME AOD users, who have never been identified as problematic users, have never sought treatment or been imprisoned for their use of AOD.

Accessing a hidden population reveals crucial differences in the use of AOD in people from those that define themselves as problematic. The emphasis is on the notion of participants culture, ethnicity, gender, age, and religion on personal and community contact, interactional influence and change and exchanges of identity among migrants from South Indian, Pakistani, Chinese, African and Mixed-ethnic backgrounds living in the West of Scotland who use alcohol and or other drugs.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter illustrates the processes that the researcher carried out, establish the epistemological and ontological understandings that led to the selection of the method, as well as how the issues that arose from applying the method were resolved. This chapter is narrated in the first person due to the personal nature of the methodology. This chapter allows me the space to explain my reasoning and choices. In other chapters I have drawn on the expertise of others and theories, and the results chapters form a space to discuss the participants' personal stories. This chapter shares my reasoning and choices in positioning myself within the theoretical dimension, as well as the ethical choices I made in carrying out this research.

The term "hidden populations" is often applied to marginalised and excluded groups (e.g. sex workers, homeless, deviant populations etc.), however it may have little in common with hard-to-reach populations, who choose to remain hidden or keep an aspect of their identity hidden (exerting agency) and private. This is explored in greater detail in Section 3.4.3.

The method employed in this research was qualitative stemming from a social constructionist epistemology and consisting of in-depth semi-structured interviews.

The majority studies documenting the use of AOD by BME utilises quantitative methods to document and estimate how AOD use is correlated with health problems or, associated with deprivation, and socioeconomic status. Furthermore, these samples are often easy to reach as they are known to and recruited through treatment or criminal justice agencies.

This qualitative research study recruited 30 people who met the inclusion criterion. The use of semi-structured interviews allow participants to reflect on their experiences. I explored how cultural norms and values influenced the use or avoidance of AOD in relation to age, gender, religious observance, and generational differences.

3.2 Philosophical Foundations

Qualitative research is panoptic in nature as it includes a wide range of approaches and methods, as indicated by Denzin and Lincoln (2011):

"...Qualitative research is difficult to define clearly. It has no theory or paradigm that is distinctively its own...Nor does qualitative research have a distinct set of methods or practices that are entirely on its own" (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011:6).

Hence, qualitative research allows the study of social phenomena which have various naturalistic and interpretive forms and draws on multiple forms of inquiry. Here the researcher embarks on a journey of discovery rather than verification of a single reality (Bryman, 1984). Indeed Bryman (1984) emphasises the epidemiological differences in both quantitative and

qualitative research as it offers an alternative 'modus operandi' for conducting social research. An absolute categorisation of the various philosophical and theoretical perspectives that influence and differentiate the types of qualitative investigation is impractical. For instance, Guba and Lincoln (2005) describe five alternative inquiry paradigms: positivism, post-positivism, critical theory, constructivism, and participatory research, while Schwandt (2007) only mentions three epistemological stances for qualitative inquiry namely – interpretivism, hermeneutics, and social constructionism. At the same time, Crotty (2012) identifies three epistemologies: objectivism, constructionism, and subjectivism. He deliberates that these have varying degrees of influence on different perspectives as positivism, interpretivism, critical inquiry, feminism and post-modernism. While it is evident that there is convergence among these frameworks, there are also differences that reflect the experience and emphasis within the history of qualitative research. However, the very existence of the different types of interpretive approaches has led to lack of acceptance, as well as criticism for defending the relativistic ontology of multiple, individually constructed, yet socially and culturally constrained realities (Goulding, 2002).

Some of the main criticisms of qualitative research include that it goes nowhere, as it does not 'fit' with applied and outcome driven research, including the creation of theory for theory's sake (Morse et al., 1998). On the contrary, these accusations need re-examination as they fail to

acknowledge the value of qualitative research. As Morse et al. (1998) writes:

"...qualitatively derived theory is a refined and tightened view of real-world experiences" (Morse et al., 1998: 336).

Another criticism of qualitative research is that the researcher is considered as the research tool, as all data is filtered through the data collector and conceived as subjective. Not only is this view condescending of the researcher, it fails to recognise the inimitable experience that the researcher possesses that would assist in avoiding recognising subjectivity. In fact, qualitative researchers widely adopt rigorous and self-conscious examination for bias at various stages during the research process (for instance, checking for negative incidents in data, occurrences that do not fit the emerging story etc.). It is also common practice for the researcher to consult colleagues, academics, and fieldworkers to check the accuracy of interpretations (Ritchie et al., 2013; Saunders and Lewis, 2012). Finally, qualitative research has also been criticised for the lack of rules on procedures and as variables are not measurable. However, the very nature of qualitative research with its flexibility and recursive nature of investigation is its advantage (Goulding, 2002).

Kant (1781) and Dilthey (1977) made key contributions in social science research by emphasising the importance of 'understanding' experiences (noumena and phenomena) which occur within a particular historical and social context. Influenced by the ideas of Kant, Max Weber (1864-1920)

proposed two types of understandings: one which is direct observational and the second, explanatory or motivational (Lebow, 2016). Weber argued that in social sciences, the aim is to understand subjective meaningful experiences. Hence, while 'interpretivism' accentuates both interpretation and understanding, the related school of thought described as 'constructionism' gives greater emphasis to culture and context in understanding what occurs in society, hence knowledge is constructed through this shared understanding (McMahon, 1997). Both approaches reject positivist approaches, and greater significance is placed on understanding lived experiences, and this is reflected in qualitative research practice.

Therefore, I reject quantitative research methodologies (positivist approaches), with their emphasis on fixed measurements, hypothesis testing and limited involvement in fieldwork, and illogical categorisation of things for ease of measurement and comparison. Exploration of BME groups and their subjective experience of being a hidden (unknown to services) drug taker, and how they manage their dual status of drug user and as a "normal" productive individual in their community cannot be captured through quantitative methods. Positivist approaches have a tendency to view events from an outsider's perspective, thereby imposing social reality with little reference to the meaning of the observations regarding the investigation. The constructionist perspective is less interested in developmental theories (Bruner, 1985) and social cognitive processes (Bandura, 2001) that accompany knowledge, and is more concerned with

how individuals construct the world through social processes that have meaning to them. This is further explored in Chapters 4 using acculturation theory in exploring participant use of AOD.

Having explained my reasoning for choosing qualitative research, in the next section I explain the use of social constructionism and its epistemology and ontology in this thesis.

3.2.1 Constructionism

Social constructionist assumptions of reality are rooted in the belief that reality is constructed through human activity, and meaning is created through individuals' interactions with each other and the environment. Hence, what is perceived and experienced is an interpretation of the situation and never a direct reflection of the environment (Burr, 2015). Willig (2012) argues that social constructionism assumes that there are multiple observations of the same phenomenon, which can be described in different ways, with neither explanation being wrong. Hence, rather than merely reflecting a single reality, social constructionist research focuses on identifying the various ways social reality in a culture is understood and shared, the various conditions of its use and implications for social practice.

According to Rogoff (1999), inter-subjectivity can be defined as the shared understanding among individuals who share a common interest, and whose interaction and assumptions form the basis of their communication. Communication and interaction results in the construction of socially agreed (or at least understood) ideas about that world, as well as social patterns

and rules of language that involves an inter-subjectivity (Ernest, 1998). Hence, constructionists exchange 'description' with 'construction' arguing that language (discourse) constructs versions of reality rather than reality determining it (Willig, 2012). However, social constructionists' view of knowledge production ranges from radical to more moderate interpretations. For instance, radical social constructionists are concerned with understanding how and why interwoven objects and positions are constructed in distinct ways and contexts, and what is achieved within that specific context. It is only the particular reality constructed for a specific conversation that is of interest. On the other hand, Willig (2013) argues that more moderate social constructionists pursue the connections between the interwoven constructions of a distinct reality and the wider sociocultural contexts within which it takes place. Here the pre-existing social reality is considered, and how it shapes and constrains the ways in which people construct meaning within specific contexts (Willig, 2013; Jarvensivu and Tornroos, 2010).

The actions of individuals that influence the immediate social process and context of the interview, as well as those actions that have been influenced by other discourses are important. My focus is on capturing what the individual knows and how shared discourses influence their perception and use of AOD. In the context of this thesis, the term moderate social constructionist refers to the construction of knowledge about the reality that the BME individuals have created through their interaction with each

other, society and the objects in their environment. And as Neimeyer and Neimeyer (1993) notes:

"...All of our understandings are contextually embedded, interpersonally forged, and necessarily limited..." (Neimeyer, 1993:1-2).

The BME individual's constructions of reality reflect their understanding and experience of transgressing social norms within their frames of reference such as gender, age, religion and ethnicity, and not merely alcohol and drug use. Here their notions of 'truth' emerge from a consensus among informed and sophisticated constructors (Patton, 1990; Patton, 2005). Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7 demonstrate how the hermeneutics of learning within the epistemological framework of constructionism are brought together with adaptation and identity concealment as well as acculturation theory.

Having outlined the principles of qualitative research and the ontology and epistemology of constructionism, the next section explores the research design of semi-structured interviews.

3.3 Research Design

3.3.1 Semi-structured Interviews

Numerous studies have identified the key features of semi-structured interviews, including the opportunity to probe for more detailed responses to establish clarity of respondent's statements. This form of interviewing offers flexibility to pursue additional questions depending on the direction

the interview takes; the dialogue between interviewer and respondents allows for capturing nuances; the interviewer is able to know who they have interviewed while being able to anonymise the transcripts; and it allows for capturing historical information (Gray, 2013; Cohen et al., 2013; Creswell, 2013).

This qualitative research study interviewed 30 AOD users from BME groups. In-depth interviews allowed me to elicit accounts of BME participants' experiences and perspectives of their use of AOD. However, it is worthwhile to indicate that critiques of qualitative methods argue that understanding others' experiences and perspectives is inconceivable, as individual experiences are socio-culturally constituted (Hammersley, 2012). Also challenged is the idea whether people can truly understand themselves and their behaviour, as individuals can misunderstand themselves and their world. Qualitative interviewing is further criticised for its reliability, stability and validity of the interview data, from the perspective that knowledge is created through interaction from the interview. The notion that there is an individual 'self' and that the interview is a performance through which data is created that merely reflects a single interaction has been refuted by (Ritchie et al., 2013). In essence, it is important to highlight that while knowledge is created through interaction in interviews, it is still a space where participants' experiences and views can be captured meaningfully. Interviews go beyond immediate interaction and hold greater value as it subsumes explicit interpretations and understandings of individuals. As Miller and Glassner (1997) indicate, interviews:

"...provide access to the meanings people attribute to their experiences and social worlds. While the interview is itself a symbolic interaction, this does not discount the possibility that knowledge of the social world beyond the interaction can be obtained..." (Miller and Glassner, 1997: 133).

The target populations in this study were adults (18+) from BME groups, and the primary focus was to contact and interview individuals who were non-white. Criteria for participation included (1) only those who had previously consumed AOD (including tobacco); users were defined as current or past users). Individuals who had received any treatment for any drug (including alcohol) were excluded from the study.

Mostly face-to-face interviews were conducted in this study, however Skype-based interviews were also arranged for six participants as alcohol and drug use is stigmatised within their family/community or religious grouping. Skype interviews were arranged with participants who were reluctant to take part in a face-to-face interview. When first contact was made with the six participants, they indicated that they were unwilling to take part in the research as they were frightened that taking part would reveal their identity, and they were concerned that I could recognise them or a member of their immediate family, as I too am from a BME background. They were concerned that participating in this research would expose them and the findings from this research could result in their family being stigmatised in the community. This is because the use of AOD is prohibited for religious reasons or sanctioned by the family. When I presented them with an option of participating through telephone or Skype,

they all opted for Skype, as it would allow them to create a new account on Skype and then be able to delete it after the interview and hence protect their identity. This option meant that the participants were very relaxed and expressed themselves freely and openly throughout the course of the interview. While consent was gathered verbally before the start of the interview, these participants very willingly also returned the consent forms through email, either before or after the interview. While these six participants were contacted through referrals by others, it was difficult to acquire further contacts from these participants as they did not want to stay in touch after the interview.

Such online means of interviews have been criticised as accuracy of responses cannot be determined (Gray, 2013). Difficulty in ascertaining participants responses as 'absolute truths' has been cited as the main criticism, as participants have the freedom to present altered or fake identities or personalities during online interactions. This is further exacerbated as the researcher is unable to observe body language and hear vocal variations of the participants (DeLorme et al., 2001). Furthermore, Skype also made it possible for me to access a population which would otherwise have been inaccessible, with the added benefit of giving participants the freedom to participate and yet remain anonymous. While engaging in rapport and reliability of accounts have been the major criticisms for Skype interviews, (Deakin and Wakefield, 2013) argue that Skype interviewees were more responsive and rapport was built quicker than face-to-face interviews.

I established trust with the participants by maintaining regular contact using email, telephone and text messaging. Contact with participants was maintained throughout to ensure that their concerns were addressed and until the day the interview was completed.

This section looked at the data collection techniques used in this research. The advantages and disadvantages were discussed, as well as how some of the problems encountered were resolved. The next section will discuss the role of interpretation, the methodological procedures associated with the use of thematic analysis (TA) and locating TA epistemologically in this research. TA as a method of recognising and organising patterns in the content and meaning in this research is discussed.

3.3.2 Thematic Analysis

TA originates from the much older tradition of content analysis which is historically rooted in quantitative traditions dating back to 20th century social sciences and humanities (Smith, 2000; Joffe, 2012). While content analysis is primarily focused on establishing categories and counting the frequency of the occurrence of these categories, TA was developed to go beyond observable material and be more implicit, through the development of themes and thematic structures (Merton, 1975). The founder of TA, Gerald Horton, coined the term 'themata' to refer to implicit preferences to particular concepts that are shared by individuals or groups, but who are unaware of this (Joffe, 2012). Contemporary TA combines elements of

content analysis, but with the added advantage of involving complexity in analysing the implicit meaning of the codes (Joffe, 2012).

Thematic analysis has been widely used, but gained recognition as a research method in its own right only recently (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Willig, 2013). However, debate surrounding the use of TA as a fully-fledged research tool or whether it is a tool or skill used across qualitative methods for data analysis is still ongoing (Howitt and Cramer, 2007; Boyatzis, 1998; Alhojailan, 2012). Additionally, TA is not tied to any particular theoretical or epistemological approach, and is well suited for use with phenomenology, social representations theory and social constructionism (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Flick et al., 2015; Clarke and Braun, 2013). The themes can also be informed by the research question and the researcher's epistemological position. Indeed, Clarke and Braun (2013) present four arguments about the usefulness of TA as a method of analysis: a) TA can be used with questions ranging from peoples' experiences or understandings to those about the representation or construction of phenomena; b) TA can be used for analysing both primary (interview/focus group transcripts) and secondary data; c) can be used with large or small data sets; and finally d) it can be applied on data or theory driven analysis.

Furthermore, TA is especially useful in identifying the process of social construction or the symbolic meanings that people attach to issues (Joffe, 2012). For instance, TA can help translate how a particular representation develops in the data. While numerous patterns can be identified across the

data set, the purpose of the analysis is to identify those relevant to answering the research question.

The meaning captured by a theme can refer to the directly observable meaning – manifested or the implicit meaning – latent, depending on how the researcher approaches the interpretation of the data (Joffe, 2012). Yet another approach to TA is an inductive and deductive approach. In inductive approaches, the researcher approaches the data without a theoretically informed coding frame. Such analysis results in themes that are firmly grounded in the data, and do not reflect the researcher's epistemological position. On the other hand, in deductive approaches the coding frame can be theoretically driven and the themes can be created from the relevant literature. Some researchers such as (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006) use a combination of inductive and deductive TA, where a template is used initially to organise the data, but where novel themes are also allowed to emerge from the analysis. The theoretically derived, template codes and newly emerging themes are then integrated to generate a comprehensive thematic description of the data.

In this research I underwent a process of immersing myself in the data and included the participants' narratives in the findings chapters liberally to keep the participants' voice and meaning present. This process permitted me to make the connections between analytical findings and the data from which they were derived. I adopted the hybrid inductive and deductive

approach to TA as used by (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). My use of this combined approach is explained in greater detail in Section 3.4 below.

3.4 Method

I adapted the hybrid inductive and deductive approach to TA by Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006) as the method in this research since BME use of AOD is under researched, and their experiences of the use of AOD were interpreted in this study. The coding framework is included in Section 3.4.2. The analysis of this data is detailed in Section 3.7. One of the main criticisms of the TA is that the researcher is not required to make a decision about their epistemological orientation. Therefore, there is a necessity to do a lot of conceptual work before starting the research (Joffe, 2012; Willig, 2013). Yet at the same time, TA is also argued to be an easy-to-use qualitative method. However, it is important to note that TA is only meaningful if there is a clear understanding of the themes that have been identified. In order to overcome this drawback, I approached the analysis of this research by locating it in moderate social constructionist thought (Willig, 2013). Furthermore, while a hybrid inductive and deductive approach was adopted, a complete template of codes was not created, and was only used as a guide. This allowed for emerging themes and new insights to be identified and explored further. The applicability and validity of existing data was kept to be a minimum, and this allowed for exploring detailed complex interpretations of socially and historically located experiences.

I also used the computer-assisted data analysis software Nvivo for the organisation and management of the qualitative data. This helped with moving beyond descriptions and considering the evaluative criteria of TA. The effectiveness of Nvivo as a data management tool has been well documented in research (Corcoran et al., 2007; Flick, 2009; Seale, 2000; Gibbs, 2002). However, criticisms also include that the frequent nature of change results in developments and the regular need to update the software (Ritchie et al., 2013). I transcribed all the interviews using Nvivo software package for qualitative analysis. An added advantage of using Nvivo for transcription was that the audio file could be slowed down, which allowed for picking up nuances especially when translating to English. Slowing the speed and reducing the background noise is a feature that is often not available in other computer media software's such as Windows Media Player, or VLC Media Player.

Using Nvivo enabled me to store all the data (transcripts, sound files, and memos) in a singular location, in a password encrypted system. The transcripts could then be exported to Microsoft word and excel as deemed necessary for further analysis. It also allowed for development of analytic structures and code segments, where similar data from across participants could be grouped. Nvivo also allowed for the reorganisation and extension of themes into higher-level categories, as well as the creation of diagrams and maps for visualisation emerging from the relationship between codes (included in Section 3.7). In comparison to manual methods, Nvivo facilitated quick handling of large amounts of data and helped with

consistency, managing and organising data. However, it is imperative to highlight that while a program facilitates the user in the development of theory, this does not guarantee that the program can develop theory nor coherence with a particular methodology. As it is only the users who can ultimately analyse the data and generate theory (Bringer et al., 2006; MacMillan and Koenig, 2004). The use of Nvivo to facilitate TA is considered next.

3.4.1 Thematic Analysis & Nvivo

Nvivo has the facility to record the researcher's initial thoughts in memos and these can be attached to participants, groups of participants or coding categories. The software allows for open coding, focused coding, coding on the basis of demographic information including visual representations. The software is intentionally designed to allow the user to analyse data as it is collected. Some additional features of the program include text searches, data coding and search, but always allowing access to the original data behind the concepts. Nowhere in this process does the software analyse the data, as the researcher must ask questions, interpret the data and decide what to code.

Interviews were the main source of data for this thesis and were saved in the form of transcripts in Nvivo. The feature of internal annotations allows for attaching pieces of information such as demographic characteristics about individuals, to be recorded which may be important but which if included as text would interrupt the flow of the transcript. I was also able

to include the definitions of the codes in these annotations (demonstrated in Table 2).

Descriptive information of participants could be interlinked with the transcripts using colour, formatting, and linking memos and nodes, helping the researcher in considering the conceptual links and associations in the data (Nowell et al., 2017; Willig, 2013). This is further demonstrated in in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Participant data in Nvivo

Sources		Transcriptions								
Sources		Name	Nodes	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By		
Internals	Interviews	P1		32	262	26/01/2016 12:12	RS	18/04/2016 11:21	LT	
	Transcriptions	P10		13	32	15/12/2015 19:34	LT	18/04/2016 11:49	LT	
		P11		13	42	19/12/2015 12:59	LT	14/05/2016 18:45	LT	
		P12		16	48	29/12/2015 19:36	LT	18/04/2016 11:55	LT	
		P13		11	51	05/01/2016 18:22	LT	18/04/2016 11:56	LT	
		P14		12	37	24/02/2016 11:14	LT	18/04/2016 11:58	LT	
		P15		13	35	24/02/2016 18:58	LT	18/04/2016 12:00	LT	
		P16		14	63	02/03/2016 17:26	LT	18/04/2016 12:02	LT	
		P17		12	34	13/03/2016 17:43	LT	18/04/2016 12:03	LT	
		P18		13	39	22/03/2016 12:36	LT	18/04/2016 12:05	LT	
		P19		9	23	23/03/2016 16:19	LT	18/04/2016 12:06	LT	
		P2		32	127	14/09/2015 17:07	LT	18/04/2016 11:20	LT	
		P20		14	41	26/03/2016 11:52	LT	18/04/2016 12:08	LT	
		P21		10	28	27/03/2016 15:18	LT	18/04/2016 12:10	LT	
		P22		11	45	27/03/2016 19:46	LT	18/04/2016 12:12	LT	
		P23		9	36	04/04/2016 15:27	LT	18/04/2016 12:13	LT	
		P24		10	50	05/04/2016 15:25	LT	18/04/2016 12:16	LT	
		P25		8	13	09/04/2016 17:50	LT	18/04/2016 12:22	LT	
		P26		7	12	09/04/2016 18:34	LT	18/04/2016 12:25	LT	
		P27		8	12	12/04/2016 11:11	LT	14/05/2016 18:55	LT	
		P28		8	27	12/04/2016 23:14	LT	18/04/2016 12:33	LT	
		P29		8	17	02/05/2016 20:35	LT	08/05/2016 12:00	LT	
		P3		30	121	15/09/2015 17:10	LT	18/04/2016 11:24	LT	
		P30		4	19	08/05/2016 12:15	LT	14/05/2016 19:43	LT	
		P4		30	87	16/09/2015 18:00	LT	18/04/2016 11:26	LT	
		P5		16	37	19/10/2015 10:05	LT	18/04/2016 11:39	LT	
		P6		16	37	02/12/2015 19:33	LT	18/04/2016 11:41	LT	

The hybrid TA model used Boyatzis' (1998) guide to data-driven TA, as well as Crabtree and Miller's (1999) template approach in the form of codes from a codebook. Applying elements from this hybrid TA model, I exercised the use of the literature to understand existing knowledge on the discipline, as well as to consider the initial sampling strategy. As a result, all relevant literature on BME alcohol and drug use, as well as the methodology of the previous studies were reviewed for comparison and for the identification of an appropriate purposive sampling strategy. Some of the predetermined codes that were acquired from the literature were used as preliminary codes (e.g. initiation, acculturation etc.), but I also assigned newly emerging, inductive codes to segments of data which could not be appropriately captured by the codes from the coding template (illustrated in Table 2 Section 3.4.2). These additional codes were either new codes or extensions of codes from the coding template. Not only did these concepts from the literature inform my ongoing analysis, it also allowed for the identification of further questions for further theoretical sampling.

A review of the literature helped me with identifying the gaps in existing literature, but also facilitated me to make an informed decision to recruit individuals from ethnic minority populations who have consumed AOD. As such, for gathering rich data, an initial sample of five core contacts and four key informants known to me were gathered (this is further elaborated in greater detail in Section 3.4.4). While I was open to new possibilities emerging from the data and data gathering approaches (e.g. focus groups), all data gathered in this study were through in-depth interviews. It is

pertinent to note that my decision to use Nvivo did not limit the data gathering and analysis process, rather it was the sensitive nature of the research which obstructed participants and their known contacts' willingness to participate in focus groups.

Interview recordings were in mp3 format, and these were directly imported into Nvivo and then transcribed into Nvivo. The subsequent files could be exported into numerous formats such as Microsoft word, PDF etc. Nvivo 10 allows for attribute information to be created and stored for each interview. This attribute information was used to record descriptive information of each participant such as, age, gender, ethnicity, drinking frequency, drug use etc. This allowed for further analytical procedures of constant comparison and ensuring fulfilment of the purposive sample. Use of attributes was also a helpful means to differentiate between individuals based on their characteristics as well as providing early insights for further investigation. The next section explores the coding process in TA.

3.4.2 Coding

Coding refers to the process of attaching labels to segments of data for intensive scrutiny and for the researcher to attempt to explain what is happening in the data (Charmaz, 2014). Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006) describe TA as a process of searching for themes that emerge from the data which reflect the description of the incident, thereby allowing for pattern recognition in the data. I initially familiarised myself with the entire data set, by reading, re-reading it, and summarising key points while

identifying initial potential themes. Following this, I systematically coded the data through line-by-line coding, to identify meaning units and label these with codes that captured the meaning identified.

A template for coding was initially created to establish the applicability of the code from the raw data. This initial framework was based on manual coding of a selection of transcripts on a random basis to that of the research question, and coding was also informed by the literature. Following this I invited my supervisor to code a few of the transcripts as well to check the applicability of the emerging themes and to check if the existing themes could be divided into sub-themes. This process also ensured the credibility of the coding process before the creation of master codes. The following (Table 2) is a small section of the initial coding template:

Table 2: Initial Coding Template

Code Name	Definition	Example
Drugs used in community	Common drugs used by people in the community, e.g. seesha, supari, cocaine etc.?	"Bidi is maybe they use it to smoke. I remember when I was young my dad used to smoke "bidi", that I know, and I've seen people in olden days walking with it. And cousins house I've seen all the old people taking bidi."
Reasons for use	Is there any specific reason in your community why people use substances, as a relaxation, or mood enhancer or for social reasons?	"Relaxation or enhance the mood or this is what they are doing in the beginning, and they later on they feel like having it every day...and doing this continuously, and they became an addict of those things. Some people cannot control, that's the way it's going on. It's all starting with some friends and therefore pleasure and enjoyment they are starting"

Following this the codes from the template were applied to the text with the intent of identifying meaningful text. As each transcript was already uploaded to Nvivo, it facilitated the process of coding through the creation of nodes, which are self-contained storage units for references to coded text (Bazeley and Jackson, 2013). I coded the text by matching the codes with segments of data that were representative of the code. The sorted segments of coded text are shown in the Figure 4.

Figure 4: Themes & Sub-themes in Nvivo

Nodes		Nodes							
		Name	Sources	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By	
Nodes	Nodes	Cultural Identity & Perceptions of Use	0	0	27/01/2016 19:03	LT	28/03/2016 13:24	LT	
Cases	Perceptions among Mixed Ethnicities	0	0	28/03/2016 13:59	LT	28/03/2016 14:08	LT		
Relationships	Culture Comparison	2	3	28/03/2016 15:07	LT	17/04/2016 12:30	LT		
Node Matrices	Perceptions of Alcohol Use	2	4	28/03/2016 14:09	LT	17/04/2016 12:27	LT		
	Perceptions of Drug Use	2	9	28/03/2016 14:09	LT	17/04/2016 12:29	LT		
	Stigma & Exclusion or Fear	2	5	28/03/2016 14:09	LT	24/05/2016 11:56	LT		
	Perceptions in African Culture	0	0	28/03/2016 13:58	LT	28/03/2016 14:08	LT		
	Culture Comparison	6	13	28/03/2016 15:08	LT	24/05/2016 11:58	LT		
	Perceptions of Alcohol Use	6	19	28/03/2016 14:09	LT	17/04/2016 13:06	LT		
	Perceptions of Drug Use	6	27	28/03/2016 14:10	LT	14/05/2016 19:07	LT		
	Stigma & Fear or Exclusion	7	13	28/03/2016 14:10	LT	24/05/2016 11:58	LT		
	Perceptions in Chinese Culture	0	0	28/03/2016 13:58	LT	28/03/2016 14:08	LT		
	Perceptions in Indian Culture	0	0	27/01/2016 19:54	LT	28/03/2016 14:07	LT		
	Perceptions in Pakistani Culture	0	0	28/03/2016 13:58	LT	28/03/2016 14:08	LT		
	Drugs Used in Community	2	3	27/01/2016 19:26	LT	24/02/2016 19:18	LT		
	Gender	22	217	27/01/2016 19:59	LT	28/03/2016 15:24	LT		
	Identity & Drug Use	0	0	28/03/2016 12:22	LT	28/03/2016 13:24	LT		
	Initiatives in Drug Use	4	9	27/01/2016 20:18	LT	23/03/2016 12:55	LT		
	Personal Use	7	83	27/01/2016 19:13	LT	23/03/2016 12:28	LT		
	Religion & Drug Use	10	18	27/01/2016 19:43	LT	21/06/2016 18:55	LT		
	Understanding of Addiction	17	80	27/01/2016 17:51	LT	23/03/2016 12:44	LT		
	Words to Describe an Addict	4	14	27/01/2016 18:11	LT	23/03/2016 12:45	LT		

Tools within Nvivo allowed for deeper analysis of the codes through non-hierarchical, hierarchical (tree nodes), memos, models and search tools for listing of categories. Using participants' own words as categories also encouraged me to stay true to the data (Glaser and Strauss, 2009; Glaser et al., 1968).

Through coding, I was able to study the data early and begin to separate, classify and synthesise the data. The coding structures accorded for making comparisons with other segments of data, taking into consideration the reflections from the participant's situation. These initial codes acted as pointers for further areas to explore in subsequent data collection. Once transcripts were produced, a process of naming themes began, beginning with parent codes, then child codes and so on. The creation and refinement of codes was a continuous process, which was driven by the questions asked in the semi-structured interviews, which allowed for reconstructing the data into meaningful and manageable pieces. Furthermore, techniques such as questioning, line-by-line, or focused coding (reappearance of codes while coding) in analysis assisted me with avoiding false assumptions and confirming data saturation. Nvivo also allowed me to code directly from a node with the added advantage of linking back to the original context whenever necessary. Yet another feature of Nvivo is its search function, which permitted me to find specific words used by the participants. Given the participants varied backgrounds, and language, they did not always use the same words to describe a concept, however the search tool allowed for

exploring sets of synonyms. Visualisation of coded data from Nvivo is included in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Visualisation of Coded Data from Nvivo

The screenshot displays the Nvivo software interface. On the left, a sidebar contains navigation options: Nodes, Cases, Relationships, and Node Matrices. Below this, a 'Sources' section is visible, followed by a 'Nodes' section which is currently selected. The main workspace is divided into two panes. The top pane shows a hierarchical tree of nodes with columns for 'Name', 'Sources', and 'References'. The bottom pane shows a detailed view of the selected node, 'Perceptions of Drug Use', including its path, coverage percentage, and a list of references with their corresponding text excerpts.

Nodes Table:

Name	Sources	References
Cultural Identity & Perceptio	0	0
Perceptions among Mixe	0	0
Perceptions in African Cul	0	0
Perceptions in Chinese Cu	0	0
Culture Comparison	4	8
Perceptions of Alcoho	2	5
Perceptions of Drug U	4	25
Stigma & Exclusion or	4	9
Perceptions in Indian Cult	0	0
Perceptions in Pakistani C	0	0
Drugs Used in Community	2	3
Alcohol	3	15
Drugs	4	20
Reasons for Use	4	11
Gender	22	217
Identity & Drug Use	0	0
Initiatives in Drug Use	4	9
Personal Use	7	83
Religion & Drug Use	10	18
Understanding of Addiction	17	80
Words to Describe an Addict	4	14

Perceptions of Drug Use - 5 5 references coded [100.00% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 100.00% Coverage

I: do you consider the use of alcohol or drugs harmful?
 P14: well in terms of alcohol and drugs, I think they are similar, because alcohol can just be as addictive as drugs, and it can be as harmful as drugs.

Reference 2 - 100.00% Coverage

But I don't take drugs at all, because I was brought up in a family who like taught me that drugs are like a "no no". It was like a death route, you can't go there.

Reference 3 - 100.00% Coverage

I: you know how you said that you were raised in your family and told you should never take drugs, is that a cultural thing? Or is it something you were taught as part of your family?
 P14: I think it would be, I don't maybe a bit of both, because in terms of taking drugs, my mum culturally she thinks its like a manly thing.

Reference 4 - 100.00% Coverage

Like something that no lady should be doing, no girls should be doing. Its not a female thing, its not lady like, because its you know disgusting. In terms of just general, she just thinks its bad for you, in terms of like health and you know getting addicted to it would be so bad, like you can risk your life your it basicaly.

Reference 5 - 100.00% Coverage

I: would you say that in Chinese culture it is a taboo to discuss alcohol or drugs?

At the bottom of the interface, a status bar shows: LT 70 Items Sources: 4 References: 25 Unfiltered 100%

While the process appeared bewildering at first, continuous analysis, reading and revisiting the entirety of the transcripts, helped with further coding and gaining clarity. These processes are similar to that in the TA, as repeated scrutiny of the raw data and the emerging thematic is useful in the recognition of potentially significant units of meaning which may have been missed in the initial coding. Systematic analysis of the transcripts following coding involved establishing patterns in the data, including relationships within each individual transcript and across each transcript, and to make discoveries in the data. While this was a time-consuming process, it helped with recognising some of the questions which were not addressed. For instance, I did not ask the participants about amounts of drugs used, the preferred routes of administration of the drug, and amounts typically purchased for consumption in a systematic manner. Early analysis of the transcripts allowed me to modify this approach and gain further insights into the participants' experiences. However, it should also be noted that several of participants used to take drugs in the past, and their accounts revealed their past and not current use. Hence, the analysis did not occur in discrete stages, rather it was an iterative process. While I immersed myself in the data which is a privileged position, I adopted several means to limit potential bias. For instance, transcripts were reviewed by an experienced supervisory team; I also tested participants' statements during the interview by repeating statements in their own words for clarification.

This section discussed the coding process that was practiced in this thesis, illustrated the use of Nvivo in the creation of the initial coding template, and also demonstrated how Nvivo allowed for separating, classifying and synthesising the data. The next section explores the concept of hard-to-reach groups and this is used in the context this research.

3.4.3 Hard-to-Reach Groups

As briefly mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, the term hidden or hard-to-reach is used as a descriptor to identify cohorts of individuals who are under-represented in research studies (Bhopal and Deuchar, 2015). As such, individuals within this category are hard to research because of engagement barriers, socioeconomic disadvantages, as well as experiencing limited opportunities to engage with research. Researching-sensitive topics such as the use of alcohol and drugs among BME groups is equally difficult, due to fears of rejection/alienation from their own community, related to religious sanctions and gender expectations (detailed in Chapter 2, 6 and 7). The participants are at a risk of shame in certain contexts even if they actively resist such processes.

It is important to note that the 30 participants in this research are not victims, as they are active subjects taking informed decisions. However, they are at risk of shame of some individuals in their family or culture when they break the norms. Within the context of this thesis, the participants are considered hidden and/or hard to reach due to their transgressive use of AOD. I intentionally resolved to explore their subjective experiences of

consuming alcohol and drugs and how they identify with their ethnic and social identity while living in Scotland. The recruitment of hard-to-reach individuals is also an impediment due to methodological inclusion barriers such as lower numbers, as BME groups are scattered in small clusters geographically meaning that obtaining a representative sample is difficult. (Marpsat and Razafindratsima, 2010; Faugier and Sargeant, 1997; Atkinson and Flint, 2001).

Furthermore, BME groups are categorised as being hard to reach due to differences in cultural perceptions, language and social inclusion. Often these individuals have membership in a group with individuals from their own ethnic background, which might prevent them from talking to 'outsiders' about matters that concern the group. In such instances the researcher or the research team is considered to be an outsider (Bhopal, 2010), and hence there is a tendency for participants to distrust the researcher. This distrust often results from a lack of understanding of the research process, specifically surrounding the researcher's obligation to a duty of care as well as the participants understanding of confidentiality. As such, the researcher's motives are regarded with suspicion and hence a reluctance to participate. Given the inaccessible nature of this group to traditional and conventional methods, I used the qualitative design of semi-structured interviews with a purposeful sample of individuals from BME backgrounds (South Indian, Pakistani, Chinese, African and mixed backgrounds) (Section 3.3.1).

Having described why the participants in this research have been characterised as hard-to-reach, the next section explores the use of snowball sampling and the use of key informants for accessing the participants in this research.

3.4.4 Snowball Sampling

Snowball sampling (also known as chain referral) is a type of purposive sampling which allowed me to access participant's network of friends and contacts, exacted in the requirement of the inclusion criteria of never having accessed treatment. As such, I made a deliberate choice to favour a participant due to the qualities they possess (Tongco, 2007). This sampling is particularly exemplified for its use of key informants who are knowledgeable of a culture and are able and willing to share their knowledge (Campbell, 1955; Bernard, 2011). However, it is important to note that this technique is not free from bias, as informants may choose out of convenience. Yet it is this interpersonal bias that is one of the greatest strengths of this technique (Topp et al., 2004). I decided against the use of Respondent Driven Sampling (RDS) despite its advantages, due to its coupon redemption system which is costly to administer (Aldana and Quintero, 2008; Marpsat and Razafindratsima, 2010) and its use of incentives. This research was highly time constrained and did not provide the participants with any form of incentives, as such RDS was deemed unsuitable.

This particular sampling technique was sought as the use of AOD among BME groups is a sensitive issue, which requires the knowledge of insiders to locate respondents for the study. The BME groups in this study included individuals from Indian, Pakistani, Chinese, African and mixed-ethnic backgrounds. Snowball sampling is an example of a technique that was developed in an attempt to include hard-to-reach and hidden populations (Atkinson and Flint, 2001). In essence, the technique relies on a series of referrals that are made within a circle of people who know each other or are loosely connected. The respondent is asked to name other persons that fit the criteria described by the researcher. The newly identified persons are then interviewed and in turn asked to nominate others that fit the criteria and so on. Contact was maintained with participants up until the time of the interview. These informal contact sessions allowed the prospective participants to accustom themselves to me and to be able to raise any concerns they had with me. The sample was sought with a purpose in mind and ensuring that the individuals met the criteria for being in the sample.

Within the context of this study, key informants refer to those individuals who helped locate study participants, and who had no affiliation with any organisation, service or society. The key informants did not hold a position or status of influence in the community or a role of a gatekeeper to regulate my access to the population of study. While the key informants only had a pre-existing relationship (e.g. of being a friend, acquaintance, colleague) with the participants, they did not officially speak for the community

members or have any influencing roles in the community. Recruitment of participants occurred initially through five core contacts and four key informants that were familiar to me. These core contacts and key informants meant that the sample was not biased with individuals who shared a similar ethos with me or the contacts. Furthermore, the key informants were not chosen for helping me with increasing the representativeness McKenna and Main (2013) of the sample, but to provide rich data that does not always match that of the general community members (Bernard, 2017). This is further illustrated in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: Contacts & Key Informants Map

Having elucidated the sampling technique and the use of key informants in this research, the next section examines the sample used in this research.

3.4.5 The Sample

Demographic details collected at the outset of the interview asked for the participants – age, gender, ethnic group, place of birth, educational attainment, religion, drinking frequency and their generation in Scotland (e.g. first, second, third etc.). Types of drugs used were extracted during the course of the interview. To gain an understanding of the cultural influence of alcohol and drugs, country of birth and ethnicity were recorded. This was adapted from Scottish 2011 Census and is crucial in this study. Extracts from all 30 participants have been used liberally in this thesis to provide a rich source of data that relate to the issues being explored.

All 30 participants that were interviewed met the inclusion criteria, however following careful consideration, one participant's (P19) account suggested that the use of alcohol and drugs was not a hidden activity in his community or culture. However, his experiences of living in Scotland as a teenager, and his use of drugs while in Scotland was stigmatised by peers from his community. This then resulted in him concealing his use of drugs and making resultant lifestyle changes. Apart from six participants who did not disclose their occupation, the majority of participants were in occupations which could be considered middle (e.g. NHS Band 7 nurses, IT Advisors etc.) or upper-middle class (General Practitioners, medical consultants, doctors, etc.).

As a higher proportion of participants in this thesis were from upper/middle-class groups it could be argued that this was a sampling bias as a

consequence of the key informants used. Furthermore, the majority of the participants (n=25/30) had acquired university-level education and were graduates or post-graduates. This renders the possibility of analysing differences in socio economic status amongst the sample possible, although this was never an objective of the thesis. While representativeness of the sample was attempted, this was remarkably difficult given the sensitive nature of the research and resulted in fewer female participants being recruited (Females n=10/30; Males n=20/30; also illustrated in Table 10). The small sample size does not accurately reflect the numbers of drug users 'out there', however the qualitative nature of this thesis intended to capture BME individuals' experiences and perceptions of illicit drug use.

Table 3 illustrates the profile of the sample recruited and is colour coded to reflect the participants' ethnic background.

The next section illustrates the ethical processes that were executed to ensure participant confidentiality, anonymity and obtaining consent for participation.

Table 3: Participants by Ethnicity, Gender, Age, Education, Religion, Generation, Drinking Frequency and Drug Use

No.	Sex	Age	Religion	Education	Generation	Time in Scotland	Employment	Place of Birth	Reasons for Being in UK	Drinking Frequency	Drug Use
1	M	30-34	Hindu	MSc	First	11 years	Advisor (P/T)	Kerala, India	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	None
2	F	18-24	Christian	BSc (Hons)	First	13 years	Advisor (P/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	None
3	M	55-59	Christian	Diploma	First	14 years	NHS (P/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	None
4	F	50-54	Christian	BSc Nursing	First	13 years	NHS (F/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	About once a month	None
5	M	30-34	Hindu	MSc (computer)	First	4 years	IT (F/T)	Kerala, India	Education & Employment	About once a month	None
6	F	45-49	Hindu	BSc Nursing	First	11 years	NHS (F/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	About once a month	Paan/Betel leaves
7	M	45-49	Hindu	Diploma (Mechanical Engg)	First	10 years	Nursing Home (F/T) Ex Navy	Kerala, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	Used to Smoke Tobacco
8	F	25-29	Muslim	College	Third	From Birth	Advisor (F/T)	Glasgow (Pakistani)	By Birth	1-2 times per week	Tobacco & Cannabis
9	M	65-69	Christian	MBBS	First	31 years	Retired NHS Doctor	Kerala, India	Migrated	3-4 times per week	Use to smoke cannabis, Morphine
10	F	65-69	Christian	FRCS OPHTM	First	31 years	Retired NHS Doctor	Kerala, India	Migrated	Everyday	None
11	F	65-69	Hindu	RCOG	First	43 years	Retired NHS Doctor	Kerala, India	Migrated	Occasionally	None
12	M	18-24	Christian	SQA Highers	First	6 years	Catering (P/T)	Saudi Arabia (Indian)	Migrated (came with parents)	Once a month	None
13	M	35-39	Muslim	Highers (Horticulture)	Second	From Birth	Coiffeur (F/T)	Egypt (Irish Egyptian)	By Birth	1-2 times per week	Cannabis, heroin, truffles, acid, ketamine, 2ci, 2cb, microdots, liquid acids, liquid MDMA, cocaine
14	F	18-24	Buddhist	BA(Hons) Management	Second	From Birth	Graduated and searching for a job	Glasgow (Chinese)	By Birth	About once a month	Smoked Seesha
15	F	25-29	Christian	B ENG (Hon)	First	11 years	Council (F/T)	Black African (Ghana)	Migrated (came with parents)	About once a month	None
16	M	35-39	Christian (conv)	MSc	First	3 years	Undisclosed	Black African (Nigeria)	Education & Employment	About once a month	Tobacco
17	M	40-44	Christian	MSc	First	6 years	Customer Service (P/T)	Black African (Nigeria)	Education & Employment	About once a month	None
18	F	30-34	Hindu	Diploma (Nursing)	First	9 years	NHS (Neuro Nurse F/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	Do not drink now	None
19	M	30-34	Christian	BA (Hons) Business	First	13 years	Council (F/T)	Zambia	Migrated	1-2 times per week	Tobacco & Cannabis/ Grass
20	M	35-39	Hindu	MBBS, FRCA	First	16 years	NHS (F/T)	Bangalore, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	Paan/Betel leaves
21	M	40-44	Buddhist	PHD	First	8 years	Higher Education (P/T)	China	Education & Employment	3-4 times per week	None
22	M	25-29	Hindu	MSc	First	9 years	BT Case Manager (F/T)	India	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	Tobacco, cocaine
23	M	25-29	Muslim	BA	First	1 year	Catering (P/T)	Pakistan	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	Tobacco, Cannabis/weed, Hashish/hash, paan, seesha
24	M	25-29	Muslim	MSc	First	3 years	Grocery Store (P/T)	Pakistan	Education & Employment	Do not drink now	Tried tobacco and bhang/marijuana, t
25	M	25-29	Muslim	College	First	10 years	Delivery Driver (F/T)	Pakistan	Migrated	Do not drink now	Tobacco
26	M	40-44	Muslim	BA	Second	From Birth	Undisclosed, student	Scotland (British Indian)	By Birth	Do not drink now	Used to take marijuana, cocaine, speed, acids, ecstasy
27	M	25-29	Christian	B ENG (Hon)	First	8 years	Undisclosed	Black African (Ghana)	Education & Employment	About once a month	None
28	M	18-24	Christian	B ENG (Hon)	First	3 years	Undisclosed	Black African (Nigeria)	Education & Employment	About once a month	Weed
29	F	30-34	Christian	MSc	First	10 years	Undisclosed	Taiwan	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	Cannabis/weed
30	M	25-29	No Religion (B)	MSc	First	4 year	Undisclosed	China	Education & Employment	About once a month	None

Indian Black African Pakistani Chinese Mixed

3.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was received from the School of Media, Culture and Society at the University of West of Scotland, prior to commencing the semi-structured interviews. Written consent was obtained from participants prior to any recorded interview taking place. In circumstances where Skype interviews were conducted, verbal and electronic consent was also acquired from the participants (Information Sheet, Appendix 1; Consent Form, Appendix 2; Semi-structured Interview Schedule, Appendix 3; Demographics Questionnaire, Appendix 4). This demonstrates that participants understood the nature and purpose of the study, had opportunity to ask any questions, as well as agreeing that their participation was on a voluntary basis (Ritchie et al., 2013). However, research evidence also indicates that asking for written consent increases individuals willingness to participate, while also making them feel compelled to take part in the study (Singer, 2003; Graham et al., 2007). Unlike biomedical research, within the social sciences and particularly so in this research, the intention of acquiring consent was not just to safeguard the needs of the participants. Acquiring consent formed the basis for a written contract between the participant and I, confirming my promises to the participants and articulating the participant's rights. Furthermore, no incentives in the form of payments or any other non-monetary form were given to the participants to encourage or pressurise participation. As the participants were consulted as experts, they were validated in recalling their experiences to me.

The interview did often digress into sensitive topics, for instance how and in what way participants engaged in the use of AOD; their experiences of stigmatisation etc. Hence, during the course of the interview whenever participants appeared to be in distress, the interview was stopped, allowing them time to regain composure. For instance, when one Pakistani female participant was explaining her efforts in concealing her use of alcohol and drugs from her family, she became distressed. She revealed a very personal account of how she was forced to undergo an abortion due to her family's persistence. She explained that her family blamed her use of AOD for transgressing from the Islamic doctrine and how she would bring shame to the family for her premarital pregnancy. As she appeared distressed while explaining the abortion, I stopped the interview and later continued after she insisted that she was happy for the interview to continue. There was only one such incident when the interview had to be paused. Likewise, the interview always commenced with a general inquiry relating to a self-introduction of the participant, before divulging into sensitive topics. The participants were also informed that they did not have to answer any question which made them feel uncomfortable.

Additionally, in accordance with the Data Protection Act 1984, participants also had the right to see their own written transcripts or listen to their own recorded interviews that I had collected. During the course of this research, every effort was made to adhere to the guidelines defined by the British

Sociological Association⁷, particularly those concerned with working with vulnerable groups⁸.

3.5.1 Confidentiality and Anonymity

Complete anonymity was guaranteed within the confines of the ethics procedures that had to be followed. Participants were not asked for their full name, and numeric pseudonym were used from the outset. The anonymity of participants was protected by numerically coding each section of data with the transcripts and keeping the responses confidential. Throughout the transcription of interviews participants were assigned numeric codes that corresponded with their demographic information. Any identifiable information of participants, for instance, place of residence, immediate geographic location and names were generalised to prevent identification. The demographics collected only asked for the participants – age, gender, ethnic group, place of birth, educational attainment, religion, drinking frequency and their generation in Scotland (e.g. first, second, third etc.).

The next section discusses my journey in this research and how I used myself as a research tool which helped with reaching the purposive sample of participants in this study.

⁷ Statement of Ethical Practice for the British Sociological Association (March 2002): <https://www.britsoc.co.uk/equality-diversity/statement-of-ethical-practice/>

⁸ Justify the purpose of using confidential information; do not use participant identifiable information unless it is absolutely necessary; Use the minimum necessary participant information that is required; Access to participant identifiable information should be on a strict need to know basis; everyone with access to participant identifiable information should be aware of their responsibilities; understand and comply with the law.

3.6 The Researcher's Identity & Reflections

This section reflects on my characteristics and experiences that influenced this dynamic data collection. Some aspects of this section have been summarised in Chapter 1 to further the rationale for this study.

This research was partly driven by my own ethnic background as I am a naturalised British Indian. I was born in Libya and raised by parents from India. The impulse that drove me to undertake this study arose from my experiences of being from a BME community, as well as experience of having worked within the field of addictions. Undertaking fieldwork as an Alcohol Advisor in the West of Scotland, helped me in identifying that very few individuals from minority backgrounds attended services and an awareness that even recreational use of AOD is concealed. This encouraged me to pursue a Master's degree comparing alcohol use among BME students and home students. The limitations from my masters which included low participation from BME students led to this thesis with a purposive sample and the use of a qualitative methodology.

My personal experiences of being one among them, primed me of the stigma that individuals from BME backgrounds encountered, were they to be identified as being a problematic AOD-user within their community. These concerns and anxiety of being perceived as a problematic user drives these individuals to great lengths to conceal even recreational use of alcohol, while the use of drugs is rare, and largely demonised by most BME individuals. Furthermore, being well acquainted with the various BME

communities in the West of Scotland, having observed their use of AOD, and being familiar with their gendered consumption practices, only increased my need to explore the transgressions that these BME individuals engaged in while in maintaining a Scottish and an ethnic identity.

The most influential factor for establishing a relationship with the participants, has been my ethnic identity. Sharing the identity of being from an ethnic background and having the status of a British Indian helped in averting awkwardness and in establishing a good rapport with all participants quickly. Being from a similar minority background, I was able to decrease the distance between the participants ethnic background and immediately introduce a degree of familiarity. In instances prior to the interview and during the interview, several participants asked questions about my background and my own use of AOD. Sharing these experiences served in the creation of an atmosphere of mutual exchange which only helped fortify the relationship even further. However, there were also several occasions when my interest in their use of drugs was regarded with suspicion and as an attempt to expose the failings within the community. This was deemed threatening as it would distinguish their community as being unsuccessful in merging with Scottish culture, but also portraying their community as being tainted with the stigma associated with (white) problematic users. There were other occasions when female participants expressed endearment to me, as they often felt their use of alcohol and drugs rendered them visible to stigmatisation and being misunderstood.

Additionally, my ability to speak Malayalam, Hindi, Urdu, and Arabic proved hugely advantageous for facilitating a more meaningful dialogue. Being multilingual also helped in simplifying access and recruitment of participants, specifically despite anticipated trust issues, as this helped in accessing those individuals who were not fluent in speaking English. While most of the research participants were extremely articulate using English, several participants communicated their experiences in their mother tongue to better express themselves (e.g. Malayalam, Hindi, and Urdu). As such, I expertly translated their accounts, making every effort during translation, to ensure that the meaning and true nature of the conversation was preserved. Translated quotes are presented in Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7. Where participants articulated accounts in Swahili, Mandarin, and Urdu I inquired further through probes, for the meaning of such accounts. The need to explore and interpret reflexively was realised during the first few interviews.

In the majority of the interviews, the participants appeared to assume that there was a level of understanding between both themselves and me based on our shared status of being a migrant. Indian and Pakistani participants were more willing to share their experiences with me due to my ability to speak their language. Equally, my status of being a migrant meant that the African, Chinese and Mixed participants exhibited trust in me. Trust and respect were important factors in participants sharing their experiences with me. However, it is important to mention that my gender and age also played a significant role in establishing and winning the trust of

participants. Having an intimate knowledge of ethnic minority customs, was also hugely advantageous in eliciting this trust.

Sporadically during the course of the interview, participants made normative assumptions in which it was taken for granted that I knew what they meant, through expressions as 'you know'? The participants had an expectation of me to be aware of their experiences of being a migrant and their use of alcohol and drugs. And perhaps because of this they were quite open about their experiences of using alcohol and drugs in their home country and in Scotland. The main aim with the interviews being semi-structured was to draw out these assumptions and make them explicit. This enabled the construction of a chain of reasoning that constituted a coherent explanation of the participant's experiences within the transcript.

The issues of validity in this research were directly addressed by ensuring that the question content directly concentrated on the research objectives. I consistently explained the aims and objectives to the participants prior to the start of the interview, irrespective of the means of initial contact, and before consent for the interview was obtained. Other measures used to ensure validity included: building rapport and trust with the participants, as this allowed the participants to express themselves better; and prompting to ensure that clarity of statements was established, as well as allowing the participants to expand on their initial responses. A reflective protocol was adhered to in the process of my research journey, which not only informed me in making the necessary changes to the subsequent

interview schedules and processes, but also improved the participant's responses. To ensure the accuracy of the data, transcriptions were also crosschecked with audio recordings. The sample size of the study was increased until no new viewpoints emerged from the Indian participants, who formed the majority in this research. While saturation was not achievable for the other groups, similar themes emerged from the analysis, and this led me to make an informed judgement to conclude data collection.

Prior to the start of the interviews, I had anticipated that my gender would form a barrier and cause participants to become hesitant to reveal some of their experiences. On the contrary, I experienced that it only helped in shaping my relationship with the participants and in many instances seemed to relax the participants. However, there were several instances where male participants imposed their masculinity on me while expressing their perceptions of gendered drinking practices. In such instances I addressed them with tact and allowed the participants to project control of the interview, and while I assumed the role of a novice. The age differences between the participants and I was not considerable and appeared to establish positive rapport. It must be acknowledged that power relations are very complex in interviews (Bhopal, 2010), especially the participants' power in what they choose to share with the researcher. As such, emphasis was given on establishing an equal relationship in most instances, but the need to assume the role of a novice in some situations.

This section explored how my characteristics and experiences guided me in being a research tool for data collection. I have also expressed how I dealt with the reliability and validity issues that arose during the course of this research. The next section discusses the analysis.

3.7 Analysis

All recordings were transcribed using Nvivo and then exported to Microsoft Word to allow for manual coding a random selection of transcripts. As previously mentioned in Section 3.5.1, every participant was given a numeric pseudonym to allow for their individual voices to be identified easily.

It is evident from the 30 participants in this study that drinking is a common feature in all the ethnic groups, with varying frequencies when compared to Scottish drinking patterns. Drinking patterns tend to vary both between and within ethnic groups. Fourteen Indian participants were recruited, of these 11 participants revealed alcohol enculturation⁹. Four Pakistani participants were recruited, all four participants reported using tobacco and its derivatives, two participants reported being abstinent from alcohol at the time of interview. All four Chinese participants consumed alcohol and two reported the use cannabis. Five African participants reported using of alcohol and drinking only once a month, while one participant reported having one to two drinks per week. Two of the six participants reported the

⁹ 'Alcohol enculturation' refers to the process of BME's accepting Scottish drinking norms, discussed in greater detail in Chapter 3.

use of cannabis. Finally, two mixed participants were recruited, both participants reported the use of alcohol and drugs, however one participant is now abstinent.

The next four sections explore the participants' demographic attributes on the basis of their ethnic origin. Furthermore, the types of drugs used by participants in this research are included in Table 9.

3.7.1 Indian Participants

Table 4: Summary of Indian Participants

No.	Sex	Age	Religion	Education	Generation in UK	Time in Scotland	Employment	Place of Birth	Reasons for Being in UK	Drinking Frequency	Drug Use
1	M	30-34	Hindu	MSc	First	11 years	Advisor (P/T)	Kerala, India	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	None
2	F	18-24	Christian	BSc (Hons)	First	13 years	Advisor (P/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	None
3	M	55-59	Christian	Diploma (Microbiology)	First	14 years	NHS (P/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	None
4	F	50-54	Christian	BSc Nursing	First	15 years	NHS (F/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	About once a month	None
5	M	30-34	Hindu	MSc (computer Applications)	First	4 years	IT (F/T)	Kerala, India	Education & Employment	About once a month	None
6	F	45-49	Hindu	BSc Nursing	First	11 years	NHS (F/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	About once a month	Paan/Betel leaves
7	M	45-49	Hindu	Diploma (Mechanical Engg)	First	10 years	Nursing Home (F/T) Ex Navy	Kerala, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	Used to Smoke Tobacco
9	M	65-69	Christian	MBBS	First	31 years	Retired NHS Doctor	Kerala, India	Migrated	3-4 times per week	Use to smoke cannabis, Morphine
10	F	65-69	Christian	FRCS OPHTM	First	31 years	Retired NHS Doctor	Kerala, India	Migrated	Everyday	None
11	F	65-69	Hindu	RCOG	First	43 years	Retired NHS Doctor	Kerala, India	Migrated	Occasionally	None
12	M	18-24	Christian	SQA Highers	First	6 years	Catering (P/T)	Saudi Arabia (Indian)	Migrated (came with parents)	Once a month	None
18	F	30-34	Hindu	Diploma (Nursing)	First	9 years	NHS (Neuro Nurse F/T)	Kerala, India	Migrated	Do not drink now	None
20	M	35-39	Hindu	MBBS, FRCA	First	16 years	NHS (F/T)	Bangalore, India	Migrated	1-2 times per week	Paan/Betel leaves
22	M	25-29	Hindu	MSc	First	9 years	BT Case Manager (F/T)	India	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	Tobacco, cocaine

Within the Indian participants (n=14/30) all 14 participants were from the South of India and had varied perceptions of the use of alcohol. The majority of the South Indians included in this study were from Kerala (n=12/14) and two were from Bengaluru (n=2/14). While most (n=11/14) participants confirmed normalisation of alcohol use within the culture, others (n=3/14) disagreed with this notion. Perceptions regarding use and problematic use were varied, with some agreeing with recreational use and others considering recreational use as harmful. Indian participants reported recreational drug use among their community and friends as being uncommon and inconceivable, as well as there being a lack of awareness of the frequency of use and the types of drugs used. Nine out of 14 participants reported no drug use; two reported use of paan/betel leaves; one reported use of cannabis and morphine; one reported tobacco use; and one reported tobacco and cocaine use.

3.7.2 Chinese Participants

Table 5: Summary of Chinese Participants

No.	Sex	Age	Religion	Education	Generation	Time in Scotland	Employment	Place of Birth	Reasons for Being in UK	Drinking Frequency	Drug Use
14	F	18-24	Buddhist	BA(Hons) Management	Second	From Birth	Graduated and searching for a job	Glasgow (Chinese)	By Birth	About once a month	Smoked Seesha
21	M	40-44	Buddhist	PhD	First	8 years	Higher Education (P/T)	China	Education & Employment	3-4 times per week	None
29	F	30-34	Christian	MSc	First	10 years	Undisclosed	Taiwan	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	Cannabis /weed
30	M	25-29	No Religion (Buddhist by Birth)	MSc	First	4 year	Undisclosed	China	Education & Employment	About once a month	None

Among Chinese participants (n=4/30), alcohol is an important aspect of the culture. Drinking is socially accepted and plays a significant part in major events. Two out of four participants reported use of drugs (one cannabis, one seesha).

3.7.3 Pakistani Participants

Table 6: Summary of Pakistani Participants

No.	Sex	Age	Religion	Education	Generation	Time in Scotland	Employment	Place of Birth	Reasons for Being in UK	Drinking Frequency	Drug Use
8	F	25-29	Muslim	College (Childcare & Education)	Third	From Birth	Advisor (F/T)	Glasgow (Pakistani)	By Birth	1-2 times per week	Tobacco & Cannabis
23	M	25-29	Muslim	BA	First	1 year	Catering (P/T)	Pakistan	Education & Employment	1-2 times per week	Tobacco, Cannabis/weed, Hashish/hash, paan, seesha
24	M	25-29	Muslim	MSc	First	5 years	Grocery Store (P/T)	Pakistan	Education & Employment	Do not drink now	Tried tobacco and bhaang/marijuana, bidi, paan, ghutka, seesha
25	M	25-29	Muslim	College	First	10 years	Delivery Driver (F/T)	Pakistan	Migrated	Do not drink now	Tobacco

Pakistani participants (n=4/30) stated that drinking was not socially accepted in their culture, as alcohol consumption is disapproved on religious grounds. Furthermore, participants also reported that they tended not to consume alcohol in front of their parents or family. Drinking was primarily initiated through their peers. Participants also reported stigma and shame if they were to be found drinking. Drug use within Pakistani communities was reported to be highly stigmatised, and as a result a hidden

activity. All four participants reported use of tobacco and its derivatives, three participants reported use of cannabis.

3.7.4 African Participants

Table 7: Summary of African Participants

No.	Sex	Age	Religion	Education	Generation	Time in Scotland	Employment	Place of Birth	Reasons for Being in UK	Drinking Frequency	Drug Use
15	F	25-29	Christian	B ENG (Hon)	First	11 years	Council (F/T)	Black African (Ghana)	Migrated (came with parents)	About once a month	None
16	M	35-39	Christian (converted from Islam)	MSc	First	5 years	Undisclosed	Black African (Nigeria)	Education & Employment	About once a month	Tobacco
17	M	40-44	Christian	MSc	First	6 years	Customer Service (P/T)	Black African (Nigeria)	Education & Employment	About once a month	None
19	M	30-34	Christian	BA (Hons) Business	First	13 years	Council (F/T)	Zambia	Migrated	1-2 times per week	Tobacco & Cannabis / Grass
27	M	25-29	Christian	B ENG (Hon)	First	8 years	Undisclosed	Black African (Ghana)	Education & Employment	About once a month	None
28	M	18-24	Christian	B ENG (Hon)	First	5 years	Undisclosed	Black African (Nigeria)	Education & Employment	About once a month	Weed

Participants from Africa (n=6/30) included those from Nigerian (n=3), Zambian (n=1) and Ghanaian (n=2) backgrounds. All participants perceived the use of alcohol harmful if exceeding the Scottish drinking guidelines. However, this notion of limit was rarely that of legal drinking limits, and more a reflection of personal limits. Drinking as part of socialisation was considered as acceptable, however regular recreational drinking was perceived negatively due to its effects on the body. Levels of education and socio-economic status appeared to be important factors in social drinking among the majority of the participants. Drunkenness was highly disapproved of due to concerns of it reflecting on the family's

reputation and bringing shame or disgrace to the family. Participants reported that use of tobacco and drugs was highly frowned upon within the community. Tobacco was also seen as a gateway to other drugs and subsequently admonished within the community. Three out of six participants reported no drug use; one participant reported sole use of tobacco; one participant reported use of cannabis alone, and one participant reported use of both tobacco and cannabis.

3.7.5 Mixed Participants

Table 8: Summary of Mixed Participants

No.	Sex	Age	Religion	Education	Generation	Time in Scotland	Employment	Place of Birth	Reasons for Being in UK	Drinking Frequency	Drug Use
13	M	35-39	Muslim	Highers (Horticulture)	Second	From Birth	Coiffeur (F/T)	Egypt (Irish Egyptian)	By Birth	1-2 times per week	Cannabis, heroin, truffles, acid, ketamine, 2ci, 2cb, microdots, liquid acids, liquid MDMA, cocaine
26	M	40-44	Muslim	BA	Second	From Birth	Undisclosed, student	Scotland (British Indian)	By Birth	Do not drink now	Used to take marijuana, cocaine, speed, acids, ecstasy

Participants from mixed backgrounds (n=2/30) reported high rates of current use of alcohol. Furthermore, drinking was described as an important aspect of their culture and as such socially accepted. Both participants from mixed ethnic backgrounds reported that the use of drugs was normalised among their friends and their community. Both participants reported use of a variety of drugs including cannabis, methamphetamine, LSD, cocaine,

ecstasy, heroin etc. Of the two participants, one participant had discontinued the use of alcohol and drugs.

Table 9: Classification of Types of Drugs in This Study

Alcohol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spirits, wine, beer
Tobacco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chewed tobacco/ paan/ betel leaves Chewed tobacco is consumed in the form of Paan and is used traditionally in many South Asian Countries. Paan is a mix of areca nut, acacia extract and inorganic lime. This is wrapped in betel leaf and includes dried tobacco (Warnakulasuriya, 2002). Paan itself is not a tobacco product; however smokeless tobacco is mixed with other ingredients. Another derivative is “Gutkha” and includes tobacco and paan masala (Millward and Karlsen, 2011). • Shisha This is an equipment for smoking tobacco through a bowl and a hose/tube. This is also alternatively known as hookah, shisha, even hubble-bubble pipes, and are traditionally used in the Middle East to smoke tobacco. However, it is widely popular among BMEs in UK and are used as an alternative to nightclubs (shisha bars) and visiting pubs (Action on Smoking and Health, 2011).

Drugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannabis (also referred to as Hashish, Grass, Weed, Indian Hemp, Bhaang, Marijuana) • Khat (quat, qat, qaadka, chat) <p>Khat is predominantly used by those from the African regions (Nigeria, Somalia etc.). It produces amphetamine-like effects, and is consumed orally by chewing, brewing, or smoking the leaves of the plant <i>Catha edulis</i> (Griffiths et al., 1997; Hassan et al., 2002).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heroin • Cocaine (power and/or crack cocaine) • Truffles • Ecstasy • Amphetamines as speed, MDMA (including liquid) • Hallucinogens as acid, liquid acid, microdots, 2C-I, 2C-B, Ketamine
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Table 10: Participants by Gender and Ethnic Group

Ethnic Group	Gender	
	Males	Females
Indian	8	6
Pakistani	3	1
Black African	5	1
Chinese	3	1
Mixed Ethnic	2	0

3.8 Conclusion

This chapter discussed the philosophical foundations of qualitative research which were embraced in this study, as well as the justifications for the rejection of positivistic traditions. A moderate social constructionist lens established how BME individual's constructions reflect their understandings of their experience of drug use, as well as the diverse situations in which they have them. Distinctions were made between radical and moderate social constructionism, as well as the reasons for adopting moderate social constructionist perspectives. The hybrid inductive and deductive TA approach adapted from Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006) was explained with the formulation of a coding template. The use of the computer assisted software Nvivo for conducting TA allowed for detecting the most salient patterns of content in the interviews. It was further discussed how purposive snowball sampling technique was sought in this study. Particularly as alcohol and drug use among BME groups is a sensitive issue, which requires the knowledge of expert insiders to locate respondents for the study.

The complex relationship between the researcher and participants were discussed, where the researcher's ethnic background served the position of being both an insider and an outsider. Power relationships between the researcher and the participants were maintained at an equal stance and facilitated rapport. The researcher's reflections of the research process and their position serves the purpose of explicating how it shapes the participants and the researcher's relationship.

The data for this research was collected from 30 BME background individuals. These participants provided multiple perspectives of their experiences and were enthusiastic in recounting their narratives. Accessing such a hard-to-reach group was difficult, time consuming, frustrating, and often disappointing when they pulled out or failed to keep their appointment; however, despite these concerns those who took part provided a rich source of data, and a multitude of perspectives.

The next four results and data analysis chapters explore who these participants are, and their use of AOD. Their perceptions of the influence of their culture, religion, gender and age are revealed, and how these impacts on their sense of identity.

4 Alcohol: “The mother of all troubles”

4.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on aspects of the participants’ identity that are hidden from their Scottish friends and workmates, as well as aspects of their behaviour and beliefs that they hide from their family values and extended family ‘back home’. It is this conflict and hidden nature that is presented through their personal perceptions of alcohol, within their family and culture, and comparing this with their current use. Accounts vary from conservative attitudes to drinking as a result of there being more restrictions imposed by their ‘home’ culture e.g. differences in perceptions based on ethnic group, differences in availability, as well as negative perceptions of Scottish drinking culture. Furthermore, initiation of alcohol use is described as occurring in ways that vary from Scottish cultural norms, and include extended family, peers and work colleagues.

In this chapter, alcohol use as deviance will be discussed using four different perspectives that have been derived and modified using the work of Roman (2015), namely – positivistic perspectives, preventative perspectives, medical-disease perspectives, and public-health perspectives. While the definitions of social deviance are central to and underpin the discussions in this thesis, in this chapter, deviance associated with alcohol use behaviour that is subject to formal or informal negative sanctions are considered. This chapter also draws upon Pitman’s (1965) classification of drinking cultures, namely – abstinent, ambivalent and

permissive cultures to elucidate the relationship between the participant, their family and religious group, and their country of origin. These three classifications, while simplistic, are helpful to compare and contrast the function of consuming alcohol in Scottish culture; also useful is the simple typology of “wet” and “dry” cultures which describe drinking patterns, levels of drunkenness, and how alcohol is regulated (Room and Makela, 2000). Finally, participants’ accounts of ‘what it means to be a drinker’ are explored through their describing use as a problem and the impact of deviance and stigma on their identity were their deviance to become known.

4.2 Personal Attitudes and Alcohol Use

Accounts in this section reflect the participants views on the use of alcohol based on their personal experiences of the use and meaning of alcohol in Scotland. Establishing this helps in providing an understanding of the norms that regulate drinking in their culture of origin and is explored below.

An Indian female participant indicates that attitudes towards moderate use of alcohol is permissive in her culture, as a means to socialise or for pleasure:

“Well alcohol seems to be quite normal in my culture people drink; it’s not some big deal. Drinking just to socialise or maybe just to enjoy yourself...” [Female, Indian; Participant 2 (P2), 18-24].

Likewise, a Chinese participant expresses how alcohol is an important medium for celebrations and gatherings in Chinese culture. A celebration is

incomplete without drinking and is an indicator of permissive drinking within his culture:

"We always have a drink for a celebration. That's normal in Chinese culture, because in our culture alcohol is frequently used as a symbol, or a medium for people to celebrate. So if you want to celebrate, without alcohol or without beer or something, as we like these things, we cannot..." [Male, Chinese, 40-44; P21].

On the contrary, Pakistani culture can be categorised as ascetic, in that there is an intolerance for anyone to publicly consume alcoholic beverages. In this regard cultural groupings living in Islamic, Hindu and Ascetic Protestant traditions do not consume alcohol, but is particularly so in the Islamic tradition as powerful forces act to restrict and demonise drinking. For Muslims who use alcohol, such as female Pakistani participants, it is reflective of cultural diffusion to Scottish drinking patterns and is often considered to be a contributory factor to an erosion of tradition. This is well articulated in theories of acculturation and reveals for her, an identity crisis:

"Well yea I do drink. I think I'm pretty much open to most things...Alcohol I know for a fact, I've been through it, you're literally poisoning yourself, but you're enjoying it at the same time..." [Female, Pakistani, 25-29; P8].

Similarly, a female Indian participant who is a Hindu sensed that she would be disrespecting her social grouping and Scottish drinking norms if she refused a drink. This also reveals how personally constructed norms regards drinking change over time. This is because drinking is viewed negatively in her community, her family, and in her religion. However, conflict in her

identity is apparent as she perceives that refusing a drink would not just be disrespectful to others, but would also indicate withdrawal from Scottish culture and a failure to blend in with Scottish norms. The participant reflects on her experience, and verifies an unseen and yet powerful expectation for her to drink alcohol, highlighting the influence of normative expectations in influencing her behaviour, which directly or indirectly are enforced by sanctions set by her subculture or social world:

"In the beginning in the 70s and 80s, we used to feel like, say if you went for a party and were offered a drink and you don't accept it, you are almost withdrawing from the society, you are not taking part in the life of the community or whatever group you are in. So, I can say in the beginning I did drink sherry or something else because I thought it was expected of me" [Female, Indian, 65-69; P11].

Some African cultures do exhibit ambivalence toward alcohol use which causes a conflict between co-existing and conflicting value structures for such migrants. These conflicts are due to changes or disintegration in traditional values which is considered to be a result of cultural contact (perceived and expressed often as contamination) with Western societies. However, conflict also results from drinking when one has been socialised in a culture that stresses respect for abstinence as it is considered to be necessary for a good healthy and successful life. This conflict is most apparent with the use of alcohol in ceremonies among certain groups (traditional African communities), and ascetic Protestant groups practiced by some African natives and migrants who consider the use of alcohol to be sinful irrespective of consumption levels. It is this ambivalence that

limits the development of stable attitudes towards drinking. An African participant describes these co-existing conflicts in justifying why consumption of alcohol is now more acceptable within her family as a requirement of acculturation and fitting in:

"It's not normal, but I think because people are getting more advanced now and going to the modern world now, they kind of find it to be a bit okay to accept..." [Female, African, 25-29; P15].

Drinking is a social activity, a way of finding acceptance with others, a symbol of celebration, a way to relax and enjoy oneself, even as one female Pakistani participant (P 8) stated one is 'literally poisoning yourself', and finally an expression from a male participant of mixed ethnicity (Irish Egyptian) that getting 'hammered' is a normal aspect of how his family uses alcohol:

"It obviously isn't a problem over here [In Scotland]. All my mum's family are from Ireland and are all stoners. Not all the time, but like often, they get together and they get fucking, I wouldn't say hammered, but they drink, spirits and shit, but it's not like they are pretending, it's not like they are sipping their drinks. I've never seen them like in a pure nick, not many of them. They hold it together, but they are used to it. That's the culture, and here it is the same..." [Male, Mixed (Irish Egyptian), 35-39; P13].

The accounts from the participants reveal how they perceive their use of alcohol and how they compare this with Scottish drinking norms. The next section explores how the participants adapt or reject their drinking practices with that of Scottish drinking norms and introduces the concept of 'alcohol enculturation'.

4.3 “You can do what you want”: Adaptation to Scotland

The act of establishing a coherent identity is an important factor in any individual's life. An individual's sense of identity is grounded in their own cultural group and the dominant culture of the country in which they live. In a diverse society such as Scotland, people from different cultures have a high likelihood of not developing a coherent sense of identity, being faced with several identities and thereby leading to identity conflict.

This section applies three aspects of the bi-dimensional model of acculturation by Landrine and Klonoff (2004) (assimilation, dissociation and marginalization) to explain how BME individuals integrate Scottish cultural norms and values while simultaneously maintaining the values and behaviours of their original culture. Illustrated are participants' experiences supporting aspects of the bi-dimensional model of acculturation, as well as how uncertainty and identification with Scottish drinking norms creates several competing identities. There are variations in perceptions of alcohol, within their family and culture, and these are further discussed by comparing participants' current use with norms 'back home'.

An Indian participant demonstrates how identifying and adopting Scottish drinking norms conflicts with inherited norms, where drinking and smoking are negatively stereotyped. Unsurprisingly the participant attempts to resolve his uncertainty about his perceptions, attitudes, and feelings towards drinking and smoking, as it was important to him in the context of his identity as an acculturated Scottish citizen, and how he presents himself

when socialising with peers. The negative perceptions towards drinking and smoking that the participant initially held have been replaced with a nuanced normalisation to Scottish drinking norms; where there is greater accessibility and occasions for drinking, which are regulated by legal and organisational control (e.g. legal age limit of 18 years and above):

"My mental thinking towards drinking and smoking was completely different when I was in India, compared to how it is now or here. So where I come from, in that city, when you see people drinking or smoking, people give a weird look like "okay this person is smoking or drinking, this person is not good or not nice, as he is doing some bad karma and stuff". This is how my childhood has been, like I've grown up in this environment, so that's the picture I had always. So when I came here, drinking it's like so easy here, like accessible wise, and going out, as long as you are over 18 you can do what you want..."
[Male, Indian, 25-29; P22].

An African participant describes a dissociative attitude in relation to adhering in some way to Scottish drinking norms, while maintaining a need to retain his ethnic identity. He believes Scottish norms are not strict enough causing youngsters to deviate and leading to a greater risk of young people in his community experimenting with drugs and alcohol. While availability and access to alcohol and tobacco is subject to a strict system of legal and organisational control in Scotland, this is not the case in Africa. This participant's view is synonymous to that of P 22 above in relation to normalisation with Scottish drinking norms, but opposes acculturation:

"...In my own generation most of our parents were very hard on us. So we couldn't misbehave. So you are brought up in a decent manner, but not to say that you are not allowed to take alcohol. It's going to be easy to access if you are here in the UK, because you can always go to a club or through friends who indulge in it, and they could always show you the way, you know?" [Male, African, 40-44; P 17].

The African participant demonstrates a level of contempt of British/Scottish culture, lacking discipline, respect and allowing greater freedom for expression among children and youngsters. Hence, he argues that stronger family restrictions should be imposed on children socialising with peers from the dominant culture, as a means of reducing acculturation to Scottish drinking norms:

"...But if the family setting is still wrong, because there is something about the UK here where you can't really be hard on your kids. They (kids) have a certain degree of freedom, whereas in Nigeria you have no freedom, you have to listen to your elders. So if a Nigerian parent adopts the British way of bringing a child, the child could go astray. Yep, could indulge in drugs or alcohol. But if you still train them, if you are hard on them, because I have some Nigerian families here who say "when you are here fine, but when you are in my house, the 4 walls of my house it is Nigeria. Outside there, it's Scotland, but inside here it's Nigeria!" [Male, African, 40-44; P 17].

An account from a Chinese participant indicates that her parents neither identify with Chinese cultural norms, nor do they identify with Scottish cultural norms, which aligns with marginal acculturation. Her experiences are also indicative of the uncertainty she experiences due to the competing identities she has to employ in identifying with Scottish norms and her familial norms:

"My parents, they were like okay it is good to have a wee sip or a glass or wine or something, or glass of just vodka or something like mixed. Because it gets your tolerance up, and if you do go out and socialise, you won't be made, you know - won't be like drunk easily and anyone can just take advantage of you or whatever. They say that to me, so yea I do drink a little, and they are okay with it. I think it's not fair because, like you know, I've been brought up here, and if are brought up in a country, and you came to this country, you are brought up here, you would think that because you are brought up here, or because you moved to this country, you try and adapt yourself towards that other culture or western culture. But my parents still have their own thoughts and stuff, like the way they did. They have adapted to western culture as well a little, but like they haven't completely transferred themselves to this western culture. They like to remain in some of their Chinese culture." [Female, Chinese, 18-24; P 14].

Participant 14 highlights the fears that she has or has been disseminated to her from her Chinese culture, and that the use of alcohol will make her vulnerable. She explains that the use of alcohol requires some degree of building up tolerance so that she can engage with Scots culture, insofar as she describes drinking to keep her 'tolerance up'. She also describes the tensions she experiences as a person from a BME group, who must also live up to the expectations of being a Chinese female.

It could be argued that alcohol in the form of champagne and expensive wines are a sign of conspicuous consumption in many western cultures, and thereby is in this sense a symbol of success, and as such to enhance one's virtual status in a social grouping. A participant with mixed ethnic origins (Irish Egyptian) notes that in his native country (Egypt) that drinking can be a hidden activity, socio-economic status and class can be demonstrated by the level of access one has to alcohol in his culture:

"...they don't drink in Egypt. The odd ones will take a drink, but I mean drink is hard to come by. Depends on who you know, if you are wealthy, getting stuff is going to be easier. A wealthy person can have pretty much whatever they want. But if you are not, I think it still pretty much depends on your environment" [Male, Mixed (Irish Egyptian), 25-29; P 13].

It is interesting, that despite alcohol intoxication being an acceptable aspect of Scots culture, where initiation into a drinking culture is considered in some ways normal, the use of alcohol and how and when one should be exposed to it differs greatly. Participant accounts reveal that while most of them perceive drinking as a normal activity in Scotland, the use of alcohol appears to allow a degree of acceptance within Scottish culture, where alcohol is widely used and accepted as normal, it is also unacceptable in certain circumstances.

The next section explores the participants' initiation into alcohol and the meanings attributed to drinking alcohol.

4.4 Initiation and Social Learning of Alcohol Use

Acculturation through several factors acts as mechanisms through which changes in attitudes to drinking occur. The participant data reveal three themes that explained how they were introduced or initiated into the use of alcohol: family, friends and work colleagues.

4.4.1 Initiation & Family

Primary exposure to drinking habits most often occur by observing parents or older siblings, and are an important part of acquiring and learning what one's family thinks about alcohol, and how and in what way it should be used, and what are and are not accepted norms for drunken comportment in all cultures. Chapter 2 discussed how cultural values and norms, transmitted within the family and other mechanisms of socialization shape the way in which different ethnic groups use alcohol and what it means to be a drinker. Below are a few illustrations from participants regarding their initiation into alcohol use through family.

A male Chinese participant describes his first encounter with alcohol being with his father at the age of seven or eight, and how the use of alcohol is positively supported within his family and culture. His account indicates an internalisation of alcohol as a social lubricant, which describes a pleasurable and gratifying time, while at the same time an acknowledgement that in Western cultures, and among males in Scotland, it is a mode of behaviour through which males gain respect for being able to hold one's drink. He also informs of the ill effects of excessive drinking:

"I think it was many years ago, like when I was 7 or 8 years old. My father used to be a very open person. My father is a very social person and he had a lot of friends. A lot of his friends liked to drink with him. So when I was young my father always used to ask me to try a little bit. I remember a time when I saw my father around the table and all the people used to show him a lot of respect, because this was a socialising process. So I found out that it is a good way to communicate, and increasingly I started trying a bit more as I was 10 and getting older. And that was my first feeling of alcohol, it is about socialisation, and meeting friends. But sometimes you can find it very hurtful if you drink too much" [Male, Chinese, 40-44; P 21].

An African female describes how the role of parental norms on drinking, and how this plays an indirect role in the development of new drinking norms as a BME living in Scotland. While alcohol use may not be a normal activity in her home country mediated and controlled via strict parental rebuke, drinking is an accepted activity in Scotland, and through her parents' drinking she learned to unlearn all she was told about alcohol in her African country. She explains:

"But with alcohol coz I mean you grow up and you've seen your own parents or your family members drinking, so its more like "I'm not gonna die, maybe I'll fall ill and fall into my bed", but I'm not gonna die, so it's more acceptable" [Female, African, 25-29; P 15].

Likewise a Pakistani participant notes that while the use of alcohol is not tolerated within his culture, family and religion, he now rejects these notions and is more accepting of Scottish norms with regards to drinking. He believes that assimilating with Scots has caused him to deviate from the norms of his country and that education has helped in enlightening his

preconceived notions of the use of alcohol. While maintaining self-control still remains important to the participant, his perceptions towards Scottish drinking norms are more tolerant:

"...My family they are very conservative, so they won't tolerate it. If I'm drinking they will not tolerate it, and from a very young age, they have been telling me "no smoking, no alcohol". This is the thing I've seen, if I had taken alcohol in Pakistan then I would be bad. But here I was fine, somehow I'm deviating from the teaching I had when I was there. I think it's because 5 years, working amongst native people and questioning many of the things. So education opens up your mind and now I have started questioning things. But it doesn't mean that my stance has changed, like alcohol I can't take it, anything which makes me have less self-control of me, I wouldn't do that..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 24].

The accounts of the Chinese, African and Pakistani participants reveal how their attitudes to drinking has been influenced by their parents, and by engaging in wider Scottish culture via processes of acculturation. Only in cultures where alcohol use is accepted do parents initiate drinking, for instance Chinese culture. The next section explores participants' initiation into alcohol through peers.

4.4.2 Initiation & Peer Groups

Alcohol use often is initiated by peers, particularly in cultures where there are few rules about how and when alcohol is to be introduced as a part of rite of passage from child to adult, and peers play a significant role in the initiation of alcohol often during high school or university. Below are a few illustrations from participants who were introduced to alcohol through their engagement with peers.

It is apparent from the Chinese participant's account that his peers have a direct influence in his initiation into drinking. The participant learned what was appropriate in a given social context, and what behaviours would lead to social acceptance. Furthermore, being a new student and attempting to develop new friendships with peers and adapting to the new school, made him accept offers of alcohol, despite disliking the taste. The sociability of his confederates during the drinking session emerges to be more appealing to the participant than the actual act of drinking:

"First experience I think it was in high school. And after the first year of high school I went to another school, so people there threw a party for me. So that's the first time. Actually I quite like the drinking experience, I don't like the alcohol. I don't think it is very delicious or tasty, but I like the environment, people talk and it is in a group, and it is very relaxing" [Male, Chinese, 25-29; P 30].

A female Pakistani participant points out that among her peers (predominantly White Scottish), initiation for them into drinking is at a much younger age, compared to her own initiation which started in her early 20s. Her attitudes to drinking have been influenced by her willingness to drink as well as a social retaliation of her delayed initiation into drinking, coupled with the need to give greater importance to the opinions of her intimate peers. She appears both proud of drinking later, but also ashamed that she was inexperienced about her tolerance to alcohol:

"When I started going out, and I didn't start going out till I was about 21/22, which is late for people around here. I was so drunk, back from the Garage (nightclub) with my friends. That was like one of the first times..." [Female, Pakistani, 25-29; P 8].

The accounts of the Chinese and Pakistani participants reveal how they were introduced to alcohol through their peers. Often during an individual's developmental period, they spend greater amount of time with their peers, and peer relationships become the primary social context influencing social development, where there is a greater susceptibility to peer influences. Initiation through peers is the Scottish norm, causes many problems, as peers do not have the experience or knowledge to transmit controlled and responsible drinking styles. Just like the influence of parents and peers, individuals are also influenced by colleagues, and initiation through colleagues is discussed in the next section.

4.4.3 Alcohol initiation & work colleagues

For some individuals, the workplace forms an important setting for engaging in drinking behaviour. At work individuals are separated from family and friends and from their peer groups. The need for peer acceptance from colleagues and even supervisory staff acts to present drinking alcohol as a required social norm. Alcohol enculturation can occur through peer pressure, and it is crucial to note that peer acceptance and "fitting in" are key factors in initiation of drinking, to feel included as part of a peer group with which they identify.

It is interesting that an Indian female in her late 60's protects her self-esteem, to avoid being judged, and reduce her experience of shame and stigma by suggesting that her initiation into the use of alcohol was by accident. Whereby she drank alcohol but was under the impression it was apple juice. She links the use of alcohol with having a social life, creating a line of demarcation between what happened in India, and what was part of recreation and enjoyment in Scotland:

"...Once we came here and started having a social life so to say, we were exposed to alcohol quite a lot. In the beginning, the first drink I ever took, I took without even knowing it was alcohol. Somebody said, I asked for a soft drink, and somebody gave me cider and said it was apple juice. And I thought it was apple juice and drank it like apple juice. And it's only later I realised that it was not just apple juice, made from apple but an alcoholic drink...So I can say in the beginning I did drink sherry or something else because I thought it was expected of me...When I have had a drink, I do enjoy having a nice glass of wine, but only as part of recreation or socialising." [Female, Indian, 65-69; P 11].

For participant 11 alcohol was used to fit in as she considered 'it expected of me'. Finally, that alcohol use has become a perceived normative behaviour, where wine is used for its pleasure which she enjoys, stating that there is a functional reason for using wine, which is for socialising and recreation. Furthermore, sensitivity to peer approval due to her need to feel that she belonged to a group may also have made her conform to the drinking norms of her peers. This could also be a means of preventing negative evaluation by her work colleagues.

In contrast, a young male Pakistani participant who already tried cannabis before experiencing alcohol, which he poured himself, as an active participant, taking full responsibility for his 'deviance'. He explains:

"That was in college and I was already smoking weed at that time, and a friend of mine was having some vodka. So I poured myself a drink and I had it. So I think the first time I had it, it was quite a mixed experience, because I was already under the influence of hash, so I didn't really realise the difference of the buzz..."

...So when I had my drink for the first time, and when I saw people, I think it was more when I started working. When I started working, I saw how my colleagues go around, they do have families, they socialise, and how they manage and how they drink. So you kind of tend to pick up everything, and then it's like drinking is not bad" [Male, Indian, 25-29; P 22].

Hence, the three anticipatory agents of initiation in Scottish drinking cultures were family, friends and co-workers. In an individual's early stages of development, parents have a strong influence on their attitudes and behaviours. As individuals get older, they tend to spend much less time with their family and more with their friends, as well as resisting the control that parents have on their selection and association with their friends. Thereby peers become increasingly important and this importance intensifies during high school or university, where peer networks become a source for support and intimacy. Furthermore, peers form the most prominent social figures in high school or university and a potent influence on drinking. As such, peers' attitudes and behaviours involving alcohol can be related to the participants' personal attitudes and behaviours. However,

peer approval and pressures to fit in persist after leaving school and university and at work.

The next section explores how participants perceived problem drinkers and drug users and describe how the use of alcohol is stigmatised and how such individuals are labelled as deviants.

4.5 Perceptions of Problem Use

Chapter 2 discussed how individuals who appear to supersede traditional social regulations of moderate and responsible use are considered to be deviant. Four categorisations of deviance that are subject to formal or informal negative sanctions have been derived and modified from work by (Roman, 2015), namely – positivistic perspectives, preventative perspectives, medical-disease perspectives, and public-health perspectives. This typology from Roman (2015) is used to analyse participant data as they describe from their perspectives how they view problematic alcohol and drugs users.

An Indian female in her late 40's considers alcohol as an agent that leads to a loss of control, and may lead to addiction, resulting in forgetting one's responsibilities and being a burden to society. Her views correspond to a preventative perspective of managing deviance, which suggests that drinking alcohol inevitably leads to damage and destruction for users, therefore serving to act to prevent the deviance occurring. Furthermore, failure to control alcohol intake would lead to failure in fulfilling expected

gender role responsibilities. Participant 6 describes how becoming addicted leads to the problem user neglecting their duties to society:

"Using alcohol I would say is, in moderation or in small quantities, I don't think it is harmful. But if a person gets addicted to this and he forgets his responsibilities, his only thought is about alcohol and alcohol and alcohol, so he becomes like a problem to the society, and then it really is a harmful thing" [Female, Indian, 45-49; P 6].

Participant 24, a male Pakistani in his late 20's states that education acts as a protective factor in preventing problems related to alcohol. However, he believes that residing in Scotland results in alcohol enculturation that can lead to problems. This is precipitated with his intense belief that persistent drinking would lead to disability or death, and that these risks are class-bound. As members in his family are highly educated, those from middle and upper classes have the wisdom to avoid temptation.

Problems are defined as a loss of control and craving, using the medical-disease concept of alcoholism to legitimise his views of alcohol not only as a disinhibitor, but as a factor in extreme behaviour change, for example extreme violence after intoxication:

"...And one of my cousins who used to drink, he had a heart attack, so it's never been perceived as a good thing. Like addiction or alcohol and drugs, especially in my family, we are all very educated. My mum she is a teacher, my dad he works as a professor, so we never had any use of it. And I was never used to it until I came here. Personally, I don't find it very good; it's the mother of every trouble. Like if you go to the town centre on a Saturday night, you can see what happens there, people go mad. Even your own true friends, when they drink too much they become a totally different person. So it transforms you, it increases your confidence to do anything, you can do anything. I've seen cases where people have stabbed each other, just because they were drunk. And I also work in an off-licence shop, and I've seen people craving for drink, because they are addicted, and because they wanted to drink, and forget their life experiences..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 24].

P24 experiences as a vendor of alcohol leads him to conclude that Scots who purchase alcohol crave it, resulting in an inability to fulfil social expectations and use alcohol to 'forget their life experiences'. The self-medication thesis and medical-disease model of addiction emerge to support his conclusions.

A male African participant, considers alcohol use in Scotland to be a problem, acting to drain Scotland's health budget, and leading to neglect of children and families, and violence. He views alcohol as an agent of social disruption, as it affects the well-being of the family:

"I think it is because I've seen people over here who are like, every time I see them they must be drinking, and they don't do anything, and they just have to be on it constantly. So yea there is a problem. Obviously when they are drinking they can't work or look after themselves. And people with families, they won't have that time to spend with their family, and also it is a big cost to the NHS, because these people are always ending up in A & E and stuff, and they are causing fights. It's got an impact not in all of the areas, but at least in most of them..." [Male, African, 30-34; P 19].

P19's opinions stem from a public-health perspective through which he explains that alcohol isn't just a risk factor for a wide range of health risks, but also the damage that is generated (e.g. violence, accidents etc.) due to its causal link with criminality.

An Indian male in his late 60s assigns a food value to alcohol, and views it as a positive ingredient that enriches social and cultural interactions:

"Alcohol is, you can say it can be a food; it can be just like anything else. If it rules you its harmful, but if it taken as part of entertainment or as part of your food and can be like anything else. When you limit it, it is not harmful, when it goes beyond the limit, then again you could say what is that limit? Which may be the lines in which you put yourself, or society puts you, or the nation puts you, or the police puts you, or the rules and law of the land puts you, whatever it is. It's their limits..." [Male, Indian, 65-69; P 9].

For P9, alcohol if used within limits, is not much of a problem, however he notes that defining such limits are fraught with difficulty.

An African participant suggests that in the Ghanaian community problematic alcohol use is frowned upon, as these individuals are considered to be unproductive members of society, who neglect their

children and families and are not good providers. As a result of their problematic use of alcohol, they are also unable to retain a job, and are transfixed with the need for alcohol. Problematic users are labelled “kohwesani” and considered to be ‘no good to society’:

“...it is perceived as a negative thing because everybody knows that, anyone who drinks usually they are more or less of no good to the society. We see them as not being to any good, for e.g. not necessarily focusing on jobs or their family, they are just focused on mostly drinking. The term they (Ghanaian community) have for them is "kohwesani" which means a person who is addicted to alcohol.” [Male, African, 25-29; P 27].

Accounts from the participants indicate how problematic use of alcohol is conceived as deviance and explain how such deviance is both described and attempted to be prevented. Also discussed were the four categorisations of deviance by Roman (2015). Apart from the different categorisations of alcohol users and the various perspectives used to define alcohol-related deviance, there are yet others who capture the constructions of problem users but at the same time integrate in with the expectations and social functions of society. The next section explores how certain aspects or categories such as – social capital, and socioeconomic status, can excuse individuals from stigma and labelling.

4.5.1 Functional Problem User

‘Functioning problem users’ adequately perform their normative assigned social roles, and as such the prevailing norms in relation to alcohol in their society are largely rejected, downplayed, or ignored. Such individuals

cannot be categorised within a medical paradigm, as they may not admit to having an illness, do not express the need for treatment, and do not consider themselves ill or suffering from a disease. Fundamental to this construction is the social capital possessed or habitus of the individual.

A participant describes her experience with functional problem users during her career as a young doctor. She explains how her superiors would present at work needing a 'fix' before starting work. Her superiors were never questioned by fellows in the same position or even those of a higher position, as they successfully managed and fulfilled their expected roles and functions, and also because it wasn't considered 'socially right':

"...I have come across people at work who were, when I was a young doctor, those days even in the medical field there were other doctors, senior doctors who would come into work and they need a fix. Sometimes it's a drug, sometimes it's a drink before they can even start working. And these people are working as anesthetists, surgeons, and nobody questioned them. You wouldn't even dare tell a friend who is drinking too much, "yes, I think you've had too much, I think you should stop" or anything. Because that's not considered to be socially right. But that's what I should say, but I don't think I would. And it's all swept under the carpet..." [Female, Indian, 65-69; P 11].

4.5.2 Social Capital & Deviant Drinking

As mentioned above, an individual's measure and types of social capital or habitus are crucial factors in determining how they are perceived, and in defining what is and is not accepted or defined as deviance. Their capital could include the possession of resources and power described by participant 11.

For instance, Participant 18, an Indian female in her early 30s states that drinking alcohol in India signalled class or status, indicating the influential impact of socioeconomic status as well as conspicuous consumption and an identity. Here distinguished identity refers to those individuals who possess social capital which rewards them and those around them with an advantage of social status. Their expendable capital signals future rewards for those around them, which they would not want to risk losing. Here deviant drinkers are intentionally declared normal:

"...They have got some kind of status in society, like "I smoke, I drink...I drink this particular brand or whisky", so they think it to be part of their social status, because if they are going for a very costly drink, which means it reflects his financial status. I think that if they go for something cheap, like a cheap wine or something it automatically reflects that person's financial status or social status. If they go for highly expensive whisky or that kind of drink, it's part of getting a good image in society, I think..." [Female, Indian, 30-34; P 18].

4.5.3 Stigma and Discrimination

A male Chinese participant explains how the family would 'lose-face' or be shamed if someone were to be negatively stereotyped as an alcoholic. This then leads to exclusion in the community, and as such controlled drinking is replicated in cultural practices:

"...The family would control and pressure them to try and stop these kinds of things. Because in China people would call this lose-face. It's not nice things to expose, you would ruin the reputation of the family. So probably the one thing that we Chinese people try to avoid is the word "alcoholic". Because this is a kind of word which isn't a nice word, and makes people uncomfortable. And if people are dubbed as alcoholic, then people don't want to talk to you, or drink with you, because sometimes you can have a bad influence from the alcoholic person. We call alcoholic those people that basically drink a little bit, and their behaviour is totally changes, like they are mad and crazy. So that's the reasons we try to avoid these people, or the name because you don't want to be named as an alcoholic because of the kind of things you can imagine associated with it. Things like break the windows, or tables or door, and smash things. They are trouble makers..." [Male, Chinese, 40-44; P 21].

Similarly, an Indian participant explains how traditions act both as a structure and constraining factor via stigmatising the problem drinker and labelling the family negatively:

"So it's always been a scare whether they keep you out of the society, because Indians are always worried about this "big society", the unknown disfigured, un-figured society. It's mainly the fear that your family will be categorised into it. If you are an alcoholic, they might think "oh his dad should be like that, or his brother should be like that", so you don't want to put your family into that kind of situation." [Male, Indian, 30-34; P 1].

Furthermore, a female Pakistani participant justifies living a 'double life' as a means of managing the multiple and sometimes contradictory effects of cultural expectations and family roles in negotiating her Scottish identity and her drinking and socialising behaviours. As a means to avoid shaming the family, she has adopted innovative means of combining aspects of Scottish and Pakistani culture, for instance separating her activities to

'specific groups', one group that strictly includes family and distant relatives, and the other exclusively with her Scottish friends and peers:

"...I obviously live a double life because I keep everything - partying, drinking, and smoking, to one side, like with a specific group of friends. And family things to another side, where I don't do any of that stuff. Because, well firstly, you just couldn't talk about it. Ermm...but you wouldn't be able to talk to your family or my cousins or anything like that. I wouldn't be able to do that. It's just, I don't really know how to explain it. It's just like, if you do, it'll just probably like a bomb would explode, you know. Everything will just explode, and it'll just like "I don't know you", and you'll just be kicked out of the family or something. I just don't want to find out. It'll shame them (the family)..." [Female, Pakistani, 25-29; P 8].

Identification of an individual as being an alcohol user, has the potential to damage the respectability of the family, often resulting in hidden use.

A male Pakistani participant describes how the use of alcohol within his community is highly stigmatised, as the family with a known drinker is shamed and shunned in the community:

"They would probably automatically connect moral corruption with alcohol, and they would be like "no they've probably gone far away from the religion, so if they drink they probably do other things too". They automatically assume the worst if they find out that somebody drinks. They would be like "if this is how they were raised, and they are fine with it, then god knows what happens behind closed doors" and what not. They would probably shame the entire family, even if it's just one person who does it and the rest of the family doesn't even know..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 23].

It is evident here that in certain cultures, individuals who consume alcohol or who are ascribed as having a spoiled identity of an alcoholic, are

alienated as they fail to maintain the identity norm of that community or group.

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter presented the participants' narratives on their personal attitudes to alcohol use which have been influenced by fixed attitudes towards alcohol in their native culture, which were further mediated by processes of acculturation. The Participants' drinking was explained using three crude classifications by Pitman (1965) – abstinent, ambivalent and permissive drinking cultures. This allowed the participants to be classified into three groups: Permissive groups (Indian and Chinese participants), Ambivalent groups (African participants), and Ascetic groups (Pakistani participants). Participants' accounts of drinking in this chapter indicate that while the consumption of alcohol is not always or easily integrated into social customs or religious rites within their groups, integration and assimilating with Scottish culture helped in normalising or accommodating the use of alcohol.

The bi-dimensional model of acculturation by Landrine and Klonoff (2004), was used to illuminate the participants' experiences of acculturating to Scottish drinking norms. Furthermore, the concept of 'alcohol enculturation' was effective in describing the process of how participants integrated Scottish cultural norms and values while simultaneously maintaining the values and behaviours of their original culture.

The three anticipatory agents of socialisation – family, friends and co-workers were discussed. Perceptions of parent's attitudes towards drinking plays a significant role in how drinking norms are transmitted and challenge or support the drinking norms of the Pakistani and African participants. Several Indian and Pakistani participant's noted that their initiation into alcohol was through peers. It was also reported that peer acceptance and blending-in were crucial factors in drinking among colleagues. Additionally, participants described 'what it means to be a drinker', as nonconformity and immoderate use of alcohol led to being considered deviant.

Four perspectives - positivistic perspectives, preventative perspectives, medical-disease perspectives, and public-health were discussed in relation to alcohol-related deviance. Furthermore, participants when asked about describing problem users, also cited instances where functioning problem users used the influence of socioeconomic status and power to overcome the controls that would and are exerted on others from lower social-economic circumstances.

Finally, in the participants' accounts to assimilate with Scottish culture, an element of inverse racism was also evident. A reflection of their perceptions and the perceptions of those within their community signify that they distinguish their own culture as morally superior which is explained by exerting controls over deviance through authoritative parenting and community monitoring of their young. They argue that Scottish culture is somewhat permissive, and this encourages greater acceptance and use of

alcohol and drugs, consequently constructing Scots as inferior. This inference of inferiority has led some of these participants to develop negative attitudes and beliefs and prejudice towards Scots and constructing them as racial outsiders. This inverse racism acts as a form of cultural validation and/or a coping mechanism to manage their minority status in wider Scottish culture.

The next chapter explores the narratives of drug using participants and how they negotiated their identity within the context of their own culture and Scotland.

5 Perceptions of Drug Use

5.1 Introduction

Drugs have been an integral part of human culture since the beginning of recorded history, with intoxicants being received with celebration and enthusiasm, trepidation and abhorrence. The use of substances which alter perception are sites of conflict between individuals and power structures. Religious institutions have typically regarded intoxication using plants and drugs derived from them as paths to enlightenment and salvation, or to death and destruction. The use of drugs is rarely considered safe, and those who use them are commonly described as weak willed, immoral and criminal.

This chapter presents the perceptions of 13 participants who are illicit drug users, as well as the perceptions of three participants who consumed tobacco. Fourteen of the participants were non-users.

Participants described how they managed several identities within their family and community and examines how the use of drugs is understood within their communities while living in Scotland. The terms inebriation and intoxication are used interchangeably in this chapter and refer to the use of drugs that cause some psychoactive effects, but not necessarily with impairments to normal healthy functioning. This chapter purposely examines the drugs used by the participants, as alcohol use has been addressed in Chapter 4. The position of drugs as a health, legal and moral

issue is also discussed, and is counterbalanced by a debate regarding normalisation or acceptance of drug use in Scots society.

5.1.1 Public Health Attitudes towards Illicit Drug Use

Many individuals consider the consumption of drugs as morally wrong, based on philosophical, spiritual or religious beliefs. On the other hand, many others see the use of drugs as a matter of individual choice.

It is interesting that a female Indian participant (participant 18) when asked about the dangers of drugs, describes tobacco as a dangerous addictive drug, which is a reflection of current prevailing public health messages that condemn smoking of tobacco. While dependence or habitual use of any drugs is rarely considered 'good', often the negative harmful use of drugs including the use of tobacco converge. The Indian female states that:

"I think it's definitely harmful, because every single packet of cigarette it says that it's injurious to health, so there is no way that it is giving any kind of good effect in your health. Even for the smoking, they are inhaling the nicotine, that's really giving the bad thing on their health system, especially the nicotine. And like in drugs like dopamine, that's another kind of serious stimulator for the brain, and gradually this nicotine and everything will affect the blood stream, so that definitely is injurious to health. It doesn't give any kind of benefit in your health. Rather than killing your health." [Female, Indian, 30-34; P 18].

In addition, public health messages proscribing the illicit use of any drugs without medical reasons were discussed by an Indian participant who stresses that drugs describe any substance for which there are no

legitimate medical reasons for taking them. Furthermore, the recreational use of drugs is described as a disease characterised by a loss of self-control. A male Indian participant shares this view and suggests that any use without medical reasons can cause harm and 'disease':

"Drugs, ermm...you can say there are different types of drugs which can affect differently in different people. Like some people call it recreational drugs, some people call it sedative drugs or whatever it is. It depends on which particular drug and what affect it can have on the people using it. Drugs are normally...it's a prescription only medicine, you normally get the drugs when it is prescribed for you for certain purposes, like medical purposes. Without any reason if you are taking the drug, it is a disease. Like there is a difference between alcohol and drugs. But I cannot positively say any good effect for a drug in a normal person. They are useful in people who require it in medicinal purposes." [Male, Indian, 65-69; P 9].

A Chinese participant reveals that the use of drugs is regarded disapprovingly and is deeply rooted in Chinese culture. Use of any drug is considered 'harmful' and as such greater emphasis is given to prevention as a mantra to protect people's health:

"Chinese people or in Chinese culture, there is very old saying for Chinese in Chinese history "whatever kind of drug, any drug is harmful". That's a very old saying, probably as old as 2000-3000 years old. It's any drugs, even if the drug is very useful for you for cure, you take it, but it is harmful." [Male, Chinese, 40-44; P 21].

It is evident that self-control is an important aspect of what is considered normal. As a result, medical and legal factors are used to describe the use of drugs as a moral issue. The next section explores how illicit drug users and considered to be a moral problem.

5.1.2 Illicit Drugs as a Moral Problem

How drugs are regulated will depend upon what problems their use are considered to contribute to. For example, if drugs cause ill health, the legitimately, medicine must regulate and control access. If however the habitual use of some drugs lead inevitably to criminality, then legal proscriptions, and the threat of incarceration are necessary to minimise problems and regulate behaviour. These discourses, constructing problem use, or even any use as medical and or legal issues were used to describe drug users as suffering from a moral failure, using terms that were more demonising than those ascribed to alcohol users.

For instance, an Indian participant suggests that drug users are legitimately considered violent and the cause of many problems in society:

"Normally the drug users are quite violent. It is the fear that the drug user could turn violent and probably make some unwanted issues" [Male, Indian, 30-34; P 1].

A male participant of mixed ethnicity (British Indian), explains how merely talking about drugs in her social circle and family is a taboo, particularly when individuals are often closely monitored by other people in his community and often judged. This social monitoring is less prevalent when mingling with Scottish peers. The participant expresses "feeling that bit free" when leaving the home, as this reduces pressure from the family:

"In a general consensus then, even speaking about is going to get them scared in the back of their head. So there are a lot of things that are taboo, that you don't say and that you don't do. And that's probably some of the driving force for going outside of the home and feeling that bit free, where you are not watched and judged..." [Male, Mixed (British Indian, 40-44; P 26].

P26 notes that despite drugs being described in moral tones, and demonising of users, he risks losing status by using them, and despite these threats and real sanctions he still takes this risk. Demand for intoxicants persists in the face of repression, for instance a Chinese participant explains that publicly drugs, gambling and prostitution are proscribed in Chinese culture, while being heavily integrated in everyday 'private' life:

"...My mother from my childhood told me that there are three things that you should never do. One of drugs, one is gambling and one is going to prostitutes or buy sex. These three things are not allowed in China, but actually it's quite normal in China..." [Male, Chinese, 25-29; P 30].

He further states that there is a greater adherence to the conventional myth that all drugs are highly addictive, to the extent where even a single use of a drug could lead to loss of control. Drug users are stigmatised and labelled 'yin juanzi' describing users as lacking self-control, condemning habitual inebriation as unacceptable. These assumptions depict an implicit conventional model of moral judgement about the impropriety of intoxication:

"...Drugs, maybe drugs are far away from our lives, because nobody wants to become an addict. "yin juanzi", in Chinese it has different meaning, like "yin" means hiding or cannot be seen. Another meaning of that is that you cannot leave that. Like many people when they touch drugs, they lose themselves, like you take it once and you want it take it again" [Male, Chinese, 25-29; P 30].

Of particular interest is how the use of drugs, engaging in using prostitutes and gambling were heavily stigmatised, and yet completely normal, albeit hidden in the culture described by participant 30.

However, it is not only drugs controlled within international law that are frowned upon, even the use of tobacco in some cultures is heavily stigmatised. P17 an African male participant stated that smoking is highly frowned upon in his culture, as it is perceived to be a gateway to other drugs:

"...I think that views when they see you smoke is that, obviously they would think you take cannabis, Indian hemp and so and so forth. I think they think it's a gateway to taking other drugs" [Male, African, 40-44; P 17].

Participant 17, an African participant states that smoking cigarettes is not a common feature within his culture, but smoking cannabis or weed in certain instances is acceptable in Nigeria as well as in Scotland. This is largely due to the perception that 'weed is natural', while cigarette smoking is considered more synthetic:

"They tend to take a lot of weed, well not to a lot, but they tend to smoke weed socially. So you could be at a party, and a group of Nigerians would say let's go get some weed to make the party more lively and things like that. In terms of cigarettes, not a lot of them smoke cigarettes. The majority of them would tell you if you asked that they don't smoke cigarettes but weed. They think it's worse to smoke cigarettes than actually weed, because it's manmade and it has a lot of chemicals in there, whereas weed is more natural, it's okay..." [Male, African, 18-24; P 28].

The world of the problem user has its own set of alternative social rules and values. It is significant to note that the participants do not consider the use of some drugs as a weakness or a failure, but as an integral part of their lives and a wider set of social values. The next section explores the role of the family in sanctioning the use of drugs.

5.1.3 Familial Sanctions

The two participants who did not consume any drugs (P14 and P29), drug use was condoned in the family and considered to be a 'death route'. As such, non-users' identification with their cultural norms is described as functioning to preserve and maintain self-control, and they categorically self-label themselves as 'non-users' to help prevent them being labelled negatively and thus spoil their identity as 'good'. As indicated by a male Indian participant below:

"To be honest, I come from an Indian background, so drugs, drug use are really out of the question in our community. So drug-wise I don't think people uses any drug in our community because in my background, drug use is really... it's not the question at all. You shouldn't use it, it's banned. So I pretty much don't know any drugs at all. So my parents were brought up like that, and I was brought up like that too. And the community is also brought up like that. So basically drugs is out of the question, we don't use it at all" [Male, Indian, 18-24; P 12].

Families sanction the use of drugs by recounting public health claims of the dangers of drug use. Hence moral condemnation and describing the laxity on the part of the user acts as mutually reinforcing factors to abstain from the use of certain drugs. Participant 14, a Chinese female learned that drugs were to be associated with death:

"I don't take drugs at all, because I was brought up in a family who like taught me that drugs are like a "no no". It was like a death route, you can't go there..." [Female, Chinese, 18-24; P 14].

The notion of bringing shame and disgrace to the family appears to be a strong deterrent for drug use described by an African male, participant 17:

"...And a lot of words have been put into your head before "that remember whose child you are". Those words continue to ring in your head, that you can afford to go to Scotland or to UK, and to go and misbehave, so you are always in check, and you don't want to disgrace your family members. So it has a lot of influence on you and whether you join a company that takes drugs..." [Male, African, 40-44; P 17].

A Pakistani male, participant 24 states that pressure from family, religion and culture serves as restraining factors against drug use. Some techniques

used by the family include that of linking the use of drugs with addiction. He clarifies the importance of parental restrictions on socialising with peers and links his brothers' addiction to cigarettes, and past use of hashish as a factor that led to his brother being scapegoated and tarnishing the reputation of his family:

"...There is much pressure from culture as well, religion as well, and your personal family as well. No one's parents would like to see their kids taking drugs, so that's why parents always try to protect their kids. They always tell them "no drugs" and even if someone offers it you for free, like cigarettes or anything "don't take it" because eventually it would become an addiction. Like my older brother he had the same thing, because when he passed his school and some of his older friends, they started giving him free cigarettes. Then they started giving him maybe a little bit of hash, so now he doesn't take drugs, but he is chain smoker. He is the only person in our family that smokes. Just because he was introduced to it. Drugs it becomes an addiction, and suddenly it ruins your life..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 24].

It is evident from the accounts of these participants that socio-cultural factors have an effect in the manner in which different cultures understand the use of drugs, and the risk associated with socialising with those who do. Here the individuals' background, personality and beliefs serve to increase or decrease their interest in using particular drugs. Hence the participants' understanding of the social world around them reflects their perception of drugs as a route to 'ruin'. These beliefs influence what is and is not defined as a drug, and their subjective experiences and accommodation of using certain substances. The next section discusses the normalisation of illicit drugs.

5.2 Learning to use drugs

This section explores participant accounts of how they learned to use some types of drugs.

A male participant of mixed ethnicity (Irish-Egyptian), states that his moderate use of controlled drugs is enjoyable and describes few negative consequences. The participant discovered his desirable patterns of use and level of sought-after intoxication through trial and error and experimentation from an early age. What is evident is a sophisticated cost-benefit analysis regarding the participant's drug taking, and a transition from an amateur drug using pattern into a more nuanced and culturally informed drug taking career, where drug use is, in his opinion neither criminal nor deviant. He emphasises the importance of moderate use and discourages use that breaches his learned set of rules and boundaries 'getting totally fucked outta your mind'. He also argues that the use of cannabis is more pleasurable without the use of tobacco, as tobacco has a tendency to 'smoke you, as you don't smoke it':

"Like you can be slightly like unmoderated at times and get away with it. But in general if you're moderate you can enjoy it more. Less is more ah find and I've learned that the hard way. Coz when ah was younger ah used to go to festivals and take a lot of recreational drugs - speed, ecstasy, acid, cocaine, all that shit, and ah used to take a lot. Well not a lot, but more than ah do now, and like ah would not remember a lot of it. That doesn't make sense to me, so quite early on in mah early twenties ah learned that getting totally fucked outta your mind is just not the way. But getting a little bit fucked, that can work. Yea you can enjoy it every now and again. I'd recommend ecstasy and MDMA to all, cannabis as well, but not with tobacco. Coz then it (tobacco) chooses you, it smokes you, you don't smoke it any

more, it smokes you..." [Male, Mixed (Irish-Egyptian), 35-39; P 13].

While some participants highlighted the ill effects of drugs, there are others who explain the use of drugs as a social behaviour, where use serves the purpose of demarcating the boundaries of inclusion and exclusion in a social group. For instance, a Chinese participant states that drug use is not a common occurrence among her friends in Taiwan, yet having spent time in Scotland and enculturation, using drugs has now become a factor of her identification with what she considered to be Scottish norms. Here disengagement with her traditions and ways of life loosens the bonds which previously anchored her to her community and is an indication of accepting Scottish cultural norms:

"...But because in my group of friends in Taiwan, I'm not aware of anyone doing drugs other than me, because it's very secretive in Taiwan. And because I have spent most of my time in western countries where this is very common. I think drugs it is harmful, but it also depends on how you use it. Like weed it is also harmful, but if for instance you take it once in a while, once a month of rarely with friends, like I don't really see it as doing any real harm to me, if I were doing that..." [Female, Chinese, 30-34; P 29].

A male Pakistani participant describes his positive experience of using cannabis as increasing his concentration and focus with music, whilst intensifying his levels of enjoyment:

"Initially I didn't realise that I was buzzed out, till I realise that all my senses were heightened. I could hear a lot; I think one of senses that I noticed was that my sense of hearing had become really clear. I could distinguish different sounds. And that's probably one of the things I quite like about doing drugs, because at least with hash or weed, I feel I can concentrate better. If I want to concentrate on something better, like if I wanted to listen to a song, I can concentrate specifically on the drum beats that are going on, and I can mute everything else around that, and just listen to the drum beats alone. Or if I'm just listening to outside nature, I can just distinguish the sound of a bird from everything else. And I can concentrate on that, so I feel like my sense of sound gets heightened..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 23].

Similarly, a female Pakistani participant who considers herself a 'rebel' explains how the use of cannabis helps her relax by giving her a sense of happiness:

"...I'm just a rebel. I don't like the idea of getting too high, I still like to be conscious and know what's going on and everything. So just a wee buzz and a just a wee happiness and relaxing, but not anything other than that..." [Female, Pakistani, 25-29; P 8].

Likewise, a male Indian participant describes using cocaine to enhance his sensory experience, pleasure and social interaction. He also states that he likes to experiment with new drugs to alter his mood. He positions his experience while on holiday and preserves his identity by referring to cocaine as an unknown drug that was 'sniffed'. He reasserts that while he did not feel intoxicated or experience a sensation of being 'high', in retrospect, traits such as being 'bold vocally' and 'daring' indicated pleasurable intoxication:

"...I was on holiday and I just tried it once. It was something white that I just sniffed through my nose. I don't what it was, was it opium or Ghanja or whatever I don't know. When I had that drug, I wouldn't say I was high, but at the moment you feel like it's not making any difference. But this was when I was on holiday and I wanted to go high, I wanted to enjoy and I had a couple of doses of the drug. But I was also drinking alcohol as well, but that doesn't make any difference. And it felt like cigarettes make a better difference. But after a while that you start enjoying, you talk, and yeah you do become more bold, in the sense vocally, your tone changes and you are loud and you can be more daring. But at the time I felt like it wasn't working. But the next day I woke up I felt like okay, no, that was good. Its then that you comprehend that actually I was high, but at that moment you don't feel it, or like you are high. You would just feel like you were being normal. But that was my choice, I wanted to try, and I tried it. I would like to try probably drugs whenever I come cross it. When I'm in the mood I'm like "I'm gonna try something new..."[Male, Indian, 25-29; P 22].

The reasons and motivations for drug use are diverse, as drugs are neither used for a unique reason nor are, they typical used for pathological reasons. While the use of controlled drugs was rarely reported by BME participants, with the exception of cannabis, a few Indian and Pakistani participants in this research also reported the use of traditional recreational drugs such as Paan¹⁰. Chewing paan was completely confined to Indian and Pakistani participants and is reported to be a culturally integrated activity. It is also not seen as a problematic form of drug use among the participants. Both male and female participants reported the use of paan, and all participants reported use of paan when they lived in India or Pakistan or consumption

¹⁰ Paan is a preparation combining betel leaf with areca nut and widely consumed throughout Southeast Asia, East Asia (mainly Taiwan), and the Indian subcontinent. It is chewed for its stimulant and psychoactive effects.

of it during short visits. Participants reported the use of paan primarily in social settings. For instance, an Indian female participant states that paan is widely available to purchase in shops under various brands in India. She also discloses pleasurable use of paan during social gatherings and with family members:

"...Most people when they socialise, I've seen people drinking and also having something like paan, it's like a betel leaf and something like areca nut they make like a mixture. I've seen in some of the shops, something like they sell things just like in different names, different brand names, but they are all like extracts of this areca nut or betel. I used to enjoy having people in the house, when there was a function, people used to eat paan and paan parag and betel leaves and things, I used to enjoy with them and it was nice for a change..." [Female, Indian, 45-49; P 6].

Similarly, a male Indian participant justifies the use of paan as an activity that served to maintain his Indian identity and 'fitting in' with traditional norms to enhance the social bond with his family. He explains that, his family feels alienated because he is 'physically distanced' having settled in Scotland. Hence, he discloses that as a means to reassure them, he consumes paan despite disliking it. He also states that paan is widely available in Asian stores in Glasgow (Albert Drive), and is consumed by his friends:

"Once a year even I try betel nut. Once a year when I go, when all my relatives are there, my grand dads or uncles would roll it up and just hand it to you, saying it won't harm you. I don't have a liking towards it or anything; I think I just belong to them at that point of time. I think for them, me being away and kind of physically distanced, probably makes them feel a bit sad. So I would probably want to fit in, at that particular point, even though I don't like it. The Asian shops, they've got paan vendors in Albert Drive. I've seen my friends go there" [Male, Indian, 35-39; P 20].

Pakistani participants expressed that there are two types of paan, one which is plain and widely consumed by everyone and another which has tobacco and other drugs mixed with it, also known as 'gutkha'. While Indian participants did not report the use of paan as having any association with socio-economic status, a Pakistani male participant stated that he considered the use of gutkha primarily among those 'in lower socio-economic classes'. He argued that his personal use of paan was limited, and he did not consume gutkha, as it has a higher association and is a more common practice by individuals from disadvantaged segments of society in Pakistan. Hence, consuming gutkha would obtrude with his social standing. It is evident that the participant makes an active choice to consume only certain drugs which would not infringe upon his higher social standing in his society:

"...Well paan is of two kinds, there is one without any sort of drugs, and paan is easily available in shops and stuff, because it is legal to sell it. And generally paan is consumed in family gatherings, after meals and all, which contains sweets and nuts and betel and something else. But there's no tobacco in paan generally. But obviously there are paans available, which have a higher content of intoxicants, but they are not widely available. And I've never consumed any paan of that sort. Because again, I think these gutkha, paan, bidi, and all are locally sourced, and then they are widely used in lower socio-economic classes than the upper ones..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 23].

Hence, it is evident that within contemporary Scottish culture, the pervasiveness of illicit drugs has resulted in a normalisation of use among some BME participants and with it a greater awareness of the types and kinds of recreational drugs consumed. This has also caused individuals to assess, re-evaluate, reconfirm and renegotiate their identity as BME individuals. Furthermore, the recreational use of illicit drugs is not perceived as leading an individual into a deviant subculture, rather it is adopted as an essential factor of everyday life, similar to other facets of life as shopping or drinking. That said, the use of certain drugs remains a taboo, and an illicit activity for BME participants for reasons already discussed. Participants' accounts reveal that drug use surpasses gender, class and race in the manner in which it occurs, and the type of drugs consumed, and as such is inconsistent across different social groups.

5.3 Conclusion

This chapter explored how participants perceived the use of certain drugs as harmful, and considered the explanations for this, while revealing the varied ways in which drugs were considered as being harmful. The drugs used by participants in this research included Tobacco (including 'Bidi'¹¹ and 'Gutkha'¹²), Cannabis (alternatively named by participants as Marijuana, Grass, Weed, Indian hemp, Ganja, Hashish and Bhang) and 'Paan'¹³.

Some participants argued that their perceptions about some drugs were reinforced by their family and culture, while others suggested that by avoiding certain drugs, loss of control and spoiling of one's identity by maintaining the semblance of being 'good' could be preserved. Yet there were those who emphasised that the illicit use of some drugs allowed them to heighten their senses and improve performance or feel more relaxed.

It is discernible from the participants' accounts that the use of some drugs is culturally accepted among BMEs in contemporary Scottish society, while others and those who use them are demonised and scapegoated. For

¹¹ Bidi is a small hand-rolled cigarette consisting of tobacco and wrapped in Tendu or Temburni leaf, which is a plant native to Asia *Diospyros melanoxylon*. Bidi contains three to five times higher concentrations of nicotine than traditional cigarettes. (Source: <https://www.verywell.com/are-bidi-cigarettes-safe-to-smoke-2825285>).

¹² Gutkha is powdery and granular in nature, and is light brown or white in colour. Gutkha when prepared contains crushed betel nut, tobacco and sweet or savory flavorings. It imparts its users a more intense buzz than that of tobacco (Source: <http://www.tobacco-facts.net/tobacco-products/gutka>).

¹³ Paan is a mix of areca nut, an acacia extract and inorganic lime, which is wrapped in betel leaves and tobacco. Ingestion usually involves chewing or smoking, and is traditionally used in many South Asian countries WARNAKULASURIYA, S. 2002. Areca nut use following migration and its consequences. *Addiction Biology*, 7, 127-132, GUPTA, P. & RAY, C. 2004. Epidemiology of betel quid usage. *Annals-Academy of Medicine Singapore*, 33, 31-36.

instance, the use of cannabis in Nigeria was considered, at least in part, normal and natural, while tobacco is unnatural when smoked. In Indian and Pakistani cultures, participants reported hidden use of tobacco products in a form that is eaten (Paan and Gutkha). Similarly, while drug use, gambling and prostitution are publicly condemned in Chinese culture, it is commonplace in private.

Some African participants indicated that tobacco was considered to be a gateway drug to use of cannabis, heroin and cocaine. Such views stem from the cultural perspectives that stigmatise smoking and could be perceived as a means to reject tobacco marketing strategies. The gateway theory or gateway hypothesis (Cohen, 1972; Kandel, 2002; O'Donnell, 1979) maintains that early experimentation with alcohol or tobacco or cannabis can lead to more addictive drug use, and hence act as a "gateway" to the use of other more addictive drugs. There is insufficient and often mixed results about the link between one drug and another (Korhonen et al., 2010; Mayet et al., 2012). The gateway hypothesis is based on the assumption that experimentation with cannabis for example leads to the problematic use of drugs such as crack cocaine and heroin. However, the direction of causality is unclear and this prompts great academic debate. Increasingly research from a public health perspective has served to indicate that alcohol and tobacco, the drugs reported used most often by adolescents may act as a gateway for further deviance. However, the debate and causality is far from clear.

While there are studies that indicate that cannabis is not a gateway drug (Drug Policy Alliance, 2017; Kleinig, 2015; Morral et al., 2002), there are also studies which indicate that alcohol can act as a gateway to the use of tobacco, cannabis and other illicit substances and lead to problematic use (Kirby and Barry, 2012; Barry et al., 2016). Additional risk factors for adult problematic use include parental circumstances, being in care, lower education attainment, involvement with criminal justice system etc. Indeed, new evidence suggests that cannabis can even help individuals to reduce or eliminate their use of more harmful drugs or alcohol by easing the withdrawal symptoms from opiate type drugs (Drug Policy Alliance, 2017). However, the evidence that tobacco is a gateway drug per se is not substantiated.

Furthermore, some African participants' accounts reveal that tobacco use is proscribed due to its association with crime, ill health and deviance. Attitudes to drugs are shaped by legal and health discourses and underpinned by familial sanctions which would spoil the identities of BME participants, if they used disapproved, or non-medically sanctioned drugs. The participants revealed their use of legal, illegal, illicit and licit drugs or categorised themselves as controlled risk aware users or recreational users. As a result, problematic drug use was not discussed, however the term addict was often used by non-users to describe those drug users with whom the participants did not identify with.

Such is the power of medicine and criminal justice discourses, coupled with religious dogma, that drugs users are rarely considered normal. Therefore, the use of certain drugs, particularly controlled drugs, is often something that is hidden, and if use is revealed, past or current, identities can be spoiled. In conjunction with family sanctions, several participants in this thesis link the use of drugs with that of the disease concept of addiction, underpinned by fears of infection or certain drugs being 'injurious to health' thereby resulting in a loss of control.

Participants indicate that choices for inebriation are more about their social and personal identity than unchallenged cultural norms. Drug practices are not uniform in any society, and repression can also lead to the use of drugs as an expression of rebellion. For instance, several Muslim participants reported the use of drugs despite prohibition in their religion.

The next chapter considers religious sanctions and how this shape the use or avoidance of alcohol and drugs among BME individuals.

6 Religion

6.1 Introduction

This chapter examines the influence of religiosity and the participants' beliefs and attitudes concerning the use of AOD in the context of their religion. Specifically, within the perspectives of four religions: a Christian perspective; an Islamic perspective; Perspectives in Hinduism; and Buddhist perspectives, as each have particular relevance in this thesis. The rules set out in the four religious texts will be discussed, and how these views inform, and influence participants' use of AOD. Christian perspectives provide a background for understanding the prohibition and temperance movement. Islamic perspectives have a strict emphasis on abstention, while Hinduism has no strict rules in relation to alcohol use, and Buddhist doctrine emphasises abstinence.

The entheogenic theory in relation to drugs and alcohol is used in this chapter to explore participants' adjuncts to religious experiences in Christianity, Hinduism, Islam and Buddhism, as it legitimises the use of drugs which would otherwise be condemned as indulgent. Furthermore, to understand the importance of religion among participants, this chapter uses two of Gunn's (2003) Facets of Religion adapted to explore and explain AOD use.

6.2 Religions & Psychoactive Sacraments

This section explores participants' use of AOD from the perspective of four religions: Christianity, Hinduism, Islam and Buddhism.

6.2.1 Christianity

A female African participant expresses a rather confused understanding of the role of alcohol in Christianity, since there are numerous verses about the use of alcohol in the Bible, but few that could be inferred to suggest a demand for abstinence. She also states that the alcohol that is mentioned in the bible is 'pure alcohol' which is unadulterated and much stronger than what is available at present. However, she argues that some sects in Christianity prohibit the use of alcohol without any reasoning. She indicates that the function of religion in indicating preferences for abstinence are about the exercise of power, rather than for an understandable reason:

"I mean in the bible it says drink, but it's nowhere in the bible that it says don't drink alcohol. And probably they used to drink even more than we do too as it was pure alcohol. So yea, there is nothing that says do not drink, but there are some churches, who in their doctrine say don't drink or use alcohol. They don't really give you a reason, they just say don't. Don't do it!" [Female, African, Christian, 25-29; P 15].

Another African participant distinguishes between sects within Christianity the Pentecostal and Catholics, based on his experience of converting from Catholicism to Pentecostalism. He explains that in Pentecostalism alcohol use is prohibited and smoking of tobacco is condemned; while in Catholicism the use of alcohol is 'no big deal' inferring liberal views on

drinking. He believes that drinking was more prevalent during his parents' generation as they are Catholics. He has observed that lately there has been a rise in Pentecostalism in the community where he was raised. And younger African people who consider themselves religious avoid alcohol as a testament to their faith:

"...But the Christians, with the Pentecostal, smoking and drinking is zero. Still within Christianity, the Catholics, if you drink, no big deal. It's probably not emphasised not to smoke, but it's not been frowned if you drink, but not in excess. And if you are a Catholic and took a couple of pints, it would be okay. Because if you compare my generation with my parents' generation, I would say my parents' generation drank more. But in the Pentecostal as a Christian it's not. Because we now have more Pentecostal churches. But even if some churches objected to Pentecostal, these communities grew, as a result younger people are now Pentecostal and they do not drink now..." [Male, African, Christian, 40-44; P 17].

The two African participants portray the influence of Christianity in their life, and their decisions to consume alcohol. It demonstrates how their social world, the world constructed by religious sanctions, and the community they live in influence their decisions and those within their community of the use of alcohol. However, avoidance of alcohol is a used to indicate religious conviction. The next section considers the use of AOD in Hinduism.

6.2.2 Hinduism

The use of alcohol and drugs in Hinduism is in many ways more tolerant, or at least in part less condemnatory or restrictive than in mainstream Christianity, and this was reported by participants. For instance, an Indian

male gives an explanation of the liberal use of AOD in Hindu mythology, as well as during festivals such as Holi, where alcohol is infused with cannabis, and is known as 'soma rasa'¹⁴ or 'moon. He emphasises that in his experience, the use of alcohol and cannabis is more common in India than in Scotland where the possession of Cannabis is illegal and subject to legal penalties:

"...There are no restrictions in drinking in Hinduism, drugs...There are instances in mythology about Gods getting drunk and they are all having fun, and we celebrate festivals where drugs are allowed. Like "bhang" (cannabis), which is used in Holi (festival of colours) in March. But during Holi, they smoke bhang and drink it too. You can make "Som rasa" with many things but the main thing is the bhang. "Raam rasa" and "Som rasa", "soma" is basically moon, "rasa" means juice, so you are drunk and looking at the moon, and the moon looks nice and white and beautiful. Being high is exactly what it is, that's why it's called moon juice. But we won't be having bhang in Scotland that much I can tell you, as its cannabis!" [Male, Indian, Hindu, 35-39; P 20].

One of the female Hindu participants, however, reports a vagueness in Hinduism concerning condemnation of the use of AOD. Her understanding of Hindu mythology and literature indicate instances of use which were permissive for Gods, but not for 'ordinary' humans. This was because of an inability of non-gods, demons or humans to control their passions while

¹⁴ Much speculation surrounds the actual identity of the drug 'soma' used by Gods in Hindu Vedas. Vedas are the ancient Hindu scriptures, and within which soma has been described as a plant from which a drink or potion was prepared and consumed by the gods. Individuals who understood the identity of the plant describe using it to empower themselves through spiritual enlightenment. Suggestions of the nature soma range from ephedra or cannabis as well as amanita muscaria which is also known as - fly agaric (mushroom). MILLER, R. J. 2013. *Drugged: The Science and Culture Behind Psychotropic Drugs*, Oxford University Press, WASSON, R. G., KRAMRISCH, S., OTT, J. & RUCK, C. A. 1986. *Persephone's quest: Entheogens and the origins of religion*, Yale University Press.

intoxicated. She also reported the specific circumstances where smoking 'ghanja' (cannabis) was permitted or at least less condemned if used for religious reasons. This shrouded the use of cannabis under a cloak of religious respectability thereby avoiding public condemnation:

"In Hinduism although it doesn't say there are any restrictions and as far as I know there is nothing written anywhere. From old mythology or Vedic literature and all that, something like alcohol is mentioned which the Gods were allowed to drink. But they wouldn't give it to the ordinary or the "Asuras" (demons), "Devas" (God) can drink it. And they had this on special occasions, and I think that must have been some sort of alcohol, from the description. But I don't think it was a not done thing. When I was young I had seen these religious guys smoking "ghanja" [cannabis] and that. Maybe a way to get to like a trance-like state. I think these people were tramps, but they give it a halo of respectability by covering it up in religion..." [Female, Indian, Hindu, 65-69; P 11].

The accounts from the participants indicate that Hinduism is more relaxed about the use of AOD. They state that the elaborate sections in the Hindu doctrine, not only makes references to the use of AOD for human pleasure but also among the 'Gods'. Thereby reducing the sanctions by the religion on the use of AOD. The next section explores the use of AOD in Islam.

6.2.3 Islam

The use of intoxicants within Islam is forbidden, and therefore when used, results in shame if discovered in their native place, but can be tolerated though hidden in the UK. For instance, a Pakistani participant explains how drinking is 'forbidden' in Islamic doctrine, and yet drinking is common among Muslims living in the UK which is described as a 'free country' where

'nobody cares'; indirectly suggesting that the onus is placed on the individual as a choice to uphold or ignore religious doctrine:

"In Islam drinking and drugs is forbidden. To be honest, I don't think anybody cares in this country. Because obviously this is a free country. But it's obviously up to you, like if you drink, then you know if it's wrong or not, that's it." [Male, Pakistani, Muslim, 25-29; P 25].

A Muslim, participant 26, with mixed ethnic origins (British Indian) emphasises the importance placed on individual volition and how they maintain control over delinquent behaviour. He asserts that while Islam prohibits the use of all intoxicants with the intention of keeping the body clean, in order to enable the person to obey God's command, the environment and social influences invariably have a powerful influence on free will. Therefore, permissive environmental factors in the UK correlates to a higher likelihood of people 'dabbling' in intoxicants:

"It is prohibited to drink or take drugs in Islam, but it doesn't make any difference whether it is prohibited or not. A religious concept of what is right or wrong, or what you are allowed to do, or what you are not allowed to do, is one thing. An individual's choice of the environment that they grow up in and the social influence is generally always greater of the influence. So the majority will dabble, will try at some point in their life..." [Male, Mixed (British Indian), Muslim, 40-44; P 26].

Portrayals of the use of AOD among Muslim participants in this research reveal that the culture is more influential than religion. This draws upon aspects of enculturation and the influence of culture despite prohibitions in

the religion. The next section explores the perceptions of the use of AOD in Buddhism.

6.2.4 Buddhism

Buddhist doctrine emphasises that abstaining from intoxicants is the path to enlightenment. This avoidance of craving is interesting and suggests how the influence of contemporary understandings of problematic use of AOD can alter how religious doctrines are understood. However, the experiences of a male Chinese participant states that there are no restrictions in Buddhism regarding the use of AOD. He emphasises that these Buddhist understandings of the role of religion on enlightenment are strongly influenced by the environment and region:

"We believe that, but no particular restrictions in our religion about drugs or alcohol. Even in Buddhism you can drink, there's no problem. Just that there are differences in views based on the different parts of the country..." [Male, Chinese, Buddhist, 40-44; P 21].

Another Chinese participant revealed that his grandmother avoided alcohol due to her religious beliefs. However, such religious proscriptions do not form part of his identity, as being a Buddhist was an important part of his grandmother's identity, and one he did not identify with. He believes in the ideologies of Communist China, and argues that in present day China, religion has no significance in life:

"I just know that my grandmother, she believed that you shouldn't drink, and even every two days in one month, she doesn't take any meat, only vegetables. As it is a special day..." [Male, Chinese, No Religion, 25-29; P 30].

The influence of religion in the use or avoidance, condemnation or celebration in the use of AOD is evident from participant data. Contemporary understandings of what drugs are, how they should be used or avoided contrast sharply with theological accounts of the use or indulgence of AOD. The regulation of norms by religion and the importance of religiosity in the construction of identity will be discussed in greater detail later. The next section considers the importance of religion in the lives of the participants.

6.3 Beliefs about Religion

Often religion is considered as a homogeneous reality in an attempt to capture disparate beliefs into a single concept. In reality when religions are compared, they appear to have many intersecting similarities. The literature review (Chapter 2) discussed in much detail Gunn's (2003) *Facets of Religion*. And this is used to understand the importance of religion among participants. The first two facets refer to beliefs and form part of an identity that an individual may be given as part of the religion. Beliefs and identity are those that an individual may bear as part of socialisation into a family or society. Gunn's third facet emphasises the development of the individual's own identity and belief system through volition and how an individual chooses to partake and adopt religion.

For instance, Gunn's first facet of 'religion as a belief' is described by the Chinese participant 29. She considers herself to be a Christian as she has been studying the Bible for a few years. While she is uncertain of what other Christians do, she affirms that religion as having an influence on her use of AOD:

"...I am considering myself as being a Christian, because I have been studying the Bible for 3-4 years now. I think possibly yes, but I'm not very sure, I don't think I know what other people do. I believe that would influence people for what they believe, and what's right and what's wrong, according to their beliefs..."
[Female, Chinese, Christian, 30-34; P 29].

A common belief among participants who considered religion as a part of their identity (Gunn's second facet) was that adherence to religious and cultural taboos were slowly being eroded by secular influences. This suggests religious affiliation through birth, and the importance of the family in maintaining religious beliefs act to influence decisions to avoid AOD. For instance, a Christian participant draws a comparison between African and British cultures. He argues that inadequate religious sanctions in Britain has led to individuals trying alcohol and tobacco, while family morals precludes the use of alcohol and tobacco in African cultures:

"...It's really down to the family and the person, and with the way it is with religion. This [UK] nation is becoming more of an Atheists nation, than Christian or Muslim region. So you will find that people just try things anyway, because they want to try it, and there is nothing really restricting them, unless it is the family morals or some things like that. But you can't really say that there is a family moral for drinking and smoking..."
[Male, African, Christian, 18-24; P 28].

Another Muslim participant suggests that religious sanctions among Muslims regulated by strong family ties are being resisted due to an indistinctness in how Islamic scriptures are understood. He legitimises his use of alcohol by maintaining control by stating that '(I) still have my senses', even though drinking is prohibited in Islam. He further maintains his religious identity though in many ways ignoring or downplaying his alcohol consumption by rationalising what the 'grey area' in Islam is:

"...I would definitely say 80% of my friends or my cousins or people who are my age don't do it (alcohol and drugs). Because of the sole reason that it is not allowed in the religion, and you are not supposed to do anything which makes you lose control of your body. So obviously the belief is that once you have lost control of your body, you might end up doing evil things. But then again a lot of people then consider it as a grey area, and they say that if I consume it enough that I still have my senses, and still have control over myself, then that is okay..." [Male, Pakistani, Muslim, 25-29; P 23].

The perceptible nature of Gunn's third facet 'religion as a way of life' is evident from a Hindu, participant 22. He states that although born into a Hindu family, he chooses not to partake and adopt the norms imposed in his religion and culture. He argues that religion does not perceive the consumption of alcohol or tobacco as a 'sin' but rather the human inclination to become 'out of control' following consumption is what should be avoided:

"...I'm not religious, but I'm interested in religions, so it's nowhere written that you shouldn't drink or that you shouldn't smoke. But the way it is being is that it is tied up with religion and religious factors. In religion it is more likely, they consider it as a sin. Sin in the sense like not the actual drug or alcohol itself is sin, but people when they take that, their mind just goes off their control, and they do things which they shouldn't be..." [Male, Indian, Hindu, 25-29; P 22].

A male African, participant 16, does not consider religion to form a part of his identity states that he was born a Muslim but converted to Christianity. He attempts to rationalise his understanding of Islamic proscription on intoxicants as a means to maintain order in society so that people do not 'cross that line' by becoming inebriated. Intoxication is described as being 'impure' in the presence of God:

"I was born a Muslim, but I'm a Christian now and I'm going to rationalise the Muslim part of it, as I'm not very deep into religion, so whatever I'm going to say will be a rationalisation. What I think is that when you get drunk, you are not clean, because I used to be a Muslim. Muslim's believe that your holiness is cleanliness, so when you get drunk your mouth smells when you talk to God. God is something that in everything you do, is the most respected and everything you do to him, you must be spic and span. You should not be dirty or anything or impure. So religion has set a standard that it is bad, so people should not cross that line and not get drunk or high..." [Male, African, Christian, 35-39; P 16].

Nevertheless, participants indicate that the influence of the family and culture are as strong as religion however, the influence of cultural norms in the UK can lead to a weakening of the effects of family and religion. Breaking taboos and violating the rules and social conventions of one's own

community and family was seen as a source of guilt and shame and will now be explored.

6.3.1 An Unspoken Rule

The literature review in Chapter 2 indicated that religion greatly influences attitudes and behaviours on the use of AOD, and the difficulties in using this category to capture the essence of a multifaceted aspect of identity results in incomplete data. Simply asking respondents in a survey to tick a box indicating religious affiliation does not represent the individual's religiosity, or salience of religion on thoughts and acts of free will.

Several participants emphasised the importance of family as being more influential than religion. For instance, a Chinese participant believes that the majority of the population in China is secular, particularly after Mao's influence, and do not practice a religion or have a religious affiliation. While Buddhism prevails as the dominant religion among the few followers, and awareness of Buddhist scriptures remains, he argues that he does not follow these religious views. Yet he emphasises the importance of maintaining family values and not 'shaming the family':

"I think in China 99% don't have a religion, because in our culture when China was built up in 1949, President Mao said no God. So people become without religion, and they see the political party as being more important, and as the party says no God, there is no God. Buddhism is the main religion, and everyone even me, believes in some things of Buddha. But I don't think it has changed my mind. It is more like it is a lot of pressure and it is big shame for the family..." [Male, Chinese, No Religion, 25-29; P 30].

An African Christian participant highlights the irrefutable influence of family on religious practices, where an individual's action can have an effect on the whole family. She states that adhering to the norm (abstention from alcohol) is an 'unspoken rule' and deviance can affect the 'reputation' of the family:

"And it always reflects back on your parents whatever you do. Always, always reflects back how you were brought up, so because of how you are brought up to be, you wouldn't want to do anything to tarnish that image or reputation. So even if your parents are beggars, you still wouldn't want anybody saying anything, or calling you a druggie or anything like that. I mean it happens, and even in this Scottish Ghanaian way, it is so bad, even though it is not spoken. It is like an unspoken rule. It's so bad, you know?" [Female, African, Christian, 25-29; P 15].

Another Christian participant who was born in India, shares her experience within her family where drinking is considered deviant among some members. While drinking is not considered a 'sin' within her family, it is unacceptable within her cousin's family. She perceives this as her cousin's family misinterpreting religion, and the pervasive influence of Indian culture than religion in condemning the use of alcohol:

"In my house they don't think that it's a big sin or something if you drink. But when I go to my cousins and everything they don't even want their husbands to drink or things like that. It's very difficult even if they come to my house, and if we offer, they won't touch. That is extreme also, though it is happening. I think that they think it's their religion, but it may be cultural and they think that it is something religious" [Female, Indian, Christian, 65-69; P 10].

Among some participants while family and religion were important factors in the use or avoidance of alcohol, caste differences were also an important aspect of identity, and how the use of AOD was understood. This is discussed below.

6.3.2 Influence of Caste in understanding Deviance

Accounts from Indian participants indicate that problem drinking is characterised as a group trait of lower castes, who are characterised as having an inability to progress and be successful due to an inability to control behaviour and a greater tendency to engage in crime. In contrast, upper castes give greater importance to the value of education, which in turn cultivates the ability to seek higher gratification, and hence believe themselves to be more capable of engaging in recreational non-problematic use of alcohol.

Caste and religion continue to be important predictors of alcohol use, as conveyed by the Hindu participant below:

"I'm from an orthodox Hindu family, so as per as the family values, it is not encouraged to drink toddy, as usually toddy¹⁵ is not an upper caste drink. And if you would find me there, it is being shameful. And there [in Kerala] actually the people who [are] educated they don't drink this. Usually people who is working in the labour class or lower castes, not all of them, certain people after tiring work they go in the evening and have one bottle of toddy or something and come back. Nowadays I don't know, things might have changed but in my time, it was always that. They [family] are not going to beat me up or something, but it is shameful. It is embarrassing, that's it.

¹⁵ 'toddy' (a locally fermented distilled sap from palm trees) SANKARANARAYANAN, R., DUFFY, S. W., PADMAKUMARY, G., DAY, N. E. & PADMANABHAN, T. K. 1989. Tobacco chewing, alcohol and nasal snuff in cancer of the gingiva in Kerala, India. *Br J Cancer*, 60, 638-43.

Nothing as such in terms of religion, more to do with the way cultural values are passed in families..." [Male, Indian, Hindu, 45-49; P 7].

Participant 7 further states that individuals from higher castes do not engage in activities such as drinking and smoking in front of elders, as it brings 'shame' to the family. Such behaviour is taught from childhood and deep internalisation of these values and norms are what maintain the social order and caste of the family within Indian society. However, he argues that in contemporary Indian society such values are uncommon as extended traditional families are diminishing due to an expansion of nuclear families, and hence an increase in drinking among younger generations:

"...See in Hindu religion especially in Kerala, my state, I've been to all other states in India as well. Especially in south side, if it is a good family, it is not acceptable or it is shame(ful) to drink or smoke in front of elders especially parents, uncles, elder brothers and sisters. So it's not forced, but it is taught since the childhood, [that] "you should not drink, you should not smoke, you don't do think, that, you should respect elders". In this modern world, due to nuclear families these values are being reduced now. You can already see that now too, as we can see that those who drink are increasing..." [Male, Indian, Hindu, 45-49; P 7].

Similarly, a Male Christian Indian participant states that religion does not advise against the use of alcohol, but that religion acts as a deterrent for the lower castes to drink who are considered to be at a higher risk of problem drinking. Higher levels of education allow for a greater appreciation of recreational drinking, and thus emulation of higher caste practices, and hence lower instances of problem drinking among educated people:

"Actually the religious way they are not saying "do not go for alcohol". It is because some people from lower castes can drink, spend their money on alcohol, and not think of their family. That's what people are telling, it's the religious saying. Some go worse from drinking, but majority educated people drink, but they are in a controlled way of drinking..." [Male, Indian, Christian, 55-59; P 3].

Caste related alcohol use was only mentioned by the Indian and Pakistani participants in this research. Caste based segregation and related group behaviour was argued to be the key aspects of personality that regulated drinking norms. It is important to note that identification on the basis of caste is no longer a legitimate approach in India, as this was constitutionally abolished in 1950. However, imposing such a social disability still prevails as a discourse and repercussions of this can be found in other parts of the Indian subcontinent. This provides important insights into the norms regulating the use of alcohol among Indian participants. Here problem drinking is assumed as a 'polluted', unclean behaviour, associated with lower-castes. Being able to demonstrate control while drinking, and ability to regulate drunken comportment is a means of socially delineation, a means to avoid, or prevent social affront, stigma and shame. Caste is automatically passed on by descent and cannot generally be overcome. These rigid social norms are enforced to differentiate themselves from others. Failure in fulfilling such expectations can result in the social ostracism of not just individual, but also the entire family.

6.4 Conclusion

Participants' accounts in this chapter indicate that from a religious perspective pleasure is considered to be sinister and immoral, as it has the capacity to contaminate personal and social life. As such, the use of AOD is a conundrum that must be regulated, means to do this include religious beliefs, the threat of individual shame or familial ostracism, or be able by social convention to be considered of a high caste and thus demonstrate a superior social position within Indian society in order to circumvent the inevitable labelling of being part of a deviant sub group.

The participants revealed that they experienced tensions between adhering to traditional practices or find a means to adapt to what are considered the contemporary norms in Scotland, which can often lead to polarised attitudes to the use of AOD.

Indian participants particularly emphasised the role of caste in regulating the use of alcohol and managing identity and what is and is not permissible. This provides important insights into the norms regulating the use of alcohol among Indian participants. Here problem drinking is associated with those of the lower-caste, whereby social standing acts not only as a protective factor in preventing problems, but as an explanatory factor in legitimising the caste system, even though it is de facto illegal to continue to adhere to these cultural norms and practices.

All Muslim participants in this study acknowledged the use of drugs and rationalised their use as the 'grey area' in Quranic texts, and that as their

own personal use of for example cannabis use was moderate it meant that it was non-problematic.

While Chinese participants made reference to Buddhism, their views on the use of AOD contrast sharply with that of Buddhist doctrine. Participants argued that they gave greater emphasis to adhering to the norms and sanctions of the family and maintaining the reputation of the family than Buddhism.

Gunn's facets of religion was applied in understanding the participants' perception of the use of AOD in their religion. The three facets include: religion as a belief, religion as identity, and religion as a way of life. The first and third facet were most applicable as participants presented views similar to these. Furthermore, several participants stated that their family had a greater impact on their decisions to use alcohol or drugs than their religious identity. Greater significance was given to the need to maintain the 'reputation' of the family.

The next chapter considers the influence of gender and age on the use of alcohol and drugs.

7 Gender & Age

7.1 Introduction

This chapter addresses alcohol use among men and women as a gendered social practice. The narratives of male and female participants from Indian, African, Chinese, and Pakistani backgrounds are described. Hegemonic gender identities regarding drug and alcohol use, and how this depicts masculine and feminine traits in their cultures are explored. This chapter examines the attitudes and expectations as well as social representations of gendered alcohol use in relation to sex and age, in an attempt to explore the differential understandings of the participants. **Constructions of Male and Female Use of Alcohol**

The gendered drinking practices among African, Indian, Chinese, and Pakistani participants are represented below.

7.1.1 'Fine Boys' and 'Fine Girls'

Polarised gendered roles were discussed by African participants describing idealised or preferred male and female character traits. For instance, a male African stated that in his culture, women are given the responsibility of maintaining order in the family by 'cautioning' men to limit drinking, and as such this creates the 'need' or belief that men should resist. Women are forbidden from drinking in African culture and 'tuned' from childhood against drinking. They are also tasked with arbitrating on social propriety and being observant of the use of alcohol, occasionally regulating men's consumption, and thereby validating their role as guardians of propriety.

Men are allowed to assert their masculinity through drinking irrespective of the amounts consumed:

"...As part of the culture, women are not seen to have alcohol as part of their social life, and cigarettes or drugs are not part of their code of conduct. Even if your husband does, you are not supposed to do it. Because the society would look at a woman who gets drunk or drinks [and think] how can she manage a family?"

We give the responsibility of marriage to a woman, so when you train a woman, you are training her to grow up and manage a family. The woman is trained not to drink, and if she sees her husband drinking, even if he can handle the drink and can have a few, she should caution him not to drink. So if you take anything and she is there, she has to quickly tell you not to. So that's how a woman is tuned up..." [Male, African, 35-39; P 16].

He further states that gendered drinking norms are obscured within cultural obligations, with greater emphasis on proscribing female drinking. Women who go to pubs or bars and drink or smoke tend to induce moral condemnation and are considered to be impure or at risk of being labelled as 'bad' or 'exposed' with the intention to 'sell herself'. As such, drinking and drug use are considered aspects of immoral women, who are there 'to have fun' with and are not deserving of being a wife or managing a family. Within African culture, a woman's competence is reflected in the public position and prestige of her husband, and as such, the husband's unmitigated drinking is indicative of not just economic ruin, but also the woman's moral ruin. He explains this position:

"...Our culture doesn't like to show our dark side, as we wouldn't wash our dirty linen outside. It's like a law; a woman must not go to a pub and drink. Because my society says that a woman should be the most clean. So when they see a lady drinking, smoking or going to the pub with you, they would say she is not a very good girl, she is exposed, this girl is a bad girl, because she wants to sell herself. Drinking or taking drugs is restricted mainly to the prostitutes. The only thing she is a good for is being a girlfriend, to have fun, and then later you would walk away, not marriage material. So when it comes to marriage, then you have to look for someone who is more serious, who doesn't drink or doesn't smoke. That's the cultural norm..." [Male, African, 35-39; P 16].

Furthermore, while women appear to possess power in regulating men's drinking within African culture, it could be argued that the power women appear to have is only by complying with these idealised gendered norms. Hence, drinking and smoking are understood to form a part of masculine identity, and use is not permitted unless the female has the legal status of being married, or considered is to be a 'good girl' or 'marriage material'. Therefore, within this African cultural context, guilt-free drinking by a woman is rare, or when it occurs must be hidden. Women who do not conform and drink or use drugs openly become moral outcasts and public intoxication may result in others stating things like - 'does she have a mother?' As recounted by a female African participant and her experiences of drinking:

"Women you would probably see 3-4 drinks just in the middle, just to pretend that they are drinking. For e.g. few people will drink, but there will probably be like one bottle of wine between us. Because we are not used to it, so something that we do drink would probably be like cocktails. Again a cocktail because others might think it is orange juice. So even though it is alcohol in it, it's probably 90% alcohol in it, but you are not gonna know, because it's camouflaged. Else it will be like why is a woman drinking or drunk, it's not acceptable. But it's not something that they do openly compare to what men do. And then it will spread like how did she grow up, you know? Does she have a mother; you know? That's a big insult from where I come from..." [Female, African, 25-29; P 15].

As a result, women who drink only do so within the confines of intimate friends, and in a largely hidden manner to avoid stigma, discrimination and shame. However, women are able to rebel against this exercise of regulatory mechanisms that influence personal conduct. The participant reported that alcoholic drinks were frequently disguised as 'fruit juice'. Even when alcohol is permitted, there is a higher tendency of conspicuously consuming highly glamorised drinks such as 'cocktails' to portray femininity. It could be argued that they actively restrict their consumption to such drinks to maintain and protect these ideals of feminine identity. Hence, while African women can enjoy alcohol, there are certain practices that must be utilised which act to protect their femininity, avoid transgression, and being labelled negatively. In essence, this practice of 'intentional dissimulation' describes drinking practices engaged in by African female participants in a largely male dominated culture.

The consumption of alcohol is very popular and widespread in Chinese culture, both among men and women. In general, social drinking is normal

and, in many cases, hard to avoid, with clearly defined expectations of those who participate. There are differences in drinking customs and attitudes in relation to gender, where women who do drink can be at risk of being labelled negatively. The stigmatising and punitive thinking with regards to female drinking is described by Chinese participants, where culturally drinking and smoking are visible signs of masculinity, while the use of drugs are dismissed on grounds of being dangerous and harmful, presumably to both sexes. The use of alcohol is permissible, but visible intoxication or the use of tobacco products are considered male traits, and women who publicly drink or smoke are at risk of 'turning into men basically'. For instance, a Chinese female participant states that within her culture 'that there are a lot of things that women can't do'. She further describes the factors that women 'must live up to':

"...Well I think there's quite a lot of things you need to live up to when you are a girl right? You are not allowed to drink; well you shouldn't be drinking because it's like quite manly. It's good to drink for socialising, but it's not good to be drinking like until you are at a really drunk stage, and then you are turning into a man basically. Your actions and everything and the way you walk and stuff. You shouldn't smoke, because that's very manly looking basically. Or take drugs, that's dangerous for you, harmful and plus its very you know, its masculine, it's not a womanly thing to do. Basically there's a lot of things that a woman can't do..." [Female, Chinese, 18-24; P 14].

She further states that within Chinese or Asian culture, greater emphasis is given to 'peoples, family and relatives' perceptions, where upholding family values and status is very important. While drinking is tolerated,

female drunkenness is highly frowned upon as it would 'bring shame to the family':

"...Because I think you know in the Asian society, they are really concerned about other people's thoughts, the family, relatives like "what will your aunty think if they see you in the streets drunk, and you are sitting there and taking your shoes out, walking about". They care a lot about that, the image thing. And they don't want to bring shame to the family and stuff like that. So I think that's really big..." [Female, Chinese, 18-24; P 14].

It is interesting that P14 highlights that in order for female behaviour to be regulated, it requires complicit acceptance that this is useful to both sexes. While female behaviour is regulated, it requires both males and females for this to happen. Male Chinese participants remark that drinking is a vital aspect of everyday life, and particularly so for men within a work environment. While social drinking is acceptable for women, within the work environment, the primary role of a woman is to serve men to allow them to succeed and earn money. So unlike African culture where all use of alcohol must be hidden, public drinking by women is accepted, however only if in relation to it being part of business, or to aid male gratification and amusement. Career-oriented women who adopt a male lifestyle risk being branded as 'indecent' or 'Jiao-ji-hua':

"...In Chinese culture it is very common that if a lady is a very good drinker, normally we would say that this particular woman is not very decent person. We call them "Jiao-ji-hua" which means a lady who is always drinking with a man. But these are for different purposes sometimes for collaboration, for job or for some business, sometimes to have a promotion, and to network with people. So these kind of women we call them jiao-ji-hua, who's always drinking, and in order to make people happy. So it's a very common kind of thing in Chinese culture, but it's a very bad image..." [Male, Chinese, 40-44; P 21].

The discourses regarding consumption and conduct emphasises the extent to which normative feminine ideals can shape women's drinking, as well as reinforcing the message that female intoxication is dramatically different from normative feminine conduct. As such, women who drink among these communities, do so within a social context in which their experiences are shaped, regulated and recreated within ideals of gendered drinking norms. The next section explores how social expectations shape the use of AOD among males and females.

7.1.2 Social Model of Expectations

Key gender distinctions as social expectations of what is permitted can be identified by the description of drinking styles of Indian and Pakistani men and women. Here participants' accounts of the role of gendered expectations help in understanding the drinking and drug use among men and women in Scotland and 'back home'. A large number of Indian participants described the process of alcohol enculturation as a contributing factor in normalising the use of alcohol within Scottish culture. While abstinence and the practice of moderation are essential features of feminine

practices among India participants, this was considered to be inessential in Scotland. Women who drink or are perceived to drink too much in India are often subject to moral condemnation, thereby reinforcing gender differences:

"In India generally, Indian women don't drink, well (a) major percentage of Indian women never consume alcohol. It's basically because they brought it through the culture that alcohol is only for men. Some people tend to look them (women), like "back in India they would never do that, but now oh because they (women) are here (Scotland) they are doing it..." [Male, Indian, 30-34; P 1].

While drinking is strictly regulated by cultural and often religion in India, in Scotland these expectations are abandoned. Shocked indignation is often a common way of describing the use of alcohol by women to the extent that women are not just denigrated by men, but their mothers too, for poorly training their daughters. Indeed, this Indian male recounts a proverb in Malayalam "kudembam mudiyum" which suggests that women's drinking would lead to the ruin of that family. Consequently, he was astounded to see his mother drinking after residing in Scotland and having enculturated to Scottish drinking norms. For this male participant, without the strict policing of female behaviour, they 'adapt to new things' and become subject to shaming and amusement as 'taking the mickey':

"...I mean, over here, when they come over here, you see girls drinking too. And when I first came here I got shocked. There is a saying that "pennu kudichal kudembam mudiyum..."

...Like when I saw my mother drinking wine, I was like "now what's happening here? Where am I?" But she [mother] was like "no, this is like the usual thing over here, and you can try wine, you can try beer, it's all up to you". You are free over here; unlike in India you cannot drink, that's the thing. Coz it is really like when people come outside of their own country, you see how people will evolve. I would say they change quite quickly, they adapt with the new community, they adapt to new things. And it's like a comedy thing. It's like taking the micky out of them [women]. But it is really acceptable over here..." [Male, Indian, 18-24; P 12].

A female Indian participant describes how a female drinker not only transgresses social conventions, but also violates the norms of being perceived as a good woman. Only through fulfilling the norms of ideal femininity, within an Indian context can a woman be good. Cultural norms in India admonish women for drinking like men as its 'not a woman's way of doing' and if she does consume, she is at risk of being labelled as 'addicted'. She also states that Indian women are not stigmatised for drinking in Scotland, as it is 'more open here' and people 'don't bother about others'. She succinctly describes the conventions and mechanism of shame that regulate female conduct, and those who transgress these conventions within the community risk being considered bad women, and poor parents:

"They [Indian norms] say that a woman, if she drinks she changes her character or nature. So it's a man's way of doing it, not a woman's way of doing it. But women always, because we have more responsibilities, we always think that if we take more it we would get addicted to it. Or you can't look after the children, and we are worried. We also worry about how will men think about us? Because normally they also have a mentality back home that women don't drink. And if we drink too much then they [men] will have a bad concept, and people too about us. All these things are affecting us there. Back home I don't think women will take at all, because, even just showing a glass of alcohol, a woman holding it with alcohol, it is like a shame for us. Society is more open here [Scotland] than there [India]. People just don't bother about other people so whatever you do, they don't bother..." [Female, Indian, 45-49; P 6].

Unlike participants from Indian, African and Chinese backgrounds who gave greater emphasis to the influence of culture, Pakistani participants emphasised the influence of religion and concerns about health as mechanisms to regulate the use of alcohol and cigarettes. Smoking was considered hazardous to health, yet is a common activity among men, while drinking is proscribed on religious grounds. Furthermore, some participants argued that women are biologically vulnerable to AOD as it would affect their reproductive capacity. Some participants reported smoking to be more gender specific than drinking, where condemnation is intensified for female smokers who are considered 'morally corrupt' and promiscuous. Smoking is considered a sign of moral corruption, and accepting western practices, BME women are at risk of condemnation and scorn. Furthermore, if a religion prohibits or condemns alcohol or tobacco, the use of it in public acts as a symbolic rejection of all aspects of that religion, further resulting

in condemnation. A male Pakistani considers gendered patterns of behaviour and states:

"Drinking is probably considered equally bad for both genders. So if a girl is drinking or boy is drinking it's just equally bad. I don't think it's something that you could say is gender specific. I think that is mostly associated with smoking. Socially sometimes people consider women who smoke to be more western and there's the whole moral corruption of things, and they would probably think that you are sleeping around with somebody as well. I don't know how but these things tend to get attached to it somehow...but drinking is probably of becoming morally corrupted. And it is obviously fuelled by the religion, because if you are not following one tenet of the religion who is to say you are not following the other. That's the normal assumption, which is not true". [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 23].

It is interesting to note that smoking rather than drinking symbolically represent sexual allure rather than drinking, which in effect renders the male and female morally corrupt. This may be due to how tobacco is marketed in the Pakistani sub-continent, where like the UK and the US in the 1960-1980, the use of tobacco was closely linked to sexual attractiveness and 'freedom' to behave as one chooses in advertising.

Another male Pakistani participant states that women are condemned in general and their use of alcohol. Hence, Pakistani families have a greater tendency to try to protect daughters from behaviours which include 'smoking, drinking, drug use, as well as extramarital affairs' all of which bring shame, condemnation and discrimination. He argues that within educated families and those who reside in the cities in Pakistan, there is greater convergence of AOD among male and females. Furthermore,

unmarried women who use alcohol would reduce their desirability for marriage and be considered 'unclean'. Such is the remonstrance that transgressing women will not be accepted within any Pakistani family and may only have a future with someone from Scotland. This was because the Pakistani families in Scotland would be unaware of the misdemeanours of the concerned woman:

"...I mean it's just because anything women do it becomes a big problem for everyone, for the family and all. Because I think the family honour is more affected with girls. Parents they want to protect their daughters from taking drugs, or smoking, taking alcohol, or going into relationships with someone. Or doing anything which is prohibited, like having sex with any males before marriage. So within Muslim communities they want to protect their women a lot. And obviously if a girl or a woman wants to take drugs, definitely it would be a big issue. I think when education is more the life in cities are completely different. Like in modern families, men and women are equal, and I've seen that even women they drink, they are taking drugs too. She will never get any "rishta", any proposal, in Asian community. I think it is an unfair thing, because if a boy if taking alcohol or drugs they are fine, but they will get clean girls. Maybe a Scottish man would be willing to accept her, but not from their own community..." [Male, Pakistani, 25-29; P 24].

It is interesting that customs, which were once useful, in early capitalism, such as considering girls as male property, when males were considered the way in which a family could relax in the knowledge that their daughter would be looked after. In late modernity they are no longer useful, and shocking and even barbaric when examined objectively. This culture clash when old meets new normative expectations becomes most apparent when a culture that still has links to a recent past clash with the ideas, customs

and practices of the UK in late modernity. If we considered the African female participant previously who demonstrated intentional dissimulation, that is, had to conceal her use of alcohol to protect her identity from becoming stigmatised, a Pakistani female also expresses similar accounts. She describes elaborate strategies to maintain two distinct identities, one to integrate with Scottish peers, and which must be concealed from her family. She refrains from visible (western) activities such as 'partying, drinking, smoking' which would expose her nature to her family group, which lead to stigmatisation and 'ruin the reputation' of the family. Furthermore, women who socialise with men within the night-time economy are deeply discredited:

"Drinking is just a no no. Ermm...and everything else is just a no no. But I mean, see for e.g. if someone found out that I was out clubbing or whatever, and they seen me smoking and I'm hanging out with guys and I'm drinking. That's the picture straight away that they would think of you as a bad person, and a slut or whatever you know? And that gets around, so for us it's more of the fact that reputation is ruined. It's such a big deal, like as soon as it's found out, the whole...everyone knows and the reputation is ruined and you've shamed your family, and all of that. So any Asians I know is really family and I don't hang out with any of them to like party or anything like that. Anyone out with that is fine...I obviously live a double life because I keep everything - partying, drinking, smoking, to one side, like with a specific group of friends. And family things to another side, where I don't do any of that stuff..." [Female, Pakistani, 25-29; P 8].

It is evident from the participants' accounts above that women's behaviour is at times labelled transgressive, unclean (unhealthy) and that women who deviate from these idealised norms are assumed to lack desirable feminine

attributes (e.g. African and Chinese cultures). Alcohol enculturation as well as living in a neoliberal country was reported among Indian participants as the outcome for women's use of alcohol. However, while participants from these ethnic groups have reported women as having a degree of freedom in consuming alcohol and smoking, for some women this freedom is marked with the real potential of risking exclusion and denigration and therefore the strategy of intentional concealment of use. The next section considers age as a factor in defining acceptable male and female identity and the concept of 'maturing out' of the use of alcohol and smoking.

7.2 Accounts of Alcohol Use and Smoking by Age

Age and gender are two archetypal factors that influence the amount, context, reason and with what effects people use alcohol and tobacco. Participants in this research have reported cohort effects (each generation exhibiting behaviours that challenge 'traditional' norms) and while there are among some BME groups a certain permissiveness in women's drinking, there remain limits to what is acceptable.

The generational drinking variations are evident from a male Nigerian participant in his mid-40s, who explains that when he was younger it was not common to see a woman exploring the nightlife and clubbing scene in Nigeria. He makes a distinct comparison with the drinking culture in Scotland and describes the concept of 'ladies' night' in a deprecating manner and the emancipation of women as unacceptable. He argues that

while Nigerian women in Scotland are adopting Scottish norms, it is still considered contemptuously within the Nigerian community:

"...In the last 5 years when I was in Nigeria you hardly see women on the blocks or ladies' nights or going to take alcohol. It's not accepted, people frown at it, but things are changing. The world is dynamic and I think now things are changing a little bit, ladies are now going out, taking alcohol and going over their head. But it's still not acceptable within the community. They can drink at home, where no one is going to see you, or lay their eyes on you. The public people frown at it..." [Male, African, 40-44; P 17].

On the other hand, another Nigerian male in his early twenties explains that denigration of women who smoke and use illicit drugs occurs mostly among older men or among those who lack life experience gained through education or travel. He argues that it is the lack of education that results in violence against women who use illicit drugs. He uses the analogy of acceptance to homosexuality as an outcome of acquiring higher education in a developed country such as Scotland, and that this greater exposure that would make people more accepting of female smoking cigarettes or cannabis. While the Nigerian male (P 17) in his forties rejected the notion of female drinking, this male participant argues that drinking is a normalised activity among both genders, particularly among those within his age range:

"...There are some guys who are older and they see them [women] as immoral, it's demeaning for a lady to smoke. That they don't want someone like that, they will say that they want someone "totally clean", that kind of thing. Some guys will say that maybe probably when they [women] are beaten they will be okay. But there are some guys are okay with the lady, so it depends on the guy as such, and his exposure in life. So maybe somebody who comes to school abroad, or is exposed to different culture, will maybe be fine with ladies who smoke, because they have seen a lot of ladies who smoke in the streets and it doesn't bother him. It is just the same thing as being a lesbian or gay. People who come abroad, or who are school abroad, they tend to be okay with these things and be friends with gay or lesbians. But people who still have that closed mind like "it's all a taboo" those kind of things, "girls shouldn't be smoking weed or cigarettes". Drinking is an exception, because generally everyone does it.." [Male, African, 18-24; P 28].

Similarly, an Indian female in her late 60s elaborates about the variations in drinking cultures as time passes, from an emphasis on teetotal temperance during her thirties to the influence of consumerist culture when she was in her fifties. She explains that when she was younger, drinking was a private activity, and predominantly engaged in by men. If the individual concerned were of a higher class (caste), drinking was frowned upon as drinking was considered an occupation of the working class. However, now she explains, abstinence is considered abnormal or unusual:

"When I was a bit older say like when I was in my thirties, I had relatives who did drink. Many of them in that generation, they will only drink quietly in the house, with just one or two friends or close relatives, but not in a party or in a public place. But as time went on, by the time I was in my forties and fifties, people of every generation, every class, started drinking openly. In the old day, if like a doctor or a lawyer or somebody like that was known to be drinking, it will be all like "oh, he takes a drink". As if it is a big thing. But now if you don't drink they'll say "you know, what sort of a man is he? He doesn't even have a drink?" [Female, Indian, 65-69; P 11].

This section reveals the participants' accounts of the differences in views that transpires through historical periods. For instance, the differences in the African participants' perception of the expectation of women's use of alcohol and smoking. The next section considers the participants' experiences of maturing out of alcohol use.

7.2.1 **'Shed it': Maturing out**

Several participants in this research disclosed accounts of maturing out within a transformational context of developing into an informed user. For instance, a male participant in his late thirties indicates that the transitional period from adolescence to young adulthood altered his drinking and smoking habits. He construes that experimenting is a symbol of 'teenage behaviour' which is then 'shed' and a new persona is applied, to adopt 'conventional' attitudes. He further states that marriage brings with it a reduction in social and recreational activities that are linked with drinking. Activities such as attending parties and social events, as well as meeting friends are reduced with marriage and that activities such as drinking, and smoking are more commonplace among single people:

"...A lot of change, because you don't do things you did then [time at university]. Once you've experimented, you've tested it in society. So you've tried it, smoking, drinking, and after a while you have to shed it. Shed the teenage behaviour, so I smoked for 17 years and I just woke up one morning and decided to stop smoking. I used to go out when I was youngster like you, but when I got married I can't continue. As it has an effect on my marriage. So what I'm trying to say is that, age matters, as age affects our actions. Because as a teenager you want to explore from childhood, but as time goes on and you get older and you push off academically, and your relationships with people grow." [Male, African, 35-39; P 16].

Similarly, a female participant in her early twenties expresses how she is 'too old' for drinking occasions or binge sessions that she used to engage in during her time at university. The social environment of university generally supports the use of alcohol, and as such it is reasonable to expect that leaving university would result in a decline in behaviours associated with peers. Furthermore, the end of formal higher education and the resultant transition to employment signals a period of maturing out from one role and assuming another role with more responsibility and less freedom. Young adults have a tendency to increase their alcohol use when they experience independence from parental restrictions. In such instances the social environment of the university proves the ideal ground for experimentation. However, as they take on the responsibilities of adult life, maturing out from such deviance occurs:

"I've passed that state of trying anyway; I'm too old for trying. I've not had a drink since New Year, and I've only had like one glass. It's not even a glass; it was just a small amount of wine. I used to go out once a month at least. I've not got out like say half a year now. It's like half a year gaps, so embarrassing. I'm getting old!" [Female, Chinese, 18-24; P 14].

Participants have illustrated how they have changed their use of alcohol and smoking habits as a result of maturing and adopting adult traits associated with control and preventing risks of demonstrating disinhibited (shameful) behaviour. For instance, while one participant expressed that their use of alcohol and smoking had reduced once getting married, another participant stated that she did not drink as much as she used to, as this was a transition of leaving university. Neither of the participants reported problematic drinking or a difficulty in reducing their use of alcohol.

7.3 Conclusion

This chapter demonstrated how constructs of masculinity and femininity act to signify what is and is not permissible in terms of sex and gender. It is evident from the participants' accounts in this chapter that the drinking activities that men and women engage in are a means of delineating gendered boundaries of what is and is not acceptable. Women who drink too much or are visibly drunk in public are subject to moral condemnation among Chinese and African participants. However, African participants described ways in which certain practices allow public deviance. As discussed earlier in this chapter, the female participants engaged in a conscious act of 'intentional dissimulation' to conceal the use of alcohol and

hiding it as fruit juice or in cocktails. Such practices act as a mechanism in which women may participate in public drinking, however behaviour is regulated by both men and women.

A woman's intrusion into the world of a man can be met with indignation or ridicule with the boundaries of differences between the genders being redrawn, and yet in certain cultures, women are considered to be moral architects and guardians of social order among African participants. In matters that relate to the home or family, it is the man who is considered disorderly with their drinking, while women maintain order by stopping men from being disorderly. As such, the burden of social propriety is borne almost entirely by women and inflicted on men. This social discrimination was also portrayed by participants with statements as 'does she have a mother', or 'does her aunt know about this', which serves to illustrate that women are regulated by female as well as male disapproval.

Male and female identities are constantly negotiated and reconstructed on the basis of place and context as a means to accommodate ever fluid and changing social situations. African and Chinese participants note that through the act of drinking, women are cast as pitiful objects, as they become targets for men to direct their disapproval and labelled as promiscuous. These processes are intimately linked to power and authority, and the social enforcement of values concerning 'good clean woman' and the 'worthy man', which are articulated and enforced within these cultural environments.

It is clear that gendered drinking is a feminist issue, as drinking is often a hidden activity among African women, while among Chinese women public inebriation is transgressive of established or expected social norms. For instance, a Chinese female participant stated that women are considered as 'turning into men basically' when inebriated. Here, intoxicated behaviour is linked with undesirable masculine behaviours.

Indian participants distinguished between drinking norms in India and Scotland. While female drinking is denounced in India, it is largely considered a norm in Scotland. Nevertheless, Pakistani participants suggested that there could be severe consequences for females who are discovered as transgressing cultural norms. For instance, being known as a woman who has transgressed established norms is considered underserving of a suitable partner with the resultant loss of family 'honour'. This was discussed by a female Pakistani who concealed her use of alcohol and had constructed separate identities to co-exist with family and peers.

The participants also expressed some support for the maturing out thesis, suggesting that the transgression of social norms was an act of youthful rebellion, and that in adulthood, engaging in deviance was less desirable, or there were less opportunities to do so.

The next chapter considers the interpretation of the key themes that emerged in the literature and in the analysis.

8 Discussion of Research Findings

8.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the findings of this research. Each of the four data chapters will be summarised, and the main findings will be discussed. Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7 presented the participants' use of alcohol and some drugs in the West of Scotland.

8.2 Perceptions of Alcohol Use

The first data chapter (Chapter 4) of this thesis presents the participants' perceptions of the use of alcohol. The social, cultural, and ethnic identities of the participants' in this research are interconnected. Accounts of their drinking indicate that their ethnic identity coexists with a British/Scottish identity. The bi-dimensional model of acculturation, as well as the concept of alcohol enculturation, are useful in explaining how participants integrate Scottish cultural norms and values while simultaneously maintaining the values and behaviours of their original culture. Acculturation involves behavioural changes that occur as a result of being exposed to a different culture; it includes integrating the beliefs and values of the host culture (Scottish culture) while maintaining the values and behaviours of the original culture (Chun et al., 2003; Siatkowski, 2007). A strong connection with their original culture was evident through accounts of alcohol initiation, which often took place either with their family or social networks.

The conflicts these individuals face in adopting Scottish drinking practices, as this is often stigmatised in their own culture is documented in this thesis.

As discussed in the literature review in Chapter 2 there are various motivations that lead people to identify and interact with social groups, and one of these motivations was uncertainty. Uncertainty-identity theory (Hogg, 2014) describes uncertainty in relation to who one is, and how one should behave. Categorisation of oneself as belonging to a group leads to a consensually validated social identity, which then mediates behaviour as it helps with situating oneself in a society on the basis of the social representations of that society including the consumption of alcohol (Howarth, 2006; Duveen and Lloyd, 1986; Bourdieu and Passeron, 1977; Brierley-Jones et al., 2014).

The use of alcohol, with its attendant intoxicated behaviours is learned and culturally mediated, which takes place through modelling, while selective reinforcement encourages or discourages behaviour (Bandura and McClelland, 1977). As such, exposure to drinking situations, drinking attitudes, awareness, opinions and beliefs, institutions e.g. family, peer groups, colleagues etc. play an important role in the development of attitudes to alcohol and drinking behaviours and cultural norms of drunken comportment (MacAndrew and Edgerton, 1969, 2003). Research has shown that individuals who interact with inter-ethnic groups are more likely to accept new behaviours than those who only interact with their own traditional culture (Landrine and Klonoff, 2004; Purser et al., 2001; Heim et al., 2004).

Perceptions of parent's attitudes towards drinking plays a significant role in how drinking norms are transmitted and illuminates the drinking norms of the Pakistani and African participants. Research has suggested that parents can have injunctive attitudes about what they think is appropriate regarding alcohol use by youngsters (Turner, 1991b; Wood et al., 2001; Graham et al., 1991; Wood et al., 2004). These norms can have their basis from cultural or social norms, or their own drinking history. Parents own rules about drinking behaviour might also have an impact on children, through children imitating parental drinking (Turner, 1991b; Turner et al., 2014).

Theoretical and empirical research has demonstrated the importance of the family, particularly parent-child relationships on the development of behaviour including alcohol use (Van Der Vorst et al., 2005; Donovan, 2004; Pedersen and von Soest, 2013). Young people tend to internalise the cultural systems of the family, and the wider society mediated through the family, for carrying out future role requirements. Thus, family socialisation provides the consensual basis for maintaining social order and promoting non-problematic behaviour (Barnes et al., 2000; Blum et al., 2000; Turner et al., 2014). Other aspects of family life that are also associated with drinking behaviour include parental support and control.

Several Indian and Pakistani participant's note that their initiation into alcohol was through peers. It was also reported that peer acceptance and blending-in were crucial factors in drinking with colleagues. Evidence from emerging literature suggests that social norms about drinking shape young

people's attitudes to alcohol and willingness to engage in the use of alcohol despite cultural proscriptions such as age, or religion (Litt et al., 2012; Trucco et al., 2011). Experimentally misrepresented drinking norms are also shown to predict willingness to drink (Litt and Stock, 2011; Kelly et al., 2012). Thus if peers also tend to be more approving of alcohol use, then likelihood of use will be high (Guo et al., 2015). The influence of norms on drinking attitudes and behaviour appear to vary by normative significance whether injunctive or descriptive. Likewise, social identity theory (Reed et al., 2007; Terry and Hogg, 1996) and reference group theory (Hyman and Singer, 1968), postulates proximal peers (in-groups) to be of greater significance than distal groups (out-group's) and therefore have a stronger influence on attitudes and behaviour because of the value placed on the in-group.

Principles of social learning theory propose direct and indirect influence of peers in decisions to use alcohol (Borsari and Carey, 2001; Andrews et al., 2002). Direct influence involves an explicit focus on getting a person to drink, and can range from polite gestures (e.g. buying a drink or offering a drink) to overt commands and encouragement to drink (e.g. forcing to drink through games) (Jackson et al., 2014; Osgood et al., 2013). Peer influences are not limited to direct offers to drink, as peers through their own actions, may inform individuals about expected and admired behaviours that are the norm within that group.

While friends are crucial in drinking experiences, wider cultural norms have a greater impact in shaping behaviour, particularly through the internalisation of norms (MacArthur et al., 2017). However, alcohol enculturation explains that exposure to social drinking practices allows the development of aspects of identity that facilitates integration into the new culture (Dar et al., 2002). In such occasions, alcohol takes on the role of a cultural facilitator whereby drinking norms which may challenge already learned beliefs about alcohol are resisted or accepted (Heath, 1995).

Chapter 4 further reveals how the possession of social capital limited negative labelling for functional problem users. The manner in which capital is exercised, emphasises how it provides rewards and social status in society (Benton, 2009). Possession of social capital implies that, while drinking could be attributed to affluence and social standing, it also prevents negative labelling of problem users, who if they were of lower social standing, would be viewed and treated unfavourably. Since for labels to be effective, an established consensus that the individual's behaviour needs changing has to be established and supported. Thus greater social capital than those surrounding them assures against any labelling or need for change in behaviour, due to fear of exclusion from the group or withdrawals of rewards (Kissin and Begleiter, 2013). Bourdieu's theory of habitus offers further support of the influence of capital through social (networks), cultural (knowledge of the importance of differentiation of drinking norms) and economic (accumulation of wealth) (Christensen and Carpiano, 2014; Demant and Jarvinen, 2011). Taken together this leads to

the generation of practices which facilitates the acceptance of deviance, with reduced risk of stigma for some and greater for others depending on age, gender, social standing and social class (by family, occupation or occupation of spouse or partner) or caste.

Indeed, participants' accounts provide support for Goffman's (1986) theories of social performance and management of social affronts (Goffman, 2009) indicating when and how to use agency and when it is 'safe' to use or to avoid drink or drugs depending on context. As such, the use of alcohol can be in some instances among BME, a symbol of power and domination over minority culture, or the ability to use without fear of stigma, in the context of alcohol, the domination of white culture over minority culture(s) (Room, 2005). Assimilation and hybridisation with Scottish culture sometimes challenges the norms and values of individuals from BME groups (Baumann, 1997). It is through 'tradition' that certain actions and practices are preserved, however challenging these traditions leads to these being asserted with exaggerated significance for the maintenance of ethnic identity boundaries (Cohen, 2012; Barth, 1998). The tendency to preserve and replicate cultural practices helps in assigning an identity to individuals through constraining choices and assures the protraction of that culture. Indeed, stereotyping and discrimination sometimes shapes group identity. Withstanding, resisting or undermining these stereotypes can be important to the identity of BME individuals and groups.

It is clear that some individuals and groups in a culture can and do impose sanctions as a means to achieve social order in the UK. How these are resisted or assimilated form the basis of this thesis.

Within the literature, there prevail multiple definitions of problem use with competing and overlapping organisational and theoretical interests, while emphasising the normative roles that various societies play in emphasising that excessive drinking accommodates both badness and sickness (i.e. controllable and uncontrollable actions). It is within the confines of society that social groups can define acceptable (or indeed unacceptable) drinking practices. As mentioned earlier, behaviours only become deviant when they are defined by individuals or groups with the legitimacy and power to do so.

Individuals in this research were broadly middle-aged and from a middle class/professional background. While there is a need to factor in sampling bias as a consequence of the key informants used, this sample reflects the divergent BME populations in Scotland. There were a greater number of first generation (n=26/30) individuals in this study, and their accounts indicate assimilation with Scottish drinking norms. These first-generation participants were also in a high income bracket given their employment status. However, there were fewer (n=3/30) second generation participants and only one third generation participant. Interestingly, while the second and third generation participants demonstrated lower levels of drinking, their use of or willingness to try drugs was high.

Additionally, in assimilating with Scottish culture, elements of inverse racism were revealed. A reflection of the perceptions of those within their community signify that minorities consider their own culture in a superior light because of the greater authoritative parenting and community monitoring of their young, than occurs in Scotland. For these participants, Scottish culture encourages deviance, consequently enabling such individuals and groups to construct Scots culture and customs as inferior. This inverse racism acts as a form of cultural validation and/or a coping mechanism to manage their status as outsiders when engaging with wider Scots society.

It was revealed that alcohol was feared as a contributory factor for the erosion of traditional norms of the culture 'back home' from cultures that proscribe alcohol or forbid the use of it. Participants report the use of alcohol to fit in when socialising with Scots in social and after work situations even when alcohol was forbidden due to religious reasons. Finally, in cultures where alcohol use is accepted, there was no threat to tainting their identity by the shame of drinking – but there may remain a gender or sex barrier insofar as there were certain behaviours expected of women, even in societies that are permissive about the use of alcohol.

8.3 Perceptions of Drug Use

The fifth chapter of this thesis reveals how and why participants perceive the use of certain drugs as harmful. There were variations in the participants' description of harm. The 14 participants who did not use any

drugs, maintain that their perceptions about addictive and dangerous drugs are underpinned by codes transmitted to them through family and cultural discourses. Similarly, three participants who smoked tobacco suggest that by avoiding certain drugs, they avoid a loss of control and the risk of spoiling of one's identity as 'good'.

Of the 13 participants who had ever used controlled drugs, a Pakistani, Indian and a mixed ethnicity participant emphasise that the illicit use of some drugs (e.g. cannabis) allows them to heighten their senses and improve performance or aid relaxation. This is also supported in the literature, for instance, Rosen and Weil (2004) indicated that people use drugs functionally to alter their conscious experience motivated by a need to reduce pain or to increase pleasure. As such, it could be argued that individuals' experiment with drugs due to a curiosity that it would be helpful in social situations (Decorte and Fountain, 2010), to feel better by reducing social anxiety or simply to alter perception and "get high" (Cohen, 1971).

People have a desire to experience an altered state of consciousness, despite opposition, and have sought numerous means to achieve this state. This diversity is also evident in the variety of drugs consumed. Furthermore, the purpose for consumption also vary, ranging from relaxation to stimulation, or to comply with social pressures etc. but some drugs are less stigmatising than others (e.g. coffee, tea, alcohol, tobacco), while others must be disguised or concealed (e.g. cannabis, amphetamines etc.). And as such, drugs and drug consumption remain for many shrouded

in myths and misconceptions. Furthermore, theories of deviance attribute a variety of factors to deviance and therefore to the use of drugs such as improper socialisation (Kandel, 1980), social interactions (Hirschi and Gottfredson, 1994; Sutherland et al., 1995), upbringing or unequal opportunities (Boardman et al., 2001). Likewise it is commonly considered in most societies that drugs have a tendency to possess the user thereby subverting or over riding their ability to act in accordance with prescribed social norms (Reinarman, 2005; Room, 2001).

The normalisation thesis (Parker et al., 1998; Parker et al., 2002; Aldridge et al., 2013) is helpful in exploring the social and cultural pressures on different social groups. According to Parker et al. (1998), normalisation of drug use occurs with an increase in positive attitudes and awareness, and also coincides with an increase in the 'perceived' availability of the illicit drug. They focused on those drugs termed 'recreational' e.g. cannabis, amphetamines, and methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA) etc. as these are associated with recreational use, rather than reported by known problem users in contact with services. This in turn leads to an increase in experimentation and regular use of drugs to the extent where use is normalised and accepted as part of an individual's leisure pattern. Indeed, normalisation refers to the process where an activity or behaviour which was previously considered deviant is culturally accommodated. This thesis introduces the term accommodation to refer to those drugs, including alcohol which have through processes of acculturation become context accommodated. This means that in certain contexts, even if alcohol use is

forbidden by religion, family convention, or cultural convention, it can for some BME individuals when engaging with the majority population be illicit, and for some regular deviant activity. AOD accommodation of use or normalisation occurs as an iterative and interactive process via acculturation. This accommodation to the use of drugs including alcohol refers to another addition to the lexicon that of 'contextual accommodation', referring to deviance that occurs as a process of acculturation.

Participants reported that the use of alcohol and for some tobacco is prohibited and forbidden for women due to an association with crime, ill health and deviance, particularly sexual deviance. While the data in this thesis reveals that illegal drugs are condemned in all BME cultures, the use of cannabis in Nigeria and Zambia is considered, at least in part, normal and natural. The Nigerian and Ghanaian participants considered smoking of tobacco as being a gateway to 'hard' drugs and hence smoking was highly stigmatised in the community in Scotland.

Among participants from Indian and Pakistani backgrounds, the hidden use of tobacco products in a form that is chewed (Paan and Gutkha) was reported. Interestingly while Indian participants cited the use of paan as a crucial element in social gatherings and celebrations in India and Scotland, Pakistani participants reported its use primarily among those from lower social classes. Similarly, while drug use, gambling and prostitution are publicly condemned in Chinese culture, it is described as commonplace in

private in China. The Chinese participants use drugs in private or in environments where they are not at risk of condemnation. However, their attitudes to drugs are shaped by legal and public health discourses and underpinned by familial sanctions which would spoil the identities of these BME participants, if they used disapproved, or non-medically sanctioned drugs.

The debate on morality is most often confined within medical and legal discourses and the repression of drugs and demonization of those who use them is justified on the basis of the health and socio-legal problems associated with problem drug use. As such, problematic users are stigmatised as evil, criminal, and untrustworthy, and considered normal when they demonstrate an ability to 'recover' from their medical and legal problems when they achieve abstinence. Such is the power of language, in describing drugs users as mad, sad and bad, that there is great difficulty in discussing the use of drugs within BME participants in this research, as drug use was considered to be a taboo.

No society is uniform, as within every society there are individuals and groups with their own aims and interests. Most individuals, who use alcohol and tobacco, can do so without challenging conventional social values, as well as the use of prescribed medication, provided it is obtained through the legitimate means of a medical practitioner. However, individuals who use illicit drugs for recreational means are at risk of being labelled hedonistic and of becoming a problematic user. Participants most often,

when referring to illegal drugs (and to alcohol if it was prohibited as part of their ethnic custom) described users as uncontrolled and causing disorder, and as such to be 'kept outside of society'. Yet these individuals still live within the same society but only where their views are at odds with conventional values. For instance, in Chapter 5 the Chinese and Indian participants stated that the social construction of drug use and users as deviant is deployed by institutions and individuals with specific interests, ideologies and cultural contexts, all of which evolve over time. Hence while the use of drugs is considered a deviant act by the previous generation, the use of some drugs can be acceptable in context, and acceptable by younger BME groups.

The demonization of drug use, and those who use them is common, and is hardly ethnically specific, however while compared to the dominant Scottish population, described in the recent Scottish social attitudes survey (Hammersley and Dalgarno, 2012a; Ormston et al., 2010; Sharp et al., 2014), participants' in this research stated that the family placed strong restrictions on social activities, in an attempt to prevent children or youngsters from exposure to drugs.

Many of the assumptions regarding the use and patterns of use among BMEs are informed by misguided simplistic discourses by the family, public health and medicalisation of drug use. These create stereotyped perceptions of drugs and drug users as something to be feared and demonised. Furthermore, the luxurious or recreational use of drugs by the

dominant culture in Scotland is considered morally wrong, and youth are protected through condemnation by family elders.

It has been argued in the literature that illicit drug use and problem drug use are not intrinsically health issues (Davies, 2013; Peele, 1985), but rather problems of morality (Szasz, 2003). These assumptions have been challenged theoretically with the argument that the most common patterns of drug use are controlled and without problems (Shewan and Dalgarno, 2005b; Alexander and Brisson, 1994; McPhee, 2012). This tendency to construct risk as a moral issue, results in condemnation of drug users as deviant and legitimises punishment of transgressors (Hammersley, 2008; McPhee, 2012).

With the growth of government regulations that seek to prohibit the possession and supply of non-medical drugs and the criminal justice system concerned with the social and health effects of illicit drugs, immense energy and resources execute control and the persecution of drug takers (Lyman, 2013; Hammersley and Dalgarno, 2012a). Drugs are linked to every conceivable evil and criminal activity in society. The conception of drugs as either licit (medically approved) or illicit (disapproved or illegal to possess) remain as the parameters of the debate. For instance, while an overdose of Paracetamol¹⁶ can be extremely dangerous, it is a drug that is legal, socially sanctioned and readily available and even construed as 'good' due to its pain-relieving properties. On the contrary, opium, which was

¹⁶ Paracetamol is a drug available for purchase over-the-counter throughout the UK, and a commonly used medicine that can help treat pain.

historically used as an analgesic, and even today used to derive morphine, is proscribed (Barton, 2011). Such is the power of medical and legal discourses, that drug users who use controlled drugs¹⁷ are stigmatised, pilloried and criminalised.

The literature review – Chapter 2, explored in some detail the fact that historically, there were few restrictions on harvesting and use of plant-based matter and users were free from physical or moral control (Escohotado, 1999; Barton, 2011). However, with the need for greater social control and to protect individuals from harm, there has been an increase in control of access, sale and use of intoxicants by trade or professional groups (e.g. General Practitioners). In the literature it is apparent that greater emphasis is given to the power of the medical and legal profession by the State in the regulation of intoxicants, thereby undermining the sanctioning power of the family (Room, 2005). Indeed, participants revealed that the cultural values and norms transmitted within the family were exceedingly important in shaping the way in which individuals choose to use or avoid alcohol and drugs (Room, 2005). These cultural-specific social norms are not irretrievable, but rather develop in interaction with other cultures and with political, social and economic factors (Room, 2005).

¹⁷ In the UK, controlled drugs refer to those drugs which are illegal to possess within the confines of the Misuse of Drugs Act 1971. The Act categorises drugs into 3 classifications A-C, with Class A drugs such as cocaine and Heroin considered the most dangerous, and hence greater legal penalties are imposed on offenders.

8.4 The Influence of Religion

The sixth chapter in this thesis presented the participants' beliefs and attitudes concerning the use of AOD in the context of four religions (Christian perspective; Islamic perspective; Perspectives in Hinduism; and Buddhist perspectives) as each have particular relevance in this thesis.

Social theorists cite religion as one of the forces that influences a sense of moral obligation to norms within specific cultural groups (Durkheim, 2012; Turner, 1991a). As developed societies become more secular, this is accompanied by a growing ambivalence in societies towards the importance of religion to regulate morality, which influences abstention from the use of AOD, and therefore avoidance of related problems in specific cultural groupings. This ambivalence has been reformed during each historical period leading to a curious worship of abstinence, which is little practiced and when practiced, seldom respected (Zinberg, 1981; Humphrey and Schmallegger, 2011).

For instance, in Christianity, while pleasure is not inherently 'wrong', it is the corruptive nature of problematic use that is perceived to be inevitably immoral. Hence, religious institutions proscribe the use of intoxicants, only granting permission and legitimacy of use through their authority. This authority can take the form of a Church, Temple, or Mosque etc. Undeniably the notion of 'private' use of intoxication is absent within the confines of religion with greater emphasis being on the 'social' order to encourage conformity than conflict. Individuals are considered to be unequipped with

the capacity to make informed decisions on their own, and hence religion facilitates the management of permissible pleasure and thereby avoids deviance.

Several studies have found an inverse relationship between the perceived importance of religion, and the influences of such beliefs on the use of AOD (Leigh et al., 2005; Luk et al., 2013; DeWall et al., 2014). Put simply, if religion is important to a person's identity, and if this aspect of identity is enhanced in religious terms as maintaining a 'clean' body controlled in their thoughts and behaviour, they are less likely to use AOD.

Participants confirmed normality of the use of alcohol and certain drugs for the facilitation of social interaction, despite religious resistance. Participants' accounts reveal that from a religious perspective pleasure is sinister and immoral, which has the capacity to contaminate personal and social life. It was difficult to ascertain the influence of religion on their use of AOD, since only a few participants (n=11/30) cited drinking only once a month, and even fewer (n=4/30) reported abstinence. However, this reduction in consumption or abstinence was inferred to maturation and greater responsibilities in life and managing a work-life balance than religion. They maintained that drinking occasions were a salient feature of burgeoning youth and less so in adulthood. Furthermore, several participants stated that their family had a greater impact on their decisions to use AOD instead of religion. Of greater significance was the need to maintain the 'reputation' of the family, especially among Pakistani

participants, due to proscriptions in Islam, but equally among African and Chinese participants in upholding the dignity of the family.

Entheogen theory was particularly useful in understanding the use and perception of AOD among Hindu participants. Entheogen theory offers interesting insights into the role of hallucinogens in the development of religion (Miller, 2013). The term entheogen was coined in 1979 by ethnobotanists¹⁸ and literally translates as that which causes God to be within a person, and therefore entheogen refers to the use of drugs for religious and spiritual purposes rather than purely recreational or for pleasure specifically (Wasson et al., 1986). Indeed prior to 1979 Lewin (1932) was the first to study the effects of psychoactive drugs on humans.

Only Indian participants emphasised the role of caste in regulating the use of alcohol. Murthy (2015) defines caste as a social group whose membership is decided at birth. While caste differences are widespread and inconspicuous in Indian societies, it has been the basis for much discussion with respect to alcohol. Carstairs (1954a) gives a good example of caste differences in attitudes and consumption of alcohol in Rajasthan. Caste differences include that between those of Upper Caste (Brahmins), who are against the use of alcohol, and Warrior Caste (Rajputs) and Working Class (Sudras) as well as the untouchables, who could consume meat and alcohol. While the study has been informative of the influences of caste and

¹⁸ Ethnobotanists are those that study the relationships between people and plants.

poverty on use or avoidance of alcohol, subsequent research indicates the impact of such negative stereotyping (Doron, 2010).

As discussed previously in Chapter 2, current religious commitments are a strong predictor of either use or abstinence from AOD (Castro et al., 2014). For instance, Islam proscribes alcohol and opium use, but tobacco, caffeine, and various forms of cannabis are not prohibited, as these were widely used before prohibition was imposed in Islam in the 7th century (Unlu and Sahin, 2015). Islamic scholars apply the general rule of the Quran and forbid use of all intoxicants (Koenig and Shohaib, 2014). However, all Muslim participants in this study acknowledged the use of drugs and rationalised their use to a 'grey area' in Quranic texts, and that as their use was moderate it acted as a signifier that their personal use was non-problematic.

Only Chinese participants acknowledged Buddhism, however no one identified as a being a Buddhist. Buddhist doctrine makes reference to Four Noble Truths which proposes that craving leads to suffering and include: the truth of suffering; the cause of suffering - craving; the cessation of suffering - Nirvana; and the Eightfold path which is achieved from cessation of suffering (Groves and Farmer, 1994, Woodward, 2005). The precepts of Buddhism describe it as virtuous to abstain from intoxicants (Tachibana, 1992). However, participants indicated that familial norms and upholding the honour of the family were of greater importance than religion when they exercised agency in choosing to use alcohol or drugs.

8.5 Gendered Use of Alcohol

The seventh chapter in this thesis presented participants' accounts of how constructs of masculinity and femininity act to signify what is and is not permissible in terms of sex and gender. This chapter draws on Butler's (1990) poststructuralist notion that gender is performative in relation to alcohol use. Butler states that masculinity and femininity are concepts that are continuously (re)created within culture through the repetition of artificial acts. Hence, gender and sex are perceived as being socially manipulated and internalised depending on the context, rather than natural identities governed by biological conditions. She clarifies that the notion of performativity is a non-voluntary character, as gendered practices and identities are shaped not simply through biological determinism but through regulatory discourses producing unconscious compliance with cultural norms than emerging from biological origins (Butler, 1993; Holmes, 2007; Butler, 2011).

Social constructionist perspectives of gender focus on 'hegemonic masculinity' and 'emphasised femininity' which are considered crucial in the understanding of male and female use of alcohol and tobacco (Connell and Connell, 2005; Allen, 2007; Connell, 2014). This perspective suggests that culturally masculine practices serve to maintain patriarchy, including behaviours such as devaluation of help-seeking when ill, thereby producing dominant forms of 'toxic' masculine behaviour. Similarly, the concept of emphasised femininity by Connell (1987) refers to the subordination of women to masculine ideals of femininity. While such concepts are the

preferred norm in relation to gendered behaviour, these are not compulsory, as individuals often display behaviours that exceed and contravene traditional social norms.

Such differences deviate based on individual perceptions on whether they consider gender to be something that is 'done' to people or something they 'do' to people, within the constraints of that society (Holmes, 2007). As such, individuals learn from a very young age how girls and boys should behave within their community (e.g. family, schools), and this shapes their understanding of how to enact masculine and feminine traits. Paechter (2007) contends that schools are gendered institutions as students' behaviours are routinely distinguished and segregated by gender. Likewise, cultural requirements either permit or forbid the consumption of alcohol, as well as what is 'correct' for men and women, with greater permissiveness for men to drink and less so for women.

Participant data reveals hegemonic gender identities regarding alcohol use and smoking, and how this represents 'ideal' but not necessarily actual masculine and feminine traits in their culture. For instance, women who drink too much or are visibly drunk in public are subject to moral condemnation among Chinese and African participants. However, the African participants described ways in which certain practices allow public deviance, through 'intentional dissimulation' of the use of alcohol.

The social norms within ethnic groups in this study revealed that smoking among women was highly stigmatised among African, Indian, Pakistani and

Chinese communities, this appears to occur for several reasons. A perception that tobacco is a male oriented behaviour, and women who exhibit the use of alcohol denigrate or defeminise all women, and as such must become compliant to conform to ideals of feminine behaviour. There was also a belief, perhaps due to how tobacco has been advertised in third world countries as enhancing sexual appeal, that use of tobacco signifies sexual availability, and hence it is denigrated.

The female participants demonstrated acute awareness of how their actions as drinker, smoker, or drug user put them at great risk of transgressing normative feminine behaviour and at risk of being shamed and condemned when such rules are breached.

Common expressions of gender differences have also been captured in the literature and include for instance - that women should not drink as they are more sensitive and risk behaving immorally, while men being more prone to natural urges cannot do otherwise. In such a world view, men are considered to be methodical and orderly (rational and logical), while women are potential sources of disorder (emotional, and irrational) are more at risk of disorderly (masculine) behaviour (McDonald, 1994; Dietler, 2006). Elements of such discourses construct a delineation of qualities between men and women and are also well documented in anthropological studies cross-culturally (Ardener, 2006; Hunt and Barker, 2001; Hunt et al., 2007). While men can choose to blame women for their impropriety, women are perceived to reshape their responsibilities to enmesh their dual role of wife

and mother and re-construct aspects of femininity to symbolise concern and sophistication as well as be part of the mechanism that perpetuates or at least risk perpetuating, social discrimination (McDonald, 1994; Dietler, 2006).

These expectations are a consequence of social context, and in actively seeking to engage in the transgression of these norms, men and women reveal how and in what way gendered expectations powerfully act to regulate conduct. The Indian participants' accounts reveal that, the process of alcohol enculturation was a contributing factor in normalising the use of alcohol to acculturate to perceived norms of Scottish culture. While abstinence and the practice of moderation are essential features of femininity in India, participants demonstrate that this is not essential in Scotland. However, men's drinking including excessive drinking and drug use is overlooked and often accepted. Pakistani participants describe severe consequences that females' risk if they transgress socially accepted familial, or gendered expectations. For instance, females who are considered as transgressive of cultural norms were considered to be underserving of a suitable partner which in addition could put at risk the honour of the family, and their community. A female Pakistani in this study describes how she had to conceal her use as well as invent separate identities to co-exist with family and Scottish peers. Concealing use may stem from fear of punishment or disapproval from family (Denscombe, 1995). This is because abstinence is considered a necessary mode of

acceptable behaviour and being in control is perceived as equating to socioeconomic success.

It is important to note that each participant in this research experiences norms differently depending on how their identities have been shaped within their unique environment, and their personal perception of the rules governing drinking and drunken comportment. Furthermore, female participants' awareness of how their actions as drinkers, smokers, or drug users and their transgressing normative feminine behaviours put them at risk of shame and condemnation if rules are breached. These expectations are a consequence of social context, and in actively seeking to engage in the transgression of these norms, men and women reveal how and in what way gendered expectations powerfully act on conduct.

In contemporary drinking culture, women are subject to stigma and moral condemnation which are reinforced through expectations around female behaviour in private and public spaces (Caetano et al., 1998; Okin, 2013). As Goffman (1963) notes, a woman who is visibly stigmatised can suffer special indignity because of her drinking, thereby disqualifying her from social acceptance by both sexes. However, men's drinking including excessive drinking is overlooked and accommodated (Mullen et al., 2007; Iwamoto et al., 2011). For men, drinking invokes pleasure, and the primary role of women is to serve male desires (Rúðólfsdóttir and Morgan, 2009).

Intersectionality theory offers some insights into the gender expressions of AOD use among the participants in this research as well as the intersections

of their social identity categories. However, intersectionality fails to recognise the diversity of ideas, and is useful in describing how individuals conform to group identities depending on context. It cannot be said to represent the identities of participants in this thesis. Participants in this thesis did not perceive themselves to be victims of racism or marginalisation, rather in the exercise of agency in the choices they made, in context, presents them as active subjects making informed decisions in their use of AOD.

Finally, Chapter 7 also illustrated how participants have changed their use of alcohol and their smoking habits as a result of maturing and adopting adult traits associated with marriage, looking after children, and in pursuit of a career. Research has indicated that younger more than older individuals tend to seek sensation and approval as well as engaging in as excessive drinking (Wilsnack and Wilsnack, 1997; Robinson and Harris, 2011).

An influential article by Winick (1962) conducted from a quantitative analysis of a large number of records of the Federal Bureau of Narcotics in the United States (US), resulted in the origination of the 'Maturing Out' thesis. Winick concluded on the basis of his research that, most addicts became abstinent between the ages of 23 and 37. He hypothesised that this was the result of a process which he referred to as "maturing out" since the problems which had originally been critical for individuals turning to drugs and becoming addicted had somehow become less salient and less

urgent. More recent evidence also supports Winick's theory in relation to problematic alcohol use, in that there is a tendency for consumption to increase through late adolescence, peaks in early 20s, and subsides as the individual ages (Dawson et al., 2005; Fillmore, 1988; Johnson et al., 2007; Christo, 1998; Donovan and Costa, 1994; Bachman et al., 2014; Abudabbeh et al., 2003).

8.6 Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the main research findings by focusing on the four data chapters which covered perceptions of alcohol and drug use and how religion and gender influence norms around use of alcohol and some drugs. Summaries of each data chapter were presented along with a discussion of the overarching themes. The next chapter will also discuss the limitations of this research and provide recommendations for future research.

9 Conclusion

This chapter presents the limitations of this research and suggests recommendations for future research. In particular, this research adds to the knowledge and understanding of the social and cultural context of alcohol use and some drugs among BME individuals in the West of Scotland.

This was accomplished through three objectives:

1. Identifying a hidden group of non-treatment seeking individuals from BME populations.
2. To examine how the use of alcohol and drugs influenced how BME's managed their personal and social identity.
3. To explore how cultural norms and values influenced the use or avoidance of alcohol and drugs by BME's in relation to age, gender, religious observance, and generational differences.

Patterns of AOD use were established from the demographic survey tool that was administered, as well as through the interview processes. In particular, the researcher's use of in-depth semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher to gathering this information by building rapport in an unthreatening manner.

The literature review demonstrated that while some research has been conducted among BMEs in the UK, the focus has primarily been on problem groups using quantitative methods that utilise inaccurate and incorrect categorisation of ethnicity often conflated with religion or geographical region of origin. Furthermore, the majority of the studies only focused on male use of AOD.

This thesis makes an original contribution to the limited research on BME individuals' use of illicit drugs in the West of Scotland, through in-depth qualitative interviews with 30 participants who reported the use of alcohol and other drugs. These BME individuals from South Indian (Kerala and Bengaluru), African (Nigeria, Zambia and Ghana), Chinese, Pakistani and mixed backgrounds in the West of Scotland revealed how they manage identities that are hidden from their Scottish friends, as well as aspects of their behaviour and beliefs that they hide from their family. It is this conflict and hidden nature that is revealed through participants' personal perceptions of the use of alcohol and some drugs, and within their family and culture. As such, the findings from this study differ from that of existing research.

Although controversial it must be acknowledged that individuals take drugs for pleasure, as well as to assert aspects of their identity within social groups. When drugs are used in a meaningful fashion, often constrained by group, societal or familial norms and expectations, it fortifies group identity. Research on the use of drugs has largely focused on the risks and problematic use, with little attention on pleasurable or non-problematic use.

Despite the lack of coherence in theological literature on the typical nature of the use and abstinence from AOD, some wide-ranging conclusions can be drawn from the participants in this research. Although the use of alcohol and drugs has been prevalent among some religious groups since historic

times, some religious doctrines promote the philosophy that abstinence from some types of drugs (used by other religious groups) acts as a signifier of their religious devotion and practice. Participants in this research confirm normalcy of the use of AOD for the facilitation of social interaction, despite the risk of religious sanction. Indeed, the legitimisation of pleasure in religion, can be regarded as a crusade between the secular and the sacred.

This thesis adds to the knowledge and understanding of the context of alcohol use among BME individuals in the West of Scotland. The prevailing literature gives greater emphasis to those in treatment and considers deprivation and educational attainment as indicators for illicit drug use. This research contradicts this as the BME participants in this research were ambitious and highly educated and were greatly assimilated with Scottish culture.

9.1 Limitations

This section reflects on the research process and addresses some of its limitations.

It is recognised that the findings of this small study (n=30) cannot present a comprehensive picture of the extent of alcohol use among BME individuals in the West of Scotland, and hence limits the possibility of generalising the findings to the wider population. As such, caution must be used when drawing conclusions from the findings of this research to the broader BME groups living in the West of Scotland. However, it must be noted that

generalisation of the findings was not the intention of this research, as the views presented are those of a hidden population and is deeply subjective.

While every attempt was made to recruit an equal number of male and female participants, this could not be achieved. This is primarily because females from BME backgrounds face greater stigmatisation than the general population, resulting in reluctance to be included in research studies. Nevertheless, the females who participated in this research did not present themselves as less powerful than males. The researcher was also further limited with time and financial constraints, which would have enabled access to more key informants.

Given the sensitive nature of the research topic, participants were unwilling to take part in sessions where their identity could be revealed/exposed. Hence, it was not possible to conduct focus groups. Furthermore, perceptions of the use of alcohol and some drugs and the associated stigma varied by each ethnic group. In this research, there was a greater concentration of participants from South India and fewer from African, Chinese and Mixed backgrounds. A larger sample with individuals from the same ethnic group would allow for greater insights into the prevalence of alcohol and drugs use.

Most participants in this study were middle-aged from middle class/professional backgrounds. Enculturation for one social grouping may be different from another on the basis of their social status in Scotland. A similarly diverse group of individuals whose occupation and education

attainment were different may yield different responses. Despite some of the limitations of this study, the findings highlight important implications for practice and recommendations for future research.

9.2 Recommendations & Future Research

It is necessary to conduct further research to explore the significance of the findings of this research. The findings of this research have practical implications for professionals working with individuals from BME backgrounds, in particular those in the health and addictions field. Some recommendations include:

- Services need to consider the impact of enculturation on individuals as this can help with understanding BME beliefs about alcohol and drug use, and the conflict BME individuals face in managing dissimilar cultures.
- Researchers that possess an understanding of BME religious beliefs and attitudes towards alcohol and drugs could provide useful insights into why consumption is hidden and stigmatised, and hence problematic.
- Future research could investigate the influence of culture on first, second and third generations of BME groups, as these would give greater insights into the effects of enculturation.
- Migration has resulted in newer ethnic groups with little information on their patterns and motivations for alcohol and drug use. While this research included a higher number of participants from Kerala, additional research is required to understand generational differences, and include a younger cohort to allow for a meaningful comparison of transition to adulthood and maturation.
- Future research employing mixed methodology is also advocated.

References

- ABBOTTS, J., WILLIAMS, R. & FORD, G., 2001. Morbidity and Irish Catholic descent in Britain. Relating health disadvantage to socio-economic position. *Social Science & Medicine*, 52(7), pp. 999-1005.
- ABDULRAHIM, D., 2005. Power, culture and the 'hard to reach': The marginalisation of minority ethnic populations from HIV prevention and harm minimisation. In *Meddling with Mythology* (pp.54-70). Routledge.
- ABEL, G. M. & PLUMRIDGE, E. W., 2004. Network 'norms' or 'styles' of 'drunken comportment'? *Health Education Research*, 19(5), pp. 492-500.
- ABUDABBEH, N., HAMID, A. & STRAUSSNER, S., 2001. Substance use among Arabs and Arab Americans. *Ethnocultural factors in substance abuse treatment*, pp. 275-290.
- ACTION ON SMOKING AND HEALTH 2011. Tobacco and ethnic minorities. *Facts Sheet*. September ed.
- ADLER, F. & LAUFER, W. S., 1995. *The Legacy of Anomie Theory*. New Brunswick, NJ: Transaction Publishers.
- AHMAD, W. I. & BRADBY, H., 2007. Locating ethnicity and health: exploring concepts and contexts. *Sociology of health & illness*, 29(6), pp.795-810.
- AKERS, R., 2017. *Social learning and social structure: A general theory of crime and deviance*. Routledge.
- AKERS, R. L., 1996. Is differential association/social learning cultural deviance theory? *Criminology*, 34(2), pp. 229-247.
- AKERS, R.L. & JENSEN, G.F. eds., 2011. Social learning theory and the explanation of crime. *Advances in Criminological Theory*, (Vol. 1). Transaction Publishers.
- AKINS, S. & MOSHER, C. J., 2015. Drug Use as Deviance. *The Handbook of Deviance*, pp. 349-68.
- ALCOHOL CONCERN 2003. Alcohol drinking among black and minority ethnic communities (BME) in the United Kingdom. *Alcohol Concern's Quarterly Information and Research Bulletin*.
- ALDANA, B. U. & QUINTERO, M. A., 2008. A comparison of three methods for sampling hard-to-reach or hidden populations. *Pensamiento Psicológico*, 4(10), pp.167-176.
- ALDRIDGE, J., MEASHAM, F. & WILLIAMS, L., 2013. *Illegal leisure revisited: Changing patterns of alcohol and drug use in adolescents and young adults*, Routledge.
- ALEXANDER, B., 1994. Do heroin and cocaine cause addiction? In P. Brisson (Ed.), *L'usage des Drogues et la Toxicomanie* (Vol. 2). Montreal: Gaétin Mouin.
- ALHOJAILAN, M. I., 2012. Thematic analysis: A critical review of its process and evaluation. *West East Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), pp. 39-47.
- ALLEN, L., 2007. "Sensitive and Real Macho All at the Same Time" Young

- Heterosexual Men and Romance. *Men and Masculinities*, 10(2), pp. 137-152.
- ALLPORT, G. W., 1963. Behavioral science, religion, and mental health. *Journal of Religion and Health*, Vol. 2(3), pp. 187-197.
- ALVIN, R. and SHEPSLE, K.A., 1972. Politics in Plural Societies: A Theory of Democratic Instability. Pp. vii, 232. *Columbus, Ohio: Charles Merrill*.
- AMEY, C. H., ALBRECHT, S. L. & MILLER, M. K., 1996. Racial differences in adolescent drug use: the impact of religion. *Substance use & misuse*, 31(10), pp.1311-1332.
- ANDREWS, J. A., TILDESLEY, E., HOPS, H. & LI, F. Z., 2002. The influence of peers on young adult substance use. *Health Psychology*, 21(4), p. 349.
- ARDENER, E., 2006. Belief and the Problem of Women and the 'Problem'Revisited. *Feminist anthropology: A reader*, pp. 47-65.
- ARORA, R. & KHATUN, A., 1998. No to Nasha: Drugs, alcohol and tobacco use in the Bradford's Asian community. *Race Relations Research Unit, Bradford*.
- ATKINSON, R. & FLINT, J., 2001. Accessing hidden and hard-to-reach populations: Snowball research strategies. *Social research update*, 33(1), pp. 1-4.
- BABOR, T., CAETANO, R., CASSWELL, S., EDWARDS, G., GIESBRECHT, N., GRAHAM, K., GRUBE, J., HILL, L., HOLDER, H., HOMEL, R. and LIVINGSTON, M., 2010. Alcohol: No Ordinary Commodity—a summary of the second edition. *Addiction*, 105(5), pp.769-779.
- BACHMAN, J. G., O'MALLEY, P. M., SCHULENBERG, J. E., JOHNSTON, L. D., BRYANT, A. L. & MERLINE, A. C., 2014. *The decline of substance use in young adulthood: Changes in social activities, roles, and beliefs*. Psychology Press.
- BALES, R. F., 1946. Cultural differences in rates of alcoholism. *Quarterly Journal of Studies on Alcohol*, 6(4), pp. 480-99.
- BANDURA, A., 2001. Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), pp.1-26.
- BANDURA, A. and WALTERS, R.H., 1977. *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-hall.
- BARNES, G. M., REIFMAN, A. S., FARRELL, M. P. & DINTCHEFF, B. A., 2000. The effects of parenting on the development of adolescent alcohol misuse: a Six-Wave latent growth model. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 62(1), pp. 175-186.
- BARROWS, S., and ROOM, R. eds., 1991. *Drinking: Behavior and belief in modern history*. Univ of California Press.
- BARRY, A. E., KING, J., SEARS, C., HARVILLE, C., BONDOC, I. & JOSEPH, K., 2016. Prioritizing Alcohol Prevention: Establishing Alcohol as the Gateway Drug and Linking Age of First Drink with Illicit Drug Use. *Journal of School Health*, 86(1), pp. 31-38.
- BARTH, F., 1998. *Ethnic groups and boundaries: The social organization of culture difference*, Waveland Press.

- BARTLETT, F. C., 1923. *Psychology and primitive culture*. University Press.
- BARTON, A., 2011. *Illicit drugs: use and control*, Routledge.
- BASHFORD, J., BUFFIN, J. and PATEL, K., 2003. *Community Engagement, Report 2: The Findings*. Preston: The Centre for Ethnicity and Health. [http://www.uclan.ac.uk/schools/school_of_social_work/files/Report_2_The_Findings.pdf] [Date Accessed: 09/04/2016].
- BAUMANN, G., 1997. Dominant and demotic discourses of culture: their relevance to multi-ethnic alliances. *Debating Cultural Hybridity: Multi-Cultural Identities and the Politics of Racism*, pp.209-225.
- BAYLEY, M. & HURCOMBE, R., 2011. Drinking patterns and alcohol service provision for different ethnic groups in the UK: a review of the literature. *Ethnicity and Inequalities in Health and Social Care*, 3(4), pp. 6-17.
- BAZELEY, P. & JACKSON, K. eds., 2013. *Qualitative data analysis with NVivo*, Sage Publications Limited.
- BECARES, L., NAZROO, J. & STAFFORD, M., 2011. The ethnic density effect on alcohol use among ethnic minority people in the UK. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 65(1), pp. 20-25.
- BECKER, H. S., 1953. Becoming a Marijuana User. *American Journal of Sociology*, 59(3), pp. 235-242.
- BECKER, Howard S. 1963. *Outsiders: Studies in the Sociology of Deviance*. New York, Macmillan.
- BECKER, H. S., 2008. *Outsiders*, Simon and Schuster.
- BEDDOES, D., SHEIKH, S., KHANNA, M. & FRANCIS, R., 2010. The impact of drugs on different minority groups: a review of the UK literature. *London: The UK Drug Policy Commission (UKDPC)*.
- BEEGHLEY, L., BOCK, E.W. & COCHRAN, J.K., 1990, June. Religious change and alcohol use: An application of reference group and socialization theory. In *Sociological Forum* (Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 261-278). Kluwer Academic Publishers-Plenum Publishers.
- BENTLEY, G. C., 1987. Ethnicity and Practice. *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 29(1), pp. 24-55.
- BENTON, S. A., 2009. *Understanding the high-functioning alcoholic: Professional views and personal insights*. Greenwood Publishing Group.
- BERNARD, H. R., 2017. *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*, Rowman & Littlefield.
- BERRIDGE, V., 1978. Victorian opium eating: responses to opiate use in nineteenth-century England. *Victorian Studies*, 21(4), pp. 437-461.
- BERRY, J. W., 1970. Marginality, Stress and Ethnic Identification in an Acculturated Aboriginal Community. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 1(3), pp. 239-252.
- BERRY, J. W., 1997. Immigration, acculturation, and adaptation. *Applied Psychology*, 46(1), pp. 5-34.
- BERRY, J. W., 2003. *Conceptual approaches to acculturation*, American Psychological Association.
- BERRY, J. W., 2005. *Acculturation: Living successfully in two cultures*.

- International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 29(6), 697-712.
- BHOPAL, K., 2010, May. Gender, identity and experience: Researching marginalised groups. In *Women's Studies International Forum* Vol. 33(3), pp. 188-195. Pergamon.
- BHOPAL, K. and DEUCHAR, R. eds., 2015. *Researching Marginalized Groups*. Routledge.
- BHOPAL, R., VETTINI, A., HUNT, S., WIEBE, S., HANNA, L. & AMOS, A., 2012. Review of prevalence data in, and evaluation of methods for cross cultural adaptation of, UK surveys on tobacco and alcohol in ethnic minority groups. *BMJ*, 328(7431), p. 76.
- BLUM, R. H. & BLUM, E. M., 1969. A cultural case study. *Drugs*, 1, pp. 188-227.
- BLUM, R. W., BEUHRING, T., SHEW, M. L., BEARINGER, L. H., SIEVING, R. E. & RESNICK, M. D., 2000. The effects of race/ethnicity, income, and family structure on adolescent risk behaviors. *American journal of public health*, 90(12), p.1879.
- BOAG-MUNROE, G. & EVANGELOU, M., 2012. From hard to reach to how to reach: A systematic review of the literature on hard-to-reach families. *Research Papers in Education*, 27(2), pp. 209-239.
- BOARDMAN, J. D., FINCH, B. K., ELLISON, C. G., WILLIAMS, D. R. & JACKSON, J. S., 2001. Neighborhood disadvantage, stress, and drug use among adults. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 42(2), pp.151-165.
- BOIGER, M., DE DEYNE, S. & MESQUITA, B., 2013. Emotions in "the world": cultural practices, products, and meanings of anger and shame in two individualist cultures. *Frontiers in psychology*, 4, p. 867.
- BONIFACE, S., KNEALE, J. & SHELTON, N., 2014. Drinking pattern is more strongly associated with under-reporting of alcohol consumption than socio-demographic factors: evidence from a mixed-methods study. *BMC Public Health*, 14(1), p. 1297.
- BORSARI, B. & CAREY, K. B., 2001. Peer influences on college drinking: a review of the research. *Journal of substance abuse*, 13(4), pp.391-424.
- BOURDIEU, P. & PASSERON, J.C., 1977. Reproduction in education, culture and society. Accessed via Google Scholar: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Reproduction+in+education%2C+culture+and+society.+&btnG= [Date Accessed: 12/10/2016].
- BOWLEG, L., 2012. The problem with the phrase women and minorities: intersectionality—an important theoretical framework for public health. *American journal of public health*, 102(7), pp. 1267-1273.
- BOYATZIS, R. E., 1998. *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. Sage.
- BRADBY, H., 2007. Watch out for the Aunties! Young British Asians' accounts of identity and substance use. *Sociology of health & illness*, 29(5), pp. 656-672.
- BRADBY, H. & WILLIAMS, R., 2006. Is religion or culture the key feature in

- changes in substance use after leaving school? Young Punjabis and a comparison group in Glasgow. *Ethnicity and Health*, 11(3), pp. 307-24.
- BRAUN, V. & CLARKE, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77-101.
- BRIERLEY-JONES, L., LING, J., MCCABE, K. E., WILSON, G. B., CROSLAND, A., KANER, E. F. & HAIGHTON, C. A., 2014. Habitus of home and traditional drinking: a qualitative analysis of reported middle-class alcohol use. *Sociology of health & illness*, 36(7), pp. 1054-1076.
- BRINGER, J. D., JOHNSTON, L. H. & BRACKENRIDGE, C. H., 2006. Using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software to develop a grounded theory project. *Field Methods*, 18(3), pp. 245-266.
- BRUNER, J., 1985. Vygotsky: A historical and conceptual perspective. *Culture, communication, and cognition: Vygotskian perspectives*, 21, p. 34.
- BRYMAN, A., 1984. The debate about quantitative and qualitative research: a question of method or epistemology?. *British journal of Sociology*, pp.75-92.
- BUCHANAN, J., 2008. Understanding and engaging with problematic substance use. *Addressing Offending Behaviour: Context, Practice and Values*, pp. 246-264.
- BULMER, M., 1991. The ethnic group question in the 1991 Census of Population. *Ethnicity in the*, pp. 33-62.
- BURR, V., 2015. *Social constructionism*, Routledge.
- BUTLER, J., 1990. Gender trouble, feminist theory, and psychoanalytic discourse. *Feminism/postmodernism*, 327, p.x.
- BUTLER, J., 1993. Bodies That Matter: On the Discursive Limits of "Sex.". *New York: Routledge*.
- BUTLER, J., 2011. *Gender trouble: Feminism and the subversion of identity*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- CAETANO, R., CLARK, C. L. & TAM, T., 1998. Alcohol consumption among racial/ethnic minorities. *Alcohol Health & Research World*, 22(4), pp. 233-241.
- CAMERON, D., MANIK, G., BIRD, R. & SINORWALIA, A., 2002. What may we be learning from so-called spontaneous remission in ethnic minorities? *Addiction Research & Theory*, 10(2), pp. 175-182.
- CAMPBELL, D. T., 1955. The Informant in Quantitative Research. *American Journal of Sociology*, 60(4), pp. 339-342.
- CARSTAIRS, G. M., 1954. Daru and bhang; cultural factors in the choice of intoxicant. *Quarterly Journal of Studies on Alcohol*, 15(2), pp. 220-237.
- CASPER, M. F., CHILD, J. T., GILMOUR, D., MCINTYRE, K. A. & PEARSON, J. C., 2006. Healthy research perspectives: incorporating college student experiences with alcohol. *Health Communication*, 20(3), pp. 289-98.
- CASTRO, F. G., BARRERA, M., MENA, L. A. & AGUIRRE, K. M., 2014. Culture and Alcohol Use: Historical and Sociocultural Themes From 75 Years

- of Alcohol Research. *Journal of Studies on Alcohol and Drugs, Supplement*, (s17), pp. 36-49.
- CHARMAZ, K., 2014. *Constructing grounded theory*, Sage.
- CHAUDRY, M., SHERLOCK, K. & PATEL, K., 1997. Drugs and ethnic health project: Oldham and Tameside. Manchester: Lifeline/Preston: University of Central Lancashire.
- CHRISTENSEN, V. T. & CARPIANO, R. M., 2014. Social class differences in BMI among Danish women: applying Cockerham's health lifestyles approach and Bourdieu's theory of lifestyle. *Social science & medicine*, 112, pp. 12-21.
- CHRISTO, G., 1998. A review of reasons for using or not using drugs: Commonalities between sociological and clinical perspectives. *Drugs: Education, Prevention, and Policy*, 5(1), pp. 59-72.
- CHUN, K. M., BALLS ORGANISTA, P. E. & MARIN, G. E., 2003. *Acculturation: Advances in theory, measurement, and applied research*. American Psychological Association.
- CLARKE, V. & BRAUN, V., 2015. Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The psychologist*, 26(2), pp. 120-123.
- CLOWARD, R.A. & OHLIN, L.E., 2015. Differential Opportunity Theory Delinquency and Opportunity. In *Criminology Theory* (pp. 159-172). Routledge.
- CLOWARD, R. A., 1959. Illegitimate Means, Anomie, and Deviant-Behavior. *American Sociological Review*, pp. 164-176.
- COCHRANE, R. & BAL, S., 1990. The drinking habits of Sikh, Hindu, Muslim and white men in the West Midlands: a community survey. *British journal of addiction*, 85(6), pp. 759-69.
- COHEN, A., 2012. *Introduction: Discriminating relations: Identity, boundary and authenticity*. In *Signifying Identities* (pp. 9-22). Routledge.
- COHEN, A., 2014. *Urban ethnicity*, Routledge.
- COHEN, A. K. & SHORT, J. F., 1958. Research in Delinquent Subcultures. *Journal of Social Issues*, 14(3), pp. 20-37.
- COHEN, A. Y., 1971. The journey beyond trips: Alternatives to drugs. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 3(2), pp. 16-21.
- COHEN, E., 2002. *The Athenian Nation*, Princeton University Press.
- COHEN, H., 1972. Multiple drug use considered in the light of the stepping-stone hypothesis. *International Journal of the Addictions*, 7(1), pp. 27-55.
- COHEN, J., COLLINS, R., DARKES, J. & GWARTNEY, D., 2007. A league of their own: demographics, motivations and patterns of use of 1,955 male adult non-medical anabolic steroid users in the United States. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*, 4(1), p. 12.
- COHEN, L., MANION, L. & MORRISON, K., 2013. Action Research. In *Research methods in education* (pp. 368-385). Routledge.
- COLE, E. R., 2009. Intersectionality and research in psychology. *American psychologist*, 64(3), p. 170.

- COLLECTIVE, C. R., 1977. 'A Black Feminist Statement' (pp. 210-218). na.
- COLLINS, P. H., 1990. Black feminist thought in the matrix of domination. *Black feminist thought: Knowledge, consciousness, and the politics of empowerment*, 138, pp.221-238.
- COMAROFF, J. L., 1987. Of totemism and ethnicity: consciousness, practice and the signs of inequality. *Ethnos*, 52(3-4), pp. 301-323.
- CONNEL, R. W., 1987. Gender and power: Society, The Person and Sexual Politics. *Polity, Cambridge*, pp. 5-334.
- CONNELL, R. W., 2013. *Gender and power: Society, the person and sexual politics*, John Wiley & Sons.
- CONNELL, R. W., 2005. *Masculinities*. Polity.
- COOMBER, R., MCEL RATH, K., MEASHAM, F. & MOORE, K., 2013. *Key concepts in drugs and society*, Sage.
- COOMBER, R. & SOUTH, N., 2004. *Drug Use and Cultural Context'Beyond the West': Tradition, Change and Post-Colonialism*. London, Free Association Books.
- CORCORAN, C., GERSON, R., SILLS-SHAHAR, R., NICKOU, C., MCGLASHAN, T., MALASPINA, D. & DAVIDSON, L., 2007. Trajectory to a first episode of psychosis: a qualitative research study with families. *Early Intervention in Psychiatry*, 1(4), pp. 308-315.
- COTTEW, G. & OYEFESO, A., 2005. Illicit drug use among Bangladeshi women living in the United Kingdom: An exploratory qualitative study of a hidden population in East London. *Drugs-Education Prevention and Policy*, 12(3), pp. 171-188.
- CRABTREE, B. F. & MILLER, W. L. eds., 1999. *Doing qualitative research*. Sage publications.
- CRAWFORD, N. D., BORRELL, L. N., GALEA, S., FORD, C., LATKIN, C. & FULLER, C. M., 2013. The influence of neighborhood characteristics on the relationship between discrimination and increased drug-using social ties among illicit drug users. *Journal of Community Health*, 38(2), pp. 328-37.
- CRENSHAW, K., 1989. Demarginalizing the intersection of race and sex: A black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, feminist theory and antiracist politics. *The University of Chicago Legal Forum*. 1989.
- CRESWELL, J. W., 2017. *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- CROTTY, M., 2012. *The foundations of social research: meaning and perspective in the research process*. Sage.
- CUADRAZ, G. H. & UTTAL, L., 1999. Intersectionality and in-depth interviews: Methodological strategies for analyzing race, class, and gender. *Race, Gender & Class*, pp. 156-186.
- CURRIE, E., 1994. *Reckoning: Drugs, the cities, and the American future*. Hill and Wang.
- DANKO, G. P., JOHNSON, R. C., NAGOSHI, C. T., YUEN, S. H., GIDLEY, J. E. & AHN, M., 1988. Judgments of "normal" and "problem" alcohol use as related to reported alcohol consumption. *Alcoholism: Clinical and Experimental Research*, 12(6), pp. 760-768.

- DAR, K., CHAUDHRY, Z. A., MIRZA, I. & ALAM, F., 2002. Ethnicity, patterns of substance misuse and criminality: a comparative study of White and Asian patient populations in West London. *Journal of Substance Use*, 7(4), pp. 244-250.
- DARLINGTON, F., NORMAN, P., BALLAS, D. & EXETER, D. J., 2015. Exploring ethnic inequalities in health: evidence from the Health Survey for England, 1998-2011. *Diversity & Equality in Health and Care*, 12(2), pp. 54-65.
- DAVENPORT-HINES, R., 2003. *The pursuit of oblivion: A global history of narcotics*, WW Norton & Company.
- DAVENPORT-HINES, R., 2012. *The pursuit of oblivion: a social history of drugs*, Hachette UK.
- DAVIES, J. B., 2013. *Myth of Addiction*, Routledge.
- DAWSON, D. A., GRANT, B. F., STINSON, F. S. & CHOU, P. S., 2005. Psychopathology associated with drinking and alcohol use disorders in the college and general adult populations. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*, 77(2), pp. 139-50.
- DE KOCK, C., DECORTE, T., VANDERPLASSCHEN, W., DERLUYN, I. & SACCO, M., 2017. Studying ethnicity, problem substance use and treatment: From epidemiology to social change. *Drugs: education, prevention and policy*, 24(3), pp. 230-239.
- DE VOS, G. & ROMANUCCI-ROSS, L., 1975. Ethnicity: Vessel of Meaning and Emblem of Contrast. *Ethnic Identity: Cultural Continuities and Change*, pp. 363-390.
- DEAKIN, H. & WAKEFIELD, K., 2013. Skype interviewing: Reflections of two PhD researchers. *Qualitative Research*, 14(5), pp. 603-616.
- DECORTE, T. & FOUNTAIN, J., 2010. *Pleasure, pain and profit: European perspectives on drugs*. Lengerich, Germany, Pabst Science Publishers.
- DEGENHARDT, L., CHIU, W. T., SAMPSON, N., KESSLER, R. C. & ANTHONY, J. C., 2007. Epidemiological patterns of extra-medical drug use in the United States: evidence from the National Comorbidity Survey Replication, 2001-2003. *Drug and alcohol dependence*, 90(2-3), pp. 210-223.
- DELORME, D. E., SINKHAN, G. M. & FRENCH, W., 2001. Ethics and the Internet issues associated with qualitative research. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 33(4), pp. 271-286.
- DEMANT, J. & JARVINEN, M., 2011. Social capital as norms and resources: Focus groups discussing alcohol. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 19(2), pp. 91-101.
- DENSCOMBE, M., 1995. Ethnic group and alcohol consumption: the case of 15-16-year-olds in Leicestershire. *Public health*, 109(2), pp. 133-142.
- DENSCOMBE, M. & DRUCQUER, N., 2000. Diversity within ethnic groups: alcohol and tobacco consumption by young people in the East Midlands. *Health Education Journal*, 59(4), pp. 340-350.
- DENZIN, N. K. & LINCOLN, Y. S. eds., 2011. *The SAGE handbook of*

- qualitative research*, Sage.
- DESPRES, L. A. & SMITH, M. G., 1967. *Cultural pluralism and nationalist politics in British Guiana* (Vol. 4). Chicago, Rand McNally.
- DEWALL, C. N., POND, R. S., CARTER, E. C., MCCULLOUGH, M. E., LAMBERT, N. M., FINCHAM, F. D. & NEZLEK, J. B., 2014. Explaining the relationship between religiousness and substance use: self-control matters. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 107(2), p.339.
- DIETLER, M., 2006. Alcohol: Anthropological/archaeological perspectives. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 35, pp. 229-249.
- DILTHEY, W., 1977. The understanding of other persons and their expressions of life. *Descriptive psychology and historical understanding* (pp. 121-144). Springer, Dordrecht.
- DONOVAN, J. E., 2004. Adolescent alcohol initiation: a review of psychosocial risk factors. *Journal of adolescent health*, 35(6), pp. 529-e7.
- DONOVAN, J. E., JESSOR, R. & COSTA, F. M., 1994. *Beyond adolescence: Problem behaviour and young adult development*, Cambridge University Press.
- DORON, A., 2010. The intoxicated poor: alcohol, morality and power among the boatmen of Banaras. *South Asian History and Culture*, 1(2), pp. 282-300.
- DOUDS, A. C., COX, M. A., IQBAL, T. H. & COOPER, B. T., 2003. Ethnic differences in cirrhosis of the liver in a British city: alcoholic cirrhosis in South Asian men. *Alcohol and Alcoholism*, 38(2), pp. 148-50.
- DRERUP, M. L., JOHNSON, T. J. & BINDL, S., 2011. Mediators of the relationship between religiousness/spirituality and alcohol problems in an adult community sample. *Addictive Behaviors*, 36(12), pp. 1317-1320.
- DRUG POLICY ALLIANCE, 2017. Debunking the "Gateway" Myth. *The vast majority of people who use marijuana do not go on to use other illicit drugs*. New York: Drug Policy Alliance.
- EUROPEAN MONITORING CENTRE FOR DRUGS and DRUG ADDICTION, 2016. *European drug report 2016: trends and developments*. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
- DURKHEIM, E. & SWAIN, J.W., 2008. *The elementary forms of the religious life*. Courier Corporation.
- DURRANT, R. & THAKKER, J., 2003. *Substance use and abuse: Cultural and historical perspectives*, Sage.
- DUVEEN, G., 2013. 12 Representations, identities, resistance. *Development as a social process: Contributions of Gerard Duveen*, p. 182.
- DUVEEN, G. & LLOYD, B., 1986. The significance of social identities. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 25(3), pp. 219-30.
- EDWARDS, R. W., THURMAN, P. J. & BEAUVAIS, F., 2002. Patterns of alcohol use among ethnic minority adolescent women. In *Recent developments in alcoholism* (pp. 369-386). Springer, Boston, MA.
- ELLISON, C. G., BRADSHAW, M., ROTE, S., STORCH, J. & TREVINO, M.,

2008. Religion and Alcohol Use among College Students: Exploring the Role of Domain-Specific Religious Salience. *Journal of Drug Issues*, 38(3), pp. 821-846.
- ENGS, R. C., 2013. Past influences, current issues, future research directions. In *Learning about drinking* (pp. 163-182). Routledge.
- ENGS, R. C. & MULLEN, K., 1999. The effect of religion and religiosity on drug use among a selected sample of post secondary students in Scotland. *Addiction Research*, 7(2), pp. 149-170.
- EPSTEIN, A. L., 1978. *Ethos and identity: three studies in ethnicity*, Transaction Publishers.
- ERENS, B. S., K. AND MINDELL, J. (EDS) 2006. Health Survey for England 2004: Health of ethnic minorities. In: Sproston, K. and Mindell, J.E. & BECKER, E. (2006). *Health survey for England 2004 Vol. 2, Vol. 2*. Leeds, Information Centre. <http://www.ic.nhs.uk/pubs/healthsurvey2004ethnicfull/hse2004vol1/file>.
- ERIKSEN, T. H., 2001. Small Places, Large Issues. *An Introduction to Social and Cultural Anthropology*. London: Pluto Press.
- ERNEST, P., 1998. *Social constructivism as a philosophy of mathematics*. Boulder, Colo, NetLibrary, Inc.
- ESCOHOTADO, A., 1999. *A brief history of drugs: From the stone age to the stoned age*. Rochester, Park Street Press
- ETTORRE, E., 2007. *Feminist Theorizing about Drugs: Gender, Power and the Body*. In *Revisioning Women and Drug Use* (pp. 17-35). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- FAUGIER, J. & SARGEANT, M., 1997. Sampling hard to reach populations. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 26(4), pp. 790-797.
- FEREDAY, J. & MUIR-COCHRANE, E., 2006. Demonstrating rigor using thematic analysis: A hybrid approach of inductive and deductive coding and theme development. *International journal of qualitative methods*, 5(1), pp. 80-92.
- FILLMORE, K. M., 1988. Alcohol use across the life course: a critical review of 70 years of international longitudinal research. Toronto, Addiction Research Foundation. http://books.google.com/books?id=F_eLKVsbEW4C.
- FILLMORE, K. M., GOLDING, J. M., GRAVES, K. L., KNIEP, S., LEINO, E. V., ROMELSJO, A., SHOEMAKER, C., AGER, C. R., ALLEBECK, P. & FERRER, H. P., 1998. Alcohol consumption and mortality. III. Studies of female populations. *Addiction*, 93(2), pp. 219-29.
- FLANAGAN, S. M. & HANCOCK, B., 2010. 'Reaching the hard to reach'-lessons learned from the VCS (voluntary and community Sector). A qualitative study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 10(1), p. 92.
- FLANNERY, W. P., REISE, S. P. & YU, J. J., 2001. An empirical comparison of acculturation models. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 27(8), pp. 1035-1045.
- FLICK, U., 2009. *An introduction to qualitative research*, fourth edition SAGE. London: British Library.

- FLICK, U., FOSTER, J. & CAILLAUD, S., 2015. Researching social representations. *The Cambridge Handbook of Social Representations*, pp. 64-80.
- FORD, J. A. & BLUMENSTEIN, L., 2013. Self-Control and Substance Use Among College Students. *Journal of Drug Issues*, 43(1), pp. 56-68.
- FORSYTH, A. J., CLOONAN, M. & BARR, J., 2005. Factors associated with alcohol-related problems within licensed premises: *report to the Greater Glasgow NHS Board*. Glasgow, UK, Glasgow Caledonian University.
- FOUNTAIN, J., BASHFORD, J. and WINTERS, M., 2003. *Black and minority ethnic communities in England: A review of the literature on drug use and related service provision*, National Treatment Agency for Substance Misuse/Centre for Ethnicity and Health.
- FOUNTAIN, J., 2009. Issues surrounding drug use and drug services among the Black Caribbean communities in England. *National Treatment Agency, London*.
- FOUNTAIN, J., BASHFORD, J., UNDERWOOD, S., KHURANA, J., WINTERS, M., CARPENTIER, C., & PATEL, K. (2004). Drug use amongst Black and minority ethnic communities in the European Union and Norway. *Probation Journal*. 51, 362-378.
- FOUNTAIN, J., BASHFORD, J. & WINTERS, M., 2003. *Black and minority ethnic communities in England: A review of the literature on drug use and related service provision*, National Treatment Agency for Substance Misuse/Centre for Ethnicity and Health.
- GADD, C.J., 1971. Code of hammurabi. *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 11, pp. 41-43.
- GEERTZ, C., 1963. The Integrative Revolution: Primordial Sentiments and Civil Politics in the New States. *Old Societies and New States: The quest for modernity in Asia and Africa*, pp.105-157.
- GIBBS, G., 2002. *Qualitative data analysis: Explorations with Nvivo*. Open University Press.
- GLASER, B.G. & STRAUSS, A.L., 2017. *Discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Routledge.
- GLASER, B. G., STRAUSS, A. L. & STRUTZEL, E., 1968. The discovery of grounded theory; strategies for qualitative research. *Nursing research*, 17(4), p. 364.
- GLAZER, N., 1983. *Ethnic Dilemmas, 1964-1982*, Harvard University Press.
- GLAZIER, S. D. ed., 1999. *Anthropology of religion: a handbook*. Greenwood.
- GOFFMAN, E., 1968. *Asylums: Essays on the social situation of mental patients and other inmates*. AldineTransaction.
- GOFFMAN, E. 1986. Stigma notes on the management of spoiled identity. 1963. *New York: Touchstone*.
- GOFFMAN, E., 1997. Selections from stigma. *The disability studies reader* (pp. 203-215). *Florence, KY US: Taylor & Frances*.
- GOFFMAN, E., 2009. *Stigma: Notes on the management of spoiled identity*, Simon and Schuster.

- DUTTON, D., 2017. *ASYLUMS: Essays on the Social Situation of Mental Patients and Other Inmates*. TAYLOR & FRANCIS.
- GOODE, E., 2006. The Sociology of Drug Use. *21st Century Sociology*, pp. 415-24.
- GOODE, E. ed., 2015. *The handbook on deviance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- GOODE, W. J., 1960. A Theory of Role Strain. *American Sociological Review*, pp. 483-496.
- GOODMAN, J., LOVEJOY, P. E. & SHERRATT, A., 2007. *Consuming habits: global and historical perspectives on how cultures*. London, Routledge.
- GORDON, R., HEIM, D. & MACASKILL, S., 2012. Rethinking drinking cultures: a review of drinking cultures and a reconstructed dimensional approach. *Public Health*, 126(1), pp. 3-11.
- GOTTFREDSON, M. R. & HIRSCHI, T., 1990. *A general theory of crime*. Stanford University Press.
- GOULDING, C., 2002. *Grounded theory: A practical guide for management, business and market researchers*, Sage.
- GRAHAM, J., GREWAL, I. & LEWIS, J., 2007. *Ethics in social research: the views of research participants*. [London], [Government Social Research Unit].
- GRAHAM, J. W., MARKS, G. & HANSEN, W. B., 1991. Social influence processes affecting adolescent substance use. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(2), p. 291.
- GRAVES, T. D., 1967. Psychological Acculturation in a Tri-Ethnic Community. *Southwestern Journal of Anthropology*, 23(4), pp. 337-350.
- GRAY, D. E., 2013. *Doing research in the real world*, Sage.
- GREENE, M. C., KANE, J. C. & TOL, W. A., 2017. Alcohol use and intimate partner violence among women and their partners in sub-Saharan Africa. *Global Mental Health*, 4.
- GRIFFITHS, P., GOSSOP, M., WICKENDEN, S., DUNWORTH, J., HARRIS, K. & LLOYD, C., 1997. A transcultural pattern of drug use: qat (khat) in the UK. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 170(3), pp. 281-284.
- GROVES, P. & FARMER, R., 1994. Buddhism and Addictions. *Addiction Research*, 2(2), pp. 183-194.
- GUBA, E. G. & LINCOLN, Y. S., 2005. Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (3rd ed., pp. 191-215). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- GUNN, T. J., 2003. The Complexity of Religion and the Definition of "Religion" in International Law. *Harvard Human Rights Journal*. 16, 189-216.
- GUO, G., LI, Y., OWEN, C., WANG, H. & DUNCAN, G. J., 2015. A natural experiment of peer influences on youth alcohol use. *Social Science Research*, 52, pp. 193-207.
- GUPTA, P. C. & RAY, C. S., 2004. Epidemiology of betel quid usage. *Annals-Academy of Medicine Singapore*, 33, pp. 31-36.

- GUSFIELD, J. R., 1986. *Symbolic crusade: Status politics and the American temperance movement*, University of Illinois Press.
- HALL, G. S., 1904. *Adolescence: Its Psychology and Its Relations To Physiology, Anthropology, Sociology, Sex, Crime, Religion And Education* Volume 2.
- HALL, J. M., 1998. Ethnicity: Rescuing the phenomenon: Reply to discussion of 'Ethnic Identity in Greek Antiquity', by author. *Cambridge Archaeological Journal*, 8(2), pp. 279-283.
- HALL, S., 2001. Foucault: Power, Knowledge and Discourse Discourse Theory and Practise. *Red. Wetherell, Margaret, Stephanie Taylor og Simeon J. Yates*.
- HAMMERSLEY, M., 2012. *What is qualitative research?* A&C Black.
- HAMMERSLEY, R., 2008. *Drugs and crime: Theories and practices* (Vol. 2). Polity.
- HAMMERSLEY, R. & DALGARNO, P., 2012. *Drugs: Policy and practice in health and social care*. Dunedin Academic Press, Edinburgh.
- HANNA, L., HUNT, S. & BHOPAL, R. S., 2006. Cross-cultural adaptation of a tobacco questionnaire for Punjabi, Cantonese, Urdu and Sylheti speakers: qualitative research for better clinical practice, cessation services and research. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 60(12), pp.1034-1039.
- HANSON, G., VENTURELLI, P. & FLECKENSTEIN, A., 2011. *Drugs and society*, Jones & Bartlett Publishers.
- HARALAMBOS, M. ed., 1985. *Sociology: new directions*. Ormskirk: Causeway Books.
- HARDING, G., 1998. Pathologising the soul: The construction of a 19th century analysis of opiate addiction. *The control of drugs and drug users: Reason or reaction*, pp. 1-13.
- HARRIES, B., HOLLINGWORTH, S., JAMES, M. & FANGEN, K., 2016. Reconstituting race in youth studies. *Young*. 24, 177-184.
- HARRISON, L. & HARRISON, M., 2002. Drinking problems among black communities. In *Alcohol problems in the community* (pp. 235-252). Routledge.
- HARRISON, L., SUTTON, M. & GARDINER, E., 1997. Ethnic differences in substance use and alcohol-use-related mortality among first generation migrants to England and Wales. *Substance Use & Misuse*, 32(7-8), pp. 849-876.
- HASSAN, N. A., GUNAID, A. A., EL-KHALLY, F. M. & MURRAY-LYON, I. M., 2002. The effect of chewing Khat leaves on human mood. *Saudi Medical Journal*, 23(7), pp. 850-853.
- HAY, C., 2001. Parenting, self-control, and delinquency: A test of self-control theory. *Criminology*, 39(3), pp. 707-736.
- HEATH, D. B., 1991. Uses and Misuses of the Concept of Ethnicity in Alcohol Studies: an Essay in Deconstruction. *International Journal of the Addictions*, 25(sup5), pp. 607-628.
- HEATH, D. B., 1995. *International handbook on alcohol and culture*, ABC-CLIO.

- HEATH, D. B., 2012. *Drinking occasions: Comparative perspectives on alcohol and culture*, Routledge.
- HEIM, D., HUNTER, S. C., ROSS, A. J., BAKSHI, N., DAVIES, J. B., FLATLEY, K. J. & MEER, N., 2004. Alcohol consumption, perceptions of community responses and attitudes to service provision: results from a survey of Indian, Chinese and Pakistani young people in Greater Glasgow, Scotland, UK. *Alcohol and Alcoholism*, 39(3), pp. 220-226.
- HEIM, D. and MACASKILL, S., 2006. Black and minority ethnic health in greater Glasgow: a comparative report on the health and well-being of African & Caribbean, Chinese, Indian and Pakistani people and the general population. Glasgow, NHS Greater Glasgow.
- HIGATE, P., HUGHES, R. & LART, R., 2006. *Drugs: Policy And Politics: Policy and Politics*, McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- HINDELANG, M. J., 1973. Causes of delinquency: A partial replication and extension. *Social problems*, 20(4), pp. 471-487.
- HIRSCHI, T., 1969. *Causes of Delinquency*. Berkeley.
- HIRSCHI, T. & GOTTFREDSON, M. R., 1994. *The generality of deviance* (pp. 23-47). New Jersey.
- HIRSCHI, T., 2017. On the compatibility of rational choice and social control theories of crime. *The reasoning criminal* (pp. 105-118). Routledge.
- HOFSTEDE, G. H. & HOFSTEDE, G., 2001. *Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions and organizations across nations*, Sage Publications.
- HOGG, M. A., 2014. From Uncertainty to Extremism: Social Categorization and Identity Processes. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 23(5), pp. 338-342.
- HOGG, M. A., ADELMAN, J. R. & BLAGG, R. D., 2010. Religion in the face of uncertainty: an uncertainty-identity theory account of religiousness. *Personality and social psychology review*, 14(1), pp. 72-83.
- HOLMES, M., 2007. *What is gender?: Sociological approaches*, Sage.
- HOLMWOOD, C., 2014. *Drugs of Dependence. The Role of Medical Professionals* edited by Howes P [editor], by Bell J, Bowden-Jones O, Ellinas T, Reed K, Rolles S, Roycroft G, Witton J; Contributors: Finch E, Gosine A, Green N, Rough E; On behalf of the BMA Board of Science London: British Medical Association, 2013 ISBN 10: 1 905545 67 3, 308 pp. Online (grey literature): <http://bma.org.uk/news-views-analysis/in-depth-drugs-of-dependence>. *Drug and Alcohol Review*, 33(1), pp.106-106.
- HOME OFFICE NATIONAL STATISTICS 2014. Drug misuse: Findings from the 2013/14 Crime Survey for England and Wales. London: Home Office.
- HOWARTH, C., 2006. A social representation is not a quiet thing: Exploring the critical potential of social representations theory. *British journal of social psychology*, 45(1), pp. 65-86.
- HOWITT, D. & CRAMER, D., 2007. *Introduction to research methods in psychology*, Pearson Education.

- HUMPHREY, J. A. & SCHMALLEGER, F., 2011. *Deviant behavior*, Jones & Bartlett Publishers.
- HUMPHREYS, K. & GIFFORD, E., 2006. Religion, Spirituality, and the Troublesome Use of Substances. In: Miller W., Carroll K., editors. *Rethinking Substance Abuse: What the Science Shows and What We Should Do About It*. New York: Guilford Press; 2006, p. 257-74.
- HUNSBERGER, B. & JACKSON, L. M., 2005. Religion, meaning, and prejudice. *Journal of Social Issues*, 61(4), pp. 807-826.
- HUNT, G. & BARKER, J. C., 2001. Socio-cultural anthropology and alcohol and drug research: towards a unified theory. *Social Science & Medicine*, 53(2), pp. 165-188.
- HUNT, G. & KOLIND, T., 2017. Researching ethnicity and substances: a contested arena. *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*. 24, 227-229.
- HUNT, G., KOLIND, T. & ANTIN, T., 2018. Conceptualizing ethnicity in alcohol and drug research: Epidemiology meets social theory. *Journal of ethnicity in substance abuse*, 17(2), pp. 187-198.
- HUNT, G. P., EVANS, K. & KARES, F., 2007. Drug use and meanings of risk and pleasure. *Journal of youth studies*, 10(1), pp. 73-96.
- HUNT, L. L., 2001. Religion, gender, and the Hispanic experience in the United States: Catholic/Protestant differences in religious involvement, social status, and gender-role attitudes. *Review of Religious Research*, pp. 139-160.
- HURCOMBE, R., BAYLEY, M. & GOODMAN, A., 2010. *Ethnicity and alcohol: a review of the UK literature*. York, Joseph Rowntree Foundation.
- HYMAN, H. H. & SINGER, E. eds., 1968. *Readings in reference group theory and research*, Free Pr.
- ISAACS, H. R., 1989. *Idols of the tribe: Group identity and political change*, Harvard University Press.
- IWAMOTO, D. K., CHENG, A., LEE, C. S., TAKAMATSU, S. & GORDON, D., 2011. "Man-ing" up and getting drunk: The role of masculine norms, alcohol intoxication and alcohol-related problems among college men. *Addictive behaviors*, 36(9), pp. 906-911.
- JACKSON, B. S., 1995. The literary presentation of multiculturalism in early Biblical law. *Revue Internationale De Semiotique Juridique*. 8, 181-206.
- JACKSON, K. M., ROBERTS, M. E., COLBY, S. M., BARNETT, N. P., ABAR, C. C. & MERRILL, J. E., 2014. Willingness to drink as a function of peer offers and peer norms in early adolescence. *Journal of studies on alcohol and drugs*, 75(3), pp. 404-414.
- JARVENSIVU, T. & TORNROOS, J. A., 2010. Case study research with moderate constructionism: Conceptualization and practical illustration. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 39(1), pp. 100-108.
- JARVIS, L., 2008. *Alcohol Consumption in Black and Minority Ethnic Groups and recent immigrants in Scotland: current situation on information available*. NHS Scotland.
- JAY, M., 2011. *Emperors of dreams: Drugs in the nineteenth century*, SCB

Distributors.

- JAYAKODY, A. A., VINER, R. M., HAINES, M. M., BHUI, K. S., HEAD, J. A., TAYLOR, S. J., BOOY, R., KLINEBERG, E., CLARK, C. & STANSFELD, S. A., 2006. Illicit and traditional drug use among ethnic minority adolescents in East London. *Public Health*, 120(4), pp. 329-38.
- JENKINS, R., 2014. *Social identity*, Routledge.
- JIVRAJ, S. & KHAN, O., 2013. Ethnicity and deprivation in England: How likely are ethnic minorities to live in deprived neighbourhoods. *Dynamics of Diversity: Evidence from the 2011 Census*, pp. 1-4.
- JOFFE, H., 2012. Thematic analysis. *Qualitative research methods in mental health and psychotherapy: A guide for students and practitioners*, 1.
- JOHL, N., 2017. An exploration of alcohol services' staff experiences of providing support to relatives of alcohol-dependent individuals from the Sikh community. *Sikh Formations*, 13(3), pp. 207-224.
- JOHNSON, B. D., 1973. *Marihuana users and drug subcultures*, John Wiley & Sons.
- JOHNSON, W., HICKS, B. M., MCGUE, M. & IACONO, W. G., 2007. Most of the girls are alright, but some aren't: Personality trajectory groups from ages 14 to 24 and some associations with outcomes. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 93(2), pp. 266.
- JONES, C. P., 1987. Stigma: Tattooing and Branding in Graeco-Roman Antiquity. *The Journal of Roman Studies*, 77, pp. 139-155.
- JONES, E. E., FARINA, A., HASTORF, A. H., MARKUS, H., MILLER, D. T. & SCOTT, R. A., 1984. *Social stigma: The psychology of sex differences*. New York: W.H. Freeman and Company.
- KANDEL, D. B., 1980. Drug and Drinking Behavior among Youth. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 6(1), pp. 235-285.
- KANDEL, D. B. ed., 2002. *Stages and pathways of drug involvement: Examining the gateway hypothesis*, Cambridge University Press.
- KANDEL, D. B., KESSLER, R. C. & MARGULIES, R. Z., 1978. Antecedents of adolescent initiation into stages of drug use: A developmental analysis. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 7(1), pp. 13-40.
- KANDEL, D. B. & LOGAN, J. A., 1984. Patterns of drug use from adolescence to young adulthood: I. Periods of risk for initiation, continued use, and discontinuation. *American journal of public health*, 74(7), pp. 660-666.
- KANT, I., 1781. Critique of pure reason. *Trans. Paul Guyer and Allen Woods*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- KELLY, A. B., CHAN, G. C., TOUMBOUROU, J. W., O'FLAHERTY, M., HOMEL, R., PATTON, G. C. & WILLIAMS, J., 2012. Very young adolescents and alcohol: evidence of a unique susceptibility to peer alcohol use. *Addictive behaviors*, 37(4), pp. 414-419.
- KHAN, F., DITTON, J. & HAMMERSLEY, R., 2000. Ethnic minority use of illegal drugs in Glasgow, Scotland: Potential difficulties for service provision. *Addiction Research*, 8(1), pp. 27-49.
- KIRBY, T. & BARRY, A. E., 2012. Alcohol as a gateway drug: a study of US 12th graders. *Journal of school health*, 82(8), pp. 371-379.

- KISSIN, B. & BEGLEITER, H., 2013. *Social aspects of alcoholism* (Vol. 4). Springer Science & Business Media.
- KLEIN, A., 2008. *Drugs and the World*, Reaktion Books.
- KLEINIG, J., 2015. Ready for Retirement: The Gateway Drug Hypothesis. *Substance use & misuse*, 50(8-9), pp. 971-975.
- KOENIG, H. G. & SHOHAIB, S., 2014. *Health and Well-Being in Islamic Societies*. London: Springer.
- KORHONEN, T., VAN LEEUWEN, A. P., REIJNEVELD, S. A., ORMEL, J., VERHULST, F. C. & HUIZINK, A. C., 2010. Externalizing Behavior Problems and Cigarette Smoking as Predictors of Cannabis Use: The TRAILS Study. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 49(1), pp. 61-69.
- KORSMEYER, P. & KRANZLER, H. R., 2009. *Encyclopedia of drugs, alcohol & addictive behaviour*. USA: Macmillan Reference.
- KULIS, S., MARSIGLIA, F. F. & NIERI, T., 2009. Perceived ethnic discrimination versus acculturation stress: influences on substance use among Latino youth in the Southwest. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 50(4), pp. 443-59.
- KULIS, S., YABIKU, S. T., MARSIGLIA, F. F., NIERI, T. & CROSSMAN, A., 2007. Differences by gender, ethnicity, and acculturation in the efficacy of the keepin'it REAL model prevention program. *Journal of drug education*, 37(2), pp. 123-144.
- LABHART, F., GRAHAM, K., WELLS, S. & KUNTSCHE, E., 2013. Drinking before going to licensed premises: An event-level analysis of predrinking, alcohol consumption, and adverse outcomes. *Alcoholism: Clinical and Experimental Research*, 37(2), pp. 284-291.
- LANDRINE, H. & KLONOFF, E. A., 2004. Culture change and ethnic-minority health behavior: an operant theory of acculturation. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 27(6), pp.527-555.
- LEACH, E., 1952. *Political Systems of Highland Burma* (London, 1954). *Leach Political Systems of Highland Burma 1954*.
- LEBOW, R. N., 2016. Max Weber (1864–1920). In *The Return of the Theorists* (pp. 173-181). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- LEIGH, J., BOWEN, S. & MARLATT, G. A., 2005. Spirituality, mindfulness and substance abuse. *Addictive behaviors*, 30(7), pp. 1335-41.
- LESHNER, A. I., 1997. Addiction is a brain disease, and it matters. *Science*, 278(5335), pp. 45-47.
- LEVINE, H. G., 1992. Temperance cultures. *Lader et E. Edwards (Eds.) The nature of alcohol and drug related problems*, pp. 16-36.
- LEVINE, R. A. & CAMPBELL, D. T., 1972. *Ethnocentrism: Theories of conflict, ethnic attitudes, and group behavior*. London, J. Wiley.
- LEWIN, L., 1931. Phantastica; Narcotic and Stimulating Drugs, their use and abuse. *The American Journal of the Medical Sciences*, 184(3), pp. 423-424.
- LEWIS, C., GLEDSON, A. & JONES, A., 2012. *Statistics from the National Drug Treatment Monitoring System (NDTMS): Statistics relating to young people*. London, UK: National Treatment Agency for Substance

Misuse.

- LIEBKIND, K., 1992. Ethnic identity-Challenging the boundaries of social psychology. In *Social psychology of identity and the self-concept*. Academic Press (Surrey University Press).
- LINK, B. G. & PHELAN, J. C., 2006. Stigma and its public health implications. *The Lancet*, 367(9509), pp. 528-529.
- LITT, D. M., LEWIS, M. A., STAHLBRANDT, H., FIRTH, P. & NEIGHBORS, C., 2012. Social comparison as a moderator of the association between perceived norms and alcohol use and negative consequences among college students. *Journal of studies on alcohol and drugs*, 73(6), pp. 961-967.
- LITT, D. M. & STOCK, M. L., 2011. Adolescent alcohol-related risk cognitions: the roles of social norms and social networking sites. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 25(4), 708-13.
- LIVINGSTON, M. & CALLINAN, S., 2015. Underreporting in alcohol surveys: whose drinking is underestimated? *Journal of studies on alcohol and drugs*, 76(1), 158-164.
- LLOYD, C., 2013. The stigmatization of problem drug users: A narrative literature review. *Drugs: education, prevention and policy*, 20(2), pp.85-95.
- LONDON POLICE FOUNDATION, 2000. *Drugs and the law: Report of the Independent Inquiry into the Misuse of Drugs Act 1971*.
- LUCZAK, S. E., PRESCOTT, C. A., DALAIS, C., RAINE, A., VENABLES, P. H. & MEDNICK, S. A., 2014. Religious factors associated with alcohol involvement: results from the Mauritian Joint Child Health Project. *Drug Alcohol Depend*, 135, pp. 37-44.
- LUGER, L., 2009. *Enhancing Cultural Competence in Staff Dealing with People with Drug and Alcohol Problems*. (Doctoral dissertation, University of West London).
- LUGER, L. & SOOKHOO, D., 2005. Rapid needs assessment of the provision of drug and alcohol services for people from minority ethnic groups with drug and alcohol problems. *Diversity in Health and Social Care*, 2(3), pp. 167-176.
- LUK, J. W., EMERY, R. L., KARYADI, K. A., PATOCK-PECKHAM, J. A. & KING, K. M., 2013. Religiosity and substance use among Asian American college students: moderated effects of race and acculturation. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*, 130(1-3), pp. 142-149.
- LUPTON, R., WILSON, A., MAY, T., WARBURTON, H. & TURNBULL, P. J., 2002. A rock and a hard place: drug markets in deprived neighbourhoods. *Home Office Research Study*.
- LYMAN, M. D., 2016. *Drugs in society: causes, concepts, and control*, Routledge.
- MACANDREW, C. & EDGERTON, R. B., 1969. A social explanation. *Chicago: AldineMacAndrewDrunken Comportment: A Social Explanation1969*.
- MACANDREW, C. & EDGERTON, R. B., 2003. *Drunken Comportment: A Social Explanation (1969)*. *Clinton Corners, NY: Eliot Werner*.
- MACARTHUR, G.J., JACOB, N., POUND, P., HICKMAN, M. & CAMPBELL, R.,

2017. Among friends: a qualitative exploration of the role of peers in young people's alcohol use using Bourdieu's concepts of habitus, field and capital. *Sociology of health & illness*, 39(1), pp.30-46.
- MACMILLAN, K. & KOENIG, T., 2004. The wow factor - Preconceptions and expectations for data analysis software in qualitative research. *Social Science Computer Review*, 22(2), pp.179-186.
- MAJOR, B. & O'BRIEN, L. T., 2005. The social psychology of stigma. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.*, 56, pp.393-421.
- MANTOVANI, N. & EVANS, C., 2019. Drug use among British Bangladeshis in London: a macro-structural perspective focusing on disadvantages contributing to individuals' drug use trajectories and engagement with treatment services. *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*, 26(2), pp.125-132.
- MARCIA, J. E., WATERMAN, A. S., MATTESON, D. R., ARCHER, S. L. & ORLOFSKY, J. L., 2012. *Ego identity: A handbook for psychosocial research*, Springer Science & Business Media.
- MARPSAT, M. & RAZAFINDRATSIMA, N., 2010. Survey methods for hard-to-reach populations: introduction to the special issue. *Methodological Innovations Online*, 5(2), pp.3-16.
- MAYET, A., LEGLEYE, S., FALISSARD, B. AND CHAU, N., 2012. Cannabis use stages as predictors of subsequent initiation with other illicit drugs among French adolescents: use of a multi-state model. *Addictive behaviors*, 37(2), pp.160-166.
- MCCALL, L., 2008. The complexity of intersectionality. *In Intersectionality and beyond (pp. 65-92)*. Routledge-Cavendish.
- MCDONALD, M. ed., 1994. *Gender, drink, and drugs* (p. 13). Oxford, UK: Berg.
- MCGOVERN, P. E., 2009. *Uncorking the past: the quest for wine, beer, and other alcoholic beverages*, Univ of California Press.
- MCINTIRE, D., 2007. Soul Searching: The Religious and Spiritual Lives of American Teenagers. *Journal of College and Character*, 9(1).
- MCKENNA, S. A. & MAIN, D. S., 2013. The role and influence of key informants in community-engaged research: A critical perspective. *Action Research*, 11(2), pp.113-124.
- MCMAHON, M., 1997, December. Social constructivism and the World Wide Web-A paradigm for learning. In ASCILITE conference. Perth, Australia (Vol. 327).
- MCPHEE, I., 2012. The intentionally unseen: exploring the illicit drug use of non-treatment seeking drug users in Scotland. <http://hdl.handle.net/1893/9921>.
- MCPHEE, I., BROWN, A. & MARTIN, C., 2013. Stigma and perceptions of recovery in Scotland: a qualitative study of injecting drug users attending methadone treatment. *Drugs and Alcohol Today*, 13(4), pp.244-257.
- MCPHEE, I., DUFFY, T. & MARTIN, C., 2009. The perspectives of drug users within the social context of drug prohibition. *Drugs and Alcohol Today*, 9(2), pp.19-23.

- MERRIAM, A., 2017. *Ethos and Identity: Three Studies in Ethnicity*, Routledge.
- MERTON, R. K., 1968. Social structure and anomie. RK Merton. *Social theory and social structure*.
- MERTON, R. K., 1975. Thematic Analysis in Science: Notes on Holton's Concept. *Science*, 188(4186), pp.335-338.
- MICHALAK, L., TROCKI, K. & BOND, J., 2007. Religion and alcohol in the US National Alcohol Survey: how important is religion for abstinence and drinking? *Drug and alcohol dependence*, 87(2-3), pp.268-280.
- MILES, R., 1984. Marxism versus the sociology of 'race relations'? *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 7(2), pp.217-237.
- MILLER, J. & GLASSNER, B., 1997. The 'inside' and the 'outside': Finding realities in interviews. *Qualitative research*, pp.99-112.
- MILLER, R. J., 2013. *Drugged: The Science and Culture Behind Psychotropic Drugs*, Oxford University Press.
- MILLS, K., 2012. Under the radar: Impact of policies of localism on substance misuse services for refugee and asylum seeking communities. *International Social Work*, 55(5), pp.662-674.
- MILLWARD, D. & KARLSEN, S., 2011. Tobacco use among minority ethnic populations and cessation. *London: Race Equality Foundation*.
- MISUSE OF DRUGS ACT 2013. Dangerous Drugs (Temporary Class Drug) *In: LEGISLATION* (ed.). UK: Home Office
- MITCHELL, O. & CAUDY, M. S., 2017. Race Differences in Drug Offending and Drug Distribution Arrests. *Crime & Delinquency*, 63(2), pp.91-112.
- MONAGHAN, M., 2014. Drug Policy Governance in the UK: Lessons from changes to and debates concerning the classification of cannabis under the 1971 Misuse of Drugs Act. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 25(5), pp.1025-1030.
- MORRAL, A. R., MCCAFFREY, D. F. & PADDOCK, S. M., 2002. Using Marijuana May Not Raise the Risk of Using Harder Drugs. *PsycEXTRA Dataset*.
- MORRIS, R. R., 1964. Female Delinquency and Relational Problems. *Social Forces*, 43(1), pp.82-89.
- MORSE, J. M., HUTCHINSON, S. A. & PENROD, J., 1998. From theory to practice: The development of assessment guides from qualitatively derived theory. *Qualitative Health Research*, 8(3), pp.329-340.
- MOTT, J. & BEAN, P., 1998. The development of drug control in Britain. *The control of drugs and drug users: Reason or reaction*, pp.31-48.
- MULLEN, K., WATSON, J., SWIFT, J. & BLACK, D., 2007. Young men, masculinity and alcohol. *Drugs: Education Prevention and Policy*, 14(2), pp.151-165.
- MULLEN, K., WILLIAMS, R. & HUNT, K., 1996. Irish descent, religion, and alcohol and tobacco use. *Addiction*, 91(2), pp.243-254.
- MURJI, K., 2019. *Policing drugs*, Routledge.
- MURTHY, P., 2015. Culture and alcohol use in India. *World Cult Psychiatry Res Rev*, 10, pp. 27-39.

- NAPPER, L.E., FISHER, D.G., JOHNSON, M.E. & WOOD, M.M., 2010. The reliability and validity of drug users' self reports of amphetamine use among primarily heroin and cocaine users. *Addictive behaviors*, 35(4), pp.350-354.
- NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICES SCOTLAND 2012. Drug Misuse Statistics Scotland 2011. In: Scotland, I.S.D., 2012. Drug misuse statistics Scotland 2011. *ISD Scotland: Edinburgh, Scotland*.
- NATIONAL RECORDS OF SCOTLAND 2018. Population Estimates Scotland & Estimating Migration. In: STATISTICS (ed.). Scotland National Records of Scotland
- NAZROO, J.Y. ed., 2006. *Health and social research in multiethnic societies*. Routledge.
- NEIMEYER, G.J., 1993. *Constructivist assessment: A casebook*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- NENCINI, P., 1997. The rules of drug taking: Wine and poppy derivatives in the ancient world. VIII. Lack of evidence of opium addiction. *Substance use & misuse*, 32(11), pp.1581-1586.
- NHS SCOTLAND 2018. Scottish Drug Misuse Database. *Overview of Initial Assessments for Specialist Drug Treatment 2016/17*. Scotland: ISD Scotland.
- NONNEMAKER, J.M., MCNEELY, C.A. AND BLUM, R.W & NATIONAL LONGITUDINAL STUDY OF ADOLESCENT, H., 2003. Public and private domains of religiosity and adolescent health risk behaviors: Evidence from the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health. *Social science & medicine*, 57(11), pp.2049-2054.
- NOWELL, L.S., NORRIS, J.M., WHITE, D.E. & MOULES, N.J., 2017. Thematic analysis: Striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16(1), p.1609406917733847.
- NYE, F. I., 1958. *Family relationships and delinquent behavior*. New York, J. Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- O'DONNELL, J. A., 1979. Cigarette smoking as a precursor of illicit drug use. *Cigarette smoking as a dependence process*, 30.
- O'CONNOR, J., 1978. *The young drinkers: A cross-national study of social and cultural influences*, Routledge Kegan & Paul.
- OETTING, E.R., DONNERMEYER, J.F., TRIMBLE, J.E. & BEAUVAIS, F., 1998. Primary socialization theory: Culture, ethnicity, and cultural identification. The links between culture and substance use. IV. *Substance Use & Misuse*, 33(10), pp.2075-2107.
- OKIN, S. M., 2013. *Women in western political thought*. Princeton University Press.
- ORFORD, J., JOHNSON, M. & PURSER, B., 2004. Drinking in second generation Black and Asian communities in the English Midlands. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 12(1), pp.11-30.
- ORMSTON, R., BRADSHAW, P. & ANDERSON, S., 2010. *Scottish social attitudes survey 2009: Public attitudes to drugs and drug use in Scotland*, Scottish Government.
- ORMSTON, R. & WEBSTER, C., 2008. *Scottish Social Attitudes Survey 2007:*

- Something to be Ashamed of Or Part of Our Way of Life?: Attitudes Towards Alcohol in Scotland.* Scottish Government Social Research.
- OSGOOD, D.W., RAGAN, D.T., WALLACE, L., GEST, S.D., FEINBERG, M.E. & MOODY, J., 2013. Peers and the emergence of alcohol use: Influence and selection processes in adolescent friendship networks. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 23(3), pp.500-512.
- OZER, S., 2013. Theories and methodologies in acculturation psychology: The emergence of a scientific revolution?. *Psychological Studies*, 58(3), pp.339-348.
- PAECHTER, C., 2007. *Being Boys; Being Girls: Learning Masculinities And Femininities: Learning Masculinities and Femininities*, McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- PALAMAR, J.J., KIANG, M.V. AND HALKITIS, P.N., 2014. Religiosity and exposure to users in explaining illicit drug use among emerging adults. *Journal of religion and health*, 53(3), pp.658-674.
- PANNU, G., ZAMAN, S., BHALA, N. & ZAMAN, R., 2009. Alcohol use in South Asians in the UK. *BMJ*, 339, b4028.
- PAOLI, L. & REUTER, P., 2008. Drug trafficking and ethnic minorities in Western Europe. *European Journal of Criminology*, 5(1), pp.13-37.
- PARKER, H., WILLIAMS, L. & ALDRIDGE, J., 2002. The normalization of 'sensible' recreational drug use: Further evidence from the North West England longitudinal study. *Sociology*, 36(4), pp.941-964.
- PARKER, H. J., ALDRIDGE, J. & MEASHAM, F., 1998. *Illegal leisure: The normalization of adolescent recreational drug use*, Psychology Press.
- PATEL, K., 2000. Using qualitative research to examine the nature of drug use among minority ethnic communities in the UK. *EMCDDA, Lisbon*.
- PATEL, K., BASHFORD, J., UNDERWOOD, S., KHURANA, J., WINTERS, M., CARPENTIER, C. & FOUNTAIN, J., 2004. Laying the Foundations of an Evidence Base on Drug Use Amongst Black and Minority Ethnic Communities: The Research Methods Used for an EMCDDA Project. *Journal of Ethnicity in Substance Abuse*, 3(1), pp.29-46.
- PATEL, N., BAMHRAH, C. & SINGH, G., 1996. Drug use in the Asian community. *Report to Lancashire Drug Action Team. Also reported in NWLHPU/GMLCA (1997), above*.
- PATTON, M. Q., 1990. *Qualitative evaluation and research methods*, SAGE Publications, inc.
- PATTON, M. Q., 2005. *Qualitative research. Encyclopedia of statistics in behavioral science*.
- PEARSON, G. & PATEL, K., 1998. Drugs, deprivation, and ethnicity: outreach among Asian drug users in a northern English city. *Journal of Drug Issues*, 28(1), pp.199-224.
- PEDERSEN, W. & VON SOEST, T., 2013. Socialization to binge drinking: A population-based, longitudinal study with emphasis on parental influences. *Drug and alcohol dependence*, 133(2), pp.587-592.
- PEELE, S., 1985. *The meaning of addiction: Compulsive experience and its interpretation*, Lexington Books/DC Heath and Com.
- PEELE, S., 1997. Utilizing culture and behaviour in epidemiological models

- of alcohol consumption and consequences for Western nations. *Alcohol and Alcoholism*, 32(1), pp.51-64.
- PETERSON, D. & PANFIL, V. R. eds., 2014. *Handbook of LGBT communities, crime, and justice*. New York, NY: Springer.
- PHINNEY, J.S. & ONG, A.D., 2007. Conceptualization and measurement of ethnic identity: Current status and future directions. *Journal of counselling Psychology*, 54(3), pp.271.
- PHIZACKLEA, A., 1984. A Sociology of Migration or Race Relations'? A View from Britain. *Current sociology*, 32(3), pp.199-218.
- PITTMAN, D.J., 1964. Social and cultural factors in drinking patterns, pathological and non-pathological. In *Selected papers presented at the 27th International Congress on Alcohol and Alcoholism* (Vol. 1, pp. 1-13).
- PITTMAN, D. J. & WHITE, H. R., 1991. *Society, culture, and drinking patterns re-examined* (Vol 1), Alcohol Research Documentation Inc.
- PLUCKROSE, H., 2017. The Problem with Intersectional Feminism. *Aero Magazine*.
- POOLE, E. D. & REGOLI, R. M., 1979. Parental support, delinquent friends, and delinquency: A test of interaction effects. *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 70, p. 188.
- POWELL, G. B., 1979. Democracy in Plural Societies: A Comparative Exploration. By Lijphart Arend. (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1977. Pp. x+ 248. \$15.00.). *American Political Science Review*, 73(1), pp. 295-297.
- PREBLE, E. & CASEY, J. J., 1969. Taking care of business—the heroin user's life on the street. *International journal of the addictions*, 4(1), 1-24.
- PURI, N., ALLEN, K. & RIEB, L., 2018. Treatment of alcohol use disorder among people of South Asian ancestry in Canada and the United States: A narrative review. *Journal of ethnicity in substance abuse*, pp. 1-13.
- PURSER, B., DAVIS, P., JOHNSON, M. & ORFORD, J., 2001. Drinking in Second and Subsequent Generation Black and Asian Communities in the English Midlands London: Alcohol Concern.
- PYKE, K. D., 2010. What is internalized racial oppression and why don't we study it? Acknowledging racism's hidden injuries. *Sociological Perspectives*, 53(4), pp.551-572.
- QUINTANA, S. M., 2007. Racial and ethnic identity: Developmental perspectives and research. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 54(3), pp.259.
- RAMSAY, M., BAKER, P., GOULDEN, C., SHARP, C. & SONDHI, A., 2001. *Drug misuse declared in 2000: results from the British Crime Survey*, Home Office Research, Development and Statistics Directorate London.
- RAMSAY, M. & PERCY, A., 1996. *Drug misuse declared: results of the 1994 British Crime Survey*. London: Home Office.
- RASSOOL, G. H., 2006. Substance abuse in black and minority Ethnic Communities in the United Kingdom: A neglected problem? *Journal*

- of Addictions Nursing*, 17(2), pp.127-132.
- REDFIELD, R., LINTON, R. & HERSKOVITS, M. J. 1936. Memorandum for the study of acculturation. *American anthropologist*, 38(1), pp.149-152.
- REED, M. B., LANGE, J. E., KETCHIE, J. M. & CLAPP, J. D., 2007. The relationship between social identity, normative information, and college student drinking. *Social Influence*, 2(4), pp.269-294.
- REINARMAN, C., 2005. Addiction as accomplishment: The discursive construction of disease. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 13(4), pp.307-320.
- REINARMAN, C., LEVINE, H.G. and LEVINE, H. eds., 1997. *Crack in America: Demon drugs and social justice*. Univ of California Press.
- RITCHIE, J., LEWIS, J., NICHOLLS, C. M. & ORMSTON, R. eds., 2013. *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*, Sage.
- ROBERTSON, L. A. B., E 2014. Scottish Crime and Justice Survey 2012-13: Drug Use. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.
- ROBINSON, S., HARRIS, H. and DUNSTAN, S., 2011. Smoking and drinking among adults, 2009. *Newport: Office for National Statistics*.
- ROGOFF, B., 1999. Cognitive development through social interaction: Vygotsky and Piaget. *Learners, learning and assessment*, pp.69-82.
- ROMAN, P.M., 2015. Alcohol Use as Deviance. *The Handbook of Deviance (Wiley Handbooks in Criminology and Criminal Justice)*. Hoboken: WileyBlackwell, pp.331-348.
- ROOM, R., 2001. Intoxication and bad behaviour: understanding cultural differences in the link. *Social science & medicine*, 53(2), pp.189-198.
- ROOM, R. 2005. Multicultural contexts and alcohol and drug use as symbolic behaviour. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 13(4), pp.321-331.
- ROOM, R. & MÄKELÄ, K., 2000. Typologies of the cultural position of drinking. *Journal of studies on alcohol*, 61(3), pp.475-483.
- ROSEN, W. & WEIL, A. T., 2004. *From chocolate to morphine: everything you need to know about mind-altering drugs*, Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- ROSENSTOCK, I.M., STRECHER, V.J. & BECKER, M.H., 1988. Social learning theory and the health belief model. *Health education quarterly*, 15(2), pp.175-183.
- RUDMIN, F. W., 2003. Critical history of the acculturation psychology of assimilation, separation, integration, and marginalization. *Review of general psychology*, 7(1), pp.3-37.
- RUDMIN, F. W., 2010. Phenomenology of Acculturation: Retrospective Reports from the Philippines, Japan, Quebec, and Norway. *Culture & Psychology*, 16(3), pp.313-332.
- RÚDÓLFSDÓTTIR, A. G. & MORGAN, P., 2009. 'Alcohol is my friend': Young middle class women discuss their relationship with alcohol. *Journal of community & applied social psychology*, 19(6), pp.492-505.
- SAGARIN, E., 1975. *Deviants and deviance: An introduction to the study of disvalued people and behavior*, Praeger Publishers New York.

- SAM, D. L., 2006. Acculturation: Conceptual background and core components. *The Cambridge Handbook of Acculturation Psychology*. 11.
- SAM, D. L. & BERRY, J. W. eds., 2006. *The Cambridge handbook of acculturation psychology*, Cambridge University Press.
- SANGSTER, D., SHINER, M., PATEL, K. & SHEIKH, N., 2002. *Delivering drug services to Black and ethnic-minority communities*, Home Office, Drugs Strategy Directorate.
- SANGSTER, D., SHINER, M., PATEL, K. & SHEIKH, N., 2002. *Delivering drug services to black and minority ethnic communities*. Drugs Prevention Advisory Service.
- SANKARANARAYANAN, R., DUFFY, S.W., PADMAKUMARY, G., DAY, N.E. & PADMANABHAN, T.K., 1989. Tobacco chewing, alcohol and nasal snuff in cancer of the gingiva in Kerala, India. *British journal of cancer*, 60(4), p.638.
- SAUNDERS, M. N. & LEWIS, P., 2012. *Doing research in business & management: An essential guide to planning your project*, Pearson.
- SAVIC, M., ROOM, R., MUGAVIN, J., PENNAY, A. & LIVINGSTON, M., 2016. Defining "drinking culture": A critical review of its meaning and connotation in social research on alcohol problems. *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*, 23(4), pp.270-282.
- SHULTES, R.E. and HOFFMAN, A., 1992. Plants of the gods. *Their sacred, healing, and hallucinogenic powers*. Rochester, Vermont.
- SCHWANDT, T., The SAGE Dictionary of Qualitative Inquiry. 2007. Epub 3. doi: 10.4135/9781412986281.
- SCOTTISH GOVERNMENT. 2014. *Ethnic Group Demographics* [Online]. Scotland's 2011 Census. Available: <http://www.gov.scot/Topics/People/Equality/Equalities/DataGrid/Ethnicity/EthPopMig> [Accessed 03/02/2015 2015].
- SEALE, C., 2000. Using computers to analyse qualitative data. *Doing qualitative research: A practical handbook*, 155-174.
- SEDDON, T., 2005. Drugs, crime and social exclusion: social context and social theory in British drugs-crime research. *British Journal of Criminology*, 46(4), pp.680-703.
- SHARP, C., MARCINKIEWICZ, A. & RUTHERFORD, L., 2014. *Attitudes towards alcohol in Scotland: results from the 2013 Scottish Social Attitudes Survey*. Edinburgh: NHS Health Scotland.
- SHAW, B., MENZIES, L., BERNARDES, E., BAARS, S., NYE, P. & ALLEN, R., 2016. Ethnicity, gender and social mobility.
- SHEWAN, D. & DALGARNO, P., 2005. Evidence for controlled heroin use? Low levels of negative health and social outcomes among non-treatment heroin users in Glasgow (Scotland). *British journal of health psychology*, 10(1), pp.33-48.
- SIATKOWSKI, A.A., 2007. Hispanic acculturation: A concept analysis. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing*, 18(4), pp.316-323.
- SIMON, R. and BURKHART, G., 2015. Regional and cultural aspects of prevention. *Textbook of Addiction Treatment: International*

- Perspectives*, pp.143-158.
- SINGER, E., 2003. Exploring the meaning of consent: participation in research and beliefs about risks and benefits. *Journal of Official Statistics*, 19(3), p.273.
- SKJÆRVØ, I., 2018. Substance use and crime: Characteristics of victim and offender roles in a longitudinal study of patients entering substance use treatment.
- SMITH, C., 2003. Theorizing religious effects among American adolescents. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 42(1), pp.17-30.
- SMITH, C. P., 2000. Content analysis and narrative analysis. *Handbook of Research Methods in Social and Personality Psychology*, pp.313-335.
- SMITH, H., GROB, C., JESSE, R., BRAVO, G., AGAR, A. & WALSH, R., 2004. Do drugs have religious import? A 40-year retrospective. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 44(2), pp.120-140.
- SMITH, S. T., 1993. *Askut and the changing nature of Egyptian imperialism in the second millennium BC*, University of California, Los Angeles.
- SPENCER-OATEY, H. & FRANKLIN, P., 2012. What is culture. *A compilation of quotations. GlobalPAD Core Concepts*, pp.1-22.
- SPENCER-OATEY, H. ed., 2008. *Culturally Speaking Second Edition: Culture, Communication and Politeness Theory*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- STADDON, P., 2009. 'Making Whoopee'?: An exploration of understandings and responses around women's alcohol use. Plymouth, University of Plymouth.
- STADDON, P. ed., 2015. *Women and Alcohol: Social Perspectives*, Policy Press.
- STERLING, S. & WEISNER, C., 2002. Women and Alcohol in Social Context: Mother's Ruin Revisited. *Addiction*, 97(6), pp.763-764.
- STOLAROFF, M. J., 1999. Are psychedelics useful in the practice of Buddhism? *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 39(1), pp.60-80.
- STRONKS, K. & KUNST, A. E., 2009. The complex interrelationship between ethnic and socio-economic inequalities in health. *Journal of Public Health*, 31(3), pp.324-325.
- SUBHRA, G., 2002. Drinking in Black and Minority Ethnic Communities. 100% Proof: Research for Action on Alcohol. In: Bayley, M. and Hurcombe, R., 2011. Drinking patterns and alcohol service provision for different ethnic groups in the UK: a review of the literature. *Ethnicity and inequalities in health and social care*, 3(4), pp.6-17.
- SUTHERLAND, E. H., 1939. *Principles of criminology* (.) JB Lippincott. New York.
- SUTHERLAND, E. H., CRESSEY, D. R. & LUCKENBILL, D., 1995. The theory of differential association. *Deviance: A symbolic interactionist approach*, 64-68.
- SYKES, G.M. and MATZA, D., 1957. Techniques of neutralization: A theory of delinquency. *American sociological review*, 22(6), pp.664-670.
- SZASZ, T. S., 2003. *Ceremonial chemistry: The ritual persecution of drugs, addicts, and pushers*, Syracuse University Press.

- TACHIBANA, S., 1992. *The ethics of Buddhism*, Psychology Press.
- TART, C.T., 1991. Influences of previous psychedelic drug experiences on students of Tibetan Buddhism: A preliminary exploration. *The Journal of Transpersonal Psychology*, 23(2), pp.139-173.
- TERRY, D. J. & HOGG, M. A., 1996. Group norms and the attitude-behavior relationship: A role for group identification. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 22(8), pp.776-793.
- THOMAS, W. I., ZNANIECKI, F. & ZARETSKY, E., 1984. *The polish peasant in Europe and America*, University of Illinois Press Urbana.
- TOBY, J., 1961. *Delinquency and opportunity: A Theory of Delinquent Gangs*. By Richard A. Cloward and Lloyd E. Ohlin. Glencoe, Illinois: The Free Press, 1960.
- TONGCO, M.D.C., 2007. Purposive sampling as a tool for informant selection. *Ethnobotany Research and applications*, 5, pp.147-158.
- TOPP, L., BARKER, B. & DEGENHARDT, L., 2004. The external validity of results derived from ecstasy users recruited using purposive sampling strategies. *Drug and alcohol dependence*, 73(1), pp.33-40.
- TRUCCO, E.M., COLDER, C.R. AND WIECZOREK, W.F., 2011. Vulnerability to peer influence: A moderated mediation study of early adolescent alcohol use initiation. *Addictive behaviors*, 36(7), pp.729-736.
- TURNER, B. S., 1991. *Religion and social theory*, Sage.
- TURNER, J. C., 1991. *Social influence*, Thomson Brooks/Cole Publishing Co.
- TURNER, R. A., IRWIN JR, C. E. & MILLSTEIN, S. G., 2014. Family structure, family processes, and experimenting with substances during adolescence. *Risks and Problem Behaviors in Adolescence*, 1(11), pp.229-247.
- UNITED NATIONS 1977. *Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs, 1961: As Amended by the 1972 Protocol Amending the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs, 1961*, UN.
- UNLU, A. & SAHIN, I., 2015. Religiosity and youth substance use in a Muslim context. *Journal of ethnicity in substance abuse*, 15(3), pp.287-309.
- VAILLANT, G. E., 2013. The Contribution of Prospective Studies to the Understanding of Etiologic Factors. *Research Advances in Alcohol and Drug Problems*, 8, 265.
- VAN DER VORST, H., ENGELS, R. C., MEEUS, W., DEKOVIĆ, M. & VAN LEEUWE, J., 2005. The role of alcohol-specific socialization in adolescents' drinking behaviour. *Addiction*, 100(10), pp.1464-1476.
- VAN WERSCH, A. & WALKER, W., 2009. Binge-drinking in Britain as a social and cultural phenomenon: the development of a grounded theoretical model. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 14(1), pp.124-134.
- WALLERSTEIN, I., 1960. Ethnicity and national integration in West Africa. *Cahiers d'études africaines*, 1(Cahier 3), pp.129-139.
- WALSH, D., BENDEL, N., JONES, R. & HANLON, P., 2010. It's not 'just deprivation': why do equally deprived UK cities experience different health outcomes? *Public health*, 124(9), pp.487-495.
- WANIGARATNE, S., DAR, K., ABDULRAHIM, D. & STRANG, J., 2003.

- Ethnicity and drug use: exploring the nature of particular relationships among diverse populations in the United Kingdom. *Drugs: education, prevention and policy*, 10(1), pp.39-55.
- WARNAKULASURIYA, S., 2002. Areca nut use following migration and its consequences. *Addiction biology*, 7(1), pp.127-132.
- WASSON, R.G., KRAMRISCH, S., RUCK, C.A. and OTT, J., 1986. *Persephone's quest: Entheogens and the origins of religion* (No. 10). Yale University Press.
- WEBER, L. & PARRA-MEDINA, D., 2003. Intersectionality and women's health: Charting a path to eliminating health disparities. In *Gender Perspectives on Health and Medicine* (pp. 181-230). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- WENHAM, C., 2015. Epidemiology and the people's health: theory and context. *Critical Public Health*. 25, 240-241.
- WEST, R. & BROWN, J., 2013. *Theory of addiction*, John Wiley & Sons.
- WIATROWSKI, M. D., GRISWOLD, D. B. & ROBERTS, M. K., 1981. Social-Control Theory and Delinquency. *American Sociological Review*, 46, pp.525-541.
- WILLIAMS, L., RALPHS, R. & GRAY, P., 2017. The Normalization of Cannabis Use Among Bangladeshi and Pakistani Youth: A New Frontier for the Normalization Thesis? *Substance use & misuse*, 52(4), pp.413-421.
- WILLIG, C., 2012. Perspectives on the epistemological bases for qualitative research. Pp. In H. Cooper, P. M. Camic, D. L. Long, A. T. Panter, D. Rindskopf, & K. J. Sher (Eds.), *APA handbooks in psychology®. APA handbook of research methods in psychology, Vol. 1. Foundations, planning, measures, and psychometrics* (p. 5-21). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/13619-002>
- WILLIG, C., 2013. *Introducing qualitative research in psychology*, McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- WILSNACK, R. W. & WILSNACK, S. C., 1997. Gender and alcohol. *Individual and social perspectives. New Brunswick: Rutgers Center of Alcohol Studies*.
- WILSNACK, R. W., WILSNACK, S. C., KRISTJANSON, A. F., VOGELTANZ-HOLM, N. D. & GMEL, G., 2009. Gender and alcohol consumption: patterns from the multinational GENACIS project. *Addiction*, 104(9), pp.1487-1500.
- WINCUP, E., 2016. Gender, recovery and contemporary UK drug policy. *Drugs and Alcohol Today*, 16(1), pp.39-48.
- WINICK, C., 1962. Maturing out of Narcotic Addiction. *Bulletin on Narcotics*, 14(1), pp.1-7.
- WIRTH, L., 1964. *On cities and social life; selected papers*. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- WISEMAN, D., 1971. Hammurabi. *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 11, pp. 40-41.
- WOOD, M. D., READ, J. P., MITCHELL, R. E. & BRAND, N. H. 2004. Do parents still matter? Parent and peer influences on alcohol involvement among recent high school graduates. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 18(1), p.19.

- WOOD, M.D., READ, J.P., PALFAI, T.P. AND STEVENSON, J.F., 2001. Social influence processes and college student drinking: the mediational role of alcohol outcome expectancies. *Journal of studies on alcohol*, 62(1), pp.32-43.
- WOODWARD, F. L., 2005. *The Book of the Kindred Sayings (Saṃyutta-nikāya) Or Grouped Suttas:(Mahā-vagga)*, Motilal Banarsidass Publishe.
- YELVINGTON, K.A., 1991. Ethnicity as practice? A comment on Bentley. *Comparative studies in society and history*, 33(1), pp.158-168.
- YEOMANS, H., 2011. What did the British temperance movement accomplish? Attitudes to alcohol, the law and moral regulation. *Sociology*, 45(1), pp.38-53.
- ZINBERG, N.E., 1981. Alcohol addiction: Toward a more comprehensive definition. *Dynamic approaches to the understanding and treatment of alcoholism*, pp.97-127.

Appendix 1: Research Information Form

Contact Details of Researcher
Linda Thomas Tel: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
E: [REDACTED]

Contact Details of Supervisor
Iain McPhee Tel: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED] 4
E: [REDACTED]

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide to take part it is important that you to understand why this study is being carried out. Please ask if there is anything that concerns you or is not clear to you. Thank you for reading this far.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you may have tried alcohol or drugs in the past, and have never been in treatment for your use of substances.

What is the purpose of this study?

The research aims to investigate the influence of culture, identity and alcohol and/or drug use among individuals from ethnic minority backgrounds. This is not a study about alcoholism. It is exploring the attitudes and opinions towards drinking and drug taking in your culture. The information you provide may contribute to policy responses.

Who is organising this study?

This study is being organised by a researcher who lectures in alcohol and drugs studies at University of the West of Scotland, and who is also a PhD student at the University. Supervisor was Iain McPhee, based at the University of West of Scotland.

Do I have to take part?

No there is no obligation, and it is your decision to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and you will be asked to sign a consent form. Even if you agree, you can still withdraw at any time, and if interviewed, can stop the interview at any time, without giving any reason.

What would I have to do?

You will be asked to be a participant in an interview with myself (Linda Thomas). This interview will take approx. 40 minutes, and will be recorded on an MP3 recorder. This will then be typed into a word document to aid understanding. This recording and the word document will be accessed by the researcher only.

Will my answers be kept confidential?

Yes, you do not need to give me your real name, and if you do, you will assigned a pseudonym, and all identifiable information will be kept anonymous. This document will be used to form part of PhD thesis to be written by the researcher.

National Drugs Helpline: 0800 77 66 00

Appendix 2: Consent Form

Name of Researcher: Linda Thomas

Please tick the boxes:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and am willing to take part in the study.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, without my medical care or legal rights being affected.

I understand that the interview will be recorded so that it can be properly transcribed and analysed.

I understand that the data obtained will be kept in confidence and that when any data is presented all personal details will be removed.

Mark/ Signature of participant

Date

Initials of Researcher and Serial No of Interview Date:

Thank you for your help with this research project

Appendix 3: Semi-structured interview

Identity & Substance Use

- What is your understanding of addiction?
- What words would you use to describe an addict?
- Do you consider using alcohol/drugs harmful? In what way?

Types of substances & Cultural identity

- What are the most common drugs used by people in your community? [Prompt: including prescriptions, illegal medications, and legal highs].
- What substances do you prefer to use, and why? [Prompt: alcohol, supari; including prescriptions, illegal medications, and legal highs]- **5WH**
- What other substances have you used? [Prompt: tobacco, paan, bidi, seesha]
- What types of drugs have you avoided, why?
- Have you ever (or felt the need) tried to stop or cut down your alcohol/drug use? [Prompt: 4 L's Model]

Cultural Identity, Belonging & Substance Use

- Why do you think people in your community use substances [Prompt: relaxation/mood enhancer, social, stress, physical etc.]
- Do people in your community/family find it difficult to talk about drug and/or alcohol related problems? [Prompt: shame, fear, reputation, stigma].
- Does cultural upbringing shape the use or avoidance of drugs or alcohol? How?

Gender, cultural identity & Substance use

- Are there any differences in the way men and/or women take substances in your culture?

Religion, cultural identity & Substance use

- Does religion have an/any impact in your use or avoidance of drugs or alcohol?
- What are the views on men and/or women who take alcohol/drugs in your religion?

Policy/regulation of substances

- What is your opinion on the measures taken by the government to tackle alcohol and drug problems?
- Does your religion provide any help for dealing with alcohol and drug problems?
- What kind of help is available for alcohol and drug problems in your area?
- In your opinion, what could be done to ease access to services?

Appendix 4: Demographics Questionnaire

Serial No:

Gender

- Male Female

Age

- 18 to 24 35 to 39 50 to 54 65 to 69
 25 to 29 40 to 44 55 to 59 70 to 74
 30 to 34 45 to 49 60 to 64 75 to 79

Ethnic

- White Indian Black Caribbean Mixed Ethnic
 Chinese Pakistani Black African Arab
 Irish Bangladeshi Black other Any other (_____)

Generatio

- First Second Third Fourth

Religion

- Christian** **Hindu** **Jain**
 Sikh **Muslim** **Other (_____)**

Drinking

- Every day** **1 or 2 times per week** **None in the last year**
 Nearly Every day **2 or 3 times per week** **Do not drink now**
 3-4 times per week **About once a month**